

**School of Media, Creative Arts & Social Inquiry
Faculty of Humanities**

Analysing Virtual Influencers

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**This thesis is presented for the Degree of
Doctor of Philosophy
of
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Declaration

To the best of my knowledge and belief this thesis contains no material previously published by any other person except where due acknowledgment has been made.

This thesis contains no material which has been accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in any university.

The research presented and reported in this thesis was conducted in accordance with the National Health and Medical Research Council National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007) – updated March 2014. The proposed research study received human research ethics approval from the Curtin University Human Research Ethics Committee (EC00262), Approval Number **HRE2021-0773**.

Signature:

Date:

Acknowledgement of Country

This project was completed on the unceded lands of the Whadjuk people of the Nyungar nation, in Boorloo (Perth), Western Australia. I pay my respects to Elders, past, present, and emerging, and recognise their continuing culture and connection to the lands and waters of this beautiful place, which has thrived under their custodianship for more than 45,000 years. Sovereignty was never ceded: this always was, and always will be, Aboriginal land.

Abstract

This thesis explores a phenomenon known as “virtual influencers”: animated characters who are native to social media, engage in the cultures and practices of visual social media platforms, and seek to capture the attention of other social media users, brands, and investors by documenting their fictional lives online. Between the late 2010s and early 2020s, virtual influencers appeared online with increasing frequency, populating an array of social media platforms, amassing large online audiences, and in some cases, entering into commercial partnerships. Guided by constructivist grounded theory and digital ethnography, I ask whether a meaningful difference exists between the social media practices of virtual influencers and human influencers. Drawing on non-participant observation of over 100 virtual influencers from January to August 2022, semi-structured online interviews conducted with their producers and industry stakeholders, and archival, press, and document analysis, I analyse how virtual influencers engage with the visual templates, processes of cultural commodification, and commercial practices associated with their human counterparts. I also detail the behind-the-scenes mechanisms involved in producing and managing virtual influencers, and chart the evolving strategies of the industry that quickly appeared to commercialise them. Based on this analysis, I develop a grounded theory of *hyper-virtuality*, arguing that the most successful virtual influencers are not those that seek to camouflage themselves as “real”, but rather those that embrace and celebrate their virtual-ness, given the value of unabashed virtuality in the contemporary visual social media landscape.

*To my grandparents,
Gran, JB, Pat, Grandad, and Jo*

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Acronyms

2D	Two-Dimensional
2.5D	2.5-Dimensional
3D	Three-Dimensional
ACG	<i>Anime</i> , Comics and Games
AFP	<i>Agence France-Presse</i>
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AR	Augmented Reality
B2B	Business-to-Business
BBC	British Broadcasting Corporation
BJs	Broadcasting Jockeys
CASA	Computers as/are Social Actors
CD	Compact Disc
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CG	Computer Graphics
CGI(I)	Computer-Generated Imagery (Influencer)
CGT	Constructivist Grounded Theory
CMC	Computer-Mediated Communication
CNN	Cable News Network
COVID-19	Coronavirus Disease 2019
DIY	Do-It-Yourself
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
DVD	Digital Versatile Disc
FACS	Facial Action Coding System
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
HD	High Definition
KISS	<i>Kisekae</i> Set System
KOL	Key Opinion Leader
LLM	Large Language Model
MMD	MikuMikuDance
MIT	Massachusetts Institute of Technology
NFTs	Non-Fungible Tokens
OOTD	Outfit of the Day
PCF	Participant Consent Form
PIS	Participant Information Statement
PR	Public Relations
RQ	Research Question
SNS	Social Network Sites
SXSW	South by Southwest
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
US	United States
VFX	Digital Effects
VIA	Virtual Influencer Agency
VK	Vkontakte (ВКонтакте)
vKOL	Virtual Key Opinion Leader
VR	Virtual Reality

Introduction

1.1 Opening

This thesis analyses a phenomenon widely known as “virtual influencers”. Gaining popularity from the mid-2010s to early 2020s, virtual influencers are animated characters who are native to social media, engage in the cultures and practices of visual social media platforms, and seek to capture (and often to monetise) the attention of other social media users, brands, and investors by documenting moments of their fictional lives online. In popular discourse, the characters’ categorisation as “virtual” generally references their mode of production: the faces and bodies of virtual influencers are most often made with computer-generated imagery and 3D graphics, created using digital animation software like Blender, Daz3D, and Maya (see Chapter 6). Their label as “influencers” enters them into the contemporary landscape of internet celebrity, joining a cohort of:

everyday, ordinary Internet users who accumulate a relatively large following on [...] social media through the textual and visual narration of their personal lives and lifestyles, engage with their following in digital and physical spaces, and monetise their following by integrating “advertorials” into their [...] social media posts. (Abidin, 2015a, n.p.)

In many ways, virtual influencers act as human influencers do, documenting the mundane and extraordinary moments of their day-to-day lives in line with the affordances (Bucher & Helmond, 2018), vernaculars (Gibbs et al., 2015), and cultures of the visual social media platforms they populate (see Chapters 7 and 8). On platforms such as Instagram and Weibo (微博), virtual influencers are often depicted posing at cafes and restaurants, stores and markets, and galleries and museums. They use these settings to showcase their outfits, meals, and social connections, and sometimes as commercial backdrops, promoting sponsored messages on behalf of brands and organisations (see Chapter 9). However, despite the many ways in which virtual influencers’ social media feeds emulate those of their human counterparts, they are often distinguished by instances of virtuality that exceed the characters themselves. Virtual influencers will regularly appear dressed in 3D garments, accompanied by 3D objects, or posed in fantastical 3D environments (see Chapters 6 and 9). In this thesis, I interrogate how the social media content of virtual influencers aligns with and depart from the established conventions and practices of human influencers, and the indicators of virtuality that distinguish them in the contemporary visual social media

landscape.

The ideas developed in this thesis are based on data collected between January and August 2022, spanning multi-sited, non-participant observation of over 100 virtual influencers; nine semi-structured online interviews with virtual influencer producers and industry stakeholders; and document analysis of promotional rhetoric produced by and about the virtual influencer industry, including presentations, podcasts, and websites, along with press and archival web materials (detailed in Chapter 5). Housed in media studies (Cubitt, 2013), and guided by the methodological tenets of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006) and digital ethnography (Markham, 2017, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012), I use these methods to answer the following research questions:

- RQ** Is there a meaningful difference between the practices of virtual influencers and the established practices of human influencers? If so:
- a)** How is this difference enacted in virtual influencers' social media content?
 - b)** How is this difference perceived and articulated by the producers of virtual influencers and other industry stakeholders?

The core argument developed by this thesis is that there is value in the virtual, and in being recognisable as a virtual object or entity in online environments. Since the mid-2010s, the visual social media landscape has been plagued by an enduring sense of ambiguity over the truth and credibility of online content (Miyake, 2022). This can be attributed to several factors, including the ubiquity of image manipulation using photo-editing software such as Photoshop and mobile apps like FaceTune (see Lavrence & Cambre, 2020); the rise of so-called "synthetic media", such as deepfakes (see Ahmed, 2023); the abundance of online disinformation circulated by predatory actors (see Vaccari & Chadwick, 2020); and, as of the early 2020s, the introduction of generative artificial intelligence (see Chapter 11). Amid this online climate of what I refer to as *ontological uncertainty*, I argue that the most successful virtual influencers seek to foreground their virtuality, drawing attention to their virtual-ness by showing us that they are virtual, telling us they are virtual, or showing us how they are virtual. In the contemporary visual social media landscape, this unabashed virtuality carries a quality of exceptionalism. Further, upon recognising virtual influencers as virtual, we judge them against a different set of criteria; become more accepting or accommodating of visual oddities or behavioural missteps; and can take pleasure in multi-dimensional encounters, seeking out opportunities to experience the entanglement of virtuality and actuality these characters embody. In the conclusion (see Chapter 11), I develop these ideas as a grounded theory of *hyper-virtuality*, encapsulating a type of virtuality that embraces, promotes, and

capitalises on its own virtual-ness by actively drawing attention to the ways it is unlike the actual.

1.2 Context

Virtual influencers have represented a growing niche in the global influencer ecology since 2018, when press coverage in prominent publications like the *BBC* (D. Fowler, 2018), *The New York Times* (Hess, 2018), *Wall Street Journal* (Koh & Wells, 2018), and *Wired* (M. Katz, 2018b) brought them into mainstream view (Choudhry et al., 2022, p. 7). These articles focused primarily on three early examples, who together contributed to the popular definition of the term “virtual influencer” (see section 1.3). These originators are American virtual influencer Lil Miquela (later known by her full name, Miquela Sousa), who first appeared online in 2016, and Paris-based virtual influencer Noonoori, who debuted on Instagram in 2018. Completing the trio was UK-based virtual mannequin Shudu, who came to public attention in early 2018 after being reposted by the Instagram account of popular American cosmetics brand Fenty Beauty (see Rosenstein, 2018).

Though she regularly featured in the same press articles, Shudu’s presence on social media was unlike her contemporaries: whereas Lil Miquela conveyed a sense of interiority through constant references to popular culture and selfies alongside actual people (see Chapter 7), and Noonoori through the “almost stream-of-consciousness series of images around fashion, aesthetics” and various other topics that populated her Instagram Stories (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 201), Shudu’s posts did not suggest psychological depth. The striking visuals uploaded to Shudu’s Instagram account focused on the model’s photorealistic features and glamorous virtual outfits (see Chapter 6); as described by her creator, Shudu was created as an “art piece” (Wilson, as cited in Rosenstein, 2018, para. 3), whose digital body could be “pose[d] in certain ways” to showcase virtual fashion designs (Wilson, as cited in Rosenstein, 2018, para. 5). Whereas Lil Miquela and Noonoori used the affordances of social media to display interiority and continuity (see section 1.3), Shudu connoted only “to-be-looked-at-ness” (Mulvey, 1975/1999), a quality which drew significant critique as an appropriation and commodification of Blackness given Shudu’s deep skin tone and purported South African heritage (Jackson, 2018; Sobande, 2021a, 2021a; Square, 2018). The conflation of these three examples in early press reflected the growing frequency with which virtual entities were being encountered online—especially on social media—as well as the need for greater conceptual clarity of the variations among these virtual beings, of which virtual influencers are just one example (see Chapter 3).

By the early 2020s, virtual influencers were an established phenomenon. Amid a period of heightened competition in the influencer economy, increased frequency and fall-out of influencer scandals, and widespread uncertainty amid the COVID-19 pandemic (see Chapter 3), the number of virtual influencers multiplied. In an interview with *Fortune Korea*, Baek Seung-yeop, CEO of virtual influencer agency LOCUS-X (née Sidus Studio X), estimated that by 2020, the global virtual influencer industry was already worth ₩2.4 trillion (USD\$1.8 billion), and would reach ₩14 trillion (USD\$10.5 billion) by 2025 (Baek, as cited in Chae, 2022). As of 2021, according to a report from social media measurement firm *HypeAuditor*, there were at least 130 virtual influencers on Instagram, three times as many as recorded in 2019 (Baklanov, 2022). Although English-language press coverage continued to focus heavily on characters from the US and UK, by the time I began this project in early 2021, virtual influencers were a globally distributed phenomenon (Choudhry et al., 2022). The characters I encountered in the course of this project claimed residence in 27 cities across 15 countries (see Chapter 5), and were often designed to resonate with the privileged aesthetics and preferences of local audiences (Abidin, 2023). Combined, their digital footprint extended across 11 social media platforms, as well as a range of other networked environments, including video games and mobile apps, online marketplaces, and music streaming services (see Chapter 5). However, I soon discovered their activity was concentrated on social media platforms “explicitly framed around the visual” (Highfield & Leaver, 2016, p. 47), which at the time of my fieldwork, included Instagram, TikTok, and Xiaohongshu (小红书, see section 1.6). Across these platforms, hundreds, thousands, and in some cases, millions of people opted-in to view the characters’ posts, following and subscribing to the content they uploaded to social media.

Like human influencers, upon reaching a certain level of popularity, virtual influencers were recruited by brands for commercial partnerships, and began to integrate sponsored messages into their social media feeds (see Chapter 9). Rather than remuneration for the (virtual) influencer, it was their producers who were compensated for these partnerships, sometimes financially, other times with free products or services, or exclusive access to brand events (see Chapter 9). A widely-cited 2020 industry report estimated that Lil Miquela could earn over £6,550 (USD\$8,450) per sponsored Instagram post (OnBuy, 2020), with other industry experts speculating her takings could be anywhere between USD\$12,000 and USD\$25,000 (Koh & Wells, 2018). In 2022, a Korean virtual influencer named Rozy purportedly earned over ₩2 million (USD\$1.5 million), with ten exclusive contracts and 150 sponsored advertisements (Ganesan & Wong, 2022). As part of such commercial partnerships, virtual influencers like Lil Miquela and Rozy have featured in television commercials, and appeared on billboards, posters, and product packaging (see Chapter 9).

These high-reach media channels introduced the characters to new audiences, attracted new partnership deals (강경희, 2021), and inspired other producers, brands, and agencies to create virtual influencers of their own.

The growth of the virtual influencer phenomenon would not have been possible without the heightened availability and capabilities of digital animation software (see Chapter 6). Most virtual influencers are created with computer-generated imagery, appearing either as fully 3D models, or as composite models, whose digital features are superimposed onto photos taken of human body doubles (see Chapter 7). The technical workflow involved in creating a virtual influencer is very similar to those used to create digital characters for film and video games (e.g. Kaufman et al., 2013; McLaughlin et al., 2011), although the production of virtual influencers is shaped by a desire to make the characters visible on social media (see Chapter 6). Whereas the 3D animation software involved in this pipeline were once restricted to computers on university campuses (Magnenat-Thalmann & Thalmann, 1987) and professional animation studios (F. Rose, 1995; Turnock, 2009)—a reflection of the significant computing power and graphics capabilities originally required to run them—artists and animators can now access industry-grade modelling software such as Maya, Houdini, and zBrush from their home computers (A. Wood, 2015). Software like Daz3D and open-sourced Blender are free to use, and repositories of online resources and “how-to” tutorials on YouTube, TikTok, and dedicated community forums offer opportunities for amateur producers to teach themselves how to create original characters. However, it would be a mistake to assume that the availability of this technology and learning resources has simplified the process of creating virtual influencers: as illustrated by the pipeline detailed in Chapter 6, the virtual influencers I encountered are a product of substantial time and effort, requiring familiarity and expertise with numerous digital animation programmes, and a variety of technical and creative skills.

The question of who is behind virtual influencers attracts significant interest in popular discourse, especially as information about their identities is regularly hidden from public view (see Chapter 10). My findings suggest that virtual influencers are either created by independent producers, or an ensemble of specialist contributors in corporate settings. Independent producers describe those who create and manage virtual influencers without access to corporate resources or support. The independent producers I interviewed for this project (see Chapter 5) variously viewed their virtual influencers as a hobby, as a platform for creative expression or experimentation, or as a pathway to future career prospects or progression. The time they devoted to their characters was typically voluntary, unpaid, and completed around other full-time employment, embodying the concept of “hope labour”,

defined as “un- or under-compensated work carried out in the present, often for experience or exposure, in the hope that future employment opportunities may follow” (Kuehn & Corrigan, 2013, p. 10).

Other virtual influencers are powered by small-to-medium-sized production teams. In some instances, these teams are housed in established advertising agencies that have expanded their business offerings to include virtual influencer production. For example, creative agencies like Dentsu Singapore, creators of Singaporean virtual influencer Rae (dentsu, 2022), and B2B (business-to-business) social media agency RAUWcc, creators of Rotterdam-based virtual influencer Esther Olofsson (RauwCC, 2020), both created bespoke virtual influencers for existing client partnerships. Advertising agencies have the advantage of established internal resources, workflows, and industry connections, which combine to streamline the creation and management of virtual influencers. In other cases, virtual influencers are made by boutique agencies who specialise in the production and management of virtual influencers. Referred to throughout this thesis as “virtual influencer agencies”, these companies comprise teams of 3D animators, creative strategists, software engineers and technologists, and social media specialists (see Chapter 10). Many virtual influencer agencies have been successful in obtaining funding from investment firms and venture capitalists: in late 2021, Beijing Next Generation Culture Media (北京次世文化传媒有限公司) completed two rounds of fundraising in just three months, accumulating almost USD\$10 million in venture investment (王毓婵, 2021); while Tokyo-based agency Aww Inc., raised JP¥860 million (approximately USD\$6 million) in funding in early 2022 (Aww Inc., 2024). In 2019, industry news outlet *TechCrunch* reported that the creators of Lil Miquela, Los Angeles-based virtual influencer agency Brud (discussed at length in Chapter 10) received a pre-money valuation of USD\$125 million (Shieber, 2019). Brud reappeared in trade headlines after the company’s acquisition in October 2021, though the final sales price was never disclosed (Matney, 2021). As trade headlines are wont to reiterate (e.g. Lohchab, 2023; Ong, 2020; Shieber, 2018), the virtuality of virtual influencers does not extend to the real money the characters are capable of attracting.

I formally concluded my data collection for this project in mid-2022, and put the finishing touches on this thesis in mid-2025. In the intervening period, the web has undergone drastic changes, especially in response to the introduction of generative artificial intelligence (GenAI) technology. GenAI tools such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT and DALL-E, along with Stability AI’s open-source Stable Diffusion, which permit users to near instantaneously generate written and visual outputs based on text-prompts, have been adopted at pace (McKinsey, 2023). Proponents of GenAI champion its capacity for “augmenting [...]”

reimagining [...] and transforming [...] creativity and creative work”, despite the harmful stereotypes and biases often reproduced in these outputs (Miltner, 2024, p. 15). Although industry fervour surrounding GenAI was in its infancy while I was undertaking data collection—at which time only a couple of early iterations of these GenAI tools were publicly available—the term “AI influencers” had appeared in press as a synonym for “virtual influencer” for several years (e.g. Strusiewicz, 2019; Wills, 2019), a label which misrepresents the autonomy and intelligence of the characters, while also obscuring the human labour involved in their production (see section 1.3.1). As outlined in Chapter 6, the virtual influencers I discuss in this thesis are all products of significant human time, skill, and resource. I return to the topic of GenAI in the conclusion, but until then, encourage the reader to consider the portrait this thesis paints of the virtual influencer industry and its mechanics as a snapshot taken mere moments before GenAI’s entry and ubiquity in the mid-2020s cultural zeitgeist.

1.3 Evolving Terminology

Though the exact origins of the term “virtual influencer” are unclear, one of the first recorded uses occurred in late 2017 at ChatbotConf, a technology conference held in Vienna, Austria. Presenter Ashley D’Arcy, then Head of Creative and Editorial at a New York-based weather start-up called Poncho, described her company’s animated chatbot mascot—an anthropomorphised cat, also named Poncho—as a “virtual influencer” (oratio, 2017, 16:58). In the final moments of her talk, D’Arcy explains that her team planned to experiment with having Poncho “sell his lifestyle, and hav[ing] products with him as he goes about his day-to-day [life]” as a way of unlocking new revenue streams for their growing company (oratio, 2017, 17:06). “We’re very hopeful that he has enough influence with his users that he could sell things [to them],” D’Arcy concludes (oratio, 2017, 17:14). Within a few months, the term was appearing in press (e.g. D. Fowler, 2018; Johnston, 2018; M. Katz, 2018a), trade news (e.g. Shieber, 2018), and early scholarly accounts (e.g. Marwick, 2018b). I briefly reflect on the varied terminology that has been used to refer to virtual influencers below, accounting for the evolution of these terms in both press and scholarship.

1.3.1 Popular & Trade Press

Early news coverage related to the virtual influencer phenomenon (from late 2016 to late 2017) was focused primarily on Lil Miquela, whose PR firm NEWHOUSE (then Mammoth Advertising) strategically seeded stories about her to press partners (*Newhouse Work | Miquela*, n.d.). It was only in early 2018 that press discourse shifted from discussing Miquela as an outlier to part of a growing trend of “computer-generated influencers” (e.g. Morency,

2018; Petrarca, 2018a; Saltzman, 2018). By April 2018, “virtual influencer” had entered the zeitgeist: the *BBC* published an article called “The fascinating world of Instagram’s ‘virtual’ celebrities” (D. Fowler, 2018) with the sub-heading “Virtual influence” (n.p.); *Financial Times* published an article called “Meet Miquela: Virtual Fashion Influencer” (Macdonald Johnston, 2018); and *TechCrunch*, a tech industry blog, reported that “The makers of the virtual influencer, Lil Miquela, snag real money from Silicon Valley” (Shieber, 2018). Later articles would sometimes describe virtual influencers as “avatars”, a term with established connotations to online interactions and virtual worlds, but still qualified with additional epithets, as in headlines like “Who is Lil Miquela, the Digital Avatar Instagram Influencer?” (Petrarca, 2018b) and “Can Luxury Brands Tap into China’s ‘Virtual Avatar’ Fever?” (Zheng, 2018).

Ultimately, virtual influencer prevailed as the dominant descriptor in popular commentary. This term appeared in industry reports (e.g. admin, 2022; Baklanov, 2019) and commentary (e.g. Bradley, 2020; Dodt, 2020; Retail News Asia, 2018; Shieber, 2019), and even in the blog post announcing Meta was developing ethical guidelines for the rising presence of “synthetic media” on its platforms (Facebook IQ, 2022; see also Leaver & Berryman, 2022). The label virtual influencer was also adopted by the characters themselves, prominently displayed in their social media profiles and utilised in the hashtags of their posts (see Chapter 6). However, in East Asia especially, the characters are still regularly referred to as “virtual idols” (e.g. Y. Jiang & Cao, 2022; Nan, 2021), with some preferring the label “virtual human” (see Fu, 2021; G. Lee, 2022; Yates, 2020). Despite these variations, to differentiate contemporary examples from the virtual idols that debuted in the 1990s (see Chapter 2) and the virtual humans programmed to handle customer queries and interactions for brands (see Chapter 3), I apply the term “virtual influencer” to all of the examples mentioned in this thesis. I delve further into the differences between virtual influencers and other entities encountered in online contexts in Chapter 3.

Misnomers

Looking across press commentary on virtual influencers highlights two recurring misnomers used to label them. The first is their description as artificially intelligent or “AI influencers” (e.g. Bobila, 2018; Nan, 2021; Strusiewicz, 2019; Teh, 2021; Wills, 2019), as mentioned in section 1.2. This epithet is rarely qualified, with few details on where and how AI is used in the production of virtual influencers. Explanations are typically vague, and seem intended to market proprietary tools and technologies. For instance, the facial expressions and gestures of Chinese virtual influencer Ling are attributed to the “artificial-intelligence animated-performance technology” of Chinese tech start-up Xmov (Q. Wang, 2020b, n.p.).

Commentary from the characters' producers adds to the confusion. For example, in an interview "with" *FEMALE* magazine, Singaporean virtual influencer Rae describes herself as "powered by AI and deep learning technology (an AI function that imitates the workings of the human brain)" (as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 9), and an article by *CNN* answers whether Korean virtual influencer Rozy is "a real person? [...] an AI? Or a robot?" by explaining that "[a]ccording to the Seoul-based company that created her, Rozy is a blend of all three" (Yeung & Bae, 2022, n.p.). The lack of clarification around this "AI" epithet has an anthropomorphising effect, misattributing a sense of agency and cognitive capability to virtual influencers (see Chapter 7), whose operation is in fact more akin to virtual puppetry (see Chapter 3). At the time of data collection, every character discussed in this thesis relied upon significant skill, time, and labour of behind-the-scenes producers (see Chapter 6), even as the availability of GenAI tools have challenged this assumption as of mid-2025 (see Chapter 11).

The second misnomer is the description of virtual influencers as "robots" (e.g. Torgerson, 2018; Trepany, 2019), also found in the term "robot influencers" (e.g. F. Lee, 2021; Licea, 2020; OnBuy, 2020). This label can primarily be attributed to the prominence of Lil Miquela in early press commentary around virtual influencers. For her first two years on Instagram, Lil Miquela did not acknowledge that she was anything other than a regular 19-year-old girl. However, in early 2018, a carefully-orchestrated dispute unfolded on her Instagram account, with a second virtual influencer, Bermuda, seemingly "hacking" Lil Miquela's account, "deleting" her Instagram posts, and publicly threatening Lil Miquela to stop "lying" to her audience (see Koebler, 2018; Petrarca, 2018a). When Lil Miquela regained control of her account, she revealed that she was not a human, but was in fact a "robot", created by a malicious technology company and saved from their plans by her managers at Brud (see Chapter 10). Over the months and years that followed, Lil Miquela's social media content regularly returned to her robotic identity, with major storylines focused on upgrading her software and unlocking new robot powers (T. C. Black, 2020). Adoption of the term "robot influencer" reveals Lil Miquela's prominent role in shaping discourses and perceptions surrounding the virtual influencer phenomenon (S. Smith, 2023). While for Miquela the term "robot" was a creative decision, for a brief period, the abbreviated labelling of virtual influencers as "bots" (e.g. T. Chen, 2020) threatened to collapse the phenomenon into contemporaneous discussions of malicious online actors and disinformation.

1.3.2 Scholarly Accounts

Scholars have likewise deployed a variety of terms in their discussions of virtual influencers. Marketing scholars Marie-Nathalie Jauffret and Vanessa Landaverde-Kastberg (2018, 2019)

call them “*personnage biodigital*” or “biodigital characters” (elaborated below); other scholars use terms like “algorithmic celebrities” (Marwick, 2018b) and “algorithmic online celebrities” (Lacković, 2021), a double-entendre that could reference either the algorithms involved in the digital animation software used to create virtual influencers (see Chapter 6), or those that organise the flow and hierarchy of information on the social media platforms virtual influencers inhabit (Brachtendorf, 2022; see also Chapter 7). Marketing scholars emphasise the characters’ persuasive function, describing them as “virtual endorsers” (Thomas & Fowler, 2021), or reiterate their digital composition, calling them “computer-generated image influencer[s]” or “CGII” (Baumgarth et al., 2021). Some scholars have even adopted the robotic epithets popularised in press (see section 1.3.1), referring to the entities as “virtual robots” (Oliveira & Chimenti, 2021), “digital robots” (Audrezet & Koles, 2023), and “robot influencers” (Baudier et al., 2023) to underscore the control exercised by their human producers. In Chapter 3, I reframe this logic to situate virtual influencers as examples of “virtual puppets”.

Over time, academic definitions of virtual influencers have taken on additional nuance. Jauffret and Landaverde-Kastberg’s (2018) early commentary emphasises the ambiguity surrounding the characters’ identities, highlighting the “[c]onfusion, the expression of doubt, and the search for truth [that] pepper the comments” of their social media accounts, written by other “internet users waiting for an answer” (p. III). In a later article, Jauffret and Landaverde-Kastberg (2019) suggest that virtual influencers have an “imprecise and unclear identity and yet [...] a very real human story to tell” (p. 287), and propose defining “biodigital influencers” as:

a character represented either as a person, an anthropomorphic, a robot, an animal or an imaginary representation. Such a being is characterised mainly by an equivocal, ambivalent and diverging interpretation of its visual identity. (p. 287)

Reflecting the infancy of the phenomenon, Jauffret and Landaverde-Kastberg’s definition identifies virtual influencers not by any formal qualities or behaviours shared by the entities themselves, but instead by the divided perspectives of those who encounter them. As virtual influencers multiplied and evolved, other scholars have offered more detailed definitions, although this undertaking has been complicated by the significant variation among the entities labelled virtual influencers (Engström, 2022; Stein et al., 2024). For example, one source offers a rubric for differentiating virtual influencers that includes four main categories (including demographic, positioning, behaviour and brand collaborations, and followers), and spans 15 variable attributes (see Baumgarth et al., 2021). My discussion of the production pipeline for virtual influencers elucidates on ways the characters differ, noting the variety of

approaches to modelling, framing, and staging virtual influencers and their social media content (see Chapter 6).

From the current body of scholarship on virtual influencers, three definitions are worthy of special mention, given their alignment with the definition I developed over the course of this project (outlined below). The first is from internet studies scholars Tama Leaver, Tim Highfield, and Crystal Abidin (2020), who define virtual influencers as “CGI or virtual celebrities who do not have a physical form at all, but are created, crafted, narrated and managed to promote or sell a particular message or brand” (p. 212). Leaver et al.’s definition usefully underscores that virtual influencers lack a singular referent in the actual world, and are intentionally created to effectively convey messaging, which can be, though is not necessarily exclusively, commercially motivated. The second definition comes from marketing scholars Carsten Baumgarth, Alexandra Kirkby, and Cosima Kaibel (2021), who study how virtual influencers are used in commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9). For them, a virtual influencer (which they refer to as a “CGII”) is

a computer-generated character resembling a human. Just like a classic, human influencer, a CGII has a large number of engaged followers and is active on social media platforms. Although a content team is responsible for actually producing content, a CGII presents itself to users as the content generator, regularly posting photos, videos, and/or texts across one or more social media platforms. (p. 151)

Baumgarth et al.’s definition is useful for the attention it draws to the behind-the-scenes producers who manage virtual influencers, as well as the first-person perspective adopted by the virtual influencer themselves. It also emphasises the way the characters’ content is styled to foster an impression of agency (see Chapter 7) and subjectivity (see Chapter 8). The third definition comes from fashion design scholar Charlotte Brachtendorf (2022). In her analysis of the characters’ fashionable bodies, Brachtendorf describes a virtual influencer as “a hyper-realistic visual representation of a virtual being [...] who mimics the practices of human influencers by posting details of their everyday lives on Instagram” (p. 484). Adding context to the social media behaviours identified in the two other definitions, Brachtendorf’s definition emphasises that virtual influencers seek to emulate the ways in which human influencers use social media platforms (see Chapter 4), as well as the fictional lives that often serve as inspiration for their content.

Inspired by these definitions, and through further consultation with scholarship, press and industry documents, as well as interviews with virtual influencer producers and industry stakeholders (see Chapter 5), I define virtual influencers as fictional characters who: a) are

native to social media, without a singular referent in the offline world; b) have a sense of interiority, and are portrayed as living lives that extend beyond their social media profiles; c) are animated, and typically created using digital animation software and computer-generated imagery (see Chapter 6); d) engage with the cultures, affordances (Bucher & Helmond, 2018), and vernaculars (Gibbs et al., 2015) of visual social media platforms (see Chapters 7 to 9); and e) are usually designed to accumulate (and monetise) the attention of online audiences (see Chapters 9 and 10). While many aspects of this definition are illustrated throughout this thesis, it is worth briefly elaborating upon one of its key components—virtual influencers as characters—given its centrality to the analytic approach adopted in this thesis.

1.4 Characterisation

Virtual influencers have been conceptualised as fictional characters across a range of academic fields, from business studies (e.g. Dabiran et al., 2024; Yan et al., 2024) to fashion studies (e.g. Wu et al., 2024). Marketing studies scholar Jon Engström (2022) describes virtual influencers as “fictional character[s]”, qualifying that a “character in this context refers to a person or other being in a narrative” (p. 2), while HCI researcher Abhinav Choudhry et al. (2022) describe virtual influencers as “a digital character with a first-person view of the world” (p. 2). From a media studies perspective, I find this framing of virtual influencers useful both for the historical trajectory it enters these entities into, and the analytical lens it encourages, points I detail below.

Character as Celebrity Trajectory

Conceiving of virtual influencers as characters connects them to a trajectory of fictional characters that have a long history of occupying mediated spaces traditionally devoted to human celebrities. This history extends back almost a century. For example, as *TIME* magazine recounts, in the 1930s, a lifelike storefront mannequin called Cynthia gained popularity among New York socialites. Cynthia regularly attended “nightclubs and social events”, and became:

something of a New York nightlife fixture. [She received] free gifts of dresses, shoes, furs and jewelry [from prominent stores and] Saks Fifth Avenue even issued her a credit card. Once she achieved a certain level of fame, gossip columnists began writing about Cynthia as if she were a living, breathing socialite. When partygoers tried to engage the mannequin in conversation, [her creator Lester] Gaba begged off by claiming she was suffering from a touch of laryngitis. (Cosgrove, 2013, n.p.)

Cynthia’s crowning achievement was her 1937 appearance on the cover of *Life* magazine,

replete with a fourteen-page photoshoot, combining behind-the-scenes images of Cynthia's disassembled plaster limbs with photos of her holding a long-stemmed cigarette, surrounded by party-goers in animated dining rooms and dimly-lit clubs (Cosgrove, 2013). Cynthia's story was shared by one of Lil Miquela's co-creators, Sara DeCou, in a podcast interview (Bradfield, 2020), and other scholars have since drawn parallels between the gifts and event invitations Cynthia received with virtual influencers today (e.g. Choudhry et al., 2022, pp. 4–5; see also Chapter 9).

Throughout the twentieth century, the music industry was responsible for introducing many examples of fictional performers to mainstream audiences. Anthropomorphised singing trio Alvin and the Chipmunks were borne from an experimentation with the effects of a voice recorder in 1958, and the four-piece animated band Gorillaz were created in 1998 “as a means to comment on the nature and power of celebrity in popular culture” (Conner, 2016, p. 138). Many of these fictional performers were from musical groups originally created for television shows, later achieving crossover success as musicians. This includes the Archies from *The Archie Show* (1968-1978; see Stahl, 2011), the Monkees from *The Monkees* (1966-68; see Stahl, 2011), and the Aurora Sisters from *anime* series *Star of the Giants* (1968-1971; see Yoshida, 2004/2016). In each instance, the records produced for these groups were created and marketed under the characters' names, instead of the (human) singers and actors who provided their voices (discussed further in Chapter 2) – a precedent many virtual influencers would follow.

By the 1990s, it was all but commonplace for popular fictional characters to transcend their narrative storyworlds and assume roles as celebrities. Characters from long-running television franchises like *The Muppets* and *Looney Toons* appeared as guests on talk shows and attended awards ceremonies, assisted either by concealed puppeteers (see Calbreath-Frasieur, 2012), or specialist software (e.g. *Alive!* or *Vactor*) capable of synchronising pre-prepared animation with live-action footage (see Magnenat Thalmann & Thalmann, 1997; Parisi, 1995). In the US, human lookalikes were hired to appear at trade conventions and fan meet-and-greets on behalf of Lara Croft, the popular protagonist of the *Tomb Raider* video game franchise (Rehak, 2003), while the digital Lara Croft adorned magazine covers, and appeared in television commercials for energy drinks and credit cards (Poole, 2001). In Chapter 2, I continue my focus on this trajectory, recounting three historical precedents for computer-generated characters capable of participating in the media and entertainment industries. Spanning cultural, industrial, and temporal contexts, these origin stories afford insight into the technologies, marketing strategies, and platforms that would later be taken up by virtual influencers.

Character as Creative Product

Conceptualising virtual influencers as characters also emphasises that they are products of creative labour, skill, and decisions. This implies a sense of distance between virtual influencers and their producers (Kaplin, 1999), useful for parsing the fact that virtual influencers are often created with different identities and backgrounds than those who create them, and cannot be read as reflections or incarnations of them. Focusing on this quality helps to differentiate virtual influencers from more established internet studies concepts like “avatars”, broadly defined as an on-screen representation of a technology user (Frow, 2012). Admittedly, the fact that many virtual influencers appear in virtual worlds, and are created using the same technologies as video game characters (perhaps the most popular contemporary example of “avatars”), often blurs this conceptual distinction. We see this blurriness in discussions of virtual influencers as “avatars” in popular press (e.g. E. Holmes, 2018; Petrarca, 2018b; Zheng, 2018), and in research on virtual influencers from scholarly fields such as marketing, where the terms “virtual influencer” and “avatar” are often equated (e.g. Audrezet & Koles, 2023; Bansal & Pruthi, 2023; de Brito Silva et al., 2022). However, in this thesis, I conceptualise virtual influencers as characters, not avatars, as a way of underscoring the distance often found in accounts by their producers. Take, for example, this quote from Reyme Husaini, creator of Singaporean virtual influencer Ava Gram, whom I interviewed for this project. As Husaini explained to me:

If someone talks to Ava on social media, yes, they're talking to me, but I am simulating her; her ideas, her personality, the way she speaks. And if you ask if, how I speak and how Ava speaks, are we the same [person]? We are two completely different [people]—we have two completely different personalities.

I observed the same sentiment among other producers, who likewise conceptualise virtual influencers as coherent entities who exist beyond their creators; while their producers are responsible for puppeteering them (see Chapter 3), the characters are not necessarily viewed as self-representational. This bears affinities to cultural anthropologist Teri Silvio's (2019) observation that Taiwanese gamers prefer the term “character” (*jiāose*, 角色) over the term “avatar”, as the entities controlled by the players in-game are perceived as “hav[ing] lives of their own” (p. 48). Likewise, virtual influencers foster an appearance of coherence and agency (see Chapters 6 and 7), reinforced by the significant effort often exerted to ensure audiences do not associate them with those responsible for their creation (see Chapter 10). It is this imagined and often carefully orchestrated distance that informs my conceptualisation of virtual influencers as “characters” throughout the thesis.

Elaborating on how this distance is manufactured, in Chapter 6, I present an overview of what is known in animation-adjacent industries as a production “pipeline” for virtual influencers, outlining the processes, technologies, and considerations involved in creating and managing them. Animation studies offers a particularly useful frame for this chapter as it encourages recognition of the wide-ranging, highly specialised tasks involved in the production of virtual influencers, and the multi-person teams often called upon to complete them. Indeed, as discussed in section 1.2, many virtual influencers are created by virtual influencer agencies whose employees specialise in specific technical and creative skills in order to streamline the production process. The input of multiple producers aligns virtual influencers with what communications scholar Matt Stahl (2011) calls “virtual labor”, a term describing “performative labor that appears to be performed by an individual, but which is actually the result of a division of labor incorporating creative and technical workers, intellectual property, and high-tech equipment” (p. 4), discussed further in Chapter 10.

A recurring interest developed throughout this thesis relates to what anthropologist Shunsuke Nozawa (2013) describes as “characterization” or “becoming-character” (p. 8). Later chapters explore different ways virtual influencers are transformed from “models”—a technical term for objects created with 3D animation technology (see Vaughan, 2011)—into characters, demonstrating a sense of interiority and continuity. For example, in Chapter 6, I detail the design decisions that implicitly or overtly invest virtual influencers with their personality, preferences, and backstory. In Chapter 7, I look at how the interactions of virtual influencers with actual people, places, and objects suggest the characters’ ability to affect the actual world. And in Chapter 8, I consider how geographic contexts and cultural identities are incorporated into the branding efforts virtual influencers use to differentiate and distinguish themselves online.

1.5 Thesis Outline

Chapters 1 to 5 introduce the reader to virtual influencers and establish the contextual, theoretical, and methodological background for this project, while Chapters 6 to 10 focus on the findings of my ethnographic fieldwork.

In **Chapter 1 (Introduction)**, I provided a brief overview of the virtual influencer phenomenon. I discussed the myriad terms by which these entities are known—including CGI influencers, digital avatars, AI influencers, and robot influencers—and introduced the definition of virtual influencers I developed over the course of this project. Key to this definition is the conceptualisation of virtual influencers as characters, which both connects virtual influencers to a historical trajectory of fictional characters being treated as celebrities,

and reiterates that these entities are products of significant creative labour. Both themes recur throughout the thesis.

In **Chapter 2 (Origin Stories)**, I suggest the story of virtual influencers begins three decades before the term “virtual influencer” entered popular parlance, and acquaint the reader with three predecessors for the virtual influencer phenomenon: Hollywood’s “synthespians” (“synthetic thespians”), East Asia’s virtual idols, and the latter’s more contemporary incarnation, Vocaloids, which originated in Japan but have since attained popularity worldwide. Each were created to realise a fantasy of “virtual celebrity”: entities created from digital data to participate in the media and entertainment industries (Yuan, 2025). To varying degrees of success and longevity, these predecessors trialed and advanced the animation technologies, marketing strategies, and platforms that were later taken up by virtual influencers.

In **Chapter 3 (Background)**, I explore the social, cultural, and technological conditions that gave rise to a new incarnation of virtual celebrity in the mid-2010s, one specifically aligned with the figure of the influencer. I begin by recounting the rise of the (human) influencer industry, and the rapid professionalisation and commercialisation of influencer practice throughout the 2010s. I then identify several points of friction that likely made the prospect of virtual influencers more desirable to brands and investors. In the second half of the chapter, I survey the variety of virtual beings found in contemporary online spaces, clarifying the focus and scope of this thesis, while also contextualising virtual influencers as part of an online landscape in which encounters with virtual entities are increasingly commonplace.

In **Chapter 4 (Literature Review)**, I introduce key concepts and conversations that orient my analysis of virtual influencers. I begin by recognising the significant academic interest in virtual influencers from fields such as Information Studies (IS) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), as well as marketing and business studies, and briefly summarise key preoccupations of this broader body of scholarship. This thesis is most closely aligned with a nascent body of critical commentary on virtual influencers by scholars working across media studies, communications, and sociology (e.g. Z. Li, 2024; Miyake, 2022; Yuan, 2025). To give context to the chapters that follow, I discuss key shifts in celebrity culture that gave rise to influencers, including the “demotic turn” (Turner, 2010b) and the rise of “microcelebrity” practice in online spaces (Marwick, 2013; Senft, 2008). I unpack the variation that the term “influencer” tends to elide, and discuss concepts from internet studies which guide my analysis, focusing especially on the value and practices associated with online attention and visibility. I then propose three conceptualisations of virtuality useful for thinking about the “virtual” of virtual influencers: digitality, potentiality, and dimensionality.

In **Chapter 5 (Methods)**, I outline the methodological design for this study. Guided by the tenets of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006) and digital ethnography (Markham, 2017, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012), I combine non-participant observation, online interviews, web archaeology, document and press analysis. I also reflect on my researcher positionality and the ethical considerations navigated throughout this project.

In **Chapter 6 (Production Pipeline)**, I outline the behind-the-scenes technologies and processes involved in creating and managing virtual influencers. I discuss the range of considerations that factor into the ideation of new characters, and argue that what distinguishes this process from other industries involved in creating digital characters (such as film and video games) is an underlying desire to achieve social media visibility. I then detail the production pipeline involved in creating content for virtual influencers, organising this into three components: the *model* (the visual representation of the character), the *stage* (the scene in which the character appears), and the *frame* (the environment in which the content is published). I use this as the analytic framework for the three chapters that follow.

In **Chapter 7 (Staging Liminality)**, I examine moments of interaction between virtual influencers and actual people, places, and objects, considering their effect when initiated within the well-worn templates of visual social media. I focus on virtual influencers' use of selfies, and argue that the characters utilise particular selfie subgenres as opportunities for what I describe as *staged liminality*: scenes where virtuality and actuality collide. I highlight staged liminality as a tactic used by virtual influencers to achieve visibility in algorithmic environments, and to encourage perceptions of the characters as capable of interacting with and affecting the actual world.

In **Chapter 8 (Framing Identity)**, I investigate why, as non-human entities, virtual influencers are often attached to geographic contexts and ascribed cultural identities. Drawing on theories of cultural commodification, I argue that the characters cultivate distinct cultural identities as a self-branding strategy, distinguishing themselves within the fast-growing cohort of virtual influencers, and appealing both to local audiences and international brand partners. Shifting my analytic focus to the social media platforms on which the content of virtual influencers is encountered, I examine how virtual influencers use various affordances forge connections with histories, traditions, and communities from the actual world.

In **Chapter 9 (Modelling Innovation)**, I explore how virtual influencers' bodies are used to promote brands and products. I begin by recognising that virtual influencers emulate many of the commercial practices of human influencers, integrating sponsored messaging into the

fictional lifestyles they depict online. I then highlight a unique visual lexicon often utilised in virtual influencers' large commercial partnerships, which I describe as an *iconography of virtuality*: a collection of tropes, aesthetics, and visual effects that, through their recurring presence in popular culture and especially science fiction media, have come to signify virtuality. I argue that these tropes are used to make the bodies of virtual influencers recognisable as more-than-human, ensuring the characters are able to extend what I call a *halo of innovation* to the actual brands and products they promote.

In **Chapter 10 (Industry Storytelling)**, I look at the industry that quickly emerged around virtual influencers, and the advent of virtual influencer agencies: companies created to specialise in the production and management of virtual influencers. I retell three stories used by stakeholders from the nascent virtual influencer industry to appeal to current and prospective investors. I argue that these shifting storytelling approaches reflect the industry's growing desire to be acknowledged and recognised for the significant human labour, creativity, and expertise on which the characters rely.

In **Chapter 11 (Conclusion)**, I summarise key findings from the thesis, and elaborate the grounded theory of *hyper-virtuality* developed over the course of this project. In the contemporary social media landscape, I argue that virtuality carries a quality of exceptionalism, and that there is value in virtuality that overtly and unashamedly draws attention to its own artifice. I offer suggestions for future research on both virtual influencers and hyper-virtuality, and conclude by reflecting on key developments in the visual social media landscape since my data collection concluded in mid-2022, looking to the future for virtual influencers in an online landscape increasingly saturated by GenAI.

Limitations

This thesis offers an original conceptual framework for analysing virtual influencers, acquainting readers with the industrial and technical histories these characters update, the visual and economic logics of the social media platforms they inhabit, and the industrial desires and tensions they reflected throughout the late 2010s and early 2020s. However, a doctoral thesis does not offer sufficient space or scope to discuss all aspects of a topic as rich and multifaceted as virtual influencers, so there are several prominent themes from the literature on this topic that have been omitted from the discussion that follows. Chief among them is the growing body of scholarship that problematises virtual influencers whose identities are unlike their creators; especially when the identities of their creators carry more privilege—across dimensions such as race, gender, and class—than those that inspire the designs for their characters. Consequently, I would strongly encourage the reader to complement their journey through this thesis by seeking out critiques by scholars such as

Zizi Li (2023, 2024), Esperanza Miyake (2022, 2024), Frida Cerna Neri (2022), and Francesca Sobande (2021a, 2021b) on the politics and political economies of virtual influencers, especially in relation to their appropriation and commodification of racialised aesthetics and identities.

1.6 Formatting

I end this introduction with a brief reflection on stylistic decisions made for this thesis. Firstly, I refer to social media platforms as they were known at the time of data collection. For example, the Chinese visual social media platform Xiaohongshu (小红书)—literally translating to “Little Red Book” in English—was known as such during the period of my fieldwork in 2022 (e.g. Nan, 2021; Ryder, 2022). For users located outside of China, the app has since been rebranded to RED, REDnote, and as of mid-2025, is known as RedNote (stylised on the App Store as rednote). However, reflecting the period in which I was collecting data from and about virtual influencers on the platform, I refer to it as Xiaohongshu throughout. Likewise, I refer to the American microblogging platform Twitter, even though the company was later rebranded to “X” following its sale at the end of 2022 (Mac & Hsu, 2023). I also refer to the Chinese microblogging platform Weibo (微博), the name by which it has been known since dropping the prefix from its original name Sina Weibo (新浪微博) in 2014 (Bischoff, 2014).

Secondly, as suggested by the paragraph above, when referencing terms or names in languages other than English, I have opted to include original scripts alongside transliterations. Likewise, for journalists or scholars writing in languages other than English, when Romanised names were not supplied, I have opted to reference the authors in their native script. As elaborated in Chapter 5, the limited budget and resources of this doctoral project tempered my ability to access professional translation services, so I opted to use freely available, machine-translation tools to generate “gists” (Nurimen, 2021) of text in languages other than English (Abidin et al., 2021). Italics and footnotes are used throughout the thesis to indicate text that has been machine-translated. Reproducing the original script is intended to safe-guard against any errors arising from these translation tools, inviting the reader’s own translations and interpretations, ensuring quotations and references are accurately credited to their original authors, and making resources in languages other than English discoverable by scholars from those linguistic communities.

Thirdly, I intentionally use first-person pronouns (he/she/they) when discussing virtual influencers. Media studies scholars Debopriya Roy and Joya Chakraborty (2023) similarly

discuss deciding “to refer to virtual influencers using ‘they/them’ or ‘he/she’ instead of ‘it’ [as] a deliberate choice” (p. 3). Gender is one facet of the identities that virtual influencers construct through their social media content and activity, albeit often in stereotypical (see Y.-H. Lee & Yuan, 2023; Y. Shin & Lee, 2023), sometimes harmful ways (see Ji et al., 2022; Roy & Chakraborty, 2023). In some cases, my decision to use first-person pronouns has the effect of implying characters’ actions were agentically and independently made, much as you might see in a discussion of a plot in fiction or film. However, it is worth reiterating that the virtual influencers discussed in this thesis do not have agency or independent thought. As of early August 2022, when I formally concluded my data collection, virtual influencers’ words and online interactions were entirely devised and orchestrated by human producers (see Chapter 6).

Finally, I use epithets to signal the international distribution of the virtual influencers I analyse throughout this thesis; for example, introducing Rozy as a “Korean virtual influencer” and Miquela as an “American virtual influencer”. Critical media and technology scholar Esperanza Miyake (2022) rightly problematises the casual use of nationalising epithets in English-language press about virtual influencers: writing specifically of virtual influencer Imma, she notes “‘Western’ popular media texts about Imma never fail to mention she is Japanese”, asking, “How can a virtual influencer be Japanese?” (p. 2). Miyake notes the frequent depiction of Imma in traditional Japanese dress, alongside recognisable Japanese products, and in “typically Japanese places” like “traditional shrines, trendy backstreets of neon Tokyo, [and] shops with Japanese manga paraphernalia” (p. 13; see Chapter 8). She argues that it is more accurate to view Imma as a representation of “Japanese-ness”, as popular ideas or imaginaries of Japan that are “repackaged, ready for global consumption on Instagram” (p. 14). While conscious of this critique, I have chosen to employ these epithets as shorthand to highlight the international distribution of the characters discussed, as well as to acknowledge the local markets for which they were designed (see, for example, Abidin, 2023; Y. Shin & Lee, 2023), and the local platform cultures in which they participate (e.g. L. Luo & Kim, 2024). The ways that virtual influencers seek to enact cultural identities as part of their self-branding efforts is explored in depth in Chapter 8.

Origin Stories

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I introduce three origin stories for virtual influencers, spanning different industries, geographies, temporalities, and technologies. I choose to begin the story of virtual influencers several decades before the term “virtual influencer” entered popular discourse to show how they continue a historical trajectory of creating non-human entities to fulfil the role and functions of (human) celebrity. Acknowledging the precedents for virtual influencers is important, as there is a tendency for media researchers to reproduce the hype surrounding the objects of their study, forgetting the histories of emergent phenomena in their haste to discuss what is new and topical (Bode, 2010). In the introduction to their handbook on internet research, editors Nancy Baym and Annette Markham (2008) remind us that “even those [studying] the cutting edge need to know what remains continuous [...] and what history has to teach us” (p. xiv). As in many other cases, for virtual influencers, these histories are often downplayed or overlooked, precisely because of the symbolic currency carried by novelty and originality in the media, entertainment, and technology industries (see Chapters 9 and 10).

I focus on three origin stories for virtual influencers: “synthespians” (synthetic thespians), virtual idols, and Vocaloids. To varying levels of success and longevity, these three precedents trialled the technologies, marketing strategies, and platforms later adopted by virtual influencers. Each involves fictional characters (see Chapter 1) created with digital technologies to participate within the “apparatus of representation, production, circulation and consumption” (Nayar, 2009, p. 26) of the (human) celebrity industry. Following other scholars (e.g. F. S. L. Cheung et al., 2022; Miyake, 2022; Yuan, 2025), I conceptualise these precedents as examples of “virtual celebrities”: well-known entities created with digital data. Examined together, these examples reveal a longstanding interest in replacing human performers and celebrities with non-human entities, and the valorisation of the virtual by the media and entertainment industries. As explored in later chapters, virtual influencers continue this trajectory, adapting the logic of virtual celebrity for the platforms, cultures, and economics of contemporary social media (Berryman et al., 2021).

My aim in situating virtual influencers as a descendent of these three precedents takes inspiration from virtual worlds scholar Tom Boellstorff (2008), as well as film and digital effects (VFX) scholars Lisa Bode (2010) and Dan North (2014), whose research addresses

the historical precedents for the emergent media phenomenon they study in order to consider “precisely what elements are new and in what ways they are new” (Boellstorff, 2008, p. 25). Likewise, the histories recounted in this chapter reveal that much of what was celebrated as new or spectacular about virtual influencers in early popular or trade press coverage has been done before. After introducing these precedents, the remainder of this thesis explores the ways in which virtual influencers update these histories, looking at the technologies (see Chapter 6), platform logics (see Chapter 7), cultural communities (Chapter 8), and industries (see Chapters 9 and 10) with which virtual influencers intersect.

2.2 Synthespians

The term “synthespian”—a portmanteau of “synthetic” and “thespian”—refers to computer-generated actors created to perform in Hollywood films (Parisi, 1995). These entities are also known as “synthetic actors” (Magnenat-Thalmann & Thalmann, 1987), “virtual actors” (see Boyle, 2004; Faier, 2004; Magnenat Thalmann & Thalmann, 1997; McKay, 1995b), “cyberactors” (F. Rose, 1995), and “artifactors” (Parisi, 1995), with the preferred nomenclature changing to “digital actors” by the first decade of the 21st century (see Bath, 2004; Kurtz, 2004; Lyman, 2001). Throughout the 1990s, synthespians became an increasingly urgent topic of debate in the Hollywood film industry (Hiltzik & Pham, 2001; Parisi, 1995; Silicon Graphics, Inc., 1994). Rapid advancements in digital animation technologies, as well as laser scanning technologies that could be used to precisely recreate human bodies as data, led many filmmakers and producers to fantasise about the potential of these new technologies: if digital bodies could convincingly (and more cost-efficiently) look, sound, and behave like human actors, they may one day be able to replace those humans entirely, not only in filmic performance, but perhaps as celebrities in the entertainment industry writ large (Creed, 2000). As I recount below, despite the buzz surrounding synthespians in the 1990s, by the turn of the 21st century, several poorly received experiments with computer-generated actors meant the prospect of the synthespian was largely abandoned. Even so, the story of synthespians presents a useful frame of reference for virtual influencers, both for the technological genealogy shared between the two, and the parallels in industry discourse surrounding them.

Talk of synthespians began in the late 1980s, amid early experiments with digital animation technologies to create realistic 3D objects and models. By this time, Hollywood had already witnessed the pioneering VFX (digital effects) of films like *TRON* (Lisberger, 1982), but ongoing advances in computational processing, digital displays, and digital animation software were making it possible to model and animate human bodies with increasing accuracy (Magnenat-Thalmann, 2006). In 1987, US animation studio Kleiser-Walczak

Construction Company commenced its “Synthespian Project”, setting out to “create life-like figures based on the digital animation of clay models” (Gibson, as cited in Creed, 2000, p. 81). Kleiser-Walczak debuted their first synthespian, a singer named Dozo, in a 1989 music video called “Don’t Touch Me” (see Kerlow, 2009; Sturman, 1994) and copyrighted the term “synthespian” the same year (Hiltzik & Pham, 2001). In a 2019 interview with online VFX magazine *before & after*, Kleiser-Walczak co-founder Jeff Kleiser reflects on the “Don’t Touch Me” music video as an early experiment in motion capture technology: a multi-camera set-up was used to film a singer adorned with tracking markers as she danced to the song; the markers’ coordinates were then processed and combined to create Dozo as a 3D model (Failes, 2019).

At the same time, working in near parallel to the Kleiser-Walczack team, computer scientists from University of Geneva’s MIRALab were also developing new methods of modelling and animating digital bodies (Magnenat-Thalmann & Thalmann, 1987). In 1987, MIRALab debuted the short film *Rendez-vous à Montréal* (Magnenat-Thalmann & Thalmann, 1987/2018), a computer-generated imagining of a posthumous encounter between Hollywood stars Humphrey Bogart and Marilyn Monroe. As with Dozo, the process of creating the models for the film was complex and time intensive: reflecting on the film’s production, lab leads Nadia Magnenat-Thalmann and Daniel Thalmann (1987) describe the painstaking attention paid to creating limbs for the two stars, commenting, for instance, that they “had to create Humphrey’s thumb and Marilyn’s thumb so that their hands would correspond to their personalities” (p. 10). To create the celebrities in digital form, a sculptor covered different limbs of human models in plaster, moulding casts on which they then drew grids, and photographed from multiple angles. The photos were uploaded to a computer, and combined to digitally reconstruct the grids, creating a “mesh” outline of each 3D limb (p. 10; see also Chapter 6). Once the modelling was complete, the film was produced using a computer programme called Human Factory, which was created to allow “synthetic actors [to be] controlled by animators and designers who have no programming knowledge” (p. 10). The Human Factory software facilitated custom direction of body movements, speech and expression, as well as control over the camera and lighting.

Rendez-vous à Montréal (Magnenat-Thalmann & Thalmann, 1987/2018) was notable as one of the first attempts to use digital animation software to recreate the bodies of Hollywood celebrities. A specific type of synthespian, these so-called “digital clones” are typically “constructed out of pre-existing stored photographic images of stars” and archival footage of past filmic performances (B. King, 2011, p. 254). As Bode (2010) explains, creating digital clones of posthumous subjects (known in some scholarship as “delebs”, or dead celebrities;

see D'Rozario, 2016) involves “a suite of different techniques such as animated computer-generated replicas of faces modeled from film or video references, or the use of digital compositing to paste a recognizable dead person’s face onto a living double’s body within a new mise-en-scène” (p. 48). Analogue efforts to achieve this effect appeared in films like *Dead Men Don’t Wear Plaid* (Reiner, 1982) and *Forrest Gump* (Zemeckis, 1994), and were regularly called upon as a visual spectacle in television commercials throughout the 1990s (see Bode, 2010; D’Rozario, 2016). As digital technologies began to streamline the process of celebrity reanimation, these “posthumous performances” (Bode, 2010) became subject to intense legal debate (see, for example, Logan, 1999). Given the ambiguity around who could permit the use of celebrities’ appearance and performances in the celebrity’s stead, later cases prompted the creation of new legislative provisions and protections for the use of individuals’ likeness after death (see Beard, 1993; Bode, 2010; Giacoppo, 1996).

Celebrity reanimation is an important element in the history of synthespians for its motivation to advance the quality and precision of digital animation technologies. Digitally recreating well-known Hollywood celebrities immediately foregrounds questions of visual fidelity, as audiences evaluate the digital version based on their pre-existing familiarity with the celebrity’s appearance. For example, when discussing another attempt to create a digital Marilyn Monroe, *WIRED* journalist Paula Parisi (1995) quips, “[s]he’s no dead ringer for Marilyn [...] but at certain angles she bears an uncanny resemblance to the original” (p. 204). The comparative aspect inherent in creating a celebrity “double” or “clone” further fuelled the desire to develop software or tools capable of achieving what is known in the film industry as “photorealism” (see Aldred, 2011; see also Chapter 6), replicating the appearance of images created with celluloid film and photography, thereby continuing an “extraordinary realist thrust that has pervaded the commercial (and military) spheres of computer imaging since the middle of the 1970s” (Darley, 2000, p. 82).

Alongside this technological development, it became increasingly commonplace for filmmakers to encounter bodies made of data (Allison, 2011). VFX artists found a wide range of uses for digital bodies, including performing dangerous or impossible stunts (McKay, 1995a; Parisi, 1995); populating large crowds with digital extras (Whissel, 2014); and perhaps most famously, choreographing posthumous performances, such as in the case of superhero movie *The Crow* (Proyas, 1994), whose lead actor, Brandon Lee, was fatally wounded during filming (Creed, 2000). Originally, the time and complexity involved in adding convincing detail to digital bodies meant they were only shown from afar. As an article in the *Los Angeles Times* put it, “While they have been used in crowds and as virtual stunt doubles, none has played a role requiring an extreme close-up because [their appearance]

wouldn't stand up to close scrutiny" (Kaplan, 1999, n.p.). However, laser scanning equipment was soon adopted to add more photorealistic detail to these digital clones. A technology originally designed for military and engineering, these scanners were used to track "the minutest details of the shape, texture, and color" of actors' features, preserving the resulting data for future use (Parisi, 1995, p. 202). By the first decade of the 21st century, scanning was a routine aspect of film production. As Sony Imageworks VFX producer Brian Keeney told *Variety*, "If there's going to be a digital character in the show, cyberscanning is the first thing we do" (as cited in Wolff, 2001, para. 21). The scanning data could also be used in tandem with motion capture systems to facilitate more complex and fluid animation sequences for digital bodies (Sturman, 1994; Wolf, 2003). With such technologies delivering increasingly photorealistic results, digital clones of lead actors could be used in pre-production—as part of the "previz" or "pre-visualisation" stage—to develop the look of the film before production commenced (see Wolff, 2001); and incorporated into post-production, adding "realistic detail" to digital stunt doubles (Allison, 2011, p. 328) or facilitating digital touch-ups and cosmetics (see Holliday, 2021).

As laser scanning and motion capture enhanced the fidelity of digital animations' appearance and movements, they also gave credence to the idea of creating a true synthespian: an actor created entirely of pixels, with no direct referent in the physical world (Aldred, 2011; Allison, 2011). The prospect was of significant appeal to film producers and directors, "who dream of an endlessly pliable performer whose work can be digitally tweaked to generate exactly the desired effect" (Lyman, 2001, para. 19). Film studies scholar Mary Flanagan (1999a) highlights the perceived economic advantages of synthespians, noting that:

While film actors demand higher salaries as they become more popular, virtual stars do not – although the designers of virtual stars do make salary demands, these amounts are generally much less than those of a rising star in the Hollywood system.
(p. 19)

These cost-savings were also echoed by the animators themselves, with production manager Matt Minor of British animation lab Createc explaining to *The Guardian*, "The costs for [...] synthetic characters will decrease massively over time [...] whereas costs of stars will continue to rise" (as cited in Logan, 1999, para. 22). Accordingly, synthespians were framed as a way to "democratise" the filmmaking process by making acting talent more readily available and economically accessible, especially for smaller film production studios. As Minor put it, "If this happens to kill people like Tom Cruise charging £10m for five weeks' work, well, I think it's right that that should die" (as cited in Logan, 1999, para. 22). At the

same time, discussions turned to whether synthespians could function within the broader celebrity ecology, serving as stars in their own right. As psychoanalytic film theorist Barbara Creed (2000) explains:

A digitized film star is a studio's dream: capable of performing any task, continuously available, cost effective - and no scandals, unless, of course, the digital star is given an offscreen life in order to keep alive other areas of the industry such as fan magazines, merchandising and promotions. (p. 80)

The first photorealistic, humanoid synthespian to take on a leading role in a feature film was Aki Ross (Aldred, 2011), protagonist of video game film adaptation *Final Fantasy: The Spirits Within* (Sakaguchi, 2001). Although the film was completely computer-generated, *The Spirits Within* was designed to emulate the principals and appearance of live-action cinema in all aspects (Monnet, 2004). In a 2001 interview with the *Los Angeles Times*, the film's director Hironobu Sakaguchi explained:

Within the first 10 minutes, I want the audience to forget that they are actually watching a [computer-generated] film [...] I want them to feel as if they were watching live humans on film and not see anything unnatural about computer-generated characters. (as cited in Hiltzik & Pham, 2001, para. 11)

Aki Ross was at the centre of the extensive promotional discourse surrounding the film. Trade press "gushed excitedly about the US\$10m hair-do consisting of 60,000 hairs [...] and the 200 digital artists and animators" responsible for designing Aki Ross' photorealistic facial features (Bode, 2006, p. 174). An animation manual published in 2003 notes the software customisations required to deliver the film's photorealistic vision, explaining the animators "used Pixar's Renderman software and customized Alisa Wavefront's Maya, creating approximately 100 plug-ins for, among other things, cloth effects, human movement, [and] realistic flowing hair and follicles" (Burns, 2003, p. 10). Screen studies scholar Jessica L. Aldred (2011) observes that the promotional material for the film elided "the multiple material underpinnings" of Aki Ross, including her human voice actor Ming-Na Wen and actress Tori Eldrige, who provided the motion capture for Aki Ross' movements, "in favour of highlighting how [Aki Ross was] entirely constructed in virtual computer space" (n.p.; see also Leaver, 2012). The privileging of virtuality was underscored by Aki Ross' animator Roy Sato, who explained to *Associated Press*, "Unfortunately, actors are kind of bound to their own personal style, their own personal way of doing things [...] [w]hereas with Aki, well ... [sic] I can make her do anything I want" (as cited in Aldred, 2011, para. 6).

Despite the industry hype which preceded *The Spirits Within*, the film was a failure at the US box office (Monnet, 2004). The immense technical mastery and resources involved in creating Aki Ross were overshadowed by her blank eyes and waxy skin, which was described as having an “unnatural smoothness” (Bode, 2006, p. 174). In the end, Aki Ross’s costly photorealistic design proved more repellent than compelling, by no means assisted by “a plot more derivative and cliched than any of the numerous video games on which it was based” (Leaver, 2012, pp. 153–154). The film’s poor reception “stalled similar projects and [rendered] the virtual actor, as an attraction in its own right, a risky proposition rather than a utopian ideal” (North, 2014, p. 88). Instead of attempting to produce convincingly photorealistic, humanoid digital stars, attention turned to the computer-generated creation of non-human characters, like actor Andy Serkis’s Gollum (see Aitken et al., 2004; Jenkins, 2003; North, 2008) and King Kong (see Allison, 2011), who received a far more positive reception from film-goers.

While the fantasy of the synthespian was mostly abandoned by the early 21st century (Bode, 2006), the project nonetheless figured as a major incentive for developing animation technologies capable of rendering photorealistic appearances, and captivating on-screen performances. Many of the techniques, tools, and software developed to bring synthespians to Hollywood screens continue to be used the production of virtual influencers (see Chapter 6), making synthespians one of virtual influencer’s primary technological predecessors. Today, these digital animation technologies are capable of producing imagery almost indistinguishable as computer-generated. Moreover, the improved hardware capabilities of personal computers and advancements in cloud-based animation software have extended their creative potential beyond major Hollywood film studios, making them increasingly accessible to independent and aspiring animators, as well as virtual influencer producers, which I discuss further in later chapters.

2.3 Virtual Idols

The second origin story for virtual influencers involves virtual idols (バーチャルアイドル, *bācharu aidoru*): fictitious musical performers created with computer-generated imagery and/or voices, whose appearance, personalities, and talents are designed to succeed in East Asia’s idol industries (D. Black, 2006). Virtual idols originated in Japan’s media and entertainment industries, where the term “idol” is used to describe “young performers who sing, pose for photographs, and appear frequently in media” (Galbraith & Karlin, 2012, pp. 4–5). Unlike synthespians, who were primarily created to deliver filmic performances, and barely extended beyond their movies’ borders, virtual idols were from the outset created as portable entities who could appear across different media forms, achieving the visibility and

saturation demanded of idols in East Asian markets (D. Black, 2006; Galbraith & Karlin, 2012). Of the three origin stories in this chapter, I consider virtual idols to be virtual influencers' closest predecessor, creating a blueprint many virtual influencers would later follow. Both are shaped by the demands of specific celebrity industries (idol and influencer, respectively), and court attention and consumption from audiences by spanning a wide network of mediated environments and commercial goods. Virtual idols also experimented with the interplay of virtual and actual for which virtual influencers would later become known (see Chapter 7), regularly appearing in the same mediated spaces as human celebrities, and being depicted in locations from the actual world.

Japan has been called the “geographical epicentre of the virtual idol phenomenon” (D. Black, 2006, n.p.), a descriptor which coheres with the country's documented affinity for animated characters. Animated characters are considered ubiquitous in Japan, from the “working characters” used to alert, instruct, and illustrate information on urban signage (see Alt & Yoda, 2007; Wilde, 2018), to the recognisable *kyara* (キャラ, characters) like Astro Boy and Hello Kitty that adorn a wide variety of consumer goods (see Gough & Lee, 2020; Occhi, 2010). Both form part of what anthropologists Hiroshi Aoyagi and Mateja Kovacic (2021) describe as the country's “ecosystem of character-idolatry or character-centred production-consumption” (p. 24), which has been in operation since the 1960s, when Japan's “content industry” (コンテンツ産業, *kontentsu sangyō*) was established to support the production of *anime* (アニメ) films and television series, video games, and *manga* (漫画) comics (Steinberg, 2012).

The earliest examples of virtual idols were fictional characters from *anime* and video games, who underwent a process of “idolization” (Galbraith, 2021, p. 75). Characters such as Lynn Minmay (リン・ミンメイ) and Sharon Apple (シャロン・アップル) from popular *anime* franchise *Super Dimension Fortress Macross* (超時空要塞マクロス), as well as Fujisaki Shiori (詩織藤崎), protagonist of dating simulator video game *Tokimeki Memorial* (ときめきメモリアル, 1994), were granted musical careers, releasing singles and CDs throughout the 1980s and early 1990s (see Figure 2.1; Galbraith, 2021; Yoshida, 2004/2016). For Lynn Minmay and Sharon Apple, who were singers and performers within the narratives of their *anime*, this was a logical crossover. But for Fujisaki Shiori, it was her particular popularity among players of *Tokimeki Memorial*—with an official fanclub of more than 10,000 members two years after the game's debut (Pollack, 1996)—that prompted her creators to grant her a musical career.

Figure 2.1: Three early virtual idol album covers. Left: Lynn Minmay's vinyl album, "Do You Remember Love?" (1984); source: Ebay (VinylStore-Japan, 2025), screengrab by author on 26 July 2025. Centre: Sharon Apple's first single, "The Cream P•U•F" (1995); source: Discogs (Sharon Apple, 1995), screengrab by author on 16 December 2022. Right: Fujisaki Shiori's first album, "My Sweet Valentine" (1997); source: Discogs (Shiori Fujisaki, 1997), screengrab by author on 16 December 2022.

Songs by early virtual idols were released without mention of the voice actor (声優, *seiyū*) to whom the characters owed their talents (Sone, 2017; Yoshida, 2004/2016), encouraging perceptions that the characters themselves were idols. Magazines and radio show hosts perpetuated the illusion, talking about the characters as though they were actual people (Galbraith, 2021). The characters appeared across a range of "idol goods" (アイドルグッズ, *aidoru guzzu*), including "CDs, DVDs, photo albums and cards, posters, calendars, and stationary" (Aoyagi & Kovacic, 2021, p. 39), which were purchased by fans of their original media properties, as well as new audiences accumulated through their visibility in the idol industry.

Efforts to create original characters to take on the role of idols commenced in the early 1990s, following a period of waning interest in idols among Japanese audiences. While the 1980s was considered a "golden age of idols" (アイドルの黄金時代, *aidoru no ōgon jidai*), with up to fifty new idols debuting each year (Galbraith, 2018, p. 204), by the 1990s, Japan's idol industry was experiencing an "idol ice age" (アイドル氷河期, *aidoru hyōgaki*) or "winter time of idols" (アイドル冬の時代, *aidoru fuyu no jidai*; Galbraith & Karlin, 2012, p. 24). Idol studies scholar Patrick W. Galbraith (2012) attributes this lull to "market saturation, scandal, and competition from other types of music" (p. 192). The stagnating popularity of idols was of significant concern to the industry reliant upon their continued commercial success. In Japan, the figureheads of the idol industry are talent agencies known as *jimusho* (事務所, literally translating to "office"). Pioneering a production model that would later become standard for music industries across East Asia, *jimusho* oversee the entire lifecycle of idols, selecting, training, (micro-)managing, and promoting idol talent (Marx, 2012). To appeal to a wide audiences and prospective brand partners, *jimusho* maintain tight control over the public image of their idols, famously issuing contracts that prohibit female idols from

“drink[ing] alcohol, smok[ing], or be[ing] seen in the company of men” (Galbraith & Karlin, 2012, p. 8). In this context, media scholar Daniel Black (2008) proposes virtual idols were “a logical progression from the more established model of idol creation” (p. 38), explaining:

Rather than invest considerable time and resources in the moulding and packaging of a biological body in order to create a product which can only ever approximate an ideal, and which will inevitably lose its appeal as it ages, the virtual idol promises the possibility of building an idol to order, ensuring that it perfectly reflects consumer tastes and will never change. (p. 38)

The world’s first computer-generated idol debuted in Japan in November 1996. Date Kyōko (伊達杏子), also known as DK-96 (Digital Kid 1996), was commissioned by leading Japanese idol *jimusho* HoriPro and created by computer graphics agency Visual Science Laboratory (D. Black, 2008). Date Kyōko was the first purpose-built virtual idol, without a former life as an *anime* or video game character (Flanagan, 1999b). According to UK newspaper *The Guardian*, creating Date Kyōko took a team of ten animators more than two years (Dodson, 2003). Her 3D design was created with a digital skeleton that could accommodate fluid body movements and dancing using motion capture, and comprised over 40,000 polygons, achieving a level of visual fidelity that, at the time, made it “easy to mistake printouts of Date for photographs of human subjects” (Flanagan, 1999b, p. 84). In a matter of months, Date Kyōko released two music singles, made a guest appearance on a local radio talk show (D. Black, 2008), and was enlisted as an ambassador for a San Francisco-based 3D software developer (Kadrey, 1998). Foreshadowing a dynamic that would come to characterise the content of virtual influencers (see Chapter 7), Date Kyōko’s music videos often showed her interacting with locations from the real world; her single “Love Communication” (1996), for example, shows her walking and dancing around the streets of New York City, her animated body composited onto actual footage (see Frank, 2007). However, Date Kyōko’s career was short-lived. She was quietly retired just a year after her debut (Dodson, 2003), with two unsuccessful relaunches: in 2001, as DK-2001, on a student portal for the Kanazawa Institute of Technology (杉浦正武, 2002); and in 2007, as DK-2007, as a MC for HoriPro idol events in the popular virtual world *Second Life* (J-CAST NEWS, 2007; see Figure 2.2).

Figure 2.2: Three incarnations of Date Kyōko. Left: The original, as DK-96; source: 伊達杏子DK-96のG1Grouper (G1G, 1996), accessed via Wayback Machine. Centre: DK-2001, for Kanazawa Institute of Technology; source: ITmedia (杉浦正武, 2002). Right: DK-2007, as a MC for HoriPro in *Second Life*; source: J-CAST ニュース (J-CAST NEWS, 2007). Screenshots by author on 9 May 2023.

Despite her short lifespan, Date Kyōko prototyped a formula many others were inspired to emulate (Flanagan, 1999b). Her creation spawned what cultural and media studies scholars refer to as different “iterations” (Y. Cho, 2011; Iwabuchi, 2014) of virtual idols across East Asia. Throughout the 1990s, Korea was home to several local “cyber idols” (사이버가수, *saibeogasu*), including the first male virtual idol, Adam (아담), launched by Korean software company Adamsoft (McClure, 1998; S. Park, 1998; see Chapter 8). By the early-2000s, the phenomenon had spread to the UK and Europe, where a roster of “virtual pop stars” were discussed in press (e.g. Austen, 2000; Gillies, 1999; ‘Fast Forward: Virtual Pop Stars’, 2000; ‘Virtual Pop Star’s Chart Bid’, 2000).

In 1997, not long after the debut of Date Kyōko, a second virtual idol, Terai Yuki (寺井有紀) was introduced, illustrating virtual idols’ commercial potential to a fuller extent than her predecessor (D. Black, 2006). Designed by animator Kutsugi Kenichi, Terai Yuki first “appeared on Kutsugi’s own homepage as part of his experimentation with 3-D graphics”, and later featured as a centre-fold model in *Weekly Young Jump* (週刊ヤングジャンプ, *Skukan Yangu Janpu*) magazine (North, 2014, p. 86). Following her public debut, Terai Yuki was licensed by software education company extage (later renamed Frog Entertainment), who saw an opportunity to develop Terai Yuki into a virtual idol (D. Black, 2006). Like Date, Terai Yuki released several musical singles, including “ETC/Bohemia” (1999), “Fly Away Alone” (2000), and “My Dearest You” (2000). She even appeared in a national television commercial for Lion Etiquette toothpaste, starring alongside (and embracing) a human co-star (see Figure 2.4; see also Chapter 7). However, unlike the *jimusho* that created Date Kyōko, Terai Yuki’s owners were chiefly “concerned with technical education, and the publication of magazines and reference books aimed at computer animators, rather than being experienced in the management of media personalities” (D. Black, 2006, n.p.).

Working with software developer eFrontier, extage made Terai Yuki available as an asset that could be purchased and downloaded for use in the 3D animation software Shade, “providing amateur computer graphics artists with resources similar to those used to professionally model and animate Yuki” (D. Black, 2006, n.p.). Black (2006) highlights this as a pivotal moment in the history of virtual celebrity, “introduc[ing] new methods of consuming celebrity” that spanned Terai Yuki’s capacity both “as a piece of intellectual property and media celebrity whose persona and representation is under extage’s control, and [...] as a set of data which can be utilised by the general public for whatever ends it desires” (n.p.).

extage’s conceptualisation of Terai Yuki as data that could be easily replicated and edited was reflected in the company’s varied approaches to commercialisation. In addition to music videos, Terai Yuki appeared on a wide range of idol goods, starring in television commercials, short film anthologies, video games, computer software, and adorning many other kinds of merchandise (see Figure 2.3). Much more effectively than Date Kyōko, Terai Yuki realised the malleability, multiplicity, and “transferability” of idols made entirely of data, who could be “composited into any situation, playing various short film roles in a number of geographical and temporal settings, while also releasing pop albums and appearing in advertisements” (North, 2014, p. 86). This transferability made Terai Yuki competitive in Japan’s local media landscape, where idols appear across a “complex network of information that includes wide shows, tabloid newspapers, weekly magazines, variety programs, [and] social media” (Galbraith & Karlin, 2012, p. 10), serving (much like animated characters) as a ubiquitous feature of daily life. The capacity of Terai Yuki’s digital body to travel across this range of media formats and consumable goods assisted her in stepping into the role, expectations, and environments associated with human idols. Within three years, Terai Yuki was reported to have a fan base of over 30,000 (D. Black, 2008, p. 38),

Figure 2.3: Various idol goods featuring Japanese virtual idol Terai Yuki. Left: DVDs of short film anthologies; source: Mercari (miyu, n.d.), screengrab by author 26 July 2025. Centre left: Terai Yuki on the cover of the *Primal Image* (2000) video game for Playstation 2, source: IMDb (*Primal Image Vol. 1 (2000)*, n.d.). Centre right: A Terai Yuki action figure; source: Yahoo! Auctions (タイタイ, n.d.). Right: Terai Yuki novelty clocks, source: Yahoo! Auctions (テライユキ 写真立てクロック 1, n.d.). All other screengrabs by author 16 December 2022.

and her idol goods were released until at least 2003 (*Yuki Terai Secrets*, 2005), marking a five-year-long idol career significantly outlasting her predecessor.

In addition to creating audience interest through publicity, creators of early virtual idols were also tasked with what anthropologist Shunsuke Nozawa (2013) calls “characterization” or “becoming-character”: the process of transforming something into a character (p. 10). Because computer-generated virtual idols like Date Kyōko and Terai Yuki did not originate in mainstream *anime* or video games, they could not rely on a larger media property to establish their narrative backstories or cultivate audience affection. It was thus commonplace for magazine interviews, official websites, and merchandise to develop the character of the virtual idol. For example, archival snapshots show the radio show on which Date Kyōko briefly starred uploaded a profile to their website describing her early life in Fussa, Tokyo. According to the fictional profile, Date Kyōko was scouted by a talent agent while working part-time in a fast-food restaurant near her local train station. The profile also features specific biographical details (including her body measurements, vision accuracy, birthdate, star sign, and blood type), and much like a celebrity magazine interview, answers about Date Kyōko’s favourite movies, actors, music, romantic history, and future aspirations (プロフィール, 1997). Flanagan (1999b) notes this biography ascribed Date Kyōko a “girl-next-door” image [...] constructed to make her as human as possible” (p. 84). However, characterisation is a delicate balancing act, tasked with maintaining audience appeal, investment, and attention (Flanagan, 1999b). For virtual idols like Date Kyōko, characterisation was a largely expository effort, established for their debut but rarely further developed, nor flexible enough to accommodate audience feedback or input. In Flanagan’s view, these virtual idols were “too well-defined to sustain interest” (p. 85). Virtual influencers would revise this approach, using each successive update to their social media feeds to reveal more detail about their backstories (see Chapter 6), or offer narrative updates, in what has been described by an anonymous industry insider as a “panel-by-panel storytelling” approach (Anonymous, as cited in Widdoes, 2018, para. 12; see also Guthrie, 2020).

The history of virtual idols reveals early efforts to commercialise celebrities created from digital data. Set against the backdrop of Japan’s idol industry, the creators of early virtual idols applied many of the same strategies effective for manufacturing human idols to create familiarity and stoke desire for these new fictional characters. They generated awareness by inserting their characters into mediated spaces traditionally inhabited by human idols, and added depth to their characters through radio interviews, and detailed biographies in magazines, websites, and on idol good packaging. To a greater degree than synthesians, whose technical development was motivated by a desire to appear indistinguishable from

human actors, the producers of virtual idols were unafraid to toy with the border between virtual and actual (see Chapter 4). Early virtual idols appeared in actual locations in their music videos, and alongside actual human co-stars in television commercials (see Figure 2.4), foreshadowing the interplay between virtual and actual utilised by virtual influencers to capture attention online more than two decades later (see Chapter 7).

Figure 2.4: Virtual idols experiment with the interplay between virtuality and actuality. Left: Date Kyōko walks through New York City in the music video for her 1996 single “Love Communication”; source: YouTube (Frank, 2007). Right: Terai Yuki kisses a human actor in a television commercial for Lion Etiquette toothpaste, standing before the Rainbow Bridge in Tokyo; source: YouTube (sTwoJapan, 2012). Video screengrabs by author on 22 July 2025.

2.4 Vocaloids

The third origin story for virtual influencers are Vocaloids (ボカロイド, *bōkaroido*), the most commercially successful model of virtual celebrity to-date. Like virtual idols, Vocaloids also originate in Japan. Their name derives from a digital voice synthesizer called VOCALOID, created by audio equipment and software producer Yamaha. First released in 2004, the VOCALOID software allows users to transform text input into voice fonts, modifying the tone and pitch to compose synthetic musical performances (Conner, 2016; Sousa, 2016). At its launch, Yamaha’s VOCALOID software was originally targeted at professional musicians and producers, but after low initial sales, the software’s Japanese distributor, Crypton Future Media (hereafter Crypton), commissioned character designs representing each voice font in an effort to appeal to a wider audience (Annett, 2015). The visual style of these characters was quite unlike that of synthespians or the early virtual idols discussed in previous sections, who both leveraged cutting-edge animation technology in pursuit of photorealistic, humanoid appearances; by contrast, the characters commissioned by Crypton adopted the stylised aesthetics of the immensely popular ACG (*Anime*, Comics & Games) industry, making their fictionality visually explicit (see Figure 2.5). The first Japanese-language voice font to receive a character form, Meiko (メイコ), reportedly “sold three thousand packages in the first year instead of [the average annual sales of] one thousand” packages (Sone, 2017, p. 141), an

early indicator of the market for these animated designs. One of the characters introduced in the software's second release (VOCALOID 2) in 2007 was blue-haired Hatsune Miku (初音ミク), who proved an “immediate, unexpected and unprecedented” success (Sousa, 2016, p. 118), and continues as the most popular Vocaloid today. In popular discourse, Hatsune Miku is perhaps best-known for her sell-out concerts, produced by Crypton, where her image is projected onto glass and translucent materials to deliver live, “holographic” performances (Conner, 2016; Leavitt et al., 2016).

Figure 2.5: Crypton Future Media added animations to the product boxes of Yamaha's VOCALOID software. Left: Meiko for VOCALOID, released in 2004; source: Crypton Future Media ([ソフト音源] MEIKO, n.d.). Right: Hatsune Miku for VOCALOID 2, released in 2007; source: Crypton Future Media ([ソフト音源] HATSUNE MIKU, n.d.). Screenshots by author on 22 July 2025.

While some scholars suggest “it is the power of anthropomorphic characterization that has made this technology globally popular” (Nozawa, 2013, n.p.), for others (e.g. Guga, 2015b; Leavitt et al., 2016) the success of Vocaloids reflects the “participatory” (Jenkins, 2006) affordances of the VOCALOID software in the context of the social web. Vocaloids differ from most other types of virtual celebrity in a central aspect: although a corporation designs the animated bodies for these characters, it is the audience that is invited to puppeteer them. With the exception of Terai Yuki, the late 1990s virtual idol sold as a digital asset, Vocaloids were revolutionary for their invitation to fans to take ownership of the characters. Using the VOCALOID synthesizing software and fan-made programmes like MikuMikuDance (MMD), fans produce original songs and choreography for their favourite Vocaloids to perform (Guga, 2015b). These creations can then be shared on user-generated video platforms like Bilibili (哔哩哔哩, also known as B Site, Station B, or B站), NicoNico (ニコニコ), YouTube, as well as Crypton's own peer-to-peer file-sharing platform PiaPro. These activities embody the ethos of “participatory culture”, a term famously associated with media and fan studies scholar Henry Jenkins, which describes a dynamic of media reception in which the roles of producers and consumers are increasingly blurred. As Jenkins (2006) explains, participatory

culture:

has its roots in practices that have occurred just below the radar of the media industry throughout the twentieth century, [but] the Web has pushed that hidden layer of cultural activity into the foreground [...] allowing [media consumers] to participate in the production and distribution of cultural goods—on their own terms. (p. 137)

In this case, the “production and distribution of cultural goods” (Jenkins, 2006, p. 137) relates to the fans’ contributions to the careers of their favourite Vocaloids. In theory, anyone could purchase the VOCALOID software, or learn how to use MMD, to create and share original songs and dance videos, thereby contributing to the Vocaloid’s discography and popularity (Leavitt et al., 2016). The circulation of fan-generated works is facilitated by a permissive licensing agreement known as the “PiaPro (Peer Production) Character License”, which allows fans to “noncommercially transform and recreate Hatsune Miku’s image, and create derivative works from it at no cost” (Zaborowski, 2016, p. 116; see also Condry, 2017). Importantly, the songs and choreography created for Vocaloids are not only intended for online circulation: there is also a chance that fan compositions will be selected for concert set-lists or official CDs (Leavitt et al., 2016). As internet studies scholar Alex Leavitt, digital media scholar Tara Knight, and Japan studies scholar Alex Yoshiba (2016) point out, “[m]any people, especially internationally, [first] encounter [Hatsune Miku] through YouTube videos of [her] concerts” (p. 215); the fan-made works showcased at these events thus become “entry points for new fans into the peer production community, engaging them further with fan art, cosplay, or even creating videos and music themselves”, sustaining a cycle of fan participation (p. 215).

Such opportunities for fan participation extend even to authorship of the Vocaloids as characters. Unlike virtual idols, for example, Vocaloids have few official biographical details. According to Crypton, Hatsune Miku is “a sixteen-year-old girl, 158 cm tall, weighing 42 kg, and with a passion for idol style and dance music” (Zaborowski, 2016, p. 115). This loose outline leaves the process of “characterization” (Nozawa, 2013) to fans, who are empowered to fill in the blanks with their own stories, theories, and creativity. As Black (2006) summarises, Hatsune Miku’s “existence as nothing but digital data allows her fans to personalize her and orchestrate the production of new performances according to their own particular desires” (p. 224). The onus on fan involvement has led scholars to describe Vocaloids as “open-source singer[s]” (Rambarran, 2016, p. 122), and “editable” (Leavitt et al., 2016, p. 217) or “crowd-sourced” (Condry, 2017) celebrities. While Yamaha’s voicebanks were originally made in Japanese and English, demand for an expanded product range—especially from Hatsune Miku’s international fan base—gave rise to new iterations of

Vocaloids who have achieved significant popularity in other languages and countries, including SeeU (시유) in Korea and Chinese “vSinger” Luo Tianyi (洛天依). For media scholar Ian Condry (2011), Vocaloids represent the winning formula for virtual celebrities: “Various companies have been experimenting with their own virtual idols since Date Kyoko’s debut in 1996, but centralized production and control was not successful; crowd-sourced openness generated the virtual idol star” (p. 12).

Although fans play an active role contributing to Hatsune Miku’s “overall stardom” (Guga, 2015b, p. 40), it is worth noting that their “grassroots artistic participation” occurs within a structure of “corporate sponsorship and partnership” (Leavitt et al., 2016, p. 202). Hatsune Miku’s image is regularly licensed to third parties, and she has become an immensely popular and successful “image character” (イメージキャラクター, *imēji kyarakuta*) in Japan, appearing on a wide range of products, and encouraging consumption of goods and services simply through her association with them (Karlin, 2012). Since her debut, Hatsune Miku has appeared “in convenience stores (Family Mart), in video games (SEGA), and in hundreds of ancillary commercial goods (from expensive Louis Vuitton branding to generic food and toys in convenience stores)” (Leavitt et al., 2016, p. 209). In addition to such commercial partnerships, Crypton also profits from a “diverse [collection of] revenue streams” including “the Vocaloid software itself, video game titles, manga adaptations, public performances, live online streaming, songs featured in karaoke chain stores, CDs and DVDs of performances and miscellaneous merchandise” (Yuan, 2025, p. 323). By combining more traditional idol marketing approaches, while at the same time encouraging fan creativity and online peer production, Vocaloids have revolutionised and reinvigorated the model sketched by earlier examples of virtual idols, achieving sustained, transnational success for almost two decades.

Vocaloids offer a vision of virtual celebrity built upon the “participatory culture” (Jenkins, 2006) of the contemporary web, whereby fans are primarily responsible for contributing the creativity that maintains the characters’ relevance, originality, and lore. The fans’ participation is then repackaged by the characters’ distributors for profit (Leavitt et al., 2016). The continued popularity and commercial success of Vocaloids like Hatsune Miku and Luo Tianyi offers evidence not only for the contemporary appetite for virtual celebrity, but also for the capacity for virtual celebrity to thrive in an online ecosystem increasingly organised by social media platforms and shaped by algorithmic logics (see Chapter 4). Indeed, Leavitt et al. (2016) discuss how algorithms influence the Vocaloid fan works that achieve the greatest online popularity, writing that, “[a]s certain songs and videos become popular, they gain more visibility, thus lending points to recommendation algorithms, leading to more people

seeing those videos and their view counts increasing exponentially” (p. 218). As discussed especially in Chapters 6 and 7, these algorithmic logics are also key forces shaping the designs and practices of virtual influencers, functioning as intermediaries for the popularity and opportunities the characters are able to access.

2.5 Summary

In this chapter, I introduced three origin stories for virtual influencers: synthespians, virtual idols, and Vocaloids. I first recounted the history of Hollywood’s synthespians, an industry myth which motivated the development of digital animation technologies capable of capturing, reproducing, and creating celebrities as data, many of which are still used in the production of virtual influencers today (see Chapter 6). I then turned to Japan’s virtual idols, considering the approaches used to commodify and characterise idols made entirely of computer-generated imagery. Recalling the “cross-dimensional travel” (Nozawa, 2013) between fiction and reality central to ACG fan cultures (see Chapter 4), virtual idols initiated experiments with the boundary between virtual and actual, which would later become a key feature in the social media content of virtual influencers (see Chapter 7). In the final section, I introduced the figure of the Vocaloid, noting the participatory logics that have fuelled the transnational popularity of characters like Hatsune Miku since the mid-2000s. Like Vocaloids, virtual influencers are also encountered primarily on social media platforms, and their success is dependent on the algorithms (see Chapters 6 and 7) and affordances (see Chapter 8) which shape these online environments, discussed at length in the later chapters of this thesis.

I view synthespians, virtual idols, and Vocaloids as three of virtual influencers’ most influential precedents, each contributing to, experimenting with, refining, and legitimising the concept of virtual celebrity. Although the accomplishments of these predecessors are often overlooked in popular accounts of virtual influencers, they are not wholly ignored by the characters’ producers. During my fieldwork, I observed Korean virtual influencer Rozy and Brazilian-Korean virtual influencer Theo posting content referencing Korean virtual idol Adam (see Figure 2.6; also Chapter 8); and in an interview with *a16z Podcast*, Trevor McFedries, co-creator of American virtual influencer Lil Miquela, quipped, “We’re standing on the shoulders of giants like [Hatsune] Miku” (S. Smith, 2023, 5:00). For McFedries, Hatsune Miku’s mainstream success set the stage for other genres and examples of virtual celebrity to emerge, attesting that the virtual body did not always elicit the response of earlier experiments such as *The Spirit Within*’s Aki Ross. Recalling Flanagan’s (1998b) suggestion that “[t]rue digital stars, that is, stars without need of their own physical body, did not exist until our culture was ready to rethink the body in the context of technology” (p. 91), for

Figure 2.6: Virtual influencers acknowledge their virtual idol predecessors on Instagram. Left: Korean virtual influencer Rozy posts a screen recording of one of Adam’s songs, and refers to him in the text caption as her “조상” (*josang*, “ancestor”); source: Instagram Stories, screengrab by author on 31 May 2022. Right: Brazilian-Korean virtual influencer Theo posts a video of Korean virtual idol Adam, writing in his caption: “*eu estou carregando seu legado*” (“*I’m carrying your legacy*”); source: Instagram (Theo 테오 [@theo.rises], 2022), video screengrab by author on 23 October 2023.

McFedries, the significant popularity and profitability of Hatsune Miku established both the cultural and industrial framework for virtual influencers’ debut in the late 2010s.

The legacy of these precedents is perhaps best illustrated by the strikingly similar industry discourse that surrounds them. When industry stakeholders and marketing professionals speak about virtual influencers, they emphasise the ability to fully control the characters’ behaviour, minimizing risks of brand scandals or controversies (e.g. Bradley, 2020; Dodt, 2020; Yates, 2020); their perpetual youth (e.g. AFP News Agency, 2021; H.-S. Ahn & Lee, 2021); their superhuman productivity, “around-the-clock work ethic” (AFP News Agency, 2021, n.p.) and “availab[ility] whenever needed” (Keegan, 2022, n.p.); as well as the portability afforded by the immateriality of their digital bodies (e.g. E.-J. Park, 2021; 강경희, 2021). These themes almost perfectly reproduce the industry discussions surrounding synthesians, virtual idols, and Vocaloids over the last three decades. These figures have likewise been praised for their ability to “make ‘appearances’ in all types of media forms simultaneously” (see Flanagan, 1999a, p. 19); their capacity to “be tweaked in both style and substance for each market” (Kadrey, 1997, n.p.); and their “amazing consistency” in always delivering perfect performances (Baseel, 2014, n.p.). Then and now, in discussions of virtual celebrity, commentary valorises the more-than-human capabilities of digital bodies (see Chapter 9), using language that strategically minimises the significant human resource, time,

and skill required behind-the-scenes to maintain these illusions (see Chapter 10). A driving ambition for this thesis is to demystify such illusions for virtual influencers, emphasising the immense involvement, creativity, and skill of their producers in bringing these characters to life.

As illustrated throughout this thesis, synthespians, virtual idols, and Vocaloids pioneered of many of the production techniques, commercial approaches, and digital platforms used by the virtual influencers I studied. By acknowledging the longstanding trajectory of virtual celebrity, we can more fully appreciate what is new and novel about virtual influencers, focusing on their practices within the context and cultures of visual social media platforms.

Background

3.1 Introduction

In Chapter 2, I highlighted that the concept of virtual celebrity has a much longer history than much mainstream discourse on virtual influencers would suggest. In this chapter, I consider the social, industrial, and technological conditions that brought about a new kind of virtual celebrity in the mid-2010s, one aligned with the figure of the influencer. The chapter proceeds in two parts. In the first half, I situate the emergence and evolution of virtual influencers in relation to the rapid maturation and growth of the (human) influencer industry throughout the 2010s. By 2018, when virtual influencers were entering mainstream view (see Chapter 1), the concept and commercial practices of the influencer were well-established. Press stories about top-tier influencers had helped to cement “influencer” as both a viable full-time vocation and a highly desirable career path: a 2017 report from Chinese news agency Xinhua found that in China, 54% of university graduates born after 1995 hoped to become an internet celebrity (新华网, 2017), echoed by a report from US research firm Morning Consult (2019) that 54% of Americans aged 13 to 38 would become an influencer if given the opportunity. As the number of participants and economic scale of this industry grew, there emerged a mounting sense of disillusionment with influencers among marketers, fallout from a growing number of influencer scandals, and as of 2020, threats to the sustainability of influencer practice following the global onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. I use this discussion to highlight why the prospect of *virtual* influencers was considered desirable, both for the producers who intended to profit from them, and the brands and marketers who agreed to partner with them.

The second half of the chapter frames virtual influencers as one of a growing number of virtual beings encountered online, particularly on social media platforms. Clarifying the scope of this thesis, this section disambiguates virtual influencers from other types of virtual entities found on social media—including virtual humans, virtual mannequins, and vTubers (virtual YouTubers)—through a focus on their perceived agency. Specifically, I highlight that virtual influencers are always reliant on the creativity, input, and actions of their producers, even as they strategically encourage perceptions of individual autonomy and sentience (see Chapter 7). This framework establishes important context for later chapters, which consider how the overestimation of virtual influencers’ agency is visualised in commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9), and leveraged in stories by the industry that surrounds them (see Chapter 10).

3.2 Influencers

The origins of the term “influencer” have been traced to the book *Personal Influence* (1955/2006), written by communications scholars Elihu Katz and Paul F. Lazarsfeld (Abidin, 2017b). Challenging earlier models of communication that privileged institutions, Katz and Lazarsfeld emphasised the role of people within the flow of communication, highlighting how individuals intercept and relay messages to their personal networks. This conceptualisation continues to shape how the term “influencer” is applied in business and marketing studies, where it is used interchangeably with terms like “Key Opinion Leader” (or “KOL”; e.g. Atwal, 2022; J. Luo, 2021) to describe “a model of marketing and advertising that targets key individuals who exert influence over a large pool of potential customers” (Abidin, 2017b, p. 159). In the context of social media, the term “influencer” carries additional nuance, not only describing someone who has potential sway over the opinions or purchasing decisions of others, but whose credibility and personal networks are established through the content they upload to social media. The definition I follow in this thesis conceptualises influencers as:

everyday, ordinary Internet users who accumulate a relatively large following on [...] social media through the textual and visual narration of their personal lives and lifestyles, engage with their following in digital and physical spaces, and monetise their following. (Abidin, 2015a, n.p.)

Influencers are ordinary people who have achieved popularity and sustained attention through their use of networked technologies. Today, they are often associated with social media platforms with strong visual cultures, including Instagram, TikTok, and Xiaohongshu (小红书). Many terms are used to describe influencers on these and other platforms, including localised terms like “*wanghong*” (网红) in China; platform-specific terms like “TikTokers”; and titles more closely aligned with cultural production, such as “content creators” (see Bishop, 2021b). In Chapter 4, I expand upon the significant variation which is often elided by the catch-all descriptor of “influencer” (Abidin, 2021a), but in this chapter, I adopt a macro lens, considering the broader landscape into which virtual influencers debuted.

3.2.1 History

Influencers descend from several earlier models of content production, self-branding (see Chapter 4), and entrepreneurship which appeared online in the late 1990s and early 2000s. Prior to the adoption of the term “influencer” in the 2010s (Abidin, 2018a), a range of terms were used to describe individuals undertaking these practices across different geographic contexts, including Japan’s “net idols” (ネットアイドル, *netto aidoru*; see Lukács, 2015,

2020), Singapore's "blogshop owners" (see Abidin & Thompson, 2012; Fletcher & Greenhill, 2009), and the so-called "camgirls" (see Senft, 2008) and "bloggers" (see Duffy & Hund, 2015; Pham, 2015) popular in North America. These prototypical influencers were predominantly young women who leveraged the growing availability, domesticity, and capabilities of early digital technologies to create and manage an online presence, and accumulate online popularity using personal profiles, blogs, and websites. They attracted audiences not only for the creative talents they showcased online (such as modelling, writing, art, and photography), but also for the intimate access they offered into their daily lives, thoughts, and emotions, and the significant time and effort they devoted to interacting with those who engaged with their content (see Lukács, 2015). These proto-influencers experimented with approaches to commercialising their online presence, adding display advertisements to their personal websites (see Abidin, 2018a), paywalling exclusive content for paying subscribers (see Senft, 2008), and creating and publishing sponsored messaging for brand partners (see Abidin & Ots, 2016). Together, they pioneered models of online popularity that fused personality-focused content with commercial opportunities, establishing a template that influencers (both human and virtual) would later follow.

Throughout the 2010s, the rise of social media platforms, the affordability of mobile media technology such as smartphones, and more reliable access to data and wireless internet connections enabled "global, interactive and commercial communication, on a scale and at a speed hitherto not possible except for privileged elites" (Khamis et al., 2017, p. 196). At the same time, the rise of image-oriented social media platforms like Instagram and Tumblr, as well as video-sharing platforms like YouTube, Vine, Snapchat, and later TikTok, cemented the centrality of the visual in "everyday life and social media practices", and engendered new forms of visual communication and self-presentation (Highfield & Leaver, 2016, p. 49). It was in this context that influencers rose to prominence, adapting and reimagining the practices pioneered by bloggers, blogshop owners, camgirls, and net idols to a new array of digital tools and platforms, increasingly commercialised environments, and vast online audiences. Although influencers were initially distinguished from celebrities by virtue of being "everyday, ordinary Internet users" (Abidin, 2015, n.p.), these individuals were quickly enveloped by an industry reminiscent of traditional forms of celebrity.

3.2.2 Industry

The debut of virtual influencers in the late 2010s coincided with a period of rapid growth for the (human) influencer industry. In 2016, the same year that American virtual influencer Lil Miquela first appeared on Instagram (see Chapter 1), the global influencer industry was already valued at an estimated USD\$2.3 billion (Statista Research Department, 2025). The

influencer industry comprises “influencers and those who aspire to be them, marketers and technologists, brands and sponsors, [and] social media corporations” (Hund, 2023, p. 6). While some influencers work independently, managing their own career progression and commercial endeavours (see Abidin, 2018a; Guo, 2022), others work with “cultural intermediaries” who assist aspiring and established influencers alike to “build and manage attention capital” on social media (Rojek, 2014, p. 458; see also Stoldt et al., 2019). Examples of these cultural intermediaries include talent networks (see Cunningham et al., 2016; Lobato, 2016), as well as PR firms and advertising agencies (see Abidin, 2018a; Foster, 2022), who profit by “connect[ing] influencers with commercial opportunities and offer a spectrum of support [...] in exchange for a percentage of influencer income” (Bishop, 2021a, p. 3). In China, where a leading genre of influencers are known as “*wanghong*”—an abbreviation of “*wangluo hongren*” (网络红人), translating to “person who is red [popular] on the internet”—so-called “*wanghong* incubators” support aspiring *wanghong* with multi-month training courses, teaching curriculum on “photography, image retouching, modelling, [content] production, and e-commerce”, and connecting them to “marketing and content production professionals [...] to build up their popularity” on popular local apps (X. Han, 2021, p. 322; see also Abidin et al., 2021). Influencer aspirants can likewise access training and resources to advance their careers via dedicated courses (see S. Edwards, 2022), coaches (see Annabell, 2025), and conferences (see Stoldt et al., 2019). The combined efforts of these intermediaries, and the growing cultural cache of the influencers themselves, fuelled a highly lucrative and rapidly expanding industry. By 2020, the global influencer industry’s estimated value had grown to USD\$9.7 billion; as of 2024, it was valued at USD\$24 billion (Statista Research Department, 2025). It was this fast-growing and increasingly lucrative industry into which virtual influencers were designed to debut.

3.2.3 Commercialisation

A key factor contributing to the growth of the influencer industry was influencers’ ability to reach people spending an increasing portion of daily life online (Asquith & Fraser, 2020; Childers et al., 2019). These shifting trends in media consumption had been underway since the beginning of the 2010s, continuing throughout the decade: between 2010 and 2014, a global survey by advertising agency ZenithOptimedia found consumers were spending less time with television (-6%), print newspapers (-26%), and print magazines (-19%) each day, but significantly more time online (+84%; see Richter, 2015). By 2018, the same year that the term “virtual influencer” began to appear in press (see Chapter 1), market research company GlobalWebIndex (2019) claimed the average person spent six hours and 45 minutes online each day. While, on the one hand, this made digital media an increasingly

desirable marketing channel, reticence towards obtrusive forms of digital advertising—such as banners, pop-ups, and pre-roll videos—posed a threat to marketers’ ability to reach and resonate with customers via existing media formats (Asquith & Fraser, 2020). Given their content was often already aligned with “commercial verticals like travel, fashion, beauty, wellness, lifestyle, sport, and video gaming” (S. Edwards, 2022, p. 3), influencers became increasingly attractive to marketers as a way to seamlessly integrate commercial messaging into the spaces and styles of content that potential customers were actively choosing to consume.

For marketers, influencers’ appeal lay both in the strong connection they fostered with audiences, and in the personalised tone of their endorsements (Arriagada & Bishop, 2021). Because they were typically unaffiliated with specific brands, influencers’ recommendations were perceived as more credible and trustworthy (Abidin & Ots, 2016). As brands and marketers channelled more spend towards influencer endorsements, influencers adapted at pace to the industrial infrastructure emerging around them, “becoming more professional and aware of their role in the branding process, [and] offering various services to companies” (Abidin & Ots, 2016, p. 155). Recalling the prototypical figures discussed in section 3.2.1, influencers codified a range of commercial post “templates” (Leaver et al., 2020; see Chapter 4) to integrate sponsored messaging into their social media content. Examples of these commercial templates included sartorial showcases known as “OOTDs” (or “Outfit of the Day” posts; see Abidin, 2016d), posts documenting the “unboxing” of gifts and promotional packages sent by brands (see Marchand et al., 2024), and posts about attending exclusive brand events and marketing activations (see Chapter 9). Together, these posts “cultivate[d] desire for an attractive life and its trappings, in a mediated environment that [made] the wares and associated lifestyles [on display] seem immediately accessible” (Hund & McGuigan, 2019, p. 27). Hashtags like #ad, #spon, and #paid became widespread signals for influencer content created as part of a value exchange, with advertising bodies in several countries around the world legislating commercial disclosures of this kind (Asquith & Fraser, 2020).

Influencers’ paradigmatic commercial format is the “advertorial”—a portmanteau of “advertisement” and “editorial”—which fuses commercial intent with the influencers’ purportedly authentic voice and point-of-view (Abidin & Ots, 2016; Arriagada & Bishop, 2021). Advertorials are “highly personalised, opinion-laden promotions of products/services that influencers personally experience and endorse for a fee” (Abidin, 2015a, n.p.). The format is commonly used to promote “facial and beauty products and services, plastic surgery and cosmetic enhancements, apparel and fashion, food and beverages, and travel”

(Abidin, 2018a, p. 76). The persuasiveness of the advertorial relies on “experiential authority”, whereby influencers emphasise they “have actually taken the time and effort to try [a product or service] out themselves before making an honest recommendation” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 107). However, as discussed further in Chapter 9, the commercial activities I observed among virtual influencers rarely emulated the advertorial format, perhaps reflecting critics’ concerns about fictional characters promoting products they are incapable of using, testing, or experiencing first-hand (e.g. L. Lee, 2022; ‘Reality Check’, 2020). Instead, virtual influencers more often called upon a distinct visual lexicon to bestow favourable meanings onto the brands and products they were enlisted to promote.

There are several ways influencers may be compensated for their promotions, including free products or services, exclusive access to brand events, or financial remuneration. Costs of influencer endorsements “fluctuate depending on the popularity of the Influencer as measured by their follower count, the type of product featured, and the nature of the campaign” (Abidin, 2016a, p. 7). However, as influencers’ audiences grew, so too did the rates they were able to negotiate (Perelli, 2019). While estimates vary across regions and markets (see Abidin, 2018a; Graziani, 2019), in a 2018 interview with *Vice*, the CEO of North American influencer agency Viral Nation suggested that influencers with up to 1 million followers could earn up to USD\$10,000 per sponsored post, and those with more than 1 million followers could charge upwards of USD\$100,000 (Lieber, 2018). The financial success of top-tier influencers became a recurring focus in popular press (e.g. Ap, 2017; Carey, 2018; Wallace, 2018), contributing to a fantasy of the “glam life” (Duffy & Hund, 2015) for those at the top rungs of the industry (see Chapter 9).

As these top-tier influencers negotiated higher rates, influencers with fewer followers became an increasingly attractive option for marketers. Known in the marketing industry as “nano-influencers” (up to 1,000 followers) and “micro-influencers” (up to 100,000 followers; see K. Fowler & Thomas, 2023), these influencers were celebrated for their ability to reach specific audience niches, achieve higher levels of engagement, and foster more positive responses to sponsored messaging (Influencer Marketing Hub, 2020). A 2020 industry report from The Influencer Marketing Hub estimates the average cost of a sponsored Instagram post from a micro-influencer with 1,000 to 100,000 followers to be between USD\$100 to USD\$5,000 (Geysler, 2020). Growing interest in nano- and micro-influencers welcomed a greater number of individuals into the influencer industry, promising opportunities for financial remuneration even for those with fewer social media followers.

Alongside advertorials, influencers can also earn money directly from the platforms they use to connect with audiences. Platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube have each

introduced monetisation schemes, making it possible for influencers to earn money from content with high views or engagement (such as likes, comments, and shares; Bishop, 2021b). However, ever-changing platform algorithms and threats of demonetisation, which make content ineligible under the monetisation schemes, have rendered these programs unpredictable and unreliable sources of income (Caplan & Gillespie, 2020; Glatt, 2022b; see also Chapter 4). It is therefore not uncommon for influencers to supplement platform monetisation and brand partnerships with other revenue streams, including affiliate marketing (receiving commission from brokering product sales), paid media and event appearances, fan patronage (through platforms like Patreon), personalised fan content (through platforms like Cameo), online shopfronts, and merchandise (Graziani, 2019; Perelli & Whateley, 2020). While many influencer aspirants devote time to building an online presence around full-time jobs, those most successful at these entrepreneurial efforts have been able to devote to themselves to social media full-time, becoming influencers as their primary vocation (Hund, 2017; Yusup, 2017). As the influencer industry continued to expand, the rewards for those capable of succeeding within it grew increasingly alluring. However, alongside this growth, several factors began to threaten the industry's sustainability, and created opportunities for *virtual* influencers to succeed.

3.2.4 Oversaturation

By the late 2010s, the same lowered barriers to the technologies, platforms, and audiences which had given rise to influencers had resulted in an abundance of influencer aspirants. With the population of influencers worldwide approaching an estimated 200 million (Linktree, 2022), trade commentary spoke of “customer fatigue” and “frustration” at the “never-ending stream of promotional content produced by unknown, generic influencers” (Gu, 2018, n.p.), and referenced consumers’ “growing appetite for something more real and original” (J. Luo, 2018, para. 2). Social media feeds were filled with the same photo filters (Lorenz, 2018a), poses (Abidin, 2016a), and backgrounds (H. Chang & Spierings, 2023; Liu, 2021), leading to “social fatigue towards the highly performative, aestheticised and impossibly beautiful digital world of social media” (Miyake, 2022, p. 11). Indeed, by the late 2010s, “the pretty, pristine, and picturesque [had] become boring” (Abidin, 2018b, n.p.), leading many influencers to begin producing content with a less polished aesthetic, and foreshadowing the focus on casual influencer content engendered by the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 (Abidin et al., 2020; see section 3.2.6).

Among this fast-growing influencer cohort, popularity was unequally distributed. Despite the meritocratic rhetoric that surrounds the influencer industry (see Chapter 4), popular influencers often align with hegemonic ideals of beauty, being young, light-skinned, slender,

and able-bodied (Foster, 2022; see also Chapter 6). Conversely, those “across intersections of marginalised identity” are often subject to “underpayment and platform obscuration”, creating additional barriers to success (Bishop, 2021a, p. 1). Moreover, the scale of visibility was highly skewed. A report by online branding portal Linktree (2022) estimated that only 20% of influencers had between 10,000 to 100,000 followers; the vast majority (69%) had less than 10,000 followers, a trend also observed in other markets (e.g. China; see Wei, 2023). Only 2% (four million) were estimated to have over 100,000 followers, and just 1% (two million) more than one million followers (Linktree, 2022).

Contending with such high levels of competition, aspiring influencers were forced to invest significant labour into standing out (see Chapter 6). Influencers were challenged to “conceive of ever-new features, topics, and visuals to make their content seem worthwhile to prospective audiences” (Stein et al., 2024, p. 2). In this context, where aesthetic distinction was highly coveted, virtual influencers presented a means of renewing the influencer formula, creating something new from what was familiar (see Chapter 7). Speaking with press, Christopher Travers, creator of virtual influencer directory and news platform VirtualHumans.org, posited that “creating truly innovative experiences ([using] virtual influencers)” was one of the most promising areas for growth in the oversaturated influencer industry: “It’s no longer about the human—it’s about the experience as a whole” (as cited in Fang, 2020, para. 8).

3.2.5 Unpredictability

Although they often worked closely with talent agents, managers, and advisors, human influencers were increasingly perceived by brands and marketers as unpredictable (Guthrie, 2020). From the revelation that Australian influencer Belle Gibson was faking her cancer diagnosis (see Baker & Rojek, 2020), to tax evasion scandals (see Pan, 2018), and resurfaced content with slurs and other offensive commentary (see Ohlheiser, 2018), news cycles throughout the 2010s were dominated by stories of influencer faux pas. The potential for “scandal spillover”, whereby the negative response to a disgraced influencers might affect brands associated with them, fuelled anxiety among marketers (Kintu & Ben-Slimane, 2020). Industry attention turned to “brand safety”, a term describing media considered suitable for sponsored messaging due to its “positive reproduction of a brand’s ideals, an avoidance of controversy, and a circumvention of sex, violence, and profanity” (Bishop, 2021a, p. 4). According to a report by Influencer Marketing Hub (2020), 84% of marketers felt brand safety was a topic of concern when running influencer marketing campaigns. To assuage marketer anxieties, various “influencer management tools” were introduced in rapid succession, developed to “present analytics data and make algorithmic calculations

designed to support marketers in selecting appropriate influencers for advertising campaigns, through subjective calculations about influencers' *brand safety* and *risk*" (Bishop, 2021a, p. 1, original emphasis). As of 2020, an estimated "40% of brands" were utilising these "third-party tools to support their digital marketing campaigns" (Bishop, 2021a, p. 2), utilising their algorithmic rankings to screen and select prospective influencer partners based on their use of profanity, audience sentiment, and press coverage. At the same time, platforms tightened their community guidelines for content that was deemed brand safe, in turn shaping how influencers produced content to appeal both to potential brand partners and platform monetisation schemes (Bishop, 2018; Kumar, 2019).

In this context, virtual influencers were praised for their "controllability" (Oliveira & Chimenti, 2021), lacking the "agentic spontaneity" (Drenten & Brooks, 2020, p. 3) that would make them susceptible to incriminating faux pas. As an executive from an American influencer agency explained:

When you're using regular influencers you have all the inherent risks of people living their lives; people can get DUI's, get arrested, say non PC [politically correct] things. You'll always have that risk. With CGI influencers, you'll have a markedly better chance of that not happening. (Detert, as cited in S. Phillips, 2018, para. 5)

While some commentators felt that the calculation involved in devising virtual influencers' behaviour would make them less interesting (see Peckham, 2020), others pointed out that "[s]ome brands enjoy the safety of associating with (virtual) influencers who have a pre-defined backstory and future" (Travers, as cited in AFP News Agency, 2021, para. 20). Marketers felt virtual influencers were less likely to go "off-message and [embarrass] a client" (Graham, 2019, n.p.) because their words and actions were purposefully devised, sometimes by multi-person creative teams (Allal-Chérif et al., 2024, p. 9; see Chapter 10). Grace Kwak, then Global Alliance Director at Tokyo-based virtual influencer agency 1sec Inc., stressed the appeal of controllability for prospective brand partners. In an interview with *Vice* magazine, Kwak explained, "When we talk to companies, the first thing they say is, 'Oh great, [virtual influencers are] not going to get arrested for drugs.' [...] It's a big worry they have right now" (as cited in Yates, 2020, para. 15).

Although later events would prove that virtual influencers could still be the subject of scandals (see Brendza, 2019; Cain, 2022; Haasch, 2020; Richards, 2019), virtual influencers were nevertheless celebrated in popular and trade commentary as a potential salve to the unpredictability of their human counterparts. They cultivated an impression of being "absolutely scandal-free" (Ewe, 2021, n.p.), with some commentators going so far as to

describe them as “post-scandal” (E. Holmes, 2018, n.p.). While human influencers foregrounded their ordinariness to appeal to audiences and brands, for virtual influencers, it was precisely their non-humanness that tempted marketers and brands seeking brand-safe commercial partners (Moustakas et al., 2020).

3.2.6 COVID-19 Pandemic

A particular turning point for influencer marketing was the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020. As infection rates and death tolls rose, people around the world followed government-mandated lockdowns and shelter-in-place orders to limit the transmission of the virus. With social distancing measures in place, people shifted “most of their economic and social activity to virtual spaces” (Yuan, 2025, p. 319). Social media use surged, with a reported 70% of internet users aged 16 to 64 spending more time using their smartphones; 47% spending more time on their computer; and 43% of users spending more time on social media (Kemp, 2020).

On the one hand, influencers seemed safe from most pandemic interruptions, given they could still “independently produce advertorial content from domestic spaces” (Bishop, 2021a, p. 2). However, while some types of influencers could continue to produce their usual genre of content (such as gaming influencers, who create content or host livestreams focused on gameplay), others struggled to adapt to lockdown conditions (Abidin et al., 2020). Travel influencers were especially affected by the onset of the COVID-19 restrictions and international travel bans, which prohibited them from visiting the glamorous or exotic locations that typically populated their social media feeds (Femenia-Serra et al., 2022). Lifestyle influencers, whose feeds were previously populated by trips to new cafes, stores, and glamorous events (see Chapters 7 and 9), were also forced to adjust their content to suit the lockdowns, physical restrictions, and “affective atmosphere” (Lupton, 2021) of the pandemic (Abidin et al., 2020).

With so many people spending time on social media, influencers seemed an especially appealing proposition for brands and marketers, with a larger prospective online audience than ever before (Kemp, 2020). Indeed, some influencers were recruited by local governments and health agencies to spread public health messaging for how to limit the spread of the virus, as well as to offer support and guidance for managing mental health and wellbeing in lockdown (see Abidin et al., 2021; Reinikainen et al., 2022). But in the first months of the pandemic, opportunities for commercial partnerships were increasingly scarce. The uncertainty of the pandemic and speculation of potential economic downturns prompted marketers to freeze their campaign spends, and postpone or cancel upcoming

campaign activity (Stewart, 2020).

By late 2020, marketers were resuming their spend and advertising activity (Perelli et al., 2020), but the COVID-19's initial impact had already raised questions about the influencer industry's resistance to pandemic-related disruptions moving forward. This created new opportunities for virtual influencers: as their producers emphasised in press, virtual influencers' incorporeal bodies could not be affected by the virus (e.g. Ang, 2020; Whateley & Bradley, 2020; 강경희, 2021). Press discussions of virtual influencers often mentioned virtual influencers' immunity to the effects of COVID-19 lockdowns (e.g. Teh, 2021), exemplified by this discussion of Korean virtual influencer Rozy:

*A representative of Sidus Studio X said, "In the world of virtual influencers, there is no such thing as 'impossible' because you can do whatever you want," and "Due to the recent restrictions on outside activities due to COVID-19, there are no restrictions for virtual characters, so you can look forward to Rozy's active activities in the future."*¹ (조성준, 2021, para. 5)

Likewise, Kara Weber, CEO of Los Angeles-based virtual influencer agency Brud, the creators of Lil Miquela, told *Business Insider*, "During the COVID pandemic when other artists can't go anywhere, Miquela can be anywhere" (as cited in Whateley & Bradley, 2020, para. 3). As the pandemic continued, debuts of new virtual influencers were increasingly attributed to the capacity for virtual influencers to work despite COVID-19 restrictions (see Lew, 2023; Suwanrumpha, 2021). For example, Thai virtual influencer Ai Ailynn was described as "largely born out of pandemic limitations" (Mei, 2021, para. 5), with her producers describing her in a comment to *The Straits Times* newspaper as a way "to overcome limitations like social distancing" (SIA Bangkok, as cited in Mei, 2021, para. 6). This commentary largely overlooked that the production of virtual influencers often involves physical tasks, including travel for photographers and body doubles who stand-in for the characters on location (see Chapter 6). Omitting this detail, as well as the labour of the other producers involved in the production pipeline (see Chapters 6 and 10), virtual influencers were roundly praised for their "around-the-clock work ethic" (AFP News Agency, 2021, n.p.)

¹ Italicised text machine translated by Google Translate. Original text: "싸이더스스튜디오엑스 관계자는 "가상 인플루언서들의 세계에서는 원하는 대로 바로 실현이 가능해 '불가능'이란 없다"며 "신종코로나바이러스감염증(코로나19)으로 인해 외부 활동의 제약이 커진 현재, 가상 인물에겐 제약이 없어 앞으로도 로지의 활발한 활동을 기대해도 좋다"고 말했다" (조성준, 2021, para. 5).

and “availab[ility] whenever needed” (Keegan, 2022, n.p.).

According to producers, brand interest in working with virtual influencers grew after the global onset of COVID-19. Brud told *Business Insider* that their “roster of virtual influencers ha[d] seen a boost in interest from brands” within the first few months of the pandemic (Whateley & Bradley, 2020, para. 15). The interest appeared to continue throughout the next year: in August 2021, Chen Yan, CEO of Beijing Next Generation Culture Media (北京次世文化传媒有限公司) and creator of Chinese virtual influencer Ling, told China’s *Global Times* newspaper that “demand from various brands for virtual images has surged since last year, when the COVID-19 pandemic brought more attention to digital assets” (H. Zhang, 2021, n.p.). This commentary reveals how the virtual was valorised amid the COVID-19 pandemic, with marketers especially drawn to the capacity for virtual influencers’ incorporeal, datafied forms to do what human influencers’ fleshy bodies could not.

3.3 Virtual Encounters

As suggested by the discussions in Chapter 2, encountering virtual beings online is not new (see also Matrix, 2006), but the 2010s offered opportunities to encounter these entities in social media environments. For instance, vlogger (video blogger) Ami Yamato, whose large brown eyes, wide smile, and waxy smooth skin give her the appearance of a 3D *anime* character, has been uploading videos to YouTube since June 2011 (Ami Yamato, 2011). She often posts vlogs documenting daily happenings in her life, wandering the streets of London or attending fan conventions, but has not yet directly addressed that her appearance is clearly a product of digital animation software (Schmieder, 2024). In another case, Lu, the animated brand mascot of Brazilian big-box retailer Magazine Luiza (also known as Magalu) was created in 2003, but has become “the primary face of the brand” alongside the expansion of Magalu’s social media strategy (Engström, 2022, p. 284). Since 2014, she has featured prominently on the brand’s Instagram account (Lu do Magalu [@magazineluiza], n.d.), appearing in “product reviews, unboxings” and technology tutorials, as well as posts with “dancing, do-it-yourself tips, and recipes” (Engström, 2022, p. 284). And in 2017, a verified Twitter account was created for Alex Hunter, a fictional football player first introduced in the 2016 video game *FIFA 17*, teasing details about the franchise’s next instalment and promoting footwear for sportswear manufacturer Adidas (Alex Hunter [@MrAlexHunter], n.d.). As these brief snapshots suggest, prior to the adoption of the term “virtual influencer”, virtual characters were already active on social media, engaging with the formats, “vernaculars”—that is, the “shared [...] conventions and grammars of communication” (Gibbs et al., 2015, p. 257)—and even commercial practices aligned with these spaces.

These examples, alongside the virtual influencers studied in this thesis, form part of an increasingly populous cohort of virtual beings found in online spaces, varying in technological capabilities, technical production, and intended purpose. In this section, I disambiguate the virtual influencers of interest in this thesis from several other contemporary examples of virtual beings. Focusing especially on the varying levels of involvement required from their producers, I split my discussion into three categories: virtual humans, virtual mannequins, and virtual puppets. In brief, virtual humans are programmed for high-level processing, and are capable of undertaking tasks independently of their producers. On the other end of the spectrum, virtual mannequins are computer-generated bodies whose primary function is to be dressed and displayed, much like digital dolls. Finally, plotted between the two, virtual puppets are graphical representations whose voices and actions are “performed” by human operators. This latter sub-category houses many of the most popular examples of virtual beings online today, including virtual influencers and vTubers (virtual YouTubers). I detail these categories not only to highlight the significant variety among virtual beings on the contemporary web, but also because of the regularity with which these examples are conflated. Virtual influencers are often perceived (see Chapter 7) or positioned (see Chapter 10) as examples of more technologically advanced and autonomous virtual humans; and virtual mannequins are often equated with virtual influencers (see Chapter 1), despite not projecting the same level of interiority or consistency.

3.3.1 Virtual Humans

In their book *Virtual Humans: Today and Tomorrow* (2020), engineer David Burden and education studies scholar Maggi Savin-Baden define virtual humans as “a digital entity (or perhaps, more generally, a program, algorithm or even a process) which (looks) thinks, feels and behaves like a human” (p. 16). For Burden and Savin-Baden, what characterises virtual humans is not just their visual, aural, or behavioural affinity to humans, but more importantly, the “higher functions” (p. 7) they are perceived to have, such as the ability to problem-solve, learn, reason, remember, and create (see Chapter 7). Often powered by complex algorithms, speech recognition, and machine-learning models, it is important to note that no virtual human currently in existence can be considered “Artificial General Intelligence (AGI)” —understood as artificial intelligence “that equals or surpasses humans across a wide range of cognitive endeavours” (Srdarov & Leaver, 2024, n.p.)—although this is the aspiration for many such experiments.

The category of virtual humans spans a wide range of examples, including chatbots created for friendship, like Korea’s Lee Luda (이루다; see Choon, 2021) and China’s Xiaoice (小冰; see Spencer, 2018), as well as chatbots that can be programmed for romantic

companionship, like Replika, created by a San Francisco start-up (see A. Chen & Li, 2021). It also includes voice assistants like Amazon's Alexa, Apple's Siri, and Google's Assistant, as well as the "embodied conversational agents" (Cassell, 2001) used to field customer queries on company websites, which increasingly take the form of photorealistic 3D avatars (see Chapter 6), like those created by New Zealand-based start-ups Uneeq (see Elder, 2020) and Soul Machines (see Bellan, 2022). A more recent addition to this category are digital representations of posthumous public figures (see Chapter 2) trained on large datasets of their personal journals and published articles, like the digital clone of artist Leonardo da Vinci created by MIT Media Lab (Pataranutaporn et al., 2023). In each case, these examples are programmed to appear with human-like abilities and, most importantly, are capable of demonstrating "higher functions" (Burden & Savin-Baden, 2020, p. 7) independently of their producers. Virtual influencers are often conflated with these more technologically advanced virtual humans. In Chapter 7, I examine how the character's behaviours contribute to this perception, and in Chapter 10, I consider how it is used as a marketing strategy by the emergent virtual influencer industry.

3.3.2 Virtual Mannequins

Virtual mannequins are created with digital animation software for the primary purpose of displaying clothes and other commercial products. Unlike virtual humans, virtual mannequins are not capable of acting autonomously; instead, they are made to be looked at and displayed. Virtual mannequins are of significant interest to the fashion industry, who have become increasingly invested in virtual fashion—garments and accessories created with 3D computer-generated imagery—as a potential salve for industry sustainability (BOF Team, 2020).

Perhaps the best-known virtual mannequin is Shudu, a dark-skinned 3D model created in 2017 by white British photographer Cameron-James Wilson. As an article in fashion magazine *WWD* describes it, "Wilson made [Shudu] with fashion in mind" (Tietjen, 2018, n.p.), taking inspiration for her appearance from a collector's edition Princess of South Africa Barbie doll and several actual models of colour, including Nyadak "Duckie" Thot, "Iman, Alek Wek, Naomi Campbell and Grace Jones" (Wong, 2018, n.p.; see also Rosenstein, 2018). In an interview with the *BBC*, Wilson explicitly describes Shudu "as a kind of mannequin. Once you've created her, you can pose her and give her an expression", equating the experience to "having a doll, a dress-up Barbie" (as cited in D. Fowler, 2018, para. 24). Since her debut, Shudu has collaborated with numerous fashion brands, appeared in leading fashion magazines, and partnered with brands including consumer electronics manufacturer Samsung (see Figure 3.1) and luxury automotive brand Lexus (see Figure 3.2). The

character's growing media presence motivated Wilson to hire writer and children's fiction editor Ama Badu as the "voice" of Shudu, and it is Badu that writes "as" Shudu in press interviews (e.g. O. Phillips, 2019). Thanks to Shudu's success, Wilson now runs a company called The Diigitals—which brands itself as the "world's first all-digital modelling agency"—with a full cast of virtual mannequins available for hire (see Turrell, 2021).

Figure 3.1: Virtual mannequin Shudu promotes the Samsung Galaxy Flip smartphone. The use of first-person "I" in the caption expresses the opinions of her creator, Cameron-James Wilson. Source: Instagram (Shudu [@shudu.gram], 2020), screengrab by author on 4 October 2024.

Figure 3.2: Virtual mannequin Shudu poses in a futuristic concept car for a paid partnership with luxury automotive brand Lexus. Source: Instagram (Shudu [@shudu.gram], 2021), video screengrab by author 2 June 2022.

The entities I refer to as virtual mannequins are often known by various combinations of terms such as “model”, “3D”, “virtual”, and “CGI”. Previous scholarship has referred to them as “virtual models” (e.g. Robinson, 2020), “3D virtual models” (e.g. Jang & Yoh, 2020), and “CGI fashion models” (e.g. S.-J. Cho & Yim, 2019), while press also calls them “virtual models” (e.g. Boan, 2018) and “CGI models” (e.g. Cadogan & Alemodu, 2018; Cresci, 2018). Perhaps surprisingly, given this array of competing terms, virtual mannequins have been active since the 1990s, when they were described as “virtual supermodels” (see Matrix, 2006). The first dedicated modelling division for computer-generated models, Illusion2K, was launched in 1999 by major modelling agency Elite Model Management (Matrix, 2006, p. 115). Then and now, virtual mannequins bear a strong affinity to the “digital paper dolls” featured in the computer games known as KISS or *Kisekae* Set System (with the Japanese “*kisekae*”, or 着せ替え, translating to “changing clothes”), first introduced in Japan in the 1990s. Transforming a popular children’s pastime into an interactive experience, in KISS games, digital “dolls can be dressed and undressed by dragging clothes and accessories from the margins of the computer screen onto the body” (Gorfinkel & Zimmerman, 1997, p. 2). In much the same way, virtual mannequins can be dressed and draped with 3D clothing, whether it be a bespoke item designed in programs like Clo3D, or apparel purchased from virtual fashion marketplaces like DressX (see Chapter 6).

Virtual mannequins do not have a subjective perspective that remains consistent across all content and media. For example, although Badu has developed a personality for Shudu expressed through her interviews in press, Shudu’s Instagram account is still primarily authored by Wilson, who speaks about Shudu as though she is an art project, and uses hashtags like #3dart (Leaver et al., 2020). This is the key difference between virtual mannequins and virtual influencers: across social media platforms and media appearances, virtual influencers curate a sense of interiority and maintain consistency. In so doing, virtual influencers encourage feelings of persistence, that they exist as a character beyond the posts on their social media feeds, unlike virtual mannequins, who are, by and large, called upon to be momentarily looked at.

3.3.3 Virtual Puppets

The final category, virtual puppets, refers to computer-generated characters whose actions and words are controlled by human input, and animated using digital technologies. This category takes inspiration from puppetry scholar Stephen Kaplin’s (1999) taxonomy of American puppet theatre, which was early to acknowledge the rising popularity of computer-generated figures puppeteered by unseen sources. At the time of my fieldwork, virtual influencers fit squarely into this category. I am far from the first to make this connection; puppet metaphors regularly appear in popular commentary on virtual influencers. For instance, one article in *USA Today* describes them as “a new kind of influencer, one whose image, agency and voice lie in the hands of people pulling their strings behind-the-scenes, often unbeknownst to their human followers” (Trepany, 2019, n.p.). The term has also appeared (albeit less often) in virtual influencer scholarship: in their study of customer perceptions of virtual influencers, business management scholars Carla Rossi and Francesca Rivetti (2023), describe “the team that created (and manages) the [virtual influencer as] a ‘hidden’ orchestrator, safely holding the strings of a *digital puppet* with a human appearance” (p. 238, emphasis added); anthropologist of technology Ada Florentyna Pawlak (2023) likewise describes virtual influencer producers as “digital puppet masters” who control “synthetic character[s]” (p. 89). As illustrated by the chapters that follow, it is the labour, creativity, and dedication of these (typically unseen) puppeteers on whom virtual influencers rely for their animation (Silvio, 2019).

Alongside virtual influencers, another notable example of virtual puppets are vTubers (ブイチューバー, *buichūbā*)—an abbreviation of “virtual YouTubers” (バーチャルユーチューバー, *bācharu yūchūbā*)—used to describe content creators whose actions and voices are expressed through 2D or 3D characters. Aesthetically, many vTubers draw from what *anime* studies scholar Stevie Suan (2021b) calls the “anime-esque”, encompassing the “many

conventionalized elements [...] that make anime recognizable” (p. 31). For example, vTubers often share the large eyes, long limbs, and angular features associated with *anime*’s character designs (see Chapter 6), and visually reproduce stylised “facial expressions” associated with this media form as part of their performance, such as “arched eyes when smiling” (p. 31; see also Suan, 2021a). Like virtual influencers, vTubers have grown dramatically in popularity since 2016, when Japanese vTuber Kizuna Ai (キズナ・アイ) began her first YouTube video introducing herself using with the label: “バーチャルYouTuber キズナ・アイです” (“*Virtual YouTuber Kizuna Ai here!*”; KizunaAI - A.I.Channel, 2016, 0:01). By the early 2020s, vTubers could be found across many video streaming platforms, including YouTube, as well as Bilibili (哔哩哔哩, also known as B Site, Station B, or B站), NicoNico (ニコニコ), and Twitch. Reflecting this cross-platform presence, vTubers are also known as “Virtual Livers” (バーチャルライバー, *bācharu raibā*) in Japan, and “Virtual Uploaders” (or VUPs; see H. Jiang et al., 2023) or “virtual anchors” (虚拟主播, *xūnǐ zhǔbō*) in China (see Zhan & Zhang, 2023). They often host livestreams with video gameplay, karaoke, and fan interactions, and have proved highly effective at attracting fan donations (Gwillim-Thomas, 2023; Zhan & Zhang, 2023). To undertake these live performances, some vTubers rely on the facial tracking-capable cameras of Apple iPhones (see Stinson, 2017); others access or invest in professional-grade performance capture technology, comprising full-body motion-capture suits and facial recognition rigs (see H. Jiang et al., 2023). Of chief importance is the vTuber’s ability to perform and record in “real-time”, as it is the immediacy of the vTubers’ reactions and interactions that is of greatest appeal to their audiences, and in turn, crucial to vTubers’ financial success (Gwillim-Thomas, 2023).

As virtual puppets, the primary difference between virtual influencers and vTubers relates to what Kaplin (1999) describes as “distance”, or “the level of separation and contact between the performer and the object being manipulated” (p. 32). To a far greater extent than virtual influencers, vTubers rely on embodied performances of specific human performers, whose movements, expressions, and voice are articulated through technology. Although it is common for the performers behind vTubers to remain anonymous, their influence is omnipresent. Adopting vocabulary originating in discussions of voice actors (声優, *seiyū*) in *anime* (see Nozawa, 2013), fans often refer to vTuber performers as *naka no hito* (中の人, translating to “the person inside”) in Japanese, or *zhong zhiren* (中之人, “person in the middle”) in Chinese (see Bredikhina, 2022; Tobin & Zhou, 2022). In the *anime* industry, the *seiyū* or *naka no hito* is credited with the ability to animate—that is, provide “a life-force [or] spirit” to (Nozawa, 2013, p. 25)—the character using their vocal talents. Fan affection for the

characters is thus closely bound to the *seiyū*, even while fans and *seiyū* alike insist on creating distance from their characters at live events, with the latter turning their back to the audience or covering their faces when they perform the characters' voices live (Nozawa, 2013, p. 23). A similar entanglement of character and performer is seen for vTubers, especially in cases where fans suspect the replacement of the *naka no hito*. For example, when two new iterations of Japanese vTuber Kizuna Ai were introduced in June 2019, fans objected to what they felt was a replacement of the (then anonymous) performer whose talents, performance, and idiosyncrasies they considered inseparable from the original (see Suan, 2021a; Zhou, 2020).

By contrast, virtual influencers involve a greater sense of distance between the characters and their producers. Virtual influencers do not inspire the same feeling that a *naka no hito* is involved and directly responsible for the character's performance. Indeed, virtual influencers' connection to human performers is complicated by their use of a seemingly revolving cast of human stand-ins for photoshoots (see Chapter 6) or one-off performances (Z. Li, 2024). For example, when Korean virtual influencer Rozy starred in a television commercial with Korean life insurance provider Shinhan Life, Rozy's dancing was both choreographed and performed by dancer and model Kang Da Hee (S. Adams, 2021), though there is little evidence to suggest that Kang has served as Rozy's stand-in on other occasions.

Although both can be considered virtual puppets, the key difference between virtual influencers and vTubers is that virtual influencers are largely unmoored from their "puppeteers". In a sense, this distinction recalls film and VFX scholar Dan North's (2014) comparison between pre-digital and digital forms of puppeteering. He writes:

The human puppeteer who creates a physically present (though concealed) manipulation of the puppet endows it with inflections which are vestigial traces of his or her own physical idiosyncrasies. The digitally animated character is different in that, while still connected to the animator's hands and body [...] the real-time causal link has been severed. The [latter] is thus a puppet without a direct indexical link to its performative source. (p. 87)

While in this case, both vTubers and virtual influencers embrace digital animation technologies, vTubers more actively embrace the real-time inputs of the puppeteer and the "vestigial traces of [their] physical idiosyncrasies" (North, 2014, p. 87), even as these physical movements and cues tend to be transformed into stylised expressions (see Suan, 2021a). By contrast, virtual influencers function more as puppets "without a direct indexical link to [their] performative source" (North 2014, p. 87), cultivating a sense of persistence that

transcends the producers involved in their behind-the-scenes creation.

3.4 Summary

In this chapter, I explored two contexts which gave shape to the debut, evolution, and growth of virtual influencers. I began with an account of the (human) influencer landscape, highlighting several points of friction that emerged over the latter half of the 2010s and that set the stage for virtual influencers. I then turned to consider the various virtual beings encountered in online spaces, and specifically on social media. I distinguished three categories of virtual beings, based on the involvement of their producers: virtual humans, virtual mannequins, and virtual puppets. Virtual influencers fall under the latter category, being wholly reliant on the creativity, skills, and labour of their producers (see Chapters 6 and 10). In the next chapter, I review the key fields, concepts, and definitions that guide my understanding of virtual influencers as descendants of celebrity; examples of influencers; and expressions of the virtual.

CHAPTER FOUR

Literature Review

4.1 Introduction

When I began this project in early 2021, only a handful of academic sources had mentioned examples of virtual influencers, with fewer still using the exact phrase. Emerging from several different disciplines, many of these early sources were interested in naming this new phenomenon (e.g. Jauffret & Landaverde-Kastberg, 2018; S. Y. Kim, 2019), and offered speculative discussions of the potential implications of virtual influencers for celebrity (e.g. Marwick, 2018b), fashion (e.g. S.-J. Cho & Yim, 2019), ethics (e.g. Robinson, 2020), misinformation (e.g. Blanton & Carbajal, 2019), and interpersonal relationships (e.g. Jauffret & Landaverde-Kastberg, 2019). In the four years that have since elapsed, academic interest in virtual influencers has flourished. The first monograph on virtual influencers was published in 2024 by critical media and technology scholar Esperanza Miyake, entitled *Virtual Influencers: Identity and Digitality in the Age of Multiple Realities* (2024). As of mid-2025, as I put the final touches on this thesis, there are over 300 book chapters and peer-reviewed journal articles on virtual influencers, with many more conference papers and proceedings contributing to an abundance of literature on the topic. This thesis engages most deeply with scholarship on virtual influencers published during my data collection (January to August 2022) and analysis (concluding in 2024), with later literature left for the reader to explore. To begin this chapter, I briefly outline the fields and interests dominating this body of virtual influencer scholarship, before acknowledging the critical commentary with which this project is most closely aligned.

Scholarship on virtual influencers overwhelmingly originates in marketing and business studies. The first journal special issue wholly dedicated to virtual influencers was published in *Journal of Business Research* in early 2024, titled “Virtual Influencers: A New Frontier in Interdisciplinary Research” (Koles et al., 2024). Research from these disciplines focus on consumer perceptions, interrogating ideas of credibility (e.g. Agnihotri et al., 2024; Awdziej et al., 2022; Baudier et al., 2023; de Boissieu & Baudier, 2023) and trustworthiness (e.g. Ameen et al., 2024; Chaihanchai et al., 2024; Muniz et al., 2023; Qu & Baek, 2024) to understand how virtual influencers can most effectively be used in marketing. They often adopt a comparative approach, contrasting consumer responses towards virtual versus human influencers (e.g. Belanche et al., 2024; Franke et al., 2023), or reactions to virtual influencers who appear more or less lifelike (e.g. K. Jiang et al., 2024; E. (A.) Kim et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2024; Xie-Carson, Magor, et al., 2023; Yan et al., 2024). Methodologically

speaking, this research often draws on consumer interviews, surveys, and focus groups. Some conduct in-depth interviews with industry experts and practitioners to situate the application of and responses to virtual influencers within local markets and industry contexts (e.g. Allal-Chérif et al., 2024; Jauffret & Aubrun, 2022; Moustakas et al., 2020; Oliveira & Chimenti, 2021).

Another prominent line of research on virtual influencers comes from Information Studies (IS) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI). These studies often discuss virtual influencers as “virtual agents” (e.g. Arsenyan & Mirowska, 2021; Y.-H. Chang & Chen, 2023; Ma & Li, 2024; J. Shin & Lee, 2020), and draw on psychological frameworks like Computers as/are Social Actors or CASA (e.g. R. J. Ahn et al., 2022; Arsenyan & Mirowska, 2021; H. Kim & Park, 2024; J. Shin & Lee, 2020) to situate virtual influencers in a longer history of interactive—often anthropomorphised—technologies, including social robots and chatbots (see Miao et al., 2022). Using qualitative approaches like online questionnaires or data scraping (e.g. extracting comments or reactions to virtual influencers on social media), these studies tend to apply content analysis, thematic analysis, and sentiment analysis to locate patterns in datasets of aggregated responses. Similar to the research from marketing and business studies, scholars from IS and HCI seek to understand impressions and responses to virtual influencers, but with a particular interest in the implications for technological design and acceptance of non-human entities as social interlocutors.

While literature from marketing, business studies, IS and HCI appears throughout this thesis—a reflection both of the precedent this early research established for scholarly attention on virtual influencers, as well as the critical concerns often guiding researchers from these fields—my project most closely dialogues with a third, emerging strain of qualitative research on virtual influencers from media studies, cultural studies, and sociology. This literature is interested in how virtual influencers relate to concepts such as celebrity (e.g. Marwick, 2018b; Yuan, 2025), platforms (e.g. Berryman et al., 2021; T. C. Black, 2020; Leaver et al., 2020; Yuan, 2025), and labour (e.g. Z. Li, 2023, 2024; Sobande, 2021b; Yuan, 2025); as well as aspects of identity such as gender (e.g. Miyake, 2022; Roy & Chakraborty, 2023), ethnicity (e.g. Z. Li, 2024; Miyake, 2022), and race (e.g. Z. Li, 2024; Neri, 2022; Sobande, 2021a). Fashion and design scholars (e.g. Brachtendorf, 2022; Y. Shin & Lee, 2023) also offer useful theorisations, contextualising the bodies of virtual influencers in relation to the aesthetic and commercial demands of the fashion industry (see Chapters 6 and 9). I return to and engage more deeply with this body of literature in the second half of this thesis.

Given most scholarship on virtual influencers was published after this project was underway,

my overarching arguments were developed through consultation with more established scholarly trajectories. In this chapter, I detail the scholarly foundation for my approach to analysing virtual influencers. I begin by situating virtual influencers in relation to broader shifts in celebrity culture, reflecting on their connection to the “demotic turn” (Turner, 2010b) and the rise of DIY or “do-it-yourself celebrity” (Turner, 2013, p. 60) facilitated by social networking sites and social media platforms. While this trajectory is familiar territory for influencer research, I draw on these concepts to highlight the continued inequities of fame on social media, and to position virtual influencers as a vehicle capable of profiting from biased platform and industry logics. I also recognise the rise of self-branding and the evolution of “microcelebrity”—a term coined to describe the entrepreneurial mindset and practices of self-branding in online contexts (Marwick, 2013; Senft, 2008)—central to the practices of virtual influencers explored in later chapters. Next, I narrow my view, unpacking the variation masked by the umbrella term “influencer”. To do so, I discuss anthropologist of digital culture Crystal Abidin’s (2021a) influencer taxonomy, noting how the virtual influencers I studied map onto these categories. I then briefly introduce concepts relevant to the focus on visibility and attention central to the analysis developed in later chapters. In the final section, I detail the conceptualisation of the term “virtual” that shaped my analysis, categorising previous scholarly writings on virtuality under three categories: digitality, potentiality, and dimensionality.

4.2 From Celebrity to Influencers

Through their designation as “influencers”, virtual influencers are immediately entered into the contemporary ecology of internet celebrity (Abidin, 2018a). Since the early 2000s, the ubiquity of the internet, social networking sites (and subsequently social media platforms), and networked technologies like smartphones have upended the concept of celebrity. These technologies accelerated shifts already underway, including the “demoticisation” (Turner, 2010b) of celebrity precipitated by new media formats like reality television (see section 4.2.3). The major intervention of networked technologies was the idea that celebrity could be a DIY or “do-it-yourself” endeavour, realised by the newfound ability to use “personal websites, blogs and social media as a means of constructing fame and trading upon it” (Turner, 2013, p. 60). These digital tools and technologies seemed to circumvent the gatekeepers of traditional celebrity industries (e.g. music, film, and television), opening the pathway to internet fame to anyone who had access to an internet-enabled device. Influencers came to figure as an epitome of DIY celebrity, even as a fully-fledged industry was quickly created to professionalise their activities (see Chapter 3).

4.2.1 Conceptualising Celebrity

Since the publication of film studies scholar Richard Dyer's influential book *Stars* (1979), academic interest in celebrity has flourished. In their introduction to the inaugural issue of *Celebrity Studies* journal, editors Su Holmes and Sean Redmond (2010) describe the blossoming field of celebrity scholarship as "the product of an expanded and expanding intellectual interest in celebrity which [...] find[s] its most energetic hub in media and cultural studies, [but] operates at the intersection of work emerging from a range of disciplines and approaches" (p. 6). A core tenet of this literature is that celebrity is a consequence of media attention and representation, not an innate quality an individual possesses (S. Holmes & Redmond, 2010; Turner, 2013). Reflecting on the multi-decade history of celebrity scholarship, China studies scholars Elaine Jeffreys and Louise Edwards (2010) recount how celebrity has shifted from a topic originally dismissed for its frivolity and superficiality (e.g. Boorstin, 1961), to a phenomenon which is culturally ubiquitous, influential, and ripe for scholarly inquiry. This is echoed in cultural and celebrity studies scholar Graeme Turner's (2013) multipronged definition of celebrity as "a genre of representation and a discursive effect"; "a commodity traded by the promotions, publicity, and media industries that produce these representations and their effects"; and "a cultural formation [with] a social function" requiring academic attention and scrutiny (p. 10). Scholarship on celebrity spans examples from television, film, music, sports, news, politics, and, increasingly, online spaces and digital cultures. Though this literature crosses fields and disciplines, it is generally united by a recognition of the media's role in affecting and amplifying public prominence and visibility.

Given the processes involved in their production (see Chapter 6), I conceptualise virtual influencers as examples of what media scholar P. David Marshall (1997) calls the "celebrity-commodity". The term accentuates celebrity as a "factory product" (Gamson, 2011, p. 1063) which is "manufactured, marketed and traded" (Turner, 2010a, p. 14) for maximum profit. Consider, for example, East Asia's idol industries, where talent agencies widely replicate the *jimusho* (事務所, "office") model originating in Japan in the 1970s, recruiting, training, and managing hundreds of aspiring idols each year in an effort to produce "idols who have the greatest economic potential" (Marx, 2012, p. 37). Focusing on the "celebrity-commodity" (Marshall, 1997) requires looking beyond the individual celebrity to consider the network of "investors, publicists, makeup artists, magazine publishers, and the like" who operate behind-the-scenes (Gamson, 2011, p. 1063). These "cultural intermediaries" (Rojek, 2014, p. 458) accelerate what media sociologist Olivier Driessens (2013b) describes as "celebrification", or the "processes by which ordinary people or public figures are transformed into celebrity" (p. 643). Driessens (2013a) elsewhere proffers the term "celebrity

capital”, which helpfully captures the primary aim of this process: to achieve “recognizability”, referring to the “accumulated media visibility that results from recurrent media representations” (p. 552). This coheres with the concept of “attributed celebrity” proposed by celebrity studies scholar Chris Rojek (2001), whereby celebrity status is conferred primarily by concentrated media attention, differing from cases of “ascribed” celebrity (by virtue of birth, connection, or proximity) or “achieved” celebrity (through skill or achievement).

Rising scholarly interest in “celebrification” (Driessens, 2013b) has attracted critical examination of the “apparatus of representation, production, circulation and consumption” sustaining the celebrity industry (Nayar, 2009, p. 26). The effectiveness of these apparatuses is perhaps most apparent in cases of non-human celebrity. For example, media psychologist David C. Giles (2013) suggests that animal celebrity exemplifies “that celebrity is essentially a process by which media turn individuals (not necessarily humans) into objects of desire” (p. 116). Analysing animals that have achieved international fame, Giles highlights “the intertwining of press interest, PR [public relations] machinations and fan activity, and the intervention of other media sources (film-makers, TV shows, websites) that combine to propagate the mythology and maintain celebrity status for [a] desired object” that is not necessarily human (p. 124). The same thread underscores writings on other kinds of non-human celebrities, including Rojek’s (2001) figure of the “celeactor”, defined as “a fictional character who is either momentarily ubiquitous or becomes an institutionalized feature of popular culture” (p. 23); and cultural studies scholar Pramod K. Nayar’s (2009) related concept of the “celefiction”, describing fictional characters who “command [significant] power and profits” independently from their authors (p. 19), and “are brought home to us through mechanisms that render them familiar, desirable and *possessable*” (p. 18, original emphasis). Aligned with these writings, virtual influencers attest to the continued effectiveness of traditional celebrity industry apparatuses in the “celebrification” (Driessens, 2013b) of non-human entities. Indeed, as illustrated throughout this thesis, virtual influencers have received extensive attention from popular press; this heightened media presence serves both to legitimate them as news-worthy, and to heighten their “celebrity capital” (Driessens, 2013a) by making them increasingly recognisable to audiences, brand partners (see Chapter 9), and investors (see Chapter 10). However, as suggested by the discussion below, networked technologies and social media have recently introduced new modes of “celebrification” (Driessens, 2013b) which seem less reliant upon the apparatuses traditionally utilised by the celebrity industry; virtual influencers illustrate the capability for these newer apparatuses to attract media visibility and attention for non-human celebrity.

4.2.2 Microcelebrity

The adoption and availability of networked, digital technologies gave rise to a new incarnation of celebrity popularly conceptualised as “microcelebrity”. The term was first coined by global studies scholar Theresa M. Senft (2008) in her autoethnographic study of North American “camgirls”: young women who, during the late-1990s and early-2000s, broadcast low-resolution images (and eventually video) from personal websites using webcams stationed around their homes. Senft observed camgirls’ commitment to “a new style of online performance that [involved] ‘amping up’ their popularity over the web using technologies like video, blogs and social networking sites” (p. 25). Noting the camgirls’ fervent and dedicated fan followings, Senft coined the term “microcelebrity” to explain the qualitative differences in their fame in comparison to “traditional” celebrities from entertainment industries such as film, television and sports. The “micro-” prefix referred both to the comparatively smaller scale of their audiences, and the more intimate tenor of their interactions (Abidin, 2018a; Marwick, 2016).

The logics of microcelebrity were soon adapted to studies of social network sites (SNS), which debuted in the early 2000s (boyd & Ellison, 2007). Whereas previously skills in coding and web design had been necessary to design and maintain a personal blog or website (see Lukács, 2020; B. Smith, 2005), SNS such as Cyworld, Facebook, and Myspace gave users a basic infrastructure with which to establish an online profile and easily connect with others, standardising affordances such as “profiles, Friends lists, public commenting tools, and stream-based updates” (boyd, 2010, p. 43). Enabling new reciprocities of friending and following, and showcasing new metrics, such as likes, comments, and shares, these networked environments streamlined and normalised the quantification of online popularity. Their widespread adoption lowered barriers to the tools with which microcelebrity could be practiced, allowing even more “regular people” the opportunity “to gain status and attention online” (Marwick & boyd, 2011, p. 156)

Senft’s (2008) conceptualisation of microcelebrity was expanded by internet studies scholar Alice E. Marwick in her book *Status Update: Celebrity, Publicity, and Branding in the Social Media Age* (2013). While researching the Silicon Valley “tech scene” (p. 8), Marwick noted the effort her informants put into strategic self-promotion, cultivating online networks, and publishing their professional accomplishments online (see Chapter 10). By using these tactics to increase their online visibility, Marwick observed that workers were also striving to present themselves as more valuable and desirable for potential employers, pursuing promotions and career advancement. Marwick’s research on Silicon Valley workers underscores the relationship between micro-celebrity and “the increase in popularity of ‘self-

branding' and strategic self-presentation" (Marwick & boyd, 2011, p. 141). As described by media and cultural studies scholar Alison Hearn (2008), self-branding is "a highly self-conscious process of self-exploitation, performed in the interests of material gain or cultural status" (p. 204). Hearn discusses the pressure to view and package oneself as a product, and the growing tendency to borrow techniques from marketing to transform one's own identity into "a detachable, saleable image or narrative" (p. 198). I refer to the techniques of self-branding throughout this thesis, especially given their centrality to influencer practice, where influencers constantly seek to make themselves recognisable, visible, and desirable to audiences and prospective brand partners (Khamis et al., 2017). Technically speaking, virtual influencers do not undertake "self-branding" as it is not (and cannot be) the fictional entity that is undertaking these practices for themselves. For virtual influencers, self-branding is always an outcome of their producers' creative input and actions (see Chapter 6). Even so, I find utility in the term (and prefer it to the broader "branding") for aligning the practices of virtual influencers with the cultures and norms of social media more broadly, and influencers specifically. Through reference to (human) influencer scholarship, Chapters 6 to 9 each consider different self-branding tactics operationalised by virtual influencers to increase their visibility and value among social media audiences and stakeholders from the virtual influencer industry (see Chapter 10).

In present usage, the term microcelebrity is generally used to describe "a mindset and a set of practices" (Marwick, 2016, p. 337) in "which people view themselves as a public persona to be consumed by others, use strategic intimacy to appeal to followers, and regard their audiences as fans" (Marwick, 2016, p. 333). Today, microcelebrity is enacted by everyday individuals, aspiring celebrities, and established celebrities alike, who all use social media platforms to accumulate and manage "a fan base, [perform] intimacy, authenticity and access, and [construct] a consumable persona" that extends across multiple platforms (Marwick & boyd, 2011, p. 140; see also Scolere et al., 2018). Its logics and practices are demonstrated *par excellence* in influencers, whose careers rely on a self-brand designed to attract and maintain high levels of online visibility and attention (Abidin, 2018a; Bishop, 2018). As Abidin (2017a) notes, for influencers, "microcelebrity is not merely a hobby or a supplementary income but an established career with its own ecology and economy" (p. 1). Indeed, the "micro-" prefix of microcelebrity can no longer be said to denote a niche community of fans; many individuals who have achieved fame online using microcelebrity tactics have millions of followers, making it commonplace "for internet celebrities to rival or surpass traditional celebrities in terms of global popularity or reach" (Abidin, 2018a, p. 14).

4.2.3 The “Demotic Turn”

The rise of microcelebrity epitomises what celebrity studies scholar Graeme Turner (2013) describes as celebrity culture’s “demotic turn” (p. 92): where once celebrity was tightly controlled and managed, new technologies have shifted the conditions of accessing fame, and encouraged the perception that anyone can become a celebrity. Importantly, Turner notes that these shifts were underway prior to the introduction of SNS or social media. Television (and especially televisual genres such as talk shows and reality television, which feature non-famous guests) was already granting ordinary people new levels of mediated visibility: “[o]rdinary people have never been more visible in the media, nor have their own utterances ever been reproduced with the faithfulness, respect and accuracy that they are today” (p. 92). In Turner’s view, the “multiplication of outlets, of formats and of the number of people subject to the discursive processes” of becoming celebrities, suggests that “the opportunity of celebrity [has spread] beyond elites [...] and into the expectations of the population in general” (p. 92). Turner’s notion of the demotic turn is closely related to what celebrity studies scholar Joshua Gamson (2011) describes as the “ordinary turn”, describing a heightened presence of non-famous, everyday people in popular culture.

Two consequences of these shifts are particularly relevant for this thesis. The first is the perception that anyone can become a celebrity. For Gamson (2011), the ordinary turn is not simply an issue of representation. He suggests the increased visibility of ordinary people in the media has led to “a heightened consciousness of everyday life as a public performance – an increased expectation that we are being watched, [and] a growing willingness to offer up private parts of the self to watchers known and unknown” (p. 1068). This is especially true of social media, where unless one undertakes deliberate steps to stay “under-the-radar” (see Abidin, 2021a), it has become widely accepted that “one must always behave on the Internet as one would if placed on a public stage, because, in a very real sense, one is” (Senft, 2013, p. 347). The heightened visibility of (other) ordinary people in the media has encouraged a mode of self-presentation that both anticipates and caters to an audience potentially larger than one’s immediate network of social connections.

The second is Turner’s (2013) emphasis on the “demotic” (not “democratic”) quality of this turn, and his reminder that “celebrity remains a hierarchical and exclusive phenomenon, no matter how much it proliferates” (p. 93). Although new technologies and media forms have changed the conditions for how celebrity is manufactured and maintained, they generally privilege the same biases and hierarchies seen in earlier industry models. In the context of social media, as sociologist Jennifer Whitmer (2021) argues:

while the rhetoric surrounding amateur content creation largely relies on a set of myths that emphasize the meritocratic quality of social media production [...] digital platforms tend to reproduce the same kinds of hierarchies seen in more traditional forms of media creation. (p. 147)

Recent scholarship has highlighted that most prominent and popular influencers on visual social media platforms tend to be young, conventionally attractive, feminine and slender, with lighter skin tones, while “women of color, women who are fuller-figured, and older women are rendered invisible” (Foster, 2022, p. 2). As noted by feminist media studies scholar Sophie Bishop (2021a), “[a]lthough influencer economies have been framed as participatory, creators across intersections of marginalized identity often suffer the consequences of this innovation and instability, through underpayment and platform obscuration” (p. 1). In online—and especially algorithmic (see section 4.2)—environments, opportunities to acquire celebrity status are not equally distributed nor accessible, even as the conviction it is plausible and possible has become more pervasive (see Bishop, 2018; S. Edwards, 2022).

Virtual influencers figure as a curious intervention in this context, given the producer’s identity and appearance are not necessarily attached to the character nor their popularity. As the host of a podcast episode dedicated to virtual influencers enthuses, “When we’re influencers online, as ourselves, you only have the face that you’re born with, but when you’re starting new with a virtual influencer, you literally can make that influencer look like anything” (S. Smith, 2023, 6:58). In many ways, this echoes the fantasy of liberation found in early scholarship on how computer-mediated communication (CMC) could be used to fashion identities untethered from offline lives (e.g. Markham, 1998; Nakamura, 2002; Turkle, 1995). The difference today is that online identity is not only related to self-expression, but also bound up with the logics of “self-branding”, in which the self is viewed, packaged, and promoted in such a way as “to garner attention, reputation, and potentially, profit” (Hearn, 2010, p. 427). Social media platforms constantly prompt users to upload new content to produce “inventories of branded selves” (Hearn, 2008, p. 22) which render identity “a work in progress played out in front of an imagined audience in a constant feedback loop” (Taylor, 2022, p. 4).

In “an image economy, where attention is monetized and notoriety, or fame, is capital” (Hearn, 2010, p. 427), it is not necessarily the liberatory potential to be “anyone” that appeals, but rather the opportunity to become someone whose “look” will unlock the benefits of online visibility (Foster, 2022). In this context, virtual influencers can be adopted as a visage by individuals who do not fit within the narrow aesthetics privileged on social media,

or indeed, for those who do not seek visibility for their own name and image. Moreover, they can also allow those individuals to benefit from the algorithmic and commercial logics and opportunities of these environments, regardless of their own, embodied appearance (Foster, 2022). In Chapter 6, I return to the question of how virtual influencers are designed to succeed within the context of visual social media platforms, drawing on media studies scholar Jonathon Hutchinson's (2020) concept of the "digital first personality" to examine how platform logics shape the decision-making involved in the characters' designs.

4.3 Influencer Taxonomy

Borne from the intersecting logics of celebrity's "demotic turn" (Turner, 2010b), the rise of "self-branding" (Hearn, 2008), and the uptake of "micro-celebrity" (Marwick, 2013; Senft, 2008), the consolidation of influencers as a genre of celebrity occurred during the 2010s. Influencers' careers rely on the successful cultivation a self-brand that can attract and maintain high levels of visibility on social media (Abidin, 2018a). The heightened prominence of influencers both in popular culture and scholarly discourse throughout the 2010s has contributed to new understandings of the significant variation among them, as well as the key factors shaping their practices, discussed in the two sections that follow.

The ubiquity of the term "influencer" tends to eschew the wide-reaching applications of this label, and the fact that what (or who) quantitatively constitutes an influencer remains a topic of debate. Marketing professionals tend to classify influencers based on follower count, using labels such as mega-influencers (usually over 1 million followers), macro-influencers (between 100,000 and 1 million followers), micro-influencers (up to 100,000 followers), and nano-influencers (up to 1,000 followers, see K. Fowler & Thomas, 2023; Riboldazzi & Capriello, 2020). However, there are many more qualities that differentiate influencers than just audience size. Abidin (2021a) suggests at least five categories to assist with categorising influencers, which I briefly outline below to acquaint the reader with the significant diversity and nuance often obscured by the term "influencer". I referred to these categories during my ethnographic fieldwork (see Chapter 5) as a way to reflect upon the variation among the virtual influencers I encountered. While some scholars suggest viewing "virtual" as a separate category alongside mega, macro, micro, and nano influencers (e.g. Riboldazzi & Capriello, 2020), I view Abidin's (2021a) criteria as applicable to human and virtual influencers alike. In the sections that follow, I discuss Abidin's taxonomy for influencers and how these aspects intersect with the virtual influencers I studied.

Genre

The first category of Abidin's (2021a) taxonomy is the dominant genre of influencers'

content, such as lifestyle, fashion and beauty, parenting, fitness, gaming, or home DIY. The virtual influencers I introduce in later chapters chiefly align with the genres of lifestyle and fashion influencers. For lifestyle influencers, the events, rhythms, and routines of their daily lives serve as the focus of their social media content (Abidin, 2016d). Every aspect of their lives has the potential to be commodified, including pets (see Ngai, 2022); children (see Abidin, 2015b); family members (see Abidin, 2017a; Berryman & Kavka, 2017); and romantic relationships (see Abidin, 2016b). Fashion influencers focus on sartorial showcases, photographing the garments and accessories they wear to express their personal style. Lifestyle and fashion are complementary domains, and often combined by influencers. For example, daily life often serves as the backdrop for showcasing the outfits worn by lifestyle influencers (known as #OOTDs or #OutfitsOfTheDay; see Chapter 9); and fashion influencers will often adopt the rhetorical style of lifestyle influencers, sharing “details of their personal lives [to] help contextualize their unique fashion perspectives” (Pham, 2015, p. 3).

Format and Platform

The second category is the format of influencer content, which may include images, text, short- or long-form videos, or livestreams. Format is closely tied to Abidin’s (2021a) third category, platform, referencing the online infrastructures and affordances that facilitate, inform and/or constrain their creation and circulation of influencers’ online content (Duffy et al., 2017; Hurley, 2019). Internet scholars Taina Bucher and Anne Helmond (2018) define social media platforms “as digital intermediaries that draw together and negotiate between different stakeholders, such as end-users, developers and advertisers, which each come with their own aims and agendas” (p. 243). Influencers tend to congregate on social media platforms that privilege visual content. At the time of writing, this includes visual social media platforms such as Instagram (see Leaver et al., 2020) and Xiaohongshu (see Guo, 2022), as well as the short-form video app TikTok (see Abidin, 2021b). Even so, to maximise their audience reach, it is commonplace for influencers to maintain a “digital estate” (Abidin, 2017a, p. 2), comprising (sometimes several) profiles across multiple social media platforms. Each profile and platform are carefully managed and maintained “to avoid over-exposure in some areas and [to] redirect audience interest to others” (Abidin, 2021a, p. 1). While content can sometimes be reposted to multiple platforms, it is usually tailored or specifically authored to suit the specific features and cultures of each. Media and design scholar Leah Scolere, along with communications scholars Urszula Pruchniewska and Brooke Erin Duffy (2018), describe this as a process of “platform-specific self-branding” (p. 4), whereby individuals “constantly (re)construct their self-presentation activities” online to align with “assumptions about platform materiality and environment, constructions of the audience, and reflections on the creator’s own self-concept” (p. 4). Attuned to the platform-specificity of online

interactions, I adopted a “platform-sensitive” (Arriagada & Ibáñez, 2020, p. 2; see Bucher & Helmond, 2018) approach to analysing social media data in this project (see Chapter 5). A platform-sensitive approach recognises how platform “affordances”—describing the “material functions of a technology which allow users to perform certain actions” (Marwick, 2016, p. 334)—shape the format and style of social media content, along with the conditions for accessing or reacting to it. Later, I discuss the platforms used by virtual influencers (see Chapter 6), and analyse their use of familiar visual social media templates (see Chapter 7), as well as platform affordances like hashtags and geotags (see Chapter 8).

In some cases, influencers tie their self-branding directly to the platform on which their career began, or which houses their largest audience (Bishop, 2022). For example, they might describe themselves as “YouTubers” (see Deller & Murphy, 2020), “TikTokers” (see Abidin, 2021b; Kaye, 2022), or in the case of livestreaming sites like Twitch and Afreeca.TV, “Streamers” (see Woodcock & Johnson, 2019) or “BJs” (Broadcasting Jockeys; see Song, 2018). Seemingly at odds with the presence of influencers across numerous online environments, influencers’ proclivity to attach their personal brand to a single platform reflects the range of definitions and (sometimes negative) connotations of the term “influencer” (Duffy & Sawey, 2021; Glatt, 2022a). Other variants of the term, such as “content creator”, have gained popularity as influencers seek to strategically align themselves with the professionalism associated with the creative industries (Bishop, 2021b). These particular variants were less common among the virtual influencers I studied, who were more likely to describe themselves as “virtual humans” (see Chapter 3) or “meta humans” (see Chapter 10). However, a similar desire for legitimacy could be seen in the promotional rhetoric surrounding the burgeoning virtual influencer industry and the behind-the-scenes contributions of the characters’ producers (see Chapter 10).

Geocultural Context

Abidin’s (2021a) fourth category relates to geocultural context, noting that:

how internet celebrity has come to emerge in various parts of the world varies, depending on the cultural norms of the people, the social practices around media devices and personalities, and the structure of technological capabilities that mediate a population's access to content. (p. 2)

For example, when appraising the size of an individual’s audience, Abidin recommends scaling expectations relative to the size of local or linguistic populations. Recent scholarship has highlighted how virtual influencers are designed to appeal to local audiences (e.g. Abidin, 2023; L. Luo & Kim, 2024). In Chapter 8, I explore how virtual influencers engage

with local internet trends, norms, and communities, arguing that this is a way for virtual influencers to brand themselves with a distinct cultural identity and connect with local audiences.

Communicative Function

Abidin's (2021a) fifth and final category is communicative function, referring to influencers' "primary role in the information ecology, whether this be serving as amplifiers of information (akin to broadcast media), opinion leaders, or persuasive converters (~word of mouth marketing)" (p. 6). For example, a prominent example of influencers as "persuasive converters" are known in China as "*wanghong*" (网红). An abbreviation of "*wangluo hongren*" (网络红人)—literally translating to "person who is red [popular] on the internet"—the term "*wanghong*" has been used since 2015 to describe individuals skilled at translating online attention into website traffic and e-commerce sales (see X. Han, 2021; G. Zhang & de Seta, 2018). Considering influencers' communicative function foregrounds the role of influencers as "intermediaries", whose "high levels of media literacy" allows them to communicate and "transfer the value of the chosen product[,] service [or message] to their large fan base" (Hutchinson, 2020, p. 1285). In Chapter 9, I explore how virtual influencers are enlisted by brands for commercial partnerships. Discussed briefly in Chapter 11, virtual influencers have also been enlisted to promote a range of social causes, including democratic participation (see Abril, 2020), sustainable consumption (see 조용철, 2021), and public health messaging (see Dodgson, 2020), and often promote fundraising initiatives for charities and community groups (D. Fowler, 2018; Newell-Hanson, 2017).

4.4 Visibility & Attention

In Chapter 3, I argued that virtual influencers' debut coincided with the oversaturated influencer landscape. Upon entering into this context, virtual influencers needed to find ways to set themselves apart from other influencer aspirants, gaining visibility in an overcrowded online landscape. Accordingly, two themes central to this thesis are visibility and attention. Both concepts feature prominently in influencer scholarship: recent literature has highlighted that achieving visibility is an increasingly fraught and labour-intensive endeavour on social media, given the platforms' organisation by opaque algorithmic logics; and attention is highly prized, invested with both symbolic and financial capital directly entwined with influencers' livelihoods. Research has underscored the highly pragmatic behaviours of influencers in order to achieve visibility and attract attention (e.g. Bishop, 2018; Cotter, 2019; O'Meara, 2019). I take particular inspiration from Abidin's (2016d) concept of "visibility labour", a term

which draws attention to the significant time and effort involved in curating one's online "self-presentations so as to be noticeable and positively prominent" (p. 90), and develop its application to virtual influencers in later chapters.

Attention Economy

In online environments, brands, publishers, influencers, and regular users compete "across more screens for increasingly distracted, dispersed and privatised audiences" (Khamis et al., 2017, p. 195) in what is often conceptualised as an "attention economy" (Goldhaber, 1997). Physicist Michael Goldhaber (1997) popularised the term in a prophetic framing of how attention would become an increasingly valuable form of currency in the immaterial context of the early web. Building on Goldhaber's work, marketers later adapted the term to theorise the implications of greater choice and competition for consumers, as well as the increased scarcity and value of public attention (e.g. Davenport & Beck, 2001). The term has since become a staple in social media research (Fairchild, 2007), especially as attention is increasingly quantified by metrics counting followers, comments, reactions and shares. Such "vanity metrics" are often interpreted as proxies for popularity (Taylor, 2022), despite the ease with which they can be manipulated, such as through the purchase of bots for followers and engagement (see Abidin, 2018a).

Since the concept of the attention economy was popularised in the late 1990s, several scholars have proposed new metaphors to reflect the heightened ephemerality of online attention. For example, Senft (2008) proposes that "on the Web, spectatorship functions less as gaze than grab" (p. 46), referring to how a user's attention must be "grabbed", if only momentarily, in a "segmented and tactile manner" (Senft & Baym, 2015, p. 1598). Communication studies scholar Diana Zulli characterises this mode of spectatorship as a "glance" (2018), whereas sociologist Elizabeth Wissinger (2015) describes it as "the digital age of the blink [...] characterized both by speed and a veritable explosion in the availability of information" (p. 9). Metaphors of grabs, glances, and blinks emphasise the increasing desperation of capturing (visual) attention in an environment containing "significantly more content produced than can be consumed" (Hutchinson, 2020, p. 1285), and an infinite volume of "data and images provid[ing] more distractions, links to click, or ideas to pursue" (Wissinger, 2015, p. 10). The later chapters of this thesis examine in detail how virtual influencers compete for the narrowing windows of attention available on social media (see Chapters 7, 8, and 9), as well as the value they accrue by doing so (see Chapter 10).

Platforms

The logics, cultures, affordances, and economics of social media platforms are key forces

shaping influencer practice and the conditions of online fame (Abidin, 2018a). This can be understood through the lens of “platformisation”, defined as “the rise of the platform as the dominant infrastructural and economic model of the social web” (Helmond, 2015, p. 1). Under platformisation, the web transformed from a relatively open and fluid online ecosystem to one organised around a handful of proprietary platforms (Nieborg & Poell, 2018).

Recent scholarship has highlighted the challenges of platformisation for independent and aspiring cultural producers (Bishop, 2021a; Scolere et al., 2018), and the precarity of influencers as creative workers whose livelihoods are heavily reliant on platform logics and interests (Arriagada & Ibáñez, 2020). As media scholars David B. Nieborg and Thomas Poell (2018) write, “cultural production is becoming increasingly platform dependent, [and] the autonomy and economic sustainability of particular forms of cultural production is increasingly compromised” (p. 4277). Media studies scholar Victoria O’Meara (2019) discusses the labour of influencers as “platformized cultural production”, where “proprietary curation algorithms wrest knowledge and control of the labor process from producers” (p. 8). Her analysis coheres with Nieborg and Poell’s (2018) framing of the relationship between cultural producers and platforms as one of “platform dependency”, where cultural producers are increasingly reliant upon “the tools, advertising revenue, and data and governance standards” of the platforms they inhabit (p. 4277). However, as highlighted by critical media and technology scholar Esperanza Miyake (2024), this dependency also demands virtual influencers perpetuate the logics of platform capitalism, which succeed by extracting and commodifying datafied user (inter)actions. Miyake writes that “virtual influencers are subtly and alluringly interpolating us to participate within the visual and interactive economy of social media” (p. 4); each view, like, comment, or share accumulated by their content is data that “becomes inevitably tied to *their* monetised identity” (p. 4, original emphasis). While these ideas are beyond the scope of this thesis to discuss in-depth, they offer a provocative lens for later chapters’ analyses of the tactics used by virtual influencers to gain attention and online visibility.

Algorithms

Algorithms are a prototypical platform affordance, designed to “assist users in finding and consuming content that is relevant to their interests” (Hutchinson, 2020, p. 1285). Increasingly, algorithms have taken on the role of gatekeepers, expanding or limiting the reach and value of online content and controlling “media visibility across emerging networked platforms” (Hutchinson, 2020, p. 1285). Given influencers’ vested interest in creating content that is seen by as many people as possible, algorithms are considered an

“especially salient” threat (Scolere et al., 2018, p. 9). The algorithmic configurations of leading social media platforms are typically proprietary, tightly protected, and rarely explained to general users. Without guides on algorithmic best practice, influencers are forced to rely on their own “folk theories” around how “curation algorithms work” and to act accordingly (Eslami et al., 2016, p. 2371). Recent ethnographic studies draw attention to the pressure felt by influencers to produce new content for algorithms that seem to privilege consistent uploads (Arriagada & Ibáñez, 2020), and highlight the intensive monitoring, experimentation and knowledge-sharing required to manage and maintain prominence in algorithmic environments (see Bishop, 2021a; Guan, 2021; O’Meara, 2019). Feminist media scholar Sophie Bishop (2018) conceptualizes these efforts as “algorithmic labour”, describing the investment “of complex and time-consuming labour [...] to understand how to create content that adheres to algorithmic requirements and avoids algorithmic punishment” (p. 73). Later in the thesis, I explore how virtual influencers’ practices are shaped by their producers’ “folk theories” (Eslami et al., 2016) around how algorithms work (see Chapter 7), and their use of other platform affordances to make their content algorithmically legible to specific cultural communities (see Chapter 8).

Templatability

In their book on Instagram, internet scholars Tama Leaver, Crystal Abidin, and Tim Highfield (2020) identify the “growing logic of templatability driven by the metrics and algorithms driving Instagram today” (p. 191), and “the formulaic, repeatable and simulatable aesthetics” (p. 210) that have come to dominate the platform. They attribute the rise of templates to the platform’s changing business priorities, which have been oriented towards maximising advertiser spend (Carah et al., 2023). Leaver et al. (2020) argue that “Instagram’s drive to serve metrics for Influencers and advertisers has meant both are increasingly behaving in similar ways” (p. 214). For influencers, this logic of templatability is further entrenched by the influencer industry. Feminist media studies scholar Sophie Bishop (2021a) suggests that the growing number of “influencer management tools” available on the market, which recommend brands and marketers influencer partners based on platform data, privilege “influencers that align with popular, commercial themes and genres” and perpetuate which behaviours, practices, and bodies are worthy of financial remuneration (Bishop, 2021, p. 4). Together, these algorithmic, platform, and industry forces have contributed to a proliferation of “visually memorable and memorizable visual stylings, settings and practices that can be replicated with relative ease” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 214). These templates are self-sustaining: the success of particular visual tropes, styles, composition, and colours inspires more of the same, in turn saturating these platforms with recurring visual motifs (see Chapter 7).

Virtual influencers emulate dominant visual stylings and compositions in order to authenticate their presence in social media spaces. For example, performance studies scholar Taylor C. Black (2020) highlights that American virtual influencer Lil Miquela has a “pitch-perfect understanding of the tropes of Instagram, from repetitions of poses to hashtag and language use” (p. 50), and “embodies mimesis, using techniques of re-performance in the highly citational world of Instagram to, ironically, construct herself as an individual” (p. 50). I return to the topic of templatability in Chapter 6’s discussion of virtual influencers’ designs; in Chapter 7’s analysis of how virtual influencers make themselves distinctive on visual social media platforms; and Chapter 9’s examination of how virtual influencers emulate and depart from influencers’ established commercial templates.

4.5 Defining Virtuality

In this final section, I outline three interpretations that inform my view of what is “virtual” about virtual influencers. Despite the many synonyms for virtual influencers (as outlined in Chapter 1), I take inspiration from the theoretical discussions of scholars like anthropologist Tom Boellstorff (2008), and gravitate towards “virtual influencer” for its utility in recognising both the technological and symbolic qualities that differentiate these entities from their fleshy counterparts. Throughout this thesis, I foreground the concept of virtuality as an entry point for my analysis, exploring ways that virtuality is made visible, and also the effect of visible virtuality. With roots in the Latin *virtualis*, “virtual” has accumulated a variety of meanings, especially since its adoption in the field of computing in the late 1950s. Spanning the term’s colloquial use, philosophical interpretation, and adoption by *anime* and *manga* fans, I highlight three interpretations most relevant to my conceptualisation of virtuality in this thesis: 1) virtual as digitality; 2) virtual as potentiality; and 3) virtual as dimensionality.

4.5.1 Digitality

Firstly, “virtual” is often used colloquially as a synonym for digital, describing something created with, simulated by, and/or experienced through digital technologies (K. M. Lee, 2004). This association is longstanding: the phrase “virtual memory” was coined to describe an innovation in computer programming in 1959 (Bryant & Pollock, 2010). By the 1990s, for science and technology scholar and posthumanism critic N. Katherine Hayles (1999), we were living in an age of virtuality, characterised by the “cultural perception” that “all material objects are interpenetrated by flows of information, from DNA code to the global reach of the World Wide Web” (pp. 13-14). Aligned with this perspective, in everyday usage, “virtual” tends to function as what sociologist Steve Woolgar (2002) calls an “epithetized phenomena”, wherein descriptors such as “digital”, “electronic”, “e-” and “cyber-” are applied

to “existing activities and social institutions [...] to conjure a future consequent upon the effects of electronic technologies” (p. 3). An example is the term “virtual reality”, which refers to “a computer-generated simulation or presentation of an environment in which the user experiences a sense of phenomenological presence or immersion in the environment” (Shields, 2003, p. 46). Along similar lines, a “virtual world” is defined as a place of “human culture realized by computer programs through the Internet” (Boellstorff, 2010, p. 126), epitomised by *Second Life* or the massive multiplayer online role-playing game (MMORPG) *World of Warcraft*. In both cases, the “virtual” epithet indicates an experience inextricable from digital technologies, but it also signals a process of transformation, whereby existing or analogue practices, objects, or experiences are made into something new. Following this logic, the “virtual” in virtual influencers distinguishes them as influencers which are created, mediated, and experienced through technology.

4.5.2 Potentiality

A second interpretation of virtuality is as potential, where the virtual manifests as “an immanent and immaterial form [...] effectively but not formally or materially existing within the interstices of everyday life” (van Doorn, 2011, p. 533). This interpretation can be seen in the term’s colloquial application as a synonym for almost, as “when someone says ‘she’s virtually my sister’ to refer to a close friend” (Boellstorff, 2008, p. 18). Following philosophers like Pierre Lévy (1997, 1998) and Brian Massumi (2002/2021), this conceptualisation holds that the opposite of virtuality is not reality, but is instead actuality. Virtuality “can be said to exist whenever there is a perceived gap between experience and ‘the actual’”; the virtual is always “approaching the actual *without* [ever] *arriving there*” (Boellstorff, 2008, p. 19, original emphasis). Recasting virtuality’s opposite as actuality is important, given the tendency to dismiss the virtual when it is opposed to “real”, even though its impact is felt not only “in the technologies, the servers, and networks that provide electronic infrastructure” for virtual experiences, but also in “the minds and interactions of the people that populate them” (Jordan, 2009, p. 182). Likewise, for virtual influencers, virtuality as potentiality presents a way to reconcile their immateriality and fictionality with their impact and appeal.

As potentiality, virtuality carries connotations of creativity and possibility. As sociologist and cultural theorist Rob Shields (2003) points out, “[t]he virtual is not merely an incomplete imitation of the real but another register or manifestation of the real,” and in “some cases it is [even] better than the real” (p. 43). Shield’s definition helpfully suggests that as site of potential, virtuality can be an attraction in its own right. The appeal of virtuality is clear in Boellstorff’s (2008) influential ethnographic analysis of the virtual world *Second Life*, as well as in the immersive experiences promised by technologies like virtual reality, which “simulate

a semblance of physicality that feigns the materiality of actual space” and “ocularly appears disconnected from the [user’s] physical environment” (Saker & Frith, 2020, p. 1431). I return to the value of the virtual especially in the discussion of the grounded theory of *hyper-virtuality* presented in this thesis’ conclusion (see Chapter 11).

4.5.3 Dimensionality

The third interpretation of virtuality relates to dimensionality, a term I borrow from the work of anthropologist Shunsuke Nozawa (2013). Nozawa uses the Japanese term “*jigen*” (次元, dimensionality) in his research on the avid *otaku* (おたく) fan communities of *anime* and *manga* in Japan. He describes how when *otaku* discuss their favourite characters and fan practices, they distinguish between the fantastical, 2D (二次元, *ni-jigen*) “fictional worlds” of the characters, and the 3D (三次元, *san-jigen*) “real world” they themselves inhabit day-to-day. In his book on *otaku*, cultural anthropologist Patrick W. Galbraith (2019) explores how Japanese animation cultivates a sense that the fictional worlds of *manga* and *anime* have their own reality, adopting *manga* author and social critic Eiji Ōtsuka’s phrase “manga/anime realism” to describe the ontological coherence of 2D spaces on their own terms, “rather than [as] an approximation of the natural world” (p. 14). Once the boundaries between 2D and 3D spaces have been established, they can be crossed or “blurred” (Jordan, 2009). Nozawa discusses the concept of 2.5D (2.5次元, *ni-ten-go-jigen*), the space between 2D and 3D (see also Sugawa-Shimada, 2020). For *otaku*, experiencing 2.5D is immensely desirable and intentionally sought. Examples of 2.5D encounters may include visiting an actual location featured in an *anime* series, dining at a maid cafe in Tokyo (Galbraith, 2019), or attending a theatrical performance where “actors/actresses thoroughly copy the appearances and nature of anime/manga/videogame characters” (Sugawa-Shimada, 2020, p. 129). In such cases, *otaku* undertake what Nozawa (2013) calls “cross-dimensional travel” (p. 14), infusing their lived, “actual” world with the experience of the virtual, “keeping the boundary intact while at the same time ‘traveling’ to the other dimension” (p. 14).

The dimensional aspect of virtuality is particularly relevant for this thesis as it opens up a way of thinking about virtuality that departs from the immersion usually associated with “virtual” technologies like virtual reality (VR). For example, in an VR experience mediated with a headset or VR goggles, users are made to feel as though they have been “transported to a dislocated space [...] that is visually and audibly distinct from the space outside of their headset” (Saker & Frith, 2020, p. 1433), an effect Boellstorff (2024) calls “sensory

immersion” (p. 50). Departing from this notion of immersion, I conceptualise virtual influencers as aligned with ideas of augmentation, much like how augmented reality (AR) technology “superimposes data onto an object (or person) through a mobile device” (Farman, 2021, p. 139). Virtual influencers add the virtual to the actual, much like mobile apps such as *Pokémon Go*, or the AR filters of popular social media apps like Snapchat and Instagram (Hawker & Carah, 2021). In such cases, digital screens show actual environments layered with virtual information, figures, and objects (Uricchio, 2011). Virtual influencers embody the notion of dimensionality by highlighting the borders between virtuality and actuality as permeable, and themselves as liminal figures capable of crossing between them. A key preoccupation of this thesis is moments of “in-between-ness” (Nozawa, 2013), when the virtuality of virtual influencers is brought into contact with the actual: Chapter 7 explores this in relation to actual people, places, and objects, while Chapter 8 considers the addition of virtuality to cultural customs and communities from the actual world.

4.6 Summary

In this chapter, I introduced key scholarly terrains, ideas, and concepts which inform my analysis of virtual influencers. I began by connecting virtual influencers to key shifts in celebrity culture, examining ubiquity of self-branding practices and the rise of microcelebrity in the context of social media. I then detailed Abidin’s (2021a) influencer taxonomy, outlining the significant variation found among human influencers, and introduced concepts related to visibility and attention which recur throughout my discussion of virtual influencers. I concluded with an overview of three different approaches to conceptualising virtuality, which shape my understanding of what is “virtual” about virtual influencers. In Chapter 5, I outline my methodological approach to studying virtual influencers, and the ethnographic lens I adopted to examine their moments of “in-between-ness” (Nozawa, 2013).

Methods

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, I detail the research methods used in this project. Inspired by situated studies of media phenomena (e.g. D'Acci, 2004; Kline et al., 2003), I approached virtual influencers as a complex and emergent phenomenon invested with sociocultural meaning and implications, traversing online and offline spaces, cultural and temporal contexts, and front-to back-end process and practices. I combined several qualitative methods, including press analysis, web archaeology, non-participant observation, semi-structured online interviews, and document analysis. I employed these methods within an inductive and qualitative methodological framework guided by the tenets of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006) and digital ethnography (Markham, 2017, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012).

This chapter is organised into five sections. In sections 5.1 and 5.2, I recount my research questions, aims and objectives, research philosophy, and methodological orientation. In section 5.3, I describe my fieldwork preparations. In section 5.4, I outline the contours of my fieldwork and data collection, reflecting on my approach to studying the three cohorts I identified as primarily constitutive of the virtual influencer phenomenon: *characters* (the virtual influencers themselves), *producers* (the individuals involved in their design, creation, and management), and *industry stakeholders* (the wider network of individuals and businesses involved and invested in their success). I also discuss key ethical considerations related to data collection, and its reproduction in this thesis. Finally, in section 5.5, I outline my approach to coding and analysing multimodal data from multiple social media platforms.

5.1.1 Research Questions

When I commenced this project in February 2021, only a handful of academic publications had mentioned virtual influencers (e.g. Jauffret & Landaverde-Kastberg, 2018, 2019; Leaver et al., 2020; Marwick, 2018b; Robinson, 2020). Reflecting the infancy of the phenomenon at the time, these early discussions tended to focus on a few recurring case studies, and were largely oriented towards how the phenomenon was unfolding on a single social media platform (Instagram). Early in my fieldwork preparations, I discovered that the virtual influencer phenomenon had grown to be much larger, more widely distributed, and more varied than captured in earlier commentary (see section 5.3). I embraced this PhD project as an opportunity to pursue a holistic approach to studying virtual influencers, and through this, to contribute a more comprehensive understanding of virtual influencers for future

scholarship. In lieu of a substantial body of scholarship on virtual influencers, I took inspiration from their popular labelling as “virtual *influencers*”, consulting literature about human influencers (see section 5.5) for “sensitizing concepts” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 16) to guide my analysis. In so doing, I set out to explore the ways that virtual influencers either align with or depart from theorisations of their corporeal counterparts, as well as how their classification as “virtual” manifest in their social media practices. Reflecting these interests, I devised the following research questions:

- RQ** Is there a meaningful difference between the practices of virtual influencers and the established practices of human influencers? If so:
- a) How is this difference enacted in virtual influencers’ social media content?
 - b) How is this difference perceived and articulated by the producers of virtual influencers and other industry stakeholders?

Between January and August 2022, I conducted six months of non-participant observation of virtual influencers, guided by the tenets of digital ethnography (see section 5.4.3). I supplemented my ethnographic observations with nine semi-structured online interviews with virtual influencer producers and industry stakeholders (see section 5.4.2). I contextualised these insights by analysing documents from and about the virtual influencer industry, including industry presentations and event recordings, podcasts, popular and trade press, company websites, job listings, and social media discussions, and historicised virtual influencers across temporal and geographic contexts through archival web research (see section 5.4.3).

5.1.2 Scholarly Orientation

This project fits within the broader academic tradition of media studies, an interdisciplinary field of study interested in how meaning arises from interactions between people, technology, and media. Media studies scholar Sean Cubitt (2013) describes the field’s overarching mission as a desire to “understand [the] materiality [of media] as objects and systems, as economies and polities, in their operations in the social, cultural, economic, and political lives of the people whose thoughts and passions they mediate” (pp. 15-16). Throughout this thesis, I draw extensively on research from scholarly domains that share this same mission—including film studies, animation studies, celebrity studies, and internet and social media studies—to contextualise and interrogate virtual influencers’ social media practices. My training as a media studies scholar attunes my attention to the different media and technologies involved in the virtual influencer phenomena, the ways in which these are used, and the implications of their production and reception (E. G. Coleman, 2010). I take

inspiration from scholars who have previously situated their study of media objects within larger circuits of production (e.g. D’Acci, 2004; Kline et al., 2003). As I outline in section 5.4, this project was similarly organised around multiple groups: *characters*, *producers*, and *industry stakeholders*.

5.1.3 Research Philosophy & Positionality

Media studies has long been criticized for perpetuating a bias towards Western case studies, contexts, and theory, and for mischaracterising and misappropriating findings from Anglophone countries as universal truths (see Curran & Park, 1999; Shome, 2016; Thussu, 2009; G. Wang, 2011). This disproportionate Anglocentric focus has persisted even in the field’s more recent preoccupations. In their introduction to *Microcelebrity Around the Globe: Approaches to Cultures of Internet Fame* (2018), editors Crystal Abidin and Megan Lindsay Brown observe that among studies of microcelebrity (discussed in Chapter 4) and influencers, “a vast majority of existing research looks into [examples] in predominantly English-speaking, middle-class, white, Anglo-centric spaces or applies Anglocentric theories to different localized case studies around the world” (pp. 1-2). They call for a reappraisal of “citation politics, intellectual biases, [and] personal attention ecologies” (p. 6), pointing out that citing “canonical” (p. 6) scholars and research—without acknowledgement, introspection, nor “critical translation” (Iwabuchi, 2014) of their application to new contexts—does harm by perpetuating the Whiteness and Anglocentrism of academic research.

Conscious of these shortcomings, I took steps to untether this project from the Anglocentricism of its orienting field, and to look beyond case studies and scholarship from the Global North. This was especially important to me as a white (Pākehā/New Zealand European) researcher, given the threat to indigenous knowledge perpetrated by settler colonialism in my home country of Aotearoa New Zealand, as well as in the unceded lands of Boorloo (Perth, Western Australia), where this project was completed. As sociologist Raewyn Connell (2007) cautions:

Social theory is built in dialogue with empirical knowledge [...] When that empirical knowledge derives wholly or mainly from the metropole [...] the effect is erasure of the experience of the majority of human kind from the foundations of social thought.
(p. 46)

Throughout the project, I made an active effort to incorporate case studies, platforms, (vernacular) histories, and theorists from beyond the Global North. Although “Global North” and “Global South” remain contested terms, I use the latter to refer to “regions outside Europe and North America, mostly (though not all) low-income and often politically or

culturally marginalized”, aligned with the recent conceptual “shift from a central focus on development or cultural difference towards an emphasis on geopolitical relations of power” (Dados & Connell, 2012, p. 12). The case studies discussed in Chapters 7 to 10 primarily claim residence in East Asia (specifically, China, Korea and Japan), Southeast Asia (Singapore and Thailand), Latin America (Brazil and Mexico), the Middle East (Israel and the United Arab Emirates), and Africa (Ghana and South Africa). These characters afforded rich cases for analysis (see section 5.5), and represent some of the most creative and commercially successful experimentations with virtual influencers I encountered.

Analysing these case studies required a multilingual and transnational research approach (Abidin et al., 2021; Thussu, 2009). The data, documents, and scholarship I consulted were often written in languages other than English. Given the limited resources and budget of this PhD project, I opted to use freely available machine translation tools to generate “gists” (Nurimen, 2021) of the contents of these sources, gleaning a surface-level understanding of websites, documents, and images containing text in languages other than English to assist with analysis. I used automated translation tools (e.g. Baidu Fanyi, Google Translate, Naver Papago, and Systran Translate), as well as the in-built translation features offered by social media platforms (e.g. Facebook, Instagram, and Weibo [微博]). I am mindful that machine translation tools can never provide completely accurate translations: as scholarship from translation studies attests, “changing languages involves translating lives rather than simply words” (Temple & Koterba, 2009, n.p.; see also Resch & Enzenhofer, 2018). Consequently, I have shown social media posts in their original form and language in all screenshots in this thesis. I use italics to indicate non-English text that has been machine-translated, along with footnotes containing the original text to invite the reader’s own translations and interpretations.

To give appropriate context to my case studies, I read widely from academic, press, and other online sources to orient and inform my analysis and theorising (see section 5.5). I also referred to several studies published over the course of the project analysing virtual influencers in specific geocultural contexts, including China (see Feng, 2022; Pan et al., 2022; Yuan, 2025; Zeng et al., 2023; 廖柯 & 孙璐, 2023), Japan (see Miyake, 2022), Korea (see K. H. Han, 2021; Kim 김유민, 2022; 강은진, 2022; 박진솔 & 구유리, 2022), Malaysia (see Yap & Ismail, 2022), and Romania (see Gross, 2022). Many of the digital environments I encountered while studying virtual influencers were “local apps” (Abidin et al., 2021, p. 120), invested with their own histories, vernaculars, and norms (see section 5.4.1). On local apps I had not used before (including Weibo and Xiaohongshu [小红书]), I spent additional time to

familiarise myself with their features and cultures of use. By de-centering Western case studies, platforms, and histories, I hope this project can join the growing body of research on influencers in the Global South (for example, see Abidin, 2016a, 2018a; Abidin & Brown, 2018; Guan, 2021; Hopkins, 2019; Hurley, 2019, 2023; Iqani, 2019; Kavakci & Kraeplin, 2017; Limkangvanmongkol & Abidin, 2018; Song, 2018), offering insights about virtual influencers that reflect their transnational distribution, and invite future geographically-specific and cross-cultural analysis.

5.1.4 Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this research was to develop new theorisations that could help to explain the role, function, and impact of virtual influencers within the broader influencer industry and visual social media landscape. I intended to offer a cross-cultural perspective of virtual influencers, prioritising case studies, pre-histories, scholarship, industry materials, and press from beyond the Global North. Additional objectives of this research were:

- To map the scale, evolution, and practices of virtual influencers from 2018, when the term “virtual influencers” began appearing in popular discourse (see Chapter 1), to mid-2022, when my data collection concluded.
- To illuminate the behind-the-scenes mechanisms involved in the creation and management of virtual influencers, and the stakeholders involved in the emergent virtual influencer industry.
- To showcase examples of virtual influencers beyond the handful that dominated early press and scholarship, looking beyond their focus on Instagram to consider the characters’ cross-platform social media footprints.

5.2 Research Paradigm

Research paradigms are “the basic belief system or worldview that guides the investigator, not only in choices of method but in ontologically and epistemologically fundamental ways” (Guba & Lincoln, 1994, p. 105). I embrace a relativist ontology and constructivist epistemology. My relativist ontology means I do not believe there is a singular, objective truth which can be uncovered through research, and instead recognise multiple constructed realities (Denzin & Lincoln, 2008, p. 13). This aligns with a constructivist epistemology, which posits that all “individuals seek understanding of the world in which they live and work”, and do so by “develop[ing] subjective meanings of their experiences” (Creswell, 2013, p. 24). I view our understanding of reality as shaped by personal and social experiences, and the contexts, cultures, and norms comprising our individual and social environments. For this

project, I use constructivism as my interpretive framework to consider a multiplicity of perspectives, where each is a product of the accumulated experiences, interactions, and environments of its author.

Complimenting these views, two methodological approaches complete my research paradigm: constructivist grounded theory (CGT) and digital ethnography. Both emphasise the validity and significance of the diverse perspectives and contexts that shape and influence the production, circulation, and reception of virtual influencers. They are also compatible in their shared recognition of the role of the researcher's subjectivity in conducting and representing research, variously describing the researcher as an author (Mills et al., 2006), interpreter (Bryant & Charmaz, 2007), or co-producer of knowledge (Charmaz, 2003). Reflecting on my own role and influence in determining the shape, process, and conclusions of this project was especially important given my etic positionality relative to many of my case studies (see section 5.1.3).

5.2.1 Constructivist Grounded Theory

My study was guided by the tenets of constructivist grounded theory (CGT), as pioneered by sociologist Kathy Charmaz (2000, 2006). CGT is an evolution of what is now termed "traditional" grounded theory (Mills et al., 2006). Developed by medical sociologists Barney G. Glaser and Anselm L. Strauss (1967/2006), traditional grounded theory was formed in response to the belief that all research must involve the imposition of existing theoretical frameworks, seeking either to prove or disprove them with empirical results. Instead, Glaser and Strauss argued for an inductive approach to research, where the researcher generates theory based on the data they collect. A grounded theory researcher "has no preconceived ideas to prove or disprove. Rather, issues of importance to participants emerge from the stories they tell" (Mills et al., 2006, pp. 26–27). Grounded theory has been praised for its effectiveness when researching novel phenomena, given its focus on deriving insights and conclusions based on data, and generating rich theories on which future research may build (Mills et al., 2006).

Fitting within this tradition, this project follows the "constructivist" approach to grounded theory proposed by Charmaz (2000, 2006), a student of Glaser and Strauss. More closely aligned with my own epistemological and ontological views, CGT emphasises that "[d]ata do not provide a window on reality," but instead, that "the 'discovered' reality arises from the interactive process and its temporal, cultural and structural contexts" (Charmaz, 2000, p. 524). Charmaz (2006) suggests viewing "grounded theory methods as a set of principles and practices" and "emphasize[s] [the] flexible guidelines" of the approach (p. 10). She identifies

several core principles of a grounded theory study: (a) an inductive approach to theory generation, rather than the imposition of existing theoretical frameworks; (b) an iterative process of data collection, coding, and theorising; (c) “constant comparison” (Glaser & Strauss, 1967/2006) between data and insights to inform, shape, and clarify codes and categories; and (d) “theoretical sampling” (Charmaz, 2006) to test, refine, develop, and expand emergent categories into theory. I referred to Charmaz’s (2006) guide to conducting constructivist grounded theory regularly over the course of this project.

5.2.2 Digital Ethnography

Inspired by the emerging collection of ethnographic studies on influencers (e.g. Abidin, 2016c; Lukács, 2020; Luvaas, 2016), I selected digital ethnography as my second methodological approach. Ethnography is effectively combined with CGT, although as Charmaz (2006) notes, “[g]rounded theory ethnography gives priority to the studied *phenomenon* or *process*—rather than to a description of a setting” (p. 22, original emphasis; see section 5.4.1). Ethnography is both a methodology and “a method for getting to the heart of meaning and enabling us to understand, in the round and in depth, how people make sense of their lives” (Hine, 2015, p. 1). With roots in cultural anthropology, ethnography is focused on generating “thick descriptions” (Geertz, 1973/1996) and “telling social stories” (Murthy, 2008, p. 837) through sustained immersion in cultural sites. It derives “claims to authenticity from the directness of the experience that the ethnographer had of the setting and from the intensity of immersion within it, rather than aspiring to the production of objective facts” (Hine, 2015, p. 20). Ethnographic research involves observations and interpretations of people, behaviour, and interactions situated within specific temporal and spatial contexts, and encompasses “the process and product of writing, recording, and describing culture” (Harrison, 2014, p. 225).

Digital ethnography has evolved alongside the uptake of digital technologies and online communication since the 1990s, developments which reshaped social practices and afforded researchers “new ways of engaging with emergent research environments” (Pink et al., 2016, p. 3). Today, “digital ethnography” forms part of a muddled constellation of “buzzword ethnograph[ies]”, each competing to “own” ethnographic research involving digitally-mediated topics and tools (Abidin & de Seta, 2020, p. 4). This list includes, but is not limited to, “ethnography of virtual spaces (virtual ethnography), cyberspace ethnography, ethnography of new media, online ethnography, and social media/new media ethnography” (Kaur-Gill & Dutta, 2017, p. 1). These approaches are each beholden to the concerns, interests and methodological underpinnings of different disciplines (Pink et al., 2016). My approach to digital ethnography is guided by my training in media studies, and fits within

anthropologist Gabriella Coleman's (2010) broader conceptualisation of media ethnography as the study of "complex relationships between the local practices and global implications of digital media, their materiality and politics, and their banal, as well as profound, presence in cultural life and modes of communication" (p. 487; see also Markham, 2020).

I conceptualise digital ethnography as an immersive methodological approach to understanding social practices, rituals and cultures wherein digital technologies are centrally—though not necessarily exclusively—involved in the object of study (Pink et al., 2016), tools or methods of data collection (Murthy, 2008, 2011), and/or representation of ethnographic findings (Underberg & Zorn, 2013). My digital ethnographic approach draws inspiration and guidance from ethnographers like Annette Markham (1998, 2020), Christine Hine (2015), Sarah Pink and John Postill (2012), and Tom Boellstorff (2008), despite the variety of methodological labels adopted in their scholarship. I used digital ethnography as a methodological orientation and a mindset to deeply engage with, understand, and contextualise the creative and communicative practices, norms, and impact of virtual influencers as an emergent online phenomenon.

5.3 Fieldwork Preparations

I began preparing for fieldwork in early 2021 while refining my methodological approach and composing my ethics documentation. From February to December 2021, I conducted initial scoping of the virtual influencer phenomenon, using press articles to familiarise myself with its scale, stakeholders, and key themes. I returned to a deeper analysis of these articles later in the project (see section 5.4.3), but my initial focus was on using press articles to build out a list of characters to observe during fieldwork (see also Choudhry et al., 2022).

To locate relevant press, I began with Google searches for two terms often applied to these characters ("virtual influencer" and "CGI influencer"; see Chapter 1), gradually expanding my parameters to include the names of new characters and companies I uncovered. Alongside Google, I utilised local search engines—including Naver (Korea) and Baidu (China)—to locate press commentary published in languages other than English (Abidin et al., 2021). These press accounts assisted in illuminating virtual influencers' transnational spread and impact (Abidin et al., 2021), and provided important cultural context for data collected and analysed later in the project (see section 5.1.4). I also used these articles to identify common translations of the term "virtual influencer" (see Table 5.1), in turn locating more relevant press by incorporating a greater array of multilingual keywords into my search queries (Abidin et al., 2021). When satisfied I had collated a sufficient number of articles, I created Google alerts for stories containing relevant keywords and their translations (see Table 5.1),

monitoring new developments over the course of the project.

To keep track of my growing list of characters, I created new social media accounts to follow the characters' profiles. These researcher accounts had several benefits: compiling the content of multiple characters into a single, coherent view; training the platforms' recommendation algorithms to surface new characters (discussed below); allowing for clear communication of my research credentials (see section 5.4.4); and separating my research interests from my personal networks, making visual trends and patterns in the content from virtual influencers more visible. Later, these accounts became key resources for my ethnographic fieldwork (see section 5.4.1). By this project's conclusion, I followed more than 300 social media accounts, which included characters, their producers (see section 5.4.2), and other stakeholders from the virtual influencer industry (see section 5.4.3).

Social Media Hashtags	Search Keywords
#virtualinfluencer #virtualinfluencers #バーチャルインフルエンサー #가상인플루언서	virtual influencer* バーチャルインフルエンサー 가상 인플루언서 버추얼 인플루언서 虚拟影响者 虚拟网红 vKOL <i>influencers virtuales</i> <i>sanal etkileyiciler</i> Виртуальный Блогер
#cginfluencer #cginfluencers #cginfluencer #cginfluencers	cgi influencer* cg influencer*
#virtualbeing #virtualbeings	virtual being*
#virtualhuman #digitalhuman	virtual human* digital human* 虚拟人 数码人 가상 인간 버추얼 휴먼 디지털 휴먼
#virtualidol #virtualidols 虚拟偶像	virtual idol* 사이버가수 虚拟偶像 バーチャルアイドル

Table 5.1: Themes of cross-language hashtags used to locate new character profiles, and keywords used for locating relevant press coverage. Asterisks in search terms are wildcards indicating an openness to suffixes and truncations. Source: author original.

I created my first researcher account on Instagram, selecting this as my “entry point” (Burrell, 2009) into the phenomenon given its prominence in academic writing on virtual influencers

when this project began (e.g. Jauffret & Landaverde-Kastberg, 2019; Leaver et al., 2020; Robinson, 2020). Soon thereafter, articles from outlets such as Chinese luxury marketing magazine *Jing Daily* (精奢商业观察) pointed me towards “virtual idols” popular on the Chinese microblogging platform Weibo (e.g. Nan, 2021). Reflecting the inaccessibility of Silicon Valley-made apps from mainland China, these characters were not typically active on Instagram, so I created a second researcher account there. Instagram and Weibo became my two “entry point[s]” (Burrell, 2009) during this scoping period, allowing me to account for the overlapping and geographically distinct cohorts of characters that populate each platform.

I used the platforms’ in-built search functionality to locate and follow characters I had discovered through press, uncovering more relevant profiles by exploring and following the hashtags used in their posts (see Table 5.1; see also Bishop, 2022). On Weibo, I additionally browsed relevant Super Topic pages (超话, *chaohua*)—community pages organised around shared interests, often idols or celebrities (see Z. Luo & Li, 2022)—to find new character profiles. The “Virtual Idol Super Topic” (虚拟偶像超话, *xūnǐ ǒuxiàng chāo huà*) proved especially valuable for familiarising myself with virtual influencers’ presence on Weibo, collating all public posts tagged with the topic, and allowing me to identify accounts that used the term “virtual idol” to label their posts.

Upon encountering a new virtual influencer, I created and populated a profile for them in a custom database in the digital notetaking app Notion (see Figure 5.1). I noted details about the “messy web” (Postill & Pink, 2012) that constituted their “digital estates” (Abidin, 2017a, p. 2), and the various social media platforms on which they were active (see section 5.4.1). I searched for the character’s name and username on Google, collating online press, websites, and podcasts in which they were mentioned to gain a sense of the character’s public reputation and popularity, while also accumulating sources for my press analysis (see section 5.4.3).

As I reviewed the characters’ profiles, I often found posts in which other virtual influencers were tagged, or that they had liked or commented upon. I discovered that these interactions had trained the platforms’ algorithms to conceptualise the accounts of virtual influencers as part of an established online network (Burrell, 2009). Like other studies of online communities that have utilised algorithmic logics to locate users with similar attributes, followers, and behaviours (e.g. Christin & Lewis, 2021; Lundy, 2023), the interactions

Virtual Influencer Template

☰ Category	Virtual Influencer
☰ Tags	Empty
📅 Years Active	Empty
📅 First Uploaded	Empty
🌐 Country	Empty
# Age	Empty
🗣️ Language	Empty
👔 Occupation	Empty
☰ Creator	Empty
🍏 Brand Affiliation	Empty
∨ 4 more properties	

Comments

👤 Add a comment...

🔦 NAVIGATION

[Online Locations](#)
[Biography and Facts](#)
[Commercial Partnerships](#)
[Notable Content](#)
[News Coverage](#)

Online Locations

Douyin		
Facebook		
Instagram		
Snapchat		
Spotify		
TikTok		
Twitch		
Twitter		
Weibo		
Xiaohongshu		
YouTube		
Miscellaneous		

Biography and Facts

Commercial Partnerships

Notable Content

News Coverage

Figure 5.1: Notion template used for new virtual influencers, recording basic demographic information, milestones, partnerships, and their cross-platform social media presence. Source: author original.

between virtual influencer accounts meant that new virtual influencers were regularly recommended to me as “suggested accounts” and “accounts [I] may know”. These recommendations helped with diversifying the cohort of characters I was following. Whereas following characters mentioned in press pointed me towards newsworthy characters, often with many thousands of followers (see Choudhry et al., 2022), algorithmic recommendations surfaced accounts with significantly fewer followers (sometimes less than fifty), and only a handful of posts. I was able to follow these accounts from their debut, watching as they gradually built out their brand and accumulated audiences.

5.4 Data Collection

My fieldwork preparations quickly illuminated the scale of the virtual influencer phenomenon. Each new keyword I searched for returned thousands of webpages; for each new character profile I discovered, the platforms’ algorithms recommended five more. “Virtual influencers” was evidently a topic much larger than a single PhD student—limited by time, budget, and resource—could study in its entirety. To make sense of this wealth of data, I consulted studies of media phenomena situated in productive and sociocultural contexts (e.g. D’Acci, 2004; Kline et al., 2003), refining my attention to focus on three key aspects of the phenomenon: *characters*, *producers*, and *industry stakeholders*. Characters refers to virtual influencers themselves (see Chapter 1), and the actions attributed to them on and beyond social media. Producers refer to the behind-the-scenes individuals involved in the design, creation, and management of virtual influencers (see Chapters 6 and 10). Industry stakeholders refer to the wider landscape of individuals and businesses invested the commercial success of virtual influencers (see Chapter 10). Identifying these three groups was key for consolidating my methodological approach, and for tailoring my methods to the concerns, environments, and data most relevant for studying each group.

5.4.1 Character Ethnography

Following formal ethical approval by Curtin University, I undertook a sustained period of ethnographic fieldwork. In the sections that follow, I reflect on my study in relation to key tenets of (digital) ethnographic fieldwork (Markham, 2013): defining the field, participation versus observation, and online versus offline. I also discuss data organisation and storage of my ethnographic data.

Defining the Field

An early and important step undertaken by ethnographers is defining the field site, “the stage on which the social processes under study take place” (Burrell, 2009, p. 182). To define my

field, I enacted Marcus' (1995) influential advice to “follow the people”. This required following the *characters*, allowing the virtual influencers to direct my attention to the many different platforms and environments they inhabit (Boellstorff, 2010). Like many digital ethnographers, I embraced anthropologist George Marcus' (1995) call for “multi-sited” ethnography, moving “across settings to gain more knowledge of the studied process” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 22), and “tracing networks or flows instead of construction-based boundaries around online communities” (Barratt & Maddox, 2016, p. 710). Although much of the early attention paid to virtual influencers in press and scholarship focused only on Instagram, during my fieldwork, I uncovered a far more intricate “network” (Burrell, 2009) of online environments in which virtual influencers were cultivating an online presence. This multi-sited presence aligns with the practices of human influencers, who are not typically “associated with a single platform but [are] rather fluid across a number of spaces” (Hutchinson, 2020, p. 1288). I followed virtual influencers across 11 social media platforms, dedicated messaging platforms, music streaming services, online marketplaces, video games, and virtual worlds (see Table 5.2). I also analysed online discussions about the characters, including popular and trade press (see section 5.4.3), as well as blog posts, YouTube videos, online forums discussions, and official character websites.

Social Media Platforms	Messaging Platforms	Music Streaming Services	Marketplaces	Video Games & Virtual Worlds
Douyin	Community	Spotify	DressX	Animal Crossing: New Horizons
Facebook	Discord	Soundcloud	Mintable	Avakin Life
iTOO (아이투)	LINE		OpenSea	Honor of Kings
Instagram				Minecraft
LinkedIn				Roblox
TikTok				ZEPETO
Twitter				Taobao Life
VK (VKontakte)				
Weibo				
Xiaohongshu				
YouTube				

Table 5.2: Digital environments in which I discovered virtual influencers were present, together comprising my ethnographic field site. Source: author original.

Participation vs. Observation

Ethnographic fieldwork often involves “participant observation”: a period of sustained immersion in a cultural field devoted to observing, learning, interpreting, and participating in local norms, rituals and practices (boyd, 2008). For many ethnographers, participant observation lays at the heart of ethnography’s claims to rich cultural knowledge: “Through participant observation, ethnographers gain access to people’s ways of life, not only by observing behavior, but also by sharing their daily life routines and social meanings”

(Ardévol & Gómez-Cruz, 2013, p. 2). However, approaches to participant observation are contested (see Snodgrass, 2014). As digital anthropologist Gabriele de Seta (2020) observes, “[t]he issue of how participatory an anthropologist’s observations should be is already hotly debated in more traditional research domains,” and “in the case of projects focusing on digital media platforms and media practices, defining standards of participation is even less straightforward” (p. 84). For this project, I opted for a non-participant style of observation akin to what media and communications scholar Kate Crawford (2009) describes as “listening” in social media research. Crawford proposes the term “listening” in place of “lurking” to avoid the latter’s often pejorative and passive connotations (see also Snodgrass, 2014, pp. 470–471). For Crawford, listening denotes more actively “tuning in” to what is being said, navigating competing demands and voices, and decoding multilayered messages and meanings. Aligned with “listening” (Crawford, 2009), I did not engage directly with virtual influencers’ accounts by publicly liking, commenting, or sharing their content; instead, I focused on the aesthetics, genres, and affordances incorporated into their social media content, and their interactions with other characters, brands, and audiences.

In practice, non-participant observation involved several of the sub-practices outlined in Postill and Pink’s (2012) discussion of social media ethnography, including “catching up”, “exploring”, and “archiving” (p. 128). For example, I would “catch up” by familiarising myself with new content posted by the character accounts I followed, relevant hashtags, and press articles surfaced by my Google alerts; I “explored” the characters’ social media content by following the hyperlinks they shared, browsing the accounts of other users they tagged, and searching for more information about topics or events mentioned in their posts; and I “archived” their posts using screenshots and screen recordings, taking care to preserve the multimodal elements, affordances, and interfaces that inflect online data with social and cultural meanings (Boellstorff et al., 2012/2024; Highfield & Leaver, 2016). Data in languages other than English was captured twice: first, in its original form and language, and secondly, translated into English using online machine translation tools (see section 5.1.3). Captured data was also accompanied by scratch notes describing the content and the reason for its documentation (Gorman, 2017). These scratch notes were later extended as longer-form field-notes (Phillippi & Lauderdale, 2018) and memos (Charmaz, 2006), reflecting on larger trends, themes, and ideas as the project progressed (see section 5.5).

Each week, I spent five to upwards of 25 hours engaged in observation, varying the time of day and day of the week. I created dedicated researcher accounts on the social media platforms I determined were most popular among virtual influencers, and used these accounts to immerse myself in content posted by and about the characters. My observations

spanned both live updates and archival content. As anthropologist John Postill (2015) observes, digital technologies alter the temporality of ethnographic observation; observation no longer “necessarily entail[s] physically shadowing participants in real time. Digital ethnographers will often retrace the steps of key participants after the fact, by means of interviews, Web archives, social media platforms, field notes and other materials” (n.p.). This dual temporal focus allowed me to reconstruct histories for the characters I encountered, while also mapping and tracking the virtual influencer phenomenon’s rapid evolution and expansion. As my fieldwork progressed, I discovered that visual social media platforms like Instagram, Xiaohongshu, and Weibo were updated more regularly than text-based microblogging sites like Twitter, or video-sharing platforms like YouTube and TikTok (see Chapter 6). I began reviewing new posts and Stories on Instagram, Weibo, and Xiaohongshu every two to three days, checking comparatively quieter platforms like Facebook, TikTok, Twitter, and Discord on a weekly or fortnightly basis. Most of the analysis in this thesis draws from the content posted to visual social media platforms, but recognises that this forms part of a “messy web” (Postill & Pink, 2012) of online activity (see Table 5.2). Aligned with the extended case method (Burawoy, 1998), over the six months I conducted non-participant observation, I became familiar with virtual influencers’ aesthetic norms and vernacular social media practices, and highly attuned to shifts and transformations over time.

Online vs. Offline

As virtual influencers rely on digital technologies for their existence, I initially expected that my observations would focus solely on online environments (following, for example, Boellstorff, 2008). I was therefore surprised to discover the frequency with which virtual influencers crossed into “offline” spaces. Indeed, this occurred every time a virtual influencer was depicted at a cafe, museum, tourist attraction, or in an unidentified urban street (see Chapter 7). But I also noticed a growing number of opportunities to encounter virtual influencers in the actual world. These were usually tied to virtual influencers’ commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9), including temporary marketing installations like Japanese virtual influencer Imma’s “live” digital screens at IKEA Harajuku (see Z. Li, 2022; Natividad, 2020), or the urban posters and billboards from Korean virtual influencer Rozy’s partnership with local insurance provider Shinhan Life (see Figure 5.2). I abandoned the assumption that my fieldwork would focus exclusively on online environments, and instead found myself drawn to examples of “cross-dimensional travel”, where virtual influencers appeared in the actual world (Nozawa, 2013, p. 14; see Chapter 7). Following the characters from online platforms to offline locations and back again, my ethnographic practice embraced a “non-digital-centric” approach, aligned with design anthropologist Sarah Pink and colleagues’

Figure 5.2: Rozy collates images of posters from her partnership with Shinhan Life on buses and in subway stations in a dedicated Story “Highlight” on her Instagram profile. Source: Instagram Highlight (Rozy [@rozy.gram], n.d.). Screenshots by author on 31 March 2022.

(2016) call to divorce the design and methods of digital ethnography from any particular medium (p. 10). Given my observations were always mediated by a smartphone or laptop (Murthy, 2008, 2011), my approach echoed media anthropologist John Postill’s (2017) discussions of “remote ethnography”, in which fieldwork is conducted from afar, and digital anthropologist Ge Zhang’s (2017) call to reclaim the title of “armchair” ethnography for studies of online phenomena.

Contingencies

Internet researchers must contend with unstable, unpredictable, and sometimes disappearing field sites, communities, and data in their research (see Barratt & Maddox, 2016; D. Wang & Liu, 2021). Reflecting on her experience studying the Dark Web, sociologist Alexia Maddox (2020) reminds ethnographers to “not to get attached to any one ‘site’ as the location of community and to be prepared for some form of site instability during the course of field work” (p. 29). Over the course of this project, I found virtual influencers to be an especially unstable object of study. Several character profiles I had followed disappeared, leaving behind only 404 errors and assorted snapshots in Google searches for their social media handles. For example, in April 2022, shortly after Russia announced it would block nationwide access to Meta platforms (see Feiner, 2022), Russian virtual

influencer Anna's profile was unavailable on Instagram. While Anna continued to post on popular Russian social media platform VK (short for VKontakte, or “ВКонтакте”), her disappearance from Instagram was a reminder of the external forces to which virtual influencers, as platformed and “platform-dependent” entities (Nieborg & Poell, 2018, p. 4276), are subject. This includes, but is not limited to, geopolitical tensions, which threaten the stability of online field sites for users in different parts of the world (see D. Wang & Liu, 2021).

Individual posts by virtual influencers also frequently disappeared, or were edited after my initial encounter with them. Varis (2015) warns that digital ethnographers often “have to deal with *products* rather than *processes*”, and that “what remains visible [online] is the end result of possibly countless edits, changes and deletions” (p. 62, original emphasis). By archiving, deleting, or editing their content, producers could alter public impressions of their characters, tweaking the visual and narrative traces (new) followers were left to encounter. I spent considerable time reconstructing the characters' histories using comparatively more stable sources (e.g. press; see section 5.4.3), and relied on screenshots and screen recordings to capture and preserve my own encounters with virtual influencers' content before it could “slide from view” (Bode, 2006, p. 185). The ethnography presented here explores virtual influencers as they were at a particular moment in time (see section 5.4.4), with no guarantee that other scholars or readers revisiting the digital artefacts discussed will encounter them in exactly the same way.

Data Organisation & Storage

I used screenshots and screen recordings to “archive” the data I observed (Postill & Pink, 2012), taking care to preserve the multimodal elements, affordances, and interfaces that inflect online data with social and cultural meanings (Boellstorff et al., 2012/2024; Highfield & Leaver, 2016). Where possible, embedded media content (e.g. image, audio or video files) was also downloaded as raw media to ensure the availability of high-quality back-ups.

All ethnographic data was organised in Notion, where I designed and maintained digital databases for character and company profiles, ethnographic data, memos, and fieldnotes (see also section 5.5). Leveraging Notion's capabilities for embedding, hyperlinking, commenting, sorting, and filtering, these databases embodied sociologist of new media Dhiraj Murthy's (2008) vision of “new types of fieldnotes that can be inputted online from the field and embedded with video streams, audio transcripts of interviews, digital pictures, and, of course, textual fieldnotes” (p. 164). Access to the digital database was arranged for the supervisors of this project, and protected with two-factor authentication. All data was saved on my laptop and securely located at my permanent residence. Back-ups of all content—

including raw files and manual exports of my full Notion database—were completed periodically throughout the project to an external hard drive.

5.4.2 Producer Interviews

To illuminate the back-stage processes involved in the virtual influencer phenomenon, I supplemented my ethnography of the characters with online interviews with their producers. Interviews are considered an ideal method for qualitative studies, and highly complementary for ethnographic research: as Charmaz (2006) writes, “[q]ualitative interviewing provides an open-ended, in-depth exploration of an aspect of life about which the interviewee has substantial experience, often combined with considerable insight” (pp. 28-29). For this project, interviews allowed me to learn more about the variety of behind-the-scenes roles, responsibilities, and processes involved in creating virtual influencers (see Chapter 6).

Recruitment

For several years, the identities of those involved in creating virtual influencers were fiercely-guarded secrets (see Chapter 10). However, for all the mystique that has publicly surrounded the virtual influencer industry, I soon discovered that many of its participants were keen to take credit for their characters and contributions. I followed a variety of “traces” (Beaulieu, 2010) pointing to producers’ identities, compiling a list of leads. Between March and July 2022, I sent 30 direct messages on Instagram, 15 InMails on LinkedIn, and 39 emails from my university email address to potential interviewees, offering a brief description of the project, and gauging interest in participating in an online interview.

One of the most effective strategies for recruitment was not contacting potential participants, but rather making myself visible for them to find. Throughout the project, I uploaded several videos of conference presentations on virtual influencers to YouTube, and published online commentary about developments in the virtual influencer industry (e.g. Leaver & Berryman, 2022). Industry stakeholders noticed these outputs, and I began to receive new connection requests from them on LinkedIn. These connections proved valuable when it came time for recruiting interview participants. The experience also affirmed a conclusion I had arrived at during my initial mapping of the virtual influencer industry: although largely concealed behind the curtain, the producers of virtual influencers were constantly peering through its gaps, eager to have their work recognised and legitimised (see Chapter 10).

Online Interviews

I conducted nine online semi-structured interviews between March 2022 and August 2022 (see Table 5.3). All participants were sent a Participant Information Statement and Consent

Form to review and sign prior to the interview (see Appendix A and Appendix B; see also section 5.4.4). At the request of Curtin University’s ethics board, synchronous interviews were conducted using Microsoft Teams. Respondents were able to request an audio-only call, but all participants opted to participate using both audio and video. Interviews ranged from 50 minutes to over three hours in length, averaging around 90 minutes. All but one interview was conducted one-on-one; collaborators Frank and Sophia were interviewed simultaneously. Respondents were also given the choice to request an email interview (Dahlin, 2021). This option was chosen by one participant, who was sent a tailored version of the interview protocol to complete via email (see Appendix D).

Participant Name(s)	Location	Character (Instagram @handle)	Producer Role	Company (if relevant)	Interview Type	Date of Interview
Ama Badu	United Kingdom	Shudu (@shudu.gram)	Voice	The Diigitals	Video Call	2 June 2022
Christopher Travers	United States	-	-	Offbeat Media, VirtualHumans.org	Email	14 July 2022
Frank and Sophia	-	John Pork (@john.pork)	-	Bytetribe	Video Call	30 June 2022
Maarten Reijgersberg	Rotterdam	Esther Olofsson (@esther.olofsson)	Creator	RAUWcc	Video Call	30 May 2022
Pablo Lorenzana	United States	Caballo Perrro (@caballo_perrro)	Creator	Offbeat Media (formerly)	Video Call	11 August 2022
Reggie Goff	Ghana	Aba Wils (@abawils)	Creator	-	Video Call	14 June 2022
Reyme Husaini	Singapore	Ava Gram (@avagram.ai) and ELLY (@ellychan.ai)	Creator	-	Video Call	16 June 2022
Yunna Albegova	Russia & United Arab Emirates	MetaKira (@meta.kira)	Creator	-	Video Call	6 August 2022

Table 5.3: Names, location, character, and company details of interviewees at the time of interviews. Source: author original.

Video interviews were semi-structured, and designed to “address specific dimensions of [my] research question while also leaving space for study participants to offer new meanings to the topic of study” (Galletta, 2013, p. 2). I developed a basic interview protocol with topics to guide our discussion (see Appendix C), and spent several hours prior to each interview devising additional questions about the character’s unique background. Interviews began with basic questions around the interviewees’ demographics and professional background (Galletta, 2013), before transitioning into more focused questions spanning four themes:

- a profile of their characters and/or the company they work for
- social media content (strategy, creative process, audience, etc.)
- commercial context (brand partnerships, the perceived value of virtual influencers, etc.)
- industry (future aspirations, market leaders, advice, etc.)

My interviewees offered perspectives on virtual influencers from various geocultural contexts, and included independent producers as well as those who have been employed to

contribute to character creation and management. Several interviewees were self-taught, learning skills and software to create their characters from free online tutorials, user forums, and many hours of practice (see Chapter 6). Others made use of technical skills developed in their professional careers to create their characters. For example, Reyme Husaini and Yunna Albegova both originally created their virtual influencers to showcase digital fashion designs, leveraging their expertise in creating 3D clothing and accessories. Some interviewees had backgrounds in industries closely related to virtual influencers, including Reggie Goff, who worked in marketing, and Ama Badu, an assistant editor in children's fiction, who cited her enjoyment of creative writing as her motivation to apply to be the "voice" of virtual mannequin Shudu (see Chapter 3).

Some of my interviewees offered dual perspectives as both producers and industry stakeholders (see section 5.4.3). For example, Maarten Reijgersberg, CEO of RAUWcc, a B2B social media agency based in Rotterdam, offered insight not only into the production of his virtual influencer Esther Olofsson, but also into how virtual influencers fit within industry discourses around brand strategy and digital communication. Christopher Travers figures as both the creator of VirtualHumans.org, a leading online resource dedicated to virtual influencers, and a co-founder of Offbeat Media Group, an Atlanta-based start-up which has its own virtual influencer, Zero. Pablo Lorenzana is both the creator of Caballo Perro—a half-dog, half-horse character he described as a "virtual *anti*-influencer"—and was formerly an intern and Creative Producer at Offbeat Media Group. Together, my interviews shed light on the wide range of contexts in and purposes for which virtual influencers are created, the experiences of those who create them, as well as the myriad processes and considerations involved in the behind-the-scenes production of virtual influencers (see Chapter 6).

Transcription

With participants' permission (see section 5.4.4), I recorded all synchronous interviews in Microsoft Teams and via my smartphone's voice recorder app. I used Teams' automatic transcription to generate a textual record, and integrated this with a transcript generated by video editing software Descript, manually correcting the errors in the two. Transcripts were sent to participants for final approval, with instructions reiterating that they may edit, amend, add or remove any of the transcript to their liking prior to analysis commencing. All participants approved the versions of transcripts referenced in this study. The published quotes in this thesis have only nominally been tweaked, removing pauses and filler words, to assist with clarity and coherence.

5.4.3 Industry Analysis

Aligned with the interests of media industry scholars, I also consider virtual influencers “within a productive context”, analysing the “the forces—both immediate and distant—that work upon [virtual influencers] to produce [their] genesis, development, specifications, narrative structures and trajectories, audience formations and readings” (Hilmes, 2008, p. 25). Central to this industry are the industry stakeholders, the broader network of individuals and companies invested in the commercial success of virtual influencers. I focused my analysis on promotional rhetoric: the public-facing commentary, discussions, and claims made by and about the virtual influencer industry in presentations and podcasts, documents, and press. Embracing the discursive and promotional quality of these texts, my interest lay in how stakeholders from this specific industry talk about themselves and each other, rather than the accuracy of their claims (see Bestor, 2016; Perren, 2015). As promotional rhetoric, these documents exist in an ecosystem with a vested interest in showcasing and emphasising its own innovation in an effort to secure investors and funding. The mythologies circulated by and about the virtual influencer industry became the focus of Chapter 10.

Industry Events & Recordings

To monitor emergent industry discussions around virtual influencers, I initially planned to attend and participate in a series of industry events and conferences featuring virtual influencers. Business studies scholars Joseph Lampel and Alan D. Meyer (2008) describe these as “field-configuring events” which, albeit temporary, “allow researchers to directly observe the sense-making and sensegiving processes that fuel field formation and transformation” (p. 1030). My hope was to use these events as additional sites for ethnographic observation (Ortner, 2009), participating in conferences that virtual influencers and their producers had a record of attending, including Austin-based tech conference South by Southwest (SXSW), and YouTube creator and industry conference VidCon. I attended SXSW2022 (14-20 May 2022) remotely, the first iteration of the conference since the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic. While the SXSW website promised options for both in-person and online attendance, I discovered after purchasing a ticket that almost all the events I hoped to watch were being held in-person only, without an option to watch via livestream. Hesitant to invest any more of my limited project budget to remotely “attend” tech conferences, I searched for alternative approaches to accessing and analysing industry discussions (Varis, 2015).

In place of attending live events, I accumulated a library of event recordings related to virtual influencers that were freely available online. Although not attending conferences eliminated the possibility of networking with other attendees, this new strategy was significantly more

effective for locating relevant resources, especially as the topic of virtual influencers was usually only discussed in a single presentation or panel in multi-day events. I searched for recordings of panels, presentations, and events on YouTube, Vimeo, and Google, in addition to manually browsed schedules of popular industry events for presentations and panels featuring producers, industry stakeholders, or related to the topic of virtual influencers. In all, I located 25 public recordings of panels and presentations, as well as 33 podcast episodes related to virtual influencers. Given these presentations and podcasts were often addressed at professional audiences, the recordings afforded behind-the-scenes insight into virtual influencer production, and new perspectives about virtual influencers from industry stakeholders invested in their success. Most recordings came packaged with text transcripts, but for those without, I used the video editing software Descript to generate text transcripts (see section 5.4.2), and conducted line-by-line coding and analysis in MAXQDA (see section 5.5). All recordings collected, transcribed, and analysed were in English.

Document Analysis

In addition to these recordings, I analysed documents produced by or about the virtual influencer industry (Bowen, 2009; Perren, 2015). These included company websites, whitepapers and market research reports, press releases, social media posts, as well as promotional and behind-the-scenes videos. I reviewed companies' investment histories and profiles on industry directories like Crunchbase and LinkedIn, and inductively coded over 70 job vacancies from virtual influencer agencies from recruitment websites including LinkedIn Jobs, Wantedly (Japan), and Liepin (China). These job listings were a particularly valuable resource, offering insights into company culture, structure and priorities, and specific detail about the software, technical capabilities, and workflows involved in the day-to-day production of virtual influencers (see Chapter 6).

Press Analysis

I also returned to the press materials collected during my fieldwork preparations (see section 5.3), conducting a deeper analysis of the coverage around virtual influencers in both popular and trade press. By "popular" press, I refer to newspapers (e.g. *Bangkok Post*, *China Daily*, *HuffPost*, *Korea JoongAng Daily*, *The New York Times*, *The Straits Times*, *South China Morning Post*, *The Guardian*, *Washington Post*) and magazines (e.g. *Cosmopolitan*, *Dazed*, *GQ*, *RADII*, *Rolling Stones*, *The Cut*, *Vogue*, *Vice*) intended for a general readership. By "trade" press, I refer to "publications that offer news, information, opinion, and advertisements about an industry for its executives and professionals" (Corrigan, 2018, p. 2753). I examined trade publications from the advertising and marketing (e.g. *Campaign Asia*, *Adweek*, *Jing Daily*, *Marketing Interactive*, *The Drum*), technology (e.g. *36Kr*,

CGWorld, *Dao Insights*, *TechCrunch*, *Wired*), and entertainment (e.g. *Variety*) industries. Analysing press discourse is an established—if under-utilised—method in influencer research (Bishop, 2022). As feminist media scholar Sophie Bishop (2022) explains, examining “wider publications about influencers in mainstream magazines, newspapers, and other journalistic sites” is useful for “map[ping] the wider cultural impact of influencers” (n.p.; see for example Abidin et al., 2021; Deller & Murphy, 2020). Offering a different view, trade press is often utilised by media industry scholars to shed light on “issues like ownership patterns, business strategies, government-industry relations, and labor practices” (Perren, 2015, p. 227). By combining both popular and trade sources, I acquainted myself with the scope, scale, and stakeholders of the virtual influencer phenomenon and the industry surrounding them. I particularly draw on these press materials to chart the evolving myth-making efforts producers have used to legitimise virtual influencers for audiences, brands, and investors (see Chapter 10).

Archival Research

The final method I employed was archival research, combining the ambitions of “web archaeology” (Leung et al., 2001) with the methods of “web historiography” (Brügger, 2012) in order to investigate the pre-histories of virtual influencers (see Chapter 2). Web archaeology is the “study of [...] the *content* of the World Wide Web”, initially proposed as a way to “study hundreds of millions of pages collected from millions of Web sites” using automated web crawlers and data extraction tools (Leung et al., 2001, pp. 1–2, original emphasis). Its description as a kind of “archaeology” suggests its dedication to uncovering and preserving historic artefacts as a source of future knowledge (Parikka, 2012). However, unlike the large-scale ambitions of web archaeology, my approach to archival web research was qualitative and manual. I pursued leads from scholarship about earlier forms of virtual celebrity (see Chapter 2), building out a corpus of archival web materials that included print newspapers and magazines, television commercials, trade press, official websites, online forums, product listings on e-commerce sites (e.g. eBay and Amazon), and fan-produced websites, blogs, and newsletters. Broken or deleted webpages, hyperlinks, and media were navigated using the Internet Archive’s Wayback Machine, which afforded an approximation of the content and commentary available to past visitors (Brügger, 2012). Spanning a variety of temporal and geographic contexts, these materials informed my understanding of the technological, industrial, and cultural precedents for virtual influencers, and what differentiates them as a contemporary cultural phenomenon.

5.4.4 Ethical Considerations

Media and communications scholar Natasha Whiteman (2012) characterises the web as a

site of “ethical destabilisation” (p. 3), wherein researchers “enter into complex, ethically charged environments” (p. 5) and undertake constant “ethical manoeuvring” (p. 5). Whiteman’s emphasis on the fraught ethical climate of online research echoes the sentiments of internet studies scholar Annette Markham (2006), who stresses that research methods should not be conducted “out of habit, but [...] through constant, critical reflection on the goals of the research and the research questions, sensitively adapted to the specificities of the context” (pp. 39-40; see also Barbosa & Milan, 2019). I consulted the ethical guidelines composed by the Association of Internet Researchers (2020), and regularly interrogated the ethical implications of my methodological processes and decisions (Markham, 2006). Below, I reflect on some of the ethical complexities that emerged during this research, focusing specifically on my digital ethnography and online interviews.

Researcher Visibility

Proponents of digital ethnography—and studies of online communities, practices, and phenomena more broadly—have long cautioned researchers of its complex ethical terrain. Murthy (2008, 2011) implores researchers consider the ethical implications of using digital tools for ethnographic observation, given the (practically) invisible access they grant researchers (see also Garcia et al., 2009; Kaur-Gill & Dutta, 2017). Heeding such warnings, I crafted an online presence that signalled my research intentions: each social media account created for this project used my full name, and mentioned my status as a PhD student, my institutional affiliation, and research topic (Barratt & Maddox, 2016; see Figure 5.3). On Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok—platforms where I often encountered characters with varied linguistic backgrounds—I translated my researcher credentials into multiple languages (English, Japanese, Korean, and Chinese). On Weibo and Xiaohongshu, two predominantly Chinese-language applications, I translated my profile into simplified Chinese. Where possible, I reposted content related to my PhD project, and included a hyperlink to my professional website, where visitors could find out more about my research.

Figure 5.3: Researcher accounts on Instagram (left) and Weibo (right). I used Instagram's Highlight features to showcase publications, and on Weibo, reposted content about my research. Source: author original. Screenshot by author on 25 February 2025.

Although I did not announce my ethnographic observations with any greater fanfare than publicly following users from my researcher accounts, there was one online context I felt obliged to seek permission to observe. I discovered several virtual influencers hosted Discord servers: customisable community chatrooms themed around the character. As of early 2022, these servers were often evidence of the characters' intention to join the hype surrounding "Web3", a prophesied evolution of web-based cultures and infrastructures reliant on blockchain technologies, involving cryptocurrency and digital collectables such as NFTs (Non-Fungible Tokens; see Belk et al., 2022). Public "invite" links to the servers were often publicised by the characters across other platforms (see Figure 5.4). However, discussions in a Discord server are obscured from public view: users must opt-in to join, and are typically required to agree to a (custom) set of server rules or code of conduct before being granted permission to see and contribute to the server's content. Given the presumption of privacy likely to characterise interactions in these intimate spaces (Franzke et al., 2020; Sveningsson Elm, 2009; Tiidenberg, 2018a, 2020), I felt uncomfortable joining without making my presence known. In their study of WhatsApp, another "closed" messaging app, social scientists Sérgio Barbosa and Stefania Milan (2019) propose "do not harm" as a mantra to "help researchers to (re-)centre the research subjects and their environment and agendas" (p. 57). Aligned with this motto, before undergoing the verification steps for smaller servers, I sent direct messages to the server administrators introducing myself, my project,

Figure 5.4: Virtual influencers promote their Discord servers on Twitter as part of NFT (Non-Fungible Token) giveaways in early 2022. Left: Japanese virtual influencer Imma, source: Twitter (imma [@imma__en], 2022), screengrab by author on 30 Jan 2022. Right: Singaporean virtual influencer Rae, source: Twitter (here.is.rae [@hereisrae], 2022), screengrab by author on 29 May 2022.

and requesting permission to access to the full server for observation. As these requests largely went unanswered, my observations did not proceed beyond the public sections of the servers. In one instance, I was enthusiastically granted access to the server, and was able to initiate a conversation with the administrator that led to an eventual interview.

Reproducing Content

I have opted to redact public comments and interactions attached to the social media content of virtual influencers in the screenshots reproduced in this thesis. This aligns with scholarly discussions around everyday internet users' expectation of privacy, which underscore that "[j]ust because the material is publicly available" does not mean the author "fully anticipates the scale or reach of their readership or expects it to be re-used without their knowledge or consent" (Page et al., 2014, p. 66; see also Markham, 2012). However, as virtual influencers can be classified as "public-facing and publicity-seeking microcelebrities and aspirants" (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 2) who actively and intentionally court attention, scrutiny and discussion, I have reproduced their social media content throughout this thesis with minimal alterations. I did apply additional parameters when deciding which content to include. Firstly, I opted to restrict my formal analysis and screenshots to social media content that was publicly accessible (that is, not hidden in private accounts), and to accounts that qualified as "micro-influencers" (over 1,000 followers) or above (e.g. Ismail, 2018). Reaching this number of followers signals an intentionality to court attention beyond immediate, intimate circles of friends and family.

All posts by virtual influencers were originally published prior to August 2022, with the exception of the screenshots in Chapter 11, which reflect on the changes in the virtual influencer landscape after my data collection formally concluded. In some instances, I took new, higher-quality screenshots in preparation for publication, so platform interfaces or post captions may have changed from when originally published (Hine, 2015). As outlined in

section 5.4.1, discovering online content was no longer accessible was a common occurrence during fieldwork, and continued throughout the writing portion of this PhD project. I determined whether to include this content on a case-by-case basis. For instance, I opted to reproduce content that automatically-expires as a consequence of platform affordances, such as Instagram Stories, which are only available for 24 hours, or Weibo posts which are sometimes archived after six months (Ye, 2019). In most cases, I chose to reproduce content that has since been archived or deleted in text: although no longer accessible, it was once uploaded for public consumption and circulation, so has been preserved in my written ethnographic account. I have visually reproduced content featured in press or other forms of public discourse only in cases where it felt especially pertinent to do so. Such cases are signalled in captions by a different “Source” than the social media platforms that served as my primary field sites (see section 5.4.1). Reflecting virtual influencers’ objective to gain online attention, posting potentially risqué or scandalous content often appeared to be an intentional strategy for attracting views, engagement, and public commentary, even if these posts were later deleted or archived. I learnt from my interviewees that it is common to archive older content in pursuit of new creative directions and storylines. I therefore reference these examples to showcase the evolution of the virtual influencer phenomenon, including missteps and abandoned experiments, so as to present a more comprehensive view of virtual influencers for readers and future researchers than what may remain on the characters’ profiles.

Interviewee Consent

Aligned with my approved ethical approach, prospective interviewees were sent a Participant Information Statement (PIS) and Participant Consent Form (PCF) to review and sign prior to our interview (see Appendix A and Appendix B). The PIS contained a description of the project, its aims, and intended outputs; the PCF allowed participants to indicate their preferred interview format (video/audio only/email), language, and permit my recording our conversation for transcription purposes. Interviewees were offered four options for identification: by their legal name, a moniker of their choosing, an assigned pseudonym, or to remain completely anonymous. While some scholars (and ethics review boards) argue that all participants should be anonymised by default (see Gerrard, 2020), a growing number of scholars argue that individuals should be given an opportunity to claim ownership and recognition for their contributions to online spaces in research (Bruckman et al., 2015). This stance is particularly prevalent in studies of micro-celebrity and influencers, for whom public recognition of their expertise, cultural production, and brand is likely desirable (Mavroudis & Milne, 2016). All interviewees opted to be named in this research, and have been referenced accordingly (see Table 5.3).

Before the interview, and in a short debrief at its conclusion, interviewees were advised that they could request specific sections of the interview be pseudonymised, anonymised, or retracted should they feel that their statements could cause personal or professional harm to themselves or others. I highlighted potentially sensitive discussion points during the post-interview debrief, and in the written transcript sent to participants, where I requested confirmation of their preferred action for sensitive statements. The transcripts sent to interviewees for approval were as close to verbatim as possible, including small annotations regarding tone, non-verbal cues or expressions (e.g. pauses, laughter), and gestures, which provided additional detail during analysis. Minor adjustments (such as removing filler words and repetition) have been made to the excerpts quoted in this thesis for clarity.

5.5 Coding & Analysis

Data was coded and analysed using the note-taking app Notion and qualitative analysis software MAXQDA. Following Charmaz (2006), I approached coding as an ongoing and iterative process, continuing throughout analysis and drafting. I coded textual data (such as interview and video transcripts) in MAXQDA. I began by coding documents line-by-line, an approach which encourages researchers “to remain open to the data and to see nuances in it” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 50). I used memo-writing to stay “actively engaged” with my data, noting patterns, adding context, asking questions, and connecting my observations to scholarly concepts (Charmaz, 2006, p. 72). Over time, my memos began to reveal recurring points of interest, and became a space for “constant comparison”: critically reflecting upon and examining the relationships between my developing “data, codes, [and] categories” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 179).

I incorporated additional analytical considerations for social media data. Despite the prominence of the visual on social media platforms, internet studies scholars Tim Highfield and Tama Leaver (2016) observe that visual analysis has largely “lag[ged] behind the text-only aspects of online communication or the structural elements” (p. 48), and implore researchers to “broaden and diversify the way social media is examined and addressed” (p. 49). Their calls are especially crucial for research on virtual influencers, given the attention paid to the visual design of characters by their producers and audiences alike (see Chapter 6), as well as the characters’ inhabitation of visual social media platforms with unique and constantly evolving visual vernaculars (see Chapter 7).

I placed a particular emphasis on visual analysis methods (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2021), adapting the “initial coding” approach Charmaz (2006) employs for interview transcripts to suit multimodal social media data. I conceived of my initial codes much like “tags” are used

to categorise content with keywords on social media platforms like Tumblr (see Bourlai, 2018), developing a personal folksonomy of elements in each entry. For example, I tagged the Weibo post by Chinese virtual influencer Starry Yoyo (许星悠) shown in Figure 5.5 with basic elements visible in the image (e.g. outdoors, fruit, another virtual influencer), as well as noting formal qualities of the image itself (e.g. photo of photo, Polaroid) and how it had been styled (e.g. handwriting, annotations/stickers). The folksonomy created through initial coding was helpful for identifying recurring codes, and allowed me to filter entries to only those containing specific elements for deeper analysis and “focused coding” (Charmaz, 2006, p. 46) as the project progressed.

Figure 5.5: Chinese virtual influencers Starry Yoyo posts an image of a Polaroid photograph of herself and fellow virtual influencer Chica having an outdoor picnic. Source: Weibo (| 许星悠 | , 2022), screengrab by author on 20 August 2023.

I further aligned my coding approach with the tenets of “visual cross-platform analysis” (Pearce et al., 2020), interpreting social media data in relation to the various “social conventions, affordances and vernaculars” (Mavroudis & Milne, 2016, n.p.) of its original platformed environments (see Chapter 8). Following social media scholars Taina Bucher and Anne Helmond’s (2018) call for researchers to be “sensitive to platform specificities” (p. 245), I captured details about the platform and format of the post, the use of affordances like geotags and audio tags (see Chapter 8), and disclosures of commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9). Using the tagging approach described above, I also included tags for extra context gleaned from captions (for Figure 5.5, this included tags such as picnic, croquet, season, friendship, etc.), and the use of other platform affordances (e.g. hashtags, linking to a SuperTalk community).

Sensitising Concepts

I used an inductive coding approach to virtual influencers' social media content. Instead of imposing existing theoretical frameworks onto my analysis, I allowed the data to guide it. While this inductive approach aligns with CGT and digital ethnography, it was also of necessity, given the few critical analyses and theoretical discussions of virtual influencers published when I began this project. As the project progressed, I found myself turning to scholarship on (human) influencers to make sense of the practices and behaviours I was observing among virtual influencers. Charmaz (2006) draws on sociologist Herbert Blumer's notion of "sensitizing concepts" to explain how researchers "background assumptions and disciplinary perspectives alert them to look for certain possibilities and processes in their data" (p. 16). She describes how sensitizing concepts "give you initial ideas to pursue and sensitize you to ask particular kinds of questions about your topic" (p. 16). Influencer scholarship was the basis of many of my sensitising concepts, and was essential for developing the conceptual frameworks for Chapters 7 to 9. While this body of scholarship helped to contextualise many of the behaviours of virtual influencers, it also assisted me in identifying what was unique about the practices of virtual influencers specifically. It is moments where virtual influencers depart or adapt what we expect of human influencers that formed my primary research interest. Where relevant, I have augmented my discussions with reference to recently-published scholarship on virtual influencers. This scholarship strengthened my analysis by offering additional context and new disciplinary perspectives, while also affirming their significance for the conversations now underway in relation to virtual influencers and other examples of virtual beings (see Chapter 3).

Purposeful Sampling

My ethnographic fieldwork brought me into contact with over 100 virtual influencers, but for this thesis, I have selected specific cases to discuss. This aligns with the practice of "purposeful sampling" in qualitative research, wherein the researcher identifies and selects "information-rich cases" for analysis (Palinkas et al., 2015, p. 534), as well as what is known in CGT as "theoretical sampling", where the researcher selects "people, events, or information to illuminate and define the boundaries and relevance of the categories" generated through grounded theory methods (Charmaz, 2006, p. 189). My analysis of these examples is informed by my familiarity with the much larger cohort of virtual influencers, recalling the collective case study approach (Stake, 1995).

5.6 Summary

In this chapter, I justified my use of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006) and

digital ethnography (Hine, 2015; Markham, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012) as my primary methodological approaches. Working within this framework, I drew upon several qualitative methods, gaining context and historical insight from press analysis and web archaeology; conducting non-participant observation of hundreds of virtual influencers; conducting semi-structured online interviews with producers and industry stakeholders; and analysing documents by and about the emerging virtual influencer industry, including event recordings, podcasts, company websites and job listings, and popular and trade press. Together, this collection of methods afforded a rich, ethnographically-grounded understanding of virtual influencers' social media practices, commercial behaviours, and industry configuration, complemented by the insights of their producers, investors, and other industry stakeholders.

Production Pipeline

6.1 Introduction

Press commentary about virtual influencers tends to privilege spectacularised stories, highlighting their financial success (see Chapter 9) or interviews “with” the characters (e.g. Ang, 2020; E. Chang, 2017; Dutta, 2022). Significantly less attention is paid to the practicalities and processes involved in creating these characters. With rare exception (e.g. Torgerson, 2018), interviews divulging behind-the-scenes insights into their production tend to be relegated to specialist trade publications, such as *CG WORLD* Japan (e.g. Okawara 大河原浩, 2019) and *Campaign Asia* (e.g. Keegan, 2022), or presentations at industry events. However, unlike creative industries such as animation, where the discursive omission of animator labour is symptomatic of tensions around workforce compensation and security (see Mihailova, 2016), for virtual influencers, this opacity is by design. Many producers of virtual influencers intentionally conceal the nature and specificities of their own labour, downplaying the significant technical skill, time, and even number of contributors required to create and manage these characters (see Chapter 10). Such efforts assist in perpetuating the fantasy that virtual influencers are not “made”, but instead are autonomous beings, with agency and sentience (see also the discussion of *ontological labour* in Chapter 7).

Looking past these mythologies, in this chapter, I bring attention to the behind-the-scenes work and contributions typically elided in popular discourse on virtual influencers. I draw on concepts from animation studies to orient my discussion of the recurring technical and creative processes involved in their production. This framework is fitting, given many of the tools and processes used to create virtual influencers have long histories of use by animation-adjacent industries, including film and television, as well as VFX (visual effects) and video games. As in animated productions, creating a virtual influencer can be the product of a single producer, or collaborative effort undertaken by an ensemble of specialist contributors (see Chapter 3). While scope prohibits my discussion of all contributors involved in this process—such as the body doubles and voice actors whose identities are rarely acknowledged and regularly replaced—critical research is beginning to emerge on this topic (see Cheon & Xu, 2024; Hughes, 2023; Z. Li, 2023, 2024).

Drawing on interviews I conducted with producers, promotional rhetoric from the virtual influencer industry (including trade press, industry presentations, podcast recordings, company websites, and social media posts), producers’ resumes and online portfolios, and

job vacancy ads posted by virtual influencer agencies (see Chapter 5), this chapter pieces together an original “pipeline” (Kaufman et al., 2013) or workflow detailing the behind-the-scenes processes involved in creating and managing virtual influencers (see section 6.3). What sets this pipeline apart from those involved in earlier examples of virtual celebrities (e.g. Kim 김동식, 2000), or other digital characters (e.g. O’Neill, 2008), is that the virtual influencer pipeline is shaped by a “digital first” design logic. This builds upon media studies scholar Jonathon Hutchinson’s (2020) concept of the “digital first personality”, a term used to describe how (human) influencers tailor their appearance, behaviour, and identities to achieve maximum visibility in algorithmic environments. Hutchinson’s concept offers a useful lens for understanding the production of virtual influencers, given the creative decisions involved in this process tend to be shaped by a desire to make the characters visible on social media (Brachtendorf, 2022; see also Chapter 7). In this chapter, I underscore how the technical processes involved in creating and managing virtual influencers often draws inspiration from the appearance, style, and practices of human influencers. Exemplifying the “simulatable aesthetics” of visual social media platforms (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 208), I highlight how virtual influencers emulate the “look” (Foster, 2022) associated with human influencers to attract the algorithmic, audience, and commercial attention bestowed upon their human counterparts.

6.2 Ideation

Creating a virtual influencer begins with ideation: devising a look, style, personality, and purpose for the character who will function as a virtual influencer. As Jesse Zhang, creator of Chinese virtual influencer Angie, explains in an interview with *RADII*, an online magazine focused on Asian youth culture,

To create a digital person, you need to think from the inside out. You define the character first, and then you shape her appearance, her figure, build her bones, and then design her facial expressions, hairstyle, and clothing [...] Her personality and appearance need to be integrated, and it’s all a constant process of polishing and thinking. (as cited in Pinheiro, 2021, para. 20)

Accounts from the producers of virtual influencers suggest that ideation tends to follow two main approaches, beginning either with the character or the audience. One approach begins with a creative vision that a producer wants to realise; the first question to be answered is “Who is the character?” This approach is common among independent producers, especially those who are motivated to create their character as a form of creative or artistic expression. If ideation begins with the character, the process may involve sketches or drawings that assist in visualising the look an original character (see Figure 6.1), collating reference images that capture a general look-and-feel, or even sculpting clay models to get a sense of the character’s physicality and proportions (see Kunkhet et al., 2019). In a virtual influencer agency, these tasks might be completed by a dedicated concept artist or character designer, whose role is to “plan the overall look of the character” (O’Neill, 2008, p. 7). In other cases, ideation may involve experimentation with digital animation software (see section 6.3.1), with conceptual questions answered as the visual design is realised.

Figure 6.1: Concept art for Chinese virtual influencer Ling (left) versus completed 3D render (right). Source: Xmov (*Virtual Human*, n.d.), screengrabs by author on 20 May 2022.

The second approach to ideation begins with the audience the character is intended to engage; the first question asked is “Who is the audience?” This approach is often espoused by industry stakeholders when explaining how they create virtual influencers as a commercial service. For example, Christopher Travers, co-founder of Atlanta-based start-up Offbeat Media, describes how his company “reverse engineer[s]” characters commissioned by clients by focusing on audience preferences. In an interview with *KrAsia*, a trade publication focused on tech start-ups in Asia, Travers explains:

As for us—and I say this in a heavily generalized sense—we reverse engineer the demographic we wish to target and identify what traits appeal to said demographic, then we start building [a character]. (as cited in Fang, 2020, para. 9)

In an appearance on technology industry podcast *Influential Visions*, Dudley Nevill-Spencer, London-based founder of Virtual Influencer Agency (VIA), suggests that designing a

character to resonate with an audience is a major advantage of virtual influencers: “the utility of a [virtual influencer] is that you can figure out what the audience is and create a character specifically for that audience” (Schooler, 2020, 3:15). Much like the “influencer management tools” studied by feminist media scholar Sophia Bishop (2021a), which use platform data and “algorithmic calculations [...] to support marketers in selecting appropriate influencers for advertising campaigns” (p. 1), the process of “figur[ing] out” (Nevill-Spencer, as cited in Schooler, 2020, 3:17) the audience often involves data-driven methods of social media monitoring and analysis. In a podcast interview, Nevill-Spencer describes using these tools at VIA:

... if a brand says to us, “We want to appeal to Gen X,” [...] we will go and scrape one hundred thousand, two hundred thousand [online] conversations of that specific [demographic], then [...] use audience intelligence and [our] other tools to figure out the psychographics—what content they’re responding to, et cetera—and then create a character that we know will appeal to that very specific audience. (as cited in Schooler, 2020, 5:21)

In other cases, popular methods from market research like surveys or focus groups were used to solicit audience input. Hirokuni Genie Miyaji, creator of Japanese virtual influencer Liam Nikuro and founder of virtual influencer agency 1sec Inc., purportedly “surveyed about 100 people” to determine a look for his character that would have widespread appeal (as cited in Begum, 2020, para. 10). The ability to customise a virtual influencers’ design to resonate with specific audiences is clearly aligned with marketing logics and objectives. When marketers enthuse about how virtual influencers’ “appearance and digital personality can be tailored precisely to industry-specific circumstances (fashion, sports, cars, energy, etc.), brand identity and the specifics of the target group” (Dodt, 2020, n.p.), they reveal the commercial ambitions they hold for these characters, and their interest in manufacturing an effective marketing channel for sponsored messaging.

Whether beginning with the character or their audience, ideation involves making creative decisions about the character’s appearance and backstory, distinguishing the character and adding depth to their behaviour. Researchers in fields such as Information Sciences (IS) and Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) tend to conflate these qualities when classifying virtual influencers as either “animated” or “humanised” (Moustakas et al., 2020, p. 4), or “*anime*-like” or “human-like” (Arsenyan & Mirowska, 2021, p. 4). Such dichotomies reflect the interest of these fields in examining how audiences respond to virtual influencers based on their perceived similarity to actual human interlocutors (see also Dabiran et al., 2022; Ma & Li, 2024). However, they have an effect of eliding the significant variation found among

virtual influencers, and the multitude of ways that the characters' appearance and backstory can be expressed. Business and management scholar Simone Lykke Tranholm Mouritzen et al. (2023) instead suggest categorising virtual influencers based on their perceived likeness to humans, as well as their perceived virtuality. They present a taxonomy for classifying virtual influencers with four categories: "hyper-realistic non-human", "hyper-realistic human", "unrealistic non-human", and "unrealistic human" (p. 8). To connect these ideas to the behind-the-scenes considerations typically involved in the ideation stage, I abstract the logic behind the categories offered by Mouritzen et al. to focus on appearance (the character's visual qualities) and backstory (the character's personal history).

6.2.1 Appearance

Appearance encompasses all aspects of how a character looks. Although most virtual influencers are created using computer-generated imagery (see section 6.3.1), a quality which unlocks potentially unlimited possibilities for their design (Brachtendorf, 2022), the appearance of most virtual influencers aligns with the aesthetic norms that dominate the human influencer industry (see Foster, 2022). This likeness can partly be explained by the use of human influencers as inspiration for virtual influencers' designs. For example, the appearance of Japanese virtual influencer Imma developed as her producer Takayuki "Producer M" Moriya was browsing posts on Instagram (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019). In another case, producer Reyme Husaini researched Singapore's local influencer cultures in order to develop a locally-resonant design for his virtual influencer, Ava. In our interview, Husaini explained:

Western influencers, such as Kylie Jenner, Kim Kardashian, Hailey Bieber [...] have a certain look—they have a certain template to them. [In] Southeast Asia, we have a different kind of template [...] and at that point [in] time, [...] I wanted to [link Ava to] the local image.

As this quote suggests, Ava's "look" was shaped by, and in reaction to, what Husaini perceived as the "template" of popular influencers in Singapore, which he later explained as "usually Chinese, female, fair, slim, and someone who is very into the whole fashion, food, [and] travel lifestyle." Husaini's comments explicitly connect virtual influencers' appearance to the concept of "templatability", proposed by internet scholars Tama Leaver, Tim Highfield, and Crystal Abidin (2020) to describe the "formulaic, repeatable and simulatable aesthetics" that dominate visual social media platforms (p. 210). As Leaver et al. explain, templates offer guidelines which others can replicate. Visual social media platforms incentivise users to replicate templates with the promise of positive reinforcement by algorithms and audiences.

For human influencers, social media’s “logic of templatability” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 214) informs not only the genre and style of content they produce (see Chapter 7), but also how they style themselves for online self-presentation. This is evident in vernacular terms like “Instagram face” (see Martin, 2016; Tolentino, 2019) and “*wanghonglian*” (*wanghong* face; see Y. Wang & Feng, 2022, p. 4), which have emerged to describe recurring facial attributes shared by popular Instagram influencers and *wanghong* (网红, internet celebrities; see Chapter 4), respectively. If not naturally bestowed, an individual’s appearance can be morphed with beauty filters, photo-editing apps, cosmetics, and for more permanent results, cosmetic surgery. Although the “single, cyborgian look” (Tolentino, 2019, n.p.) denoted by the “Instagram face” and “*wanghonglian*” represent extremes of aesthetic conformity, in seeking to emulate the look of human influencers, virtual influencers subscribe to the same “logic of templatability” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 214) that motivates this self-presentation and self-posturing in their human counterparts. In so doing, they tend to perpetuate the status quo of the human influencer industry, especially in regards to gender and beauty (Brachtendorf, 2022).

Gender Presentation

Aligned with the gender norms celebrated by the influencer industry, virtual influencers are overwhelmingly gendered female (Y. Shin & Lee, 2023). Like other examples of digital characters, their femininity is articulated through a combination of facial “expression[s], language, hair, actions, costumes, and colors” (O’Riordan, 2006, p. 249; see also Y. Shin & Lee, 2023). It is also expressed via pronouns visible in the characters’ social media bios, or

Figure 6.2: Three examples of male virtual influencers, outliers among the primarily female virtual influencer cohort. Left: Japanese virtual influencer Liam Nikuro; source: Instagram (Liam Nikuro [@liam_nikuro], 2020). Centre: Chinese virtual influencer Vince; source: Weibo (虚拟人Vince, 2022). Right: Korean virtual influencer Noah; source: Instagram (노아 [@noah.seoul], 2022). Screenshot by author on 1 October 2024.

epithets like Japanese virtual influencer Imma’s self-description as a “virtual girl” from Tokyo (see Miyake, 2022). There are only a handful of male-presenting virtual influencers (see Figure 6.2), and even fewer gender non-conforming virtual influencers (including Thai virtual influencer Bangkok Naughty Boo, who uses they/them pronouns, and is described as “nonbinary”; see AFP News Agency, 2021).

The overrepresentation of female virtual influencers aligns with the “presumed feminization of the influencer space” (Duffy & Sawey, 2021, p. 137), where female bodies are regularly employed “as the site of display or conduit of desire” for commercial goods (Abidin & Thompson, 2012, p. 471). Indeed, when asked why Korean virtual influencer Rozy was designed as a woman, creator Baek Seung-yeop explained that her gender was determined based on the commercial opportunities available to female influencers:

The ratio of people using Instagram is much higher among women. The reason why Rozy was set as a woman was to select a character who can be good at Instagram activities. There is a lot to show with a female character, from jewellery to beauty, fashion, and hobbies. It was to convey trends better.² (as cited in Chae, 2022, para. 81)

Baek’s quote offers another example of how virtual influencers are created as “digital first personalities” (Hutchinson, 2020), shaped by the commercial logics of social media platforms. As suggested by communication studies scholar Sarah Banet-Weiser’s (2021) description of social media’s “gendered economies of visibility” (p. 57), the female body continues to carry significant value in the “attention economy” (Fairchild, 2007; Goldhaber, 1997) of contemporary social media (see, for example, Carah & Dobson, 2016). Virtual influencers are feminised to appeal to brands in the product categories popularly marketed on social media, including jewellery, beauty, and fashion (see Chapter 9), and to resonate with the demographic of potential consumers of the goods they may someday promote.

Beauty Standards

Emerging scholarship on virtual influencers affirms that the appearance of most characters reproduces hegemonic standards of beauty. This follows a precedent set by the human influencer industry, where it is accepted logic that “physical attractiveness [is] key to

² Italicised text machine translated by Google Translate. Original text: “로지를 여성으로 설정한 것은 인스타 활동을 잘 할 수 있는 캐릭터를 잡은 것이다. 주얼리부터 뷰티, 패션, 취미 등 여성 캐릭터가 보여줄 것이 많다. 트렌드를 좀 더 잘 전달하기 위한 것이었다” (Baek, as cited in Chae, 2022, para. 81).

producing fame and [...] attracting online partnerships” (Foster, 2022, p. 5). Writing of virtual influencers from the United States and United Kingdom, fashion design scholar Charlotte Brachtendorf (2022) observes that:

with their young, wrinkle-free, symmetrical faces [virtual influencers] are without a doubt considered beautiful in contemporary western society. Their faces have clear, smooth skin, large eyes, full lips, high cheekbones and small, straight noses – all features of normative western ideals. (p. 487)

Media studies scholars Debopriya Roy and Joya Chakraborty (2023) likewise observe that virtual influencers tend to “possess youthful characteristics and are designed with facial features that are considered beautiful within their specific cultural contexts”, including “symmetrical faces”, “well-groomed hairstyles”, and “flawless skin” (p. 9). Offering additional insight into how local contexts shape characters’ appearance, fashion design scholars Yeongyo Shin and Selee Lee (2023) observe that among characters from East Asian countries, virtual influencers tend to have fair skin, long limbs, “a small oval face, a high and narrow nose, and even teeth [...] reproduc[ing] particular aesthetic criteria” privileged in the region (pp. 13-14; see, for example, Y. Wang & Feng, 2022). As cultural sociologist Jordan Foster (2022) explains, “online as elsewhere in our cultural economy, beauty plays a role in structuring opportunity, returning significant social and material rewards to those who are thought to possess it” (p. 5). In an effort to obtain online visibility, “followers, likes, and lucrative endorsements and promotions” (Foster, 2022, p. 5), virtual influencers likewise perpetuate the same hegemonic ideals of beauty and attractiveness. Following in the footsteps of several recent studies on the self-perceptions of young women who use augmented reality (AR) filters and beauty apps (e.g. Lavrence & Cambre, 2020; L. A. Miller & McIntyre, 2022), the idealised—arguably unrealistic—beauty standards upheld by virtual influencers has already inspired research into their effects on followers’ self-image (see Deng & Jiang, 2023; Ji et al., 2022).

Recognisable Features

At the same time as virtual influencers work within these established templates of gender and beauty, they also visually distinguish their appearance with recognisable or “trademark” features. This is not dissimilar from human influencers, who “strive to produce and present a look that will distinguish themselves from others while maximizing their appeal among followers online” (Foster, 2022, p. 3; see also Abidin & Thompson, 2012). However, unlike human influencers, who can accentuate features they already possess, the producers of virtual influencers are able to devise distinctive elements for their characters’ designs from

the earliest stages of production. A particularly telling example is the prevalence of heterochromia (differently-coloured irises) in virtual influencers: although estimated to affect less than one percent of the global population (see Dabkowski et al., 2022), it can be seen in Rotterdam-based virtual influencer Esther Olofsson, as well as Chinese virtual influencers ALiCE and Chuan, suggesting an overrepresentation among virtual influencers compared to their human counterparts. In this example, virtual influencers' recognisable features are typically compatible with the aesthetic ideals and templates their appearance otherwise seeks to emulate: complementing their striking heterochromatic eyes, Esther Olofsson, ALiCE, and Chuan can each be seen to reproduce ideals of beauty and attractiveness.

Like human influencers, whose "[r]epeated emphasis of [specific] body parts helps [them] to distinguish their appearance in the market" (Abidin & Thompson, 2012, p. 471), virtual influencers leverage their recognisable features as a self-branding tactic (see Chapter 4), differentiating themselves from other influencers, human and virtual. In an interview with the *a16z Podcast*, Trevor McFedries, co-creator of American virtual influencer Lil Miquela, recalls that early discussions of her design centred upon the notion of a "Halloween costume":

Like, if you were going to be Miquela for Halloween, [there were] identifiers. People would know who you were. [...] the space buns, the freckles, like certain things like that [...] we [tried] not to deviate from too much. (S. Smith, 2023, 13:05)

Several Halloweens have since proved the success of these ambitions, with "Lil Miquela's [Instagram] Stories [...] filled with reposts of hundreds of fans who had dressed like the virtual influencer", emulating her trademark features (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 204). The effectiveness of this strategy is reflected in press commentary on virtual influencers, where the characters' recognisable features are regularly evoked as epithets: Japanese virtual influencer Imma is often identified by her "bubblegum-pink bob" (as cited in Begum, 2020, para. 1); Singaporean virtual influencer Rae's hair is "powder rose, purple with brilliant streaks of fuchsia" (Rae, as cited in Sim, 2021, para. 9); and Chinese virtual influencer Ling's eyes are frequently described as "designed to look good while wearing Peking Opera makeup" (Q. Wang, 2020b, para. 12). These recognisable features assist virtual influencers in achieving visual distinction, making the character identifiable at a glance (S. Smith, 2023; see also Chapter 7).

Art Style

While the previous discussion has considered the ways virtual influencers tend to emulate the aesthetic templates of human influencers, there is one quality in which their appearance is unique: the art style used to animate them. In their discussion of the appearance of virtual influencers, Mourtizen et al. (2023) categorise virtual influencers as either “hyper-realistic” or “unrealistic” (p. 8). However, aligned with my interest in animation studies, I suggest that it is more useful to consider artistic style along a spectrum from “photorealistic” to “cartoonal” (see Figure 6.3), as it creates space to consider the differently-mediated dimensions that virtual influencers are intentionally designed to occupy (Galbraith, 2019; Silvio, 2019).

Figure 6.3: A spectrum of artistic styles used for virtual influencers, ranging from photorealistic to cartoonal. Left source: Instagram (Rozy [@rozy.gram], 2021). Centre-left source: Weibo (CallMeVila, 2022). Centre-right source: Weibo (| 许星悠 | , 2022). Right source: Instagram (Life of Mia ❤️ [@via.de.mia], 2020). Screenshot by author on 20 August 2023.

The term “photorealism” emerged in art criticism in the 1960s to describe “artists who unabashedly used [...] camera[s] to gather the information they needed to make a painting” and “had the discipline and technical ability [...] to create a painting with enough detail or illusion of detail to simulate a photograph” (Meisel, 2013, pp. 16–17). The term has been adopted by industries including computer engineering (see Nakamae & Tadamura, 1995) and film (see Purse, 2013; Turnock, 2009) to describe computer-generated imagery that is visibly indistinguishable from photographic or cinematographic imagery. Photorealism bears a close affinity to what film scholar Andrew Darley (2000) calls “second-order realism”, referring to an abstracted version of realism that does not aim to reproduce actuality, but rather to imitate other forms of mediation. In the context of animation, a photorealistic art style is thus one that “emulate[s] the characteristics of photography and cinematography” (Dinur, 2021, p. 9), and at its most convincing, achieves verisimilitude, with no perceptible difference from elements or events actually filmed by a camera (see Chapter 7).

On the other end of the spectrum are what are described in animation studies as “cartoonal”

designs (Hosea, 2012, p. 54). Animation scholar Birgitta Hosea (2012) defines “cartoonal” animation as when characters “squash, stretch, exaggerate and otherwise defy the conventional laws of physics and human biology” (p. 54). Compared to photorealistic virtual influencers, the appearance of cartoonal characters is more abstracted, stylised, and expressive, with features (e.g. oversized heads or eyes), dimensions (e.g. elongated or squashed limbs), or movements that can only exist in the realm of the fantastic (see also McCloud, 1993; Wells, 2011). “Cartoonal” designs includes *anime*-like designs (with features like long legs, thin necks, and oversized facial features; see Horno-López, 2016), as well as those from other popular animation traditions, including the influential aesthetic of “Disney-formalism” (see Pallant, 2010), and the modern, caricatured style of 3D animation studios like Pixar and Dreamworks (see van Rooij, 2019). As this chapter will later highlight, even characters who are animated in a cartoonal style can adhere to the behavioural templates of human influencers, whether through their backgrounds and poses (see section 6.3.2), or posting practices (see section 6.3.3).

6.2.2 Backstory

Another key consideration for ideation is backstory. In narrative theory, this term is used to describe events that have taken place prior to, or that “that in some way explain or ground[,] the plot of a given narrative” (Robertson, 2017, p. 37). It is also used “in the context of dramatic performance” to refer to “those aspects of a character’s past upon which an actor focuses and draws to motivate, define, or otherwise comprehend the character in the present” (Robertson, 2017, p. 38). For virtual influencers, backstory can be understood as the content of a character’s life prior to their debut on social media. Some virtual influencers have very detailed backstories; others hint at or reveal little of their past, but still have clearly-defined personalities, hobbies, and passions.

For some characters, backstory is closely tied to species. Marketing studies scholars Carsten Baumgarth et al. (2021) suggest that most virtual influencers “imitate human appearance” (p. 154), but even characters with photorealistic, humanoid designs can still be paired with non-human backstories, like those who claim to be “robots” (e.g. American virtual influencer Lil Miquela, discussed further below) or “aliens” (e.g. American virtual influencers Binxie and Aliza REXX). Other virtual influencers are more recognisably non-human, including rabbit-like Korean virtual influencer Apoki; half-man, half-pig chimera John Pork; and American virtual influencer Qai Qai, a sentient children’s doll (see Figure 6.4). Emerging research on non-human virtual influencers reveals the variety of forms assumed by these characters, including animals, amorphous objects, “personified foods, toys, and fantastical creatures” (Ju et al., 2024, p. 4; see also Choudhry et al., 2022; Xie-Carson et al., 2023).

Creating a non-human virtual influencer will often lead to questions assisting with backstory ideation: for example, how did this non-human character come to be present in the actual world?

Figure 6.4: Examples of non-human virtual influencers, including rabbit Apoki, half-man, half-pig John Pork, and anthropomorphised doll Qai Qai. Left source: Instagram (APOKI 아쁘키 [@imapoki], 2022). Centre source: Instagram (John Pork [@john.pork], 2018). Right source: Instagram (Qai Qai [@realqaiqai], 2020). Screenshot by author on 1 May 2025.

Detailing or alluding to a backstory is one way that virtual influencers can demonstrate interiority, as this suggests the characters lead (and have led) a life beyond the content posted to their social media feed. How backstory is integrated into the characters' content depends on the extent to which they are viewed as storytelling vehicles, which varies from character to character. Perhaps the most elaborate example is American virtual influencer Lil Miquela: upon first joining Instagram in 2016, Lil Miquela claimed to be a regular 19-year-old from Downey, California, but this original backstory was soon upended by the revelation she was actually a "robot" (see Petrarca, 2018a). Setting in motion a new narrative of a "self-aware android rebelling against [and eventually reconciling with] her creators" (Marwick, 2018b, p. 162), Lil Miquela involved her audience in unravelling the details of her robot backstory over the years that followed, reconstructing the past she had been "programmed" to forget. References to this backstory make frequent appearances in Lil Miquela's Instagram feed, whether in another image of a birthday celebrating her turning 19-years-old (again), or photos paired with jokes about her operating software. This sits in contrast to other virtual influencers, for whom backstory is mostly a behind-the-scenes consideration. In such cases, backstory informs the character's personality, style, and behaviour, but is not overtly communicated to the character's followers. For example, during our interview, RAUWcc CEO Maarten Reijgersberg recounted the detailed backstory of his virtual influencer Esther Olofsson, replete with a messy break-up and estranged family members. It

was clear this backstory played an important role in how Reijgersberg envisioned the style, tone, and focus of Esther Olofsson’s content. However, this backstory was only subtly hinted at in Esther Olofsson’s actual Instagram posts, with just a handful of post captions (see section 6.3.3) alluding to her recent heartbreak. Whether it prompts an elaborate storyline, or is used mainly for content planning, devising a backstory for a virtual influencer assists the characters’ producers in conceptualising and depicting their character as an entity that is more than the sum of their social media posts.

6.3 Pipeline

The steps involved in creating and managing a virtual influencer follow a general process which can be understood as a “pipeline”, a term used in the VFX (visual effects) and video game industries to describe a linear series of tasks and processes that recur during creative production (see Kaufman et al., 2013; Nicoll & Keogh, 2019). As I outline below, creating a virtual influencer begins with the character’s design, but also requires an ongoing commitment to creating content for their social media feeds. Managing a virtual influencer is a labour- and time-intensive task: creating a single social media post can take anywhere between a couple of hours and several days (see Keegan, 2022; Yeung & Bae, 2022), depending on the complexity of the creative concept, and the number of contributors available.

To organise the pipeline involved in creating a virtual influencer, I draw on media and animation studies scholar Thomas LaMarre’s (2009) concept of the “multiplanar image” (p. xxiii). LaMarre uses the “multiplanar image” to describe the cel animation techniques used in *anime*, wherein backgrounds, middle-ground, and foreground elements are separately illustrated on transparent celluloid sheets and stacked to form a coherent animated frame. Like cel animation, I argue that virtual influencers’ visual social media content is also “composed of multiple layers or planes” (LaMarre, 2009, p. xxiii). In the sections that follow, I propose an original pipeline for conceptualising the production of virtual influencers’ social media content, comprised of three primary layers: the *model*, the *stage*, and the *frame* (see Figure 6.5). The *model* is the visual representation of the character. The *stage* is the scene in which the character appears. And the *frame* is the (digital) environment in which the content is published. Each of these layers involves different tasks, tools, and considerations (see Figure 6.6). The pipeline outlined in this chapter is neither exhaustive nor exact, but instead is intended to illuminate the scope and complexity of the behind-the-scenes processes involved in virtual influencers’ production, both of which have largely been obscured from public view.

Figure 6.5: Illustration of multiplanar (LaMarre, 2009) composition of virtual influencers' social media posts, with layers combined (left) and isolated (right). Source: author original.

Figure 6.6: Basic pipeline for creating a virtual influencer. Source: author original.

6.3.1 Model

Producing a virtual influencer begins with designing the *model*: the visual representation of the character. This layer takes its name from the technical process of “modelling” in 3D animation, which involves “creating a mathematical representation of a three-dimensional shape of an object” (Vaughan, 2011, p. 4). It realises the creative decisions from the ideation stage (see section 6.2). While some virtual influencers are hand-drawn as 2D entities, most virtual influencers are created either as composite 3D models or fully 3D models (see Figure 6.7). A composite virtual influencer is made by grafting a computer-generated, 3D face onto the body of a human body double; a fully 3D virtual influencer’s face and body are completely sculpted from digital data. Some virtual influencers switch between composite and fully 3D models for different social media platforms, or between posts, in order to showcase different outfits or fulfill different creative visions (H. Jiang, 2023; Yeung & Bae, 2022). For instance, Korean virtual influencer Sua often appears as a composite model in the lifestyle-focused static images posted to her Instagram account, but as a fully 3D model for short dance challenge videos she uploads to TikTok (see Figure 6.8). Although composite and fully 3D virtual influencers have unique production considerations, both require modelling an original 3D face.

Figure 6.7: Comparison of a *composite* virtual influencer and *fully 3D* virtual influencer. Left: Dutch virtual influencer Esther Oloffson (composite); source: Instagram (Esther Oloffson [@esther.olofsson], 2022), screengrab by author on 5 May 2023. Right: United Arab Emirates virtual influencer Meta Kira (fully 3D); source: Instagram (MetaKira [@meta.kira], 2022), screengrab by author on 26 July 2025.

Figure 6.8: Different approaches to modelling the same character. Left: Korean virtual influencer Sua appears as a composite model in lifestyle content on Instagram; source: Instagram (나수아 SUA [@sua_to_z], 2021b). Right: A fully 3D model is used for the dance videos Sua uploads to TikTok; source: TikTok (나수아 SUA [@sua_to_z], 2021a). Screengrabs by author on 8 May 2025.

Creating a model from scratch is often very time- and resource-intensive. In an interview with advertising industry blog *Campaign Asia*, Stan Lim, Chief Creative Officer at Dentsu Singapore explains, “If we are creating a fully custom virtual identity from scratch, the process will likely take between eight to 12 weeks [...] split between strategy, creative, and the CGI process” (as cited in Keegan, 2022, para. 5). In theory, this process need only be completed once, as the first step in the production pipeline. However, Lim explains that most virtual influencers are:

constantly getting upgrades. From more realistic skin textures to lighting, new wardrobe and hair styles, the ability to appear in live streams and interact with audiences and automated motion transfer to improve production efficiency, among others [... virtual influencer] capabilities are constantly being brought online to keep the [virtual influencer] interesting and to keep offering new possibilities for brands. (as cited in Keegan, 2022, para. 16)

Creating a model may therefore be a recurring process, such as when a character’s design requires upgrading, or the character needs to be rebuilt in a new software to appear in a new creative format (Seymour, 2021). The steps involved in creating a model are largely unchanged from those followed more than two decades ago (cf. Kim 김동식, 2000). Much like the virtual idols that preceded them (see Chapter 2), virtual influencers are also “crude skeleton[s] of intersecting, jointed polygons responsible for movement, which is then covered with a surface layer, or 'skin', which creates the impression of organic wholeness, hiding the geometric, 'mechanical' components beneath” (D. Black, 2008, p. 46). Creating a model to serve as a virtual influencer involves a range of steps that I categorise as sculpting, refining, and detailing.

Sculpting

Like the work of a sculptor, *sculpting* describes creating a new form or shape from a material such as clay, stone, or metal. For virtual influencers, this process typically involves the use of digital animation software to create the character in 3D form. In a virtual influencer agency, sculpting will often be completed by a character artist using an industry-leading animation software such as Cinema 4D, Houdini, Maya, and zBrush. These 3D modelling programs were primarily developed for the film and video game industries, but are now regularly used to produce virtual influencers (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019). Moreover, where once this software required the processing power and graphic capabilities of industry-grade computers, advancements in personal computing have made this software increasingly accessible to independent, aspiring, and self-taught animators (A. Wood, 2015). While in

theory, anyone with a laptop and an annual subscription to this software could create their own model to use as a virtual influencer, my interviewees stressed the steep learning curve required to actually use these programmes. Other popular programmes used to create virtual influencers include the open-source 3D animation software Blender, along with Daz Studio, LightWave 3D, and Reallusion's Character Creator.

Sculpting typically follows one of two approaches. The first approach is akin to sculpting a model from clay. It involves an initial blocking stage, where larger, lower-quality shapes are combined to create a general silhouette. This rough geometry is then adjusted, morphed, and defined with detailed brushes to carve out an original character design. A variation of this approach is "box modelling", where a set of polygon cubes is used to model individual body parts, and eventually combined into a complete body (Kunkhet et al., 2019, p. 46). The second sculpting method uses reference imagery or detailed data from a 3D scan of an actual human as a guide (see H. Jiang, 2023). Generally speaking, blocking methods are preferable for more stylised, cartoonal designs, while reference photos and scanning facilitate the more intricate and true-to-life features of photorealistic designs (H. Jiang, 2023; Oosterom et al., 2023). Both approaches require a significant degree of creative and technical ability, and sometimes access to expensive equipment, such as the multi-camera set-up required for 360-degree 3D scans.

An alternative approach involves purchasing a preset model. Several online marketplaces offer premade models that can be downloaded free or for a one-time payment. These models typically come pre-rigged, textured (discussed below), and bundled with a variety of customisation options (e.g. eye colour, cosmetics), bypassing the need for many of the technical steps usually involved in creating a model from scratch. The use of a preset model appears to be the route initially taken for American virtual influencer Lil Miquela, whose producers purportedly used a preset model called "Sapphire HD" from the marketplace attached to Daz Studio as the character's base (Smith, 2023; Turner-Williams, 2020; see Figure 6.9). Meeting the rising demand for virtual beings (see Chapter 3), a growing suite of tools are simplifying the process of character creation, allowing those without the technical skills and knowledge of animation software to easily generate their own 3D models. In April 2021, popular game developers Epic Games launched MetaHuman Creator, a browser-based application marketed as "a complete framework that gives anyone the power to create, animate, and use highly realistic digital human characters in any way imaginable" (*MetaHuman | Realistic Person Creator*, n.d.). Users can select from several preset models based on digital scans of actual people, and edit their facial features using freestyle sculpting tools to export a custom 3D model fit for use as a virtual influencer in a matter of hours.

The screenshot shows the Daz3D marketplace interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Daz^{3D}' logo and links for SHOP, NFT, TECHNOLOGY, COMMUNITY, HELP, and DOWNLOAD STUDIO. A search bar is on the right. Below the navigation, a breadcrumb trail reads '3D Models > People > Genesis 3 People > Female > Vendor > Sapphire HD for Victoria 7'. The main product title is 'Sapphire HD for Victoria 7'. To the right of the title, the price is '\$17.95' and there's an 'ADD TO CART' button. Below the title, the artist is 'Raiya'. The 'Required Products' section lists 'Victoria 7'. The 'Compatible Figures' section lists 'Genesis 3 Female'. The 'Compatible Software' section lists various software options like Daz to C4D Bridge, Daz to 3ds Max Bridge, etc. The 'Install Types' section lists 'DazCentral', 'Daz Connect', 'DIM', and 'Manual Install'. The 'SKU' is '24250'. There's an 'Optional License Add-Ons' section with two options: '*Interactive License \$35.00' and '*3D Printing License \$1.99', each with a 'What is this?' link. A disclaimer states '*Unless otherwise specified, no discounts or offers will apply to License Add-Ons.' Below the main product image, there are four smaller thumbnail images showing different views of the model.

Figure 6.9: Comparison between early iterations of American virtual influencer Lil Miquela and a pre-set model available via the Daz Studio marketplace. Top: Sapphire HD model for Daz3D; source: Daz3D (Raiya, n.d.), screengrab by author on 6 May 2023. Bottom left: Pictured in April 2016; source: Instagram (Miquela [@lilmiquela], 2016), screengrab by author on 6 May 2023. Centre: Pictured in November 2017; source: Instagram (Miquela [@lilmiquela], 2017), screengrab by author on 22 July 2024. Right: Pictured in June 2018; source: Instagram (Miquela [@lilmiquela], 2018), screengrab by author on 22 July 2024.

Although some producers have found preset models limiting, incapable of more complex animations otherwise possible with characters built from scratch (Amirova, 2021), preset models from Daz Studio or MetaHuman Creator circumvent the time, knowledge, and technical skill otherwise necessary to sculpt a character from scratch, lowering the technical barriers to creating a virtual influencer.

Refining

The next stage focuses on *refining* the composition of the 3D design (topology) and preparing it for animation (rigging). Topology involves mapping the surface and contours of a 3D form using a network of geometric shapes known as “polygons” (see Figure 6.10). The form’s structure is visualised as a “wireframe”—sometimes referred to as a “mesh”—which corresponds to the number and arrangement of polygons required to create it (discussed as a visual trope in Chapter 9). In this step, unnecessary polygons are removed to streamline the underlying structure of the model. Topology is a central step for mapping musculature and joints, and for preparing areas of expected movement with the level of structural detail required for animation (O’Neill, 2008, p. 70).

Figure 6.10: A behind-the-scenes look at the topology of Japanese virtual influencer Imma. Source: *CGWorld Japan* (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019), screengrab by author on 6 June 2023.

After topology comes rigging, where the model’s digital skeleton and musculature are defined to enable movement. Many digital animation programmes offer in-built rigging capabilities (e.g. Maya, Blender, LightWave 3D), and Daz Studio and Poser are also popularly used for this task. Rigging involves designing a “motion system” to instruct how the model’s “joints, controls, and procedures” may be animated (O’Neill, 2008, p. 79). The motion system is developed alongside a “deformation system”, which details how connected elements of the model (such as muscles) will respond to the movement of particular limbs (O’Neill, 2008, p. 7). A final consideration is facial expressions, a step which often utilises well-known taxonomies like the Facial Action Coding System (FACS) to produce various facial expressions using different combinations of muscle movements (see Calzolari et al., forthcoming). Sidus Studio X, creators of Korean virtual influencer Rozy, purportedly created 800 facial expressions to allow Rozy to express a wider and more nuanced range of

emotions (강경희, 2021). Rigging usually requires a sound understanding of anatomy, though its implementation may differ based on the character's art style (see section 6.2.1). For example, whereas photorealistic characters may be rigged to enable naturalistic movements, cartoonal characters may be rigged to “squash, stretch, exaggerate and otherwise defy the conventional laws of physics and human biology” (Hosea, 2012, p. 54).

Texturing

Once the model has been sculpted, it is ready for *texturing*. Until this point, the model typically appears as a kind of monochromatic mannequin, composed of a uniformly smooth substance reminiscent of clay. Texturing adds colour, detail, and dimension to the surface of the model's appearance. For example, digital skin is added and customised with colour and shading (see Figure 6.11), textured to add roughness, and enhanced with micro-details like pores, wrinkles, and blemishes (H. Jiang, 2023; Kunkhet et al., 2019). Cosmetics are applied, painted onto the skin to achieve a desired make-up look (see Figure 6.11; see also Okawara 大河原浩, 2019; Torgerson, 2018). These steps typically involve dedicated programmes like Substance Painter, Substance Designer, and 3D Coat, with some steps completed in popular photo-editing software Adobe Photoshop. For greater customisation, precision, and control of face and body hair, specialist grooming plug-ins like Maya's XGen and Unreal's Groom can also be used (see Kunkhet et al., 2019, p. 47; Okawara 大河原浩, 2019). Adding hair is a crucial step, especially for photorealistic characters; as engineer David Burden and education scholar Maggi Savin-Baden note in their book *Virtual Humans: Today and Tomorrow* (2020), “Without good simulated hair, the high-quality rendering and animation of an avatar can be worthless as any sense of true believability of the virtual human can be lost” (p. 55). Texturing is a crucial step for adding visual interest to the character's appearance, and for preparing it for interactions with new environments.

Figure 6.11: A flat-lay view of Japanese virtual influencer Imma's digital skin, showing the addition of colour and cosmetics (left) and texture (right). Source: CG World Japan (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019), screengrabs by author on 6 June 2023.

Before (left) and after (right) cosmetics like blush, lip tint, eyeshadow, and eyeliner are added to Imma's face. Source: CG World Japan (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019), screengrabs by author on 6 June 2023.

6.3.2 Stage

For each piece of new content created for a virtual influencer, the model must be *staged*. As in a theatre prepared with a set and props, the *stage* refers to the scene in which the virtual influencer appears. Drawing from the same theatrical origins, “staging” describes the process of organising the scene's composition (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2021, p. 179). It looks beyond the character to consider the environment in which they appear (background), how they will look (styling), and how they will interact with other elements in the scene (direction). The final step is the technical combination of these three elements (composition).

Depending on the creative concept for the image, staging can take several days (L. D. Coleman, 2018; Keegan, 2022), and may need to be completed several times for a single social media post if multiple images or videos are involved.

Background

The producer must first decide on a *background*: the environment in which the scene will take place. Backgrounds can be static images or animated videos. Most often, the backgrounds of virtual influencers' content are photographs of locations that exist in the actual world. These photographs may be scouted (captured in-person by the character's producers, or someone sent in their stead) or sourced (selected from a photographer's portfolio, downloaded from a stock image repository, or submitted by followers). On rarer occasion, the backgrounds for virtual influencers' content are virtual environments designed using digital animation software like Unreal Engine, Unity, or 3ds Max (see Figure 6.12). These backgrounds often allow the characters to appear in more abstract or fantastical settings (see Chapter 9). However, building backgrounds from scratch can take several weeks, requiring significantly more investment than a single day in which multiple actual locations can be visited and photographed (Keegan, 2022).

Figure 6.12: Korean virtual influencer Rozy sits in a floral 3D environment designed by artist Jenny Jiang. Source: Instagram (Rozy [@rozy.gram], 2022), screengrab by author on 4 September 2023.

The actual places featured as virtual influencers' backgrounds are often examples of "Instagrammable" (see H. Chang & Spierings, 2023), "Instaworthy" (see Gupta & Ray, 2022), or "ins style" (Liu, 2021, p. 246) locations, vernacular terms denoting an alignment with the visual stylings privileged on social media platforms like Instagram. For example, in our interview, producer Reyme Husaini told me that he photographed "Instagram-worthy" locations around Singapore for the first posts by his virtual influencer Ava:

I knew certain places in Singapore that are very Instagram-worthy [...] And at that point of time, as I was creating Ava, I knew at the back of my mind, I have to [...] simulate her in a real-life setting [so] I also had to, you know, go around Singapore to take pictures.

Instagrammable locations exemplify social media's "simulatable aesthetics" (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 208). Foliage, décor, artwork, windows, and lighting cue visitors to compose photographs that highlight the location's aesthetic value to its greatest advantage, producing images similar in visual composition (see H. Chang & Spierings, 2023; Gupta & Ray, 2022). For example, in Figure 6.13, Thai virtual influencers Ailynn and Wunni are shown visiting the same Instagrammable café in Bangkok. In images uploaded to Instagram a month apart, the two virtual influencers sit in the same bright yellow seat and are photographed from a similar angle, revealing the café's second-floor loft and green furnishings behind them. Much like

Figure 6.13: Two Thai virtual influencers visit Chim Chim café in Bangkok, sitting in the same yellow chair in front of the same staircase. Left: Ai Ailynn; source: Instagram (Ailynn [@ai_ailynn], 2021). Right: Wunni; source: Instagram (Wunni [@callmewunni], 2022). Screenshot by author on 27 November 2023.

human influencers, virtual influencers are shown visiting Instagrammable locations for the cultural capital associated with them (see H. Chang & Spierings, 2023; S. P. Smith, 2021). By reproducing the “recurrent ocular motifs” (Gupta & Ray, 2022, p. 683) iconographic of these places, virtual influencers curate content designed to resonate with platform audiences and algorithms.

Styling

Before they are added to the scene, the model is *styled* with different fashion ensembles. For 1sec Inc. CEO Hirokuni Genie Miyaji, styling is a central component of the production of virtual influencers: “*even if you have the technology, it is difficult to develop a character without understanding the fields of fashion and entertainment*”³ (as cited in 横山泰明, 2019, para. 10). Fashion design scholar Charlotte Brachtendorf observes (2022) that “virtual influencers are – for the most part – clothed in highly fashionable apparel” (p. 489), often sporting popular streetwear brands, and garments by luxury fashion houses. For composite models, outfits are usually accounted for on-location, styled as part of the photoshoot with the human body double. Clothing may be independently sourced, borrowed from local designers, or featured as part of paid promotions with brands (see Chapter 9). Alternatively, characters may be dressed in virtual fashion. Virtual fashion and accessories made frequent appearances over the course of my fieldwork (see Chapter 5), especially as investment in virtual clothing labels was rising (McDowell, 2022). While virtual outfits are a requirement for fully 3D models, virtual fashions often featured in posts by composite models (see Figure 6.14; see also Chapter 9). Virtual clothing can be added directly to a model through a process of deformation (see Kunkhet et al., 2019), or separately designed in programs like Clo3D and Marvellous Designer, which specialise in 3D clothing designs and fabric simulations. Virtual fashion and other digital assets can also be purchased or downloaded from independent online marketplaces (e.g. DressX), community-run repositories (e.g. Artstation Marketplace, Blender Kit), or online stores created for the users of digital animation software (e.g. CLO-SET CONNECT, Daz 3D Store, Poser Store, and Unity Asset Store).

³ Italicised text machine translated with Google Translate. Original text: “... 技術だけあってもファッションやエンターテインメントの分野自体を理解していないと、キャラクターを育てることは難しい” (Miyaji, as cited in 横山泰明, 2019, para. 10).

Figure 6.14: Japanese virtual influencer Imma takes a mirror selfie wearing a virtual dress, described in the caption as an outfit she made “to go to the beach with”. Source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2021a), screengrabs by author on 30 July 2024.

Direction

The final step to prepare the character is to *direct* the pose or movement of their face and body, much like an actor is directed in a film production. One method of posing a character is by purchasing pre-configured poses or animations from marketplaces like Daz 3D Store. In other cases, poses are manually configured, often using human influencers as sources of inspiration. In our interview, producer Yunna Albegova explained, “when I’m scrolling Instagram, I always save good poses” (see Chapter 7). If emulating a human influencer’s poses, the producer can manually configure the character’s rig (see section 6.3.1) in a choreographed pose or movement, or use motion capture technology to emulate a human guide (see Figure 6.15; see also Allal-Chérif et al., 2024; Kong et al., 2021). Motion capture is a technology well-suited for creating videos with virtual influencers, given its ability to capture sophisticated series of movements, including precise actions or choreographed dances (Allal-Chérif et al., 2024). It can also be configured to capture facial expressions, a technique also known in the film industry as “performance capture” (see Bestor, 2016), using headsets and facial scanners (Pan et al., 2022, p. 69). Direction and posing also requires consideration of how virtual influencers engage with the environment around them, including people, places, and objects (see Chapter 7).

Figure 6.15: Joerg Zuber (left) models a pose for his virtual influencer Noonouri (right) using an Xsens motion-capture suit. Source: YouTube (Xsens | Movella, 2021), video screengrab by author on 21 July 2023.

Composition

The final step of staging is *composition*, a term used in visual studies to describe “the way in which the representational and interactive elements are [...] integrated into a meaningful whole” (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2021, p. 179). For virtual influencers, composition involves integrating the staged model with the background. In the case of fully 3D models, the model can be layered atop a 2D image using software like Adobe Photoshop, Blender, Cinema 4D, Daz Studio, Poser, or 3ds Max. If the background is a 3D environment, then the 3D character can often be imported directly into the software and photographed using a “virtual camera” (see Bédard, 2022). In the case of a composite model, whose appearance is created by layering a computer-generated face onto the body of a human body double, it is in this stage that the character’s face is layered onto the photo. For static images, compositing be completed in software like Adobe Photoshop or NUKE (Okawara 大河原浩, 2019; Yates, 2020).

Once the model and the background have been combined, virtual light sources are added to ensure the lighting, colour levels, exposure and shadows of the model and background align. As Noonouri’s creator Joerg Zuber describes in an interview with *Forbes*, this step requires close attention to both the visual and physical arrangement of the scene: “We pay a lot of attention to light sources, [and] wrinkles as they reflect the surrounding light. Is the skin shiny or matte? Is there a soft wind inside the hair or is it flat?” (as cited in L. D. Coleman, 2018, para. 13). Once the composition is complete, the final image is ready for rendering, and the

image can be exported as a file type suitable for digital upload.

6.3.3 Frame

In the final stage, the producer's attention turns to the *frame*: the (digital) environment where the content is published, and the context in which it is encountered by audiences. In the process of sharing their content online, it is *framed* by interface, "affordances" (Bucher & Helmond, 2018), and "vernaculars" (Gibbs et al., 2015) of social media: the audience encounters the visual content not as an isolated object, but instead as embedded within a social media environment, which affects how the audience will experience and interpret it (see Spyer & Steedly, 2013). For characters with larger creative teams, framing is a task often entrusted to a dedicated social media manager. Reminiscent of the posting practices undertaken by human influencers, I propose three components of the frame relevant for virtual influencers: posting, cross-promotion, and community management.

Posting

When posting content online, the producers of virtual influencers will use platform features and "affordances" (Bucher & Helmond, 2018) to add additional meaning to their visual content. For example, text captions allow producers to add "character language" (Nozawa, 2013, p. 10) to an image, adding narration written from the character's first-person perspective (Engström, 2022; Wight, 2022). Other platform affordances—such as geotags, hashtags, or @ mentions—can also be used to add information to inform and enhance the audience's interpretation (see Chapter 8). Hashtags are often used to signal the character's virtuality (see Table 6.1). Like human influencers, virtual influencers use different strategies to tag their posts, often reflecting stylistic preferences around how overtly these are attached to a viewer's initial impression of the image (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 74; see Chapter 8). Some characters will feature these hashtags in their text captions; others use line breaks to hide them below-the-fold in their caption, or submit them in bulk in a comment. These hashtags provide metadata which assists the platforms' tagging, sorting, and categorising mechanisms, assisting with making virtual influencers "algorithmically recognizable" (Gillespie, 2017) to their platforms. By networking their content with that posted by other virtual influencers, the characters can make themselves more visible to users engaging with other virtual influencer-related content.

Theme	Example Hashtag	Language	Transliteration/Translation
Virtual Influencer	#VirtualInfluencer	English	-
	#バーチャルインフルエンサー	Japanese	#BācharuInfuruensā [Virtual Influencer]
	#虚拟影响者	Chinese	#XūnǐYǐngxiǎngZhě [Virtual Influencer]
	#虚拟网红	Chinese	#XūnǐWǎnghóng [Virtual Influencer]
	#가상인플루언서	Korean	#GasangInpeulleuonseo [Virtual Influencer]
	#버추얼인플루언서	Korean	#BeochueollInpeulleuonseo [Virtual Influencer]
Virtual Idol	#VirtualIdol	English	-
	#バーチャルアイドル	Japanese	#BācharuAidoru [Virtual Idol]
	#虚拟偶像	Chinese	#Xūnǐǒuxiàng [Virtual Idol]
	#사이버가수	Korean	#Saibeogasu [Cyber Idol]
Virtual Entity	#Virtual	English	-
	#VirtualBeing	English	-
	#VirtualHuman	English	-
	#バーチャルヒューマン	Japanese	-
	#버추얼휴먼	Korean	#BācharuHyūman [Virtual Human]
	#가상인간	Korean	#BeochueolHyumeon [Virtual Human]
	#DigitalHuman	English	#GasangIngan [Virtual Human]
Metaverse	#Metaverse	English	-
	#元宇宙	Chinese	#YuánYǔzhòu [Metaverse]
	#MetaverseHuman	English	-
	#MetaHuman	English	-
CG Imagery & Art	#CGI	English	-
	#CGArt	English	-
	#CGInfluencer	English	-
	#3D	English	-
	#3DArt	English	-
	#3DCharacter	English	-
Narrativised > Species / Self-Awareness	#AI	English	-
	#Robot	English	-
	#IThinkImCGI	English	-
	#あたしCGらしい	Japanese	#AtashiCGRashii [I think I might be CG]
	#IAmCG	English	-
	#あいあむバーチャル	Japanese	#AiAmuBācharu [I am virtual]

Table 6.1: Examples of common hashtags used by virtual influencers, grouped by theme. Translations deviating from the associated theme expressed in [brackets], machine-translated with Google Translate. Source: author original.

Like human influencers, virtual influencers tend to maintain a presence on two or more social media platforms (Baumgarth et al., 2021). During my fieldwork, I observed that virtual influencers tend to have a primary platform where they focus on cultivating their online brand. Most often, this would be a platform “driven by the visual consumption of highly aestheticised everyday life and consumer culture” (Miyake, 2022, p. 8), such as Instagram, Weibo (微博), or Xiaohongshu (小红书). To maximise the content's reach or diversify its audience, producers would sometimes post their characters' content to multiple social media platforms. For example, Japanese virtual influencer Imma will often post content from her Instagram account to Xiaohongshu and Weibo, rewriting her captions in simplified Chinese to suit the audiences on these platforms (see Chapter 8). Based on my observations, there were few examples where the platforms that comprise virtual influencers' “digital estates” (Abidin, 2017a, p. 2) are exact replicas. Instead, virtual influencers' producers appeared to have “platform-specific” (Scolere et al., 2018) content strategies, making active decisions about which content to post where, and how to frame that visual content for different audiences or platform affordances (Engström, 2022; see also Chapter 8).

Publicity

According to my observations, virtual influencers emulate many of the publicity strategies employed by human influencers to draw attention to their latest posts. For example, many characters announce that they have uploaded a new Instagram post by sharing it to their Instagram Stories, a popular influencer practice, given the prominence of the Story feature at the top of Instagram's algorithmically-organised home feeds. Characters will also leverage their audiences on other platforms, engaging in cross-platform promotion. Singaporean virtual influencer Rae uses a bot (see Kocik et al., 2024) in her Discord fan server to automatically announce when new Instagram posts have been posted. By default, the bot notifies all members of the community, posting a short message with a link to the post: "Hey @everyone! here.is.rae just posted a new shot! Go check it out!"

One notable aspect of these publicity strategies is that virtual influencers often accentuate their virtuality in order to publicise their content. For example, virtual influencers will intentionally cover sections of their post with animated stickers when sharing their posts to Instagram Stories (see Figure 6.16). Primarily, these stickers are used to cover the character's digitally-created facial features, concealing the main locust of the producers' technical artistry and expertise to pique audience attention, interest, and responses. The chapters that follow pay close attention to other instances where virtual influencers emphasise and leverage their virtuality as a point of distinction.

Figure 6.16: Virtual influencers Ailynn (left; screengrab by author on 13 June 2022) and Rozy (right; screengrab by author on 23 April 2022) use stickers to cover their computer-generated faces when promoting new posts on Instagram Stories.

Community Management

The final consideration is community management: interactions with other social media users in a bid to maintain and grow their online popularity. Like the “reciprocal intimacies” (Abidin, 2015a, p. 7) enacted by human influencers, for virtual influencers, community management involves liking and replying to comments, responding to direct (private) messages (see Begum, 2020; Chaiyong, 2022), and reposting content created by others which mentions them. This has some similarities to digital media scholar Nancy Baym's (2018) conceptualisation of “relational labour”, coined to describe the changing expectations and dynamics of artist-fan interactions in the contemporary music industry. However, whereas Baym's “relational labour” is defined as “the ongoing, interactive, affective, material, and cognitive work of communicating with people over time to create structures that can support continued work” (p. 19), virtual influencers seem to fulfil these obligations with comparatively less emotional exertion. Aligned with the utilitarian connotations of “community management”, my observations suggested that the priority of most virtual influencers is functional reciprocation (a like for a like, or a comment for a comment; see Figure 6.17), rather than the affective reciprocation often involved in relational labour. This may relate to the challenges of inspiring deep, affective bonds towards virtual influencers as fictional characters (see Lim & Lee, 2023; Stein et al., 2024), or perhaps ethical uncertainty the producers feel about cultivating intimate relationships with followers under the guise of a fictional character. Based on my interviews with producers (see Chapter 5), this functional

Figure 6.17: Japanese virtual influencer Imma thanks her followers for their support in a whimsical Instagram selfie. Source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2020). Screengrab by author on 30 June 2024.

reciprocity also seemed to be an unintended but largely unavoidable outcome of the exhausting virtual influencer pipeline: the significant undertaking of creating a character, and producing content for them on an ongoing basis, limited the amount of time and effort that could practically be invested into community building.

6.4 Summary

In this chapter, I detailed the significant complexity, skill, and creative input required to create and manage virtual influencers. This production often requires an ensemble of unseen creative and technical contributors, as well as highly specialised technologies and skills. I introduced the reader to these specialised technologies and skills by composing an original production pipeline for virtual influencers. I organised this pipeline into three steps, inspired by the different layers that comprise virtual influencers' social media content: the *model*, the *stage*, and the *frame*. I highlighted how the processes involved in the production pipeline are shaped by a "digital first" (Hutchinson, 2020) logic, wherein creative decisions are made to achieve online visibility, often by emulating the look, style, and posting practices of human influencers.

In the next three chapters, I demonstrate how these three layers can be utilised as part of an analytic schema for analysing virtual influencers. Chapter 7 focuses on the layer of the stage, exploring the presence of actual people, places, and objects in the selfies of virtual influencers, and the effect of scenes where virtuality and actuality collide. Chapter 8 focuses on the layer of the frame, examining how virtual influencers use affordances to brand themselves with cultural identities, and connect with communities, traditions, and histories from the actual world. Chapter 9 focuses on the layer of the model, analysing how virtual influencers' bodies are used to connote ideas of innovation in commercial partnerships with actual brands. Following this, in Chapter 10, I examine the mythologies of the virtual influencer industry, complementing the technical detail described in this chapter with their producers' evolving tactics for attaining recognition for their labour, creativity, and innovation.

Staging Liminality

7.1 Introduction

Popular discourse surrounding virtual influencers often reproduces concerns that have historically accompanied the debut of new technologies (see, for example, Chapter 2), asking whether the advent of virtual influencers will make human influencers obsolete. Headlines highlight the prospect of virtual influencers “taking over” (e.g. Bobila, 2018; Licea, 2020) the influencer economy, and “taking on media roles traditionally held by humans” (M.-C. Cheung, 2021). They ask whether “virtual social media influencers [will someday] replace human ones” (Tee, 2021), and describe virtual influencers as a “big threat coming after celeb [sic] influencers” (Lam, 2022). In response to these concerns, producers often use interviews to emphasise their intentions for peaceful coexistence between virtual and human influencers (e.g. Chaiyong, 2022; L. D. Coleman, 2018). For example, in an interview with *South China Morning Post*, Hirokuni Genie Miyaji, CEO of Tokyo-based virtual influencer agency 1sec Inc., clarifies that “[t]here is room for everyone – human and virtual – in the influencer world” (Begum, 2020, para. 36), assuring readers, “We do not want to replace human influencers, but co-exist with them” (as cited in Begum, 2020, para. 36).

In this chapter, I consider this notion of “co-existence” from two directions. I first explore how virtual influencers seek to position themselves as influencers by adopting popular visual “templates” (Leaver et al., 2020) associated with their human counterparts. I focus my discussion on how virtual influencers emulate selfies, a genre of online self-representation and self-branding instrumental to influencer practice (Abidin, 2016a). Secondly, I explore how the virtual and the actual “co-exist” within virtual influencers’ selfies. Examining the layer of the *stage* (see Chapter 6), I structure my discussion around three visual motifs that often appear in these images: actual people, places, and objects. I propose conceptualising these selfies, which depict interactions between virtual influencers and actual people, places, and objects, as examples of *staged liminality*. I argue that staged liminality is a tactic used by virtual influencers to gain visibility in online spaces, and distinguish their content from human influencers. I conclude by suggesting that virtual influencers’ interactions with actual people, places, and objects have a secondary effect I conceptualise as *ontological labour*, fostering an impression of sentience and agency that exceeds their actual capabilities as virtual puppets (see Chapter 4).

7.1.1 Staging

Building on the multi-layered schema of model, stage, and frame introduced in Chapter 6, in this chapter, I focus my analysis on the *stage*: the scene in which the character appears. The stage includes the background (the environment, either captured photographically or created digitally), styling (how the model is dressed), direction (how the model is posed), and composition (the technical combination of model and background to produce the final image). Considered within the stage's production pipeline, the actual people, places, and objects of interest in this chapter typically form part of the background. They tend to be photographed at the same moment, flattened into the background onto which the model is later composited (see Figure 7.1).

Figure 7.1: Approaches to production when actual people and places are featured in the social media images of virtual influencers. Source: author original.

The theatrical connotations of the term “staging” makes it a particularly useful analytic lens for this chapter. Although often conceived as a spontaneous act (Iqani & Schroeder, 2016), scholarship has underscored that influencer selfies are often the result of “highly scripted, choreographed, *staged*, digitally manipulated processes” (Hurley, 2019, p. 3, emphasis added). Producing a “good” selfie requires significant skill, from strategic composition and disciplined self-posturing, to incisive curation and expert photo-editing (see Abidin, 2016a; Lavrence & Cambre, 2020; Liu, 2021). For anthropologist of digital cultures Crystal Abidin (2016a), selfie-taking is an example of influencers’ “tacit labour”: “a collective practice of work that is understated and under-visibility from being so thoroughly rehearsed that it

appears as effortless and subconscious” (p. 10). In actuality, the attention influencers dedicate to choreographing, lighting, and photographing themselves for consumption by an online audience bears a strong resemblance to a staged production.

Selfies by virtual influencers take the logic of staging to its extreme. They reproduce the visual conventions associated with this genre: a close-up at a slight high angle; a forearm extended out of frame; a look, smile, or expression directed towards the camera’s lens (see Figure 7.3). The characters also regularly appear in “selfie scenes” (Ruchatz, 2018), depicted in the process of selfie-taking (see Figure 7.2 and Figure 7.4). However, given the selfie “signifies a sense of human agency” (Senft & Baym, 2015, p. 1589), describing any of these images as “selfies” involves a degree of irony: as fictional characters whose actions are always reliant on human input and oversight (see section 7.3), it is impossible for virtual influencer to take selfies. I therefore employ this label with a level of critical self-awareness, not to imply that the characters have taken these images of themselves, but rather to refer to images that have been deliberately staged to appear as examples of this photographic genre and practice. The elaborate process involved in creating content for virtual influencers (see Chapter 6) affirms the intentionality with which these images should be read. Unlike human influencers, who will routinely take a great number of selfies, “at times with only very small changes to their facial expressions [or] body angles” (Abidin, 2016a, p. 12), and spend considerable time “meticulously selecting” (Liu, 2021, p. 242) the best version to edit and post online, every selfie posted by a virtual influencer is a product of substantial creative labour. As producer Yunna Albegova explained in our interview:

[A] human influencer can take, for example, twenty or, like, forty or, like, a thousand shots of one outfit, and choose the best one. For me, it's [different]. I only make one photo, and I don't have this option to choose. Because if I make two photos, it doubles the time; three photos triples the time.

Given their subjects lack the agency or spontaneity often associated with selfie-taking as a practice, the selfies of virtual influencers illustrate how the aesthetics and poses associated with this genre may be deliberately staged.

7.1.2 Selfies & Influencers

Virtual influencers’ selfies illuminate how the characters seek to establish themselves as influencers by replicating the aesthetics and behaviours associated with their human counterparts. Because virtual influencers use selfies much like human influencers do, I begin this chapter with a brief overview of literature on selfies and (human) influencers.

Selfies are “self-representational, networked photographs” (Tiidenberg, 2018b, p. 21) which perform communicative and identity-making functions valuable for influencer practice. Some scholars (e.g. Abidin, 2016a; Jerslev & Mortensen, 2016) conceptualise selfies’ communicative function as a kind of “phatic communion”, a term coined by anthropologist Bronisław Malinowski (1923) to describe language that is used to “fulfil a social function” (p. 315). Likewise, selfies do not necessarily offer meaningful contributions, but the ease and instantaneity with which they may be captured and shared makes them highly effective for maintaining social bonds (Abidin, 2016a). This phatic function is augmented by the formal qualities associated with selfies as a photographic genre: selfies are often captured in close range, with the subject at arm’s length from the camera. As visual cultures scholar Paul Frosh (2015) describes, selfies “invite the viewer to infer and adopt a physical position in relation to the photographer [...] propos[ing] a particular kind of sociable interaction: the act of accompanying and the subject position of companionship” (p. 1617). The closeness of audience and photographer holds even for selfies that contain little to no visual trace of the person taking the photograph, such as “inferred” or “implied” selfies which encourage photographer and viewer to share a single perspective of the scene before the camera (Zhao & Zappavigna, 2018). For influencers, selfies form part of the “communicative intimacies” (Abidin, 2015a) enacted with their followers, providing “interested onlookers with glimpses into their lives” (Marwick, 2015, p. 155), and collapsing the sense of distance between them by communicating “not only ‘see this, here, now,’ but also ‘see me showing you me’” (Frosh, 2015, p. 1610).

Like other kinds of celebrity, influencers also use selfies “strategically to build, maintain and manage [their] personal reputation” (Tiidenberg, 2018b, p. 72). Selfies’ tendency to focus on the face allows influencers to foreground their own identity and develop a self-brand tied to “their appearances and everyday lifestyles” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 107; see also Chapter 9). They are also useful as relational objects, conveying ideas about the identity of the subject based on their surroundings (Koliska & Roberts, 2021). As media scholars Germaine R. Haleboua and Ghyong Patrick Moon (2021) observe in their study of selfie-taking by young women in Korea, “[t]he composition of the image, situation, and location photographed indicate aesthetic and ontological choices that reveal cultural values, performances of identity and social status of the person taking the selfie” (p. 650). Inversely, as noted by Frosh (2015), “*not* photographing oneself as part of an event or scene becomes an aesthetic, social, political and moral choice” (p. 1612, original emphasis). Influencers leverage these relational logics when they utilise selfies to evidence interactions, experiences, or possessions that carry social and cultural capital (Koliska & Roberts, 2021; Marwick, 2015).

The communicative and identity-making functions of selfies make them valuable for what Abidin (2016d) calls the "visibility labour" undertaken by influencers. Visibility labour is "the work individuals do when they self-posture and curate their self-presentations so as to be noticeable and positively prominent" for online audiences, including current or prospective followers, as well as industry and brand partners (Abidin, 2016d, p. 90). In the hyper-competitive "attention economy" (Fairchild, 2007; Goldhaber, 1997) of visual social media, undertaking visibility labour is increasingly complex (see Chapter 4). Influencers will often turn to popular visual templates, reproducing images with "visually memorable and memorizable visual stylings, settings and practices" (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 214) in order to maintain online visibility. In their research on Instagram travel influencers, media scholars Loes van Driel and Delia Dumitrica (2021) observe that as "influencers become more invested in the economic success of their account, they look toward those with large followings in an effort to emulate their practices", a tendency that "often leads to standardization" in the style of content they produce (p. 73). This is also the case for virtual influencers, who regularly emulate the templates favoured by their human counterparts. In what follows, I briefly discuss three templates popular among human and virtual influencers alike: group selfies, travel selfies, and "merchandise selfies" (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9). I highlight that virtual influencers use these selfies in much the same way as human influencers do: as markers of social standing, cultural capital, and commercial potential.

Group Selfies

A group selfie is a catch-all term for any selfie featuring more than one subject (Page, 2019; Wright, 2015). The visual composition of a group selfie is distinctive: "the photographer is usually at the forefront of a mass of faces and bodies, visibly participating in the process of composing the image as it is taken" (Frosh, 2015, p. 1612). These images have a symbolic function, establishing social identity by representing the selfie-taker or -poster as part of a particular social group (Page, 2019). In Figure 7.2, Japanese virtual influencer Imma holds a smartphone aloft, taking a group selfie with model Kozue Akimoto. Smiling at the camera, the pair wear garments from the women's Fall 2019 collection of UNDERCOVER—a streetwear-turned-high-end fashion brand originally based in Tokyo (Rabkin, 2015)—printed with stills from the 2018 horror film *Suspiria* (Guadagnino, 2018; see also Mowatt, 2019). The image attests to how virtual influencers use group selfies to evidence their inclusion in certain social milieus (Abidin, 2014). Akimoto is a prominent editorial and runway model from

Figure 7.2: Example of a group selfie. Japanese virtual influencer Imma (left) takes a selfie with model Kozue Akimoto (right) at Paris Fashion Week. Source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2019), screengrab by author on 17 July 2024.

Japan, whose modelling career and distinctive style has seen her featured in fashion magazines around the world (The Business of Fashion, 2018). Appearing in a selfie with Akimoto works to imply Imma's own standing in the fashion industry, an implication further affirmed by her access to the UNDERCOVER runway show at Paris Fashion Week. Just as human influencers deliberate over who to include or exclude in their selfies (Abidin, 2014), virtual influencers utilise group selfies with actual people to establish a social identity and self-brand through their association with others.

Travel Selfies

Travel selfies are selfies that emphasise “interaction[s] between the self and places” (Koliska & Roberts, 2021, p. 1). The locations captured in travel selfies range from luxury tourist destinations (see S. Edwards, 2022) to locales closer to home, such as cafés and restaurants, hotels and shops, and other popular landmarks (see Leaver et al., 2020; Liu, 2021). As only a fraction of places visited are deemed worthy of documenting and sharing online, travel selfies are illuminating for the ways they make place(s) visible, legible, and meaningful (Koliska & Roberts, 2021; Schwartz & Halegoua, 2015). Virtual influencers often post selfies with actual places as their background. Characters are regularly depicted visiting cafes, shops, art galleries, amusement parks, and tourist destinations that exist in the actual world. For example, in Figure 7.3, Korean virtual influencer Rozy grins in a selfie taken at

Figure 7.3: Example of a travel selfie. Korean virtual influencer Rozy poses next to Victoria Falls in Zimbabwe. Source: Instagram (Rozy [@rozy.gram], 2020), screengrab by author on 27 May 2025.

Victoria Falls, a UNESCO World Heritage site located between Zimbabwe and Zambia known for its waterfalls and cliff-edge rock pools. The composition of the image is emblematic of a travel selfie: Rozy stands a distance from the waterfall, her back turned towards it, angling the upraised camera to capture the expansive landscape behind her (Dinhopl & Gretzel, 2016). Rozy appears in the bottom corner of the image, allowing the landscape to take visual priority: the viewer's eye is invited to survey plains in the distance, the water rushing between the jagged cliff face, and the large cloud of mist rising from the valley below. By documenting Rozy's "presence" at Victoria Falls—one of the seven wonders of the natural world according to US news organisation *CNN* (1997)—the travel selfie allows her to accumulate cultural capital, while at the same time conveying ideas about Rozy's personality, expressing a love of travel and adventure to appeal to present and future followers.

Merchandise Selfies

Finally, "merchandise selfies" (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9), also known as "product placement selfies" (Abidin, 2016a, p. 4), are selfies that feature the subject with a commercial product. Merchandise selfies are a popular format for the sponsored messaging produced by influencers in exchange for compensation from brand partners (Abidin, 2016a; Abidin & Ots, 2016; see also Chapter 9). By positioning the object close to the face,

Figure 7.4: Example of a “merchandise selfie” (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9). Korean virtual influencer Woori takes a selfie with a can of organic Hoegaarden beer. Source: Instagram (우리 [@woori.gram], 2022), screengrab by author on 26 September 2024.

merchandise selfies forge an association between selfie-taker and the product, implying a personal endorsement often accentuated using captions with written testimonials (e.g. Abidin, 2016a, pp. 8–10; de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9). In Figure 7.4, Korean virtual influencer Woori takes a merchandise selfie with a can of Hoegaarden beer. Woori appears in a cozy domestic scene: sitting in a fleece-covered rattan chair, she wears sweatpants and a loosely fitted jumper, surrounded by a soft light from the room’s white linen curtains. The loungewear, domestic setting (the post’s geotag translates to “*in my warm home*”⁴), and an open pizza box on the coffee table contextualise the beer she holds as part of a casual evening at home. However, imagining the selfie Woori is taking in this image reveals the beer’s conspicuousness. For example, the sideways angle of Woori’s head serves to bring her face closer to the can; and the can itself is rotated to reveal several Roman letters and a delicate floral design, providing just enough detail to identify it as an organic beer from Belgium brand Hoegaarden. Although it is unclear whether this image is a product of a

⁴ Italicised text machine-translated using Naver Papago. Original text: “따뜻한우리집에서” (우리 [@woori.gram], 2022).

formal brand collaboration, it still foregrounds what communication studies scholars Emily Hund and Lee McGuigan (2019) describe as the “shoppable life”, or “the idea that social media users perform and document aspirational lifestyles whose constituent elements can be bought instantly” (p. 20). “Merchandise selfies” (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9) accentuate the relationship between virtual influencers and consumption, naturalising products and brands within the characters’ fictional day-to-day lives (see Chapter 9), and attesting to their capacity to serve as commercial partners.

Like human influencers, virtual influencers use group selfies, travel selfies, and “merchandise selfies” (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9) to develop their self-brands through their association with other people, notable places, and commercial products. However, I propose that such templates have an additional appeal for virtual influencers: through their focus on people, places, and objects, these templates present opportunities for the characters to interact with the actual world. Aligned with the discussion of virtuality in Chapter 4, in describing people, places, and object as “actual”, I refer to those that have analogous, fleshy, or material referents in our world. Though this delineation does not make them impervious to mediation or digital manipulation, I argue that these actual elements are nevertheless productive for the visual juxtaposition they instigate, which I will next discuss as examples of *staged liminality*.

7.2 Staged Liminality

I conceptualise images of virtual influencers that feature actual people, places, and objects as examples of *staged liminality*: scenes where virtuality and actuality collide. The phrase intentionally evokes the theatrical connotations of staging (see section 7.1.1), and the concept of liminality, which I understand as “a philosophy and a set of practices that describe a state of transition between two or more boundaries” (N. Campbell et al., 2006, p. 3). Staged liminality recalls the concept of 2.5 *jigen* (2.5 次元, *ni-ten-go-jigen*) or 2.5D (2.5-dimensional) introduced in Chapter 4. Derived from Japanese fan cultures around *anime* and *manga*, “2.5D” describes interactions between fans, narratives, characters, and the actors who portray them that combine the 3D world of fans with 2D worlds of fiction (Sugawa-Shimada, 2020). Staged liminality shares 2.5D’s quality of “in-between-ness” (Nozawa, 2013, p. 8), combining virtual (2D) and actual (3D) elements as its defining characteristic and primary source of appeal. However, where staged liminality and 2.5D depart is that 2.5D is always experiential, whereas staged liminality belongs to the realm of representation. Recent scholarship on the rise of 2.5D-culture examines “experience[s] that blend [...] fiction and reality” (Gn, 2023, p. 71), including *anime* musicals (see Gn, 2023), maid cafes (see

Galbraith, 2019), and theatrical adaptations (see Sugawa-Shimada, 2021). In these settings, fans feel a heightened sense of closeness to fictional characters, creating spaces of 2.5D where the boundaries between actuality and fiction are blurred. Although staged liminality and 2.5D are closely related, I use staged liminality to describe moments of “in-between-ness” (Nozawa, 2013, p. 8) where virtuality and actuality are brought into contact as a visual effect, which need not involve 2.5D’s personal experience of “cross-dimensional travel” (Nozawa, 2013, p. 18). In this section, I consider why staged liminality is so prevalent in the feeds of virtual influencers, exploring how it differentiates the content of virtual influencers from other social media users, especially human influencers.

7.2.1 Folk Theories of Visibility

As the discussion in section 7.1.2 suggests, staged liminality is a prominent feature of virtual influencers’ social media feeds: characters often appear alongside actual people, places, and objects. One explanation for the prevalence of staged liminality relates to “folk theories” (Eslami et al., 2016) held by the producers of virtual influencers about how to achieve algorithmic visibility. “Folk theories” are hypotheses that social media users “develop and sometimes share [...] about how [...] curation algorithms work in order to plan their behaviour” (Eslami et al., 2016, p. 2371; see also Ytre-Arne & Moe, 2021). Because influencers’ careers rely on attracting and maintaining online attention, their “folk theories” often pertain to achieving visibility for their content in environments organised by algorithms (Cotter, 2019). Feminist media scholar Sophie Bishop (2018) uses the term “algorithmic labour” to describe the “complex and time-consuming labour” influencers invest “to understand how to create content that adheres to algorithmic requirements and avoids algorithmic punishment” (p. 73). Algorithmic labour often involves researching industry resources and blogs (Cotter, 2019); consuming “algorithmic lore” (Bishop, 2020) presented by digital marketing gurus; and engaging in “algorithmic gossip” (Bishop, 2019) with other influencers. It may also entail “gathering and assessing empirical evidence” (Cotter, 2019, p. 902), such as by observing and emulating the behaviours of successful peers (van Driel & Dumitrica, 2021), or undertaking “experiential practices” to test hypotheses and evaluate the performance of one’s own social media content (Duffy & Hund, 2015). The information generated through such practices informs influencers’ “folk theories” about what is currently favoured by algorithmic logics, which in turn shapes their future posting behaviour. Scholarship has highlighted that human influencers hold “folk theories” around post engagement and follower interaction (see Cotter, 2019; O’Meara, 2019); post scheduling (see Abidin, 2014) and frequency (see Arriagada & Ibáñez, 2020); as well as linguistic practices (see Bishop, 2018).

Comments from the producers of virtual influencers suggest they view staged liminality as a means of making their characters' content more prominent. Several of the producers I interviewed mentioned the strong performance of posts that featured their characters alongside actual people. For example, digital fashion designer Yunna Albegova recalled the response to the first post of her virtual influencer, Meta Kira, with an actual person as an early milestone. In the image, Meta Kira and Ana Soufull (a friend of Albegova's and founder of a Dubai-based wellness group) are shown sitting at a wooden table outside Le Pain Quotidien café in Dubai (see Figure 7.5). Both wear lightweight blouses under panelled-front *abaya* (a style of robe popular in the Middle East) and dangling ornamental earrings, resting their hands on the table in front of them. In our interview, Albegova grinned as she recalled the unexpected response to the post:

[That] photo was so crazily popular for Kira. Because before, for example, she had—like, I don't know—like five hundred people would look at her. With that photo, it's like four thousand people, so it was really, like, booming.

Figure 7.5: Meta Kira poses with Dubai-based wellness guru Ana Soufull at Le Pain Quotidien café in Dubai. Source: Instagram (MetaKira [@meta.kira], 2022b), screengrab by author on 27 July 2023.

In another interview, CEO of Rotterdam-based social media agency RAUWcc Maarten Reijgersberg recounted a similar response to the first Instagram post of his virtual influencer, Esther Olofsson, alongside an actual person (see Figure 7.6). Set against a backdrop of leaves and tree trunks, Esther Olofsson stands next to Dutch lifestyle blogger and nature influencer Jennie Gielen (and Gielen's dog Cody) in Kralingse Bos, an urban park in Rotterdam. Reijgersberg explained:

In the beginning, we did a few tests—for instance, making pictures of Esther with a real-life influencer. And we use[d] the sweetest, most nature-loving real-life influencer there was to see if this contrast would work. [...] For us, that was a big test: how do people react if we put Esther next to a real-life person, or to an animal? We [...] found out that Esther in combination with a real-life person works better than just [a photo of Esther by herself], so that's kind of cool.

Figure 7.6: Esther Olofsson documents a walk in the forest with Dutch lifestyle blogger Jennie Gielen, and Gielen's dog Cody. Source: Instagram (Esther Olofsson [@esther.olofsson], 2022), screengrab by author on 27 July 2023.

Like human influencers (see Cotter, 2019), these producers monitor and measure the performance of their characters' content using platform metrics: Albegova points to the number of views achieved by Kira's post as evidence of its success, while Reijgersberg, who has access to the resources of a social media agency, complements platform metrics with

additional insights from social media measurement tools like HypeAuditor (mentioned later in our interview). Both accounts reveal how the first-hand experiences and “experiential practices” (Duffy & Meisner, 2023, p. 287) of producers are subjectively “decoded” (see Lomborg & Kapsch, 2020) to form hypotheses about specific elements that led to or detracted from a post’s success. Reijgersberg and his team at RAUWcc deliberately set out to “test” different hypotheses to see what style of content would perform best for Esther, concluding that posts including actual people “work better” than photos of the character alone. For Albegova, the success of the post was an unexpected discovery. When asked why she felt it was so successful, Albegova clarified: “A photo of just Kira is not [as] interesting [as a] photo of her *with* someone. Photos with someone [else] are always more popular, always more interesting, always make people react more.” The recurring “always” in this quote speaks to the conviction with which Albegova holds staged liminality as an algorithmic folk theory. This is also evidenced by its impact on her subsequent content production, with Kira appearing in many more group selfies with human companions in the months that followed. These quotes—and those in the section that follows—situate staged liminality in the realm of folk theory: an aesthetic configuration with proven and projected success for achieving visibility in algorithmic environments.

7.2.2 Defamiliarisation

Staged liminality’s ability to capture online attention can be understood as an effect of “defamiliarisation”. With roots in literary theory—more precisely, early twentieth-century Russian Formalism (as *ostranenie*; see Shklovsky, 1917/1988)—“defamiliarisation” describes the act of making what is familiar feel unfamiliar, or what is expected suddenly strange. Defamiliarisation is both relational and intertextual, arising from a subversion of convention. According to literary critic Daniel P. Gunn (1984), “To produce an effect of defamiliarization, an artist must consciously violate the accepted ways of making meaning” (p. 30). Film theorist Simon Spiegel (2008) further explains defamiliarisation as an artistic technique that renews attention towards that which we have become desensitised:

In daily life, we often perceive things only superficially—i.e., we do not really see them the way they are. To truly see things again we must overcome our “blind” perception, and this is only possible when they are made strange[.] (p. 369)

In literature, art, and film, defamiliarisation demands and directs attention to what would otherwise be overlooked. This effect has considerable value in the context of social media. Although reproducing the “formulaic, repeatable and simulatable aesthetics” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 210) favoured by human influencers is a popular tactic for increasing online visibility

(van Driel & Dumitrica, 2021), posts that too faithfully reproduce these templates risk fading into the background, as one of countless other identical images (see Leaver et al., 2020; Stevens, 2021). Instead, “[s]uccessful reinterpretations require comprehending the original, then using technical and creative skill to put one’s own spin on the same theme, producing something simultaneously derivative and unique” (Hautea et al., 2021, p. 3). I argue that virtual influencers achieve this through defamiliarisation, adding virtuality to make the visual templates and aesthetics of social media unfamiliar.

Defamiliarisation is often alluded to in discussions of virtual influencers. For example, UK-based marketing consultant Scott Guthrie (2020) observes that the visual templates of visual social media platforms like Instagram “have become so ingrained; so ubiquitous we no longer see them” (p. 274); in this context, he suggests, virtual influencers serve as a “fresh pair of eyes to jolt us out of our blind spot” (p. 274). In an interview with *a16z Podcast*, Trevor McFedries, co-creator of American virtual influencer Lil Miquela, likewise highlights how virtual influencers disrupt “familiar” patterns:

In a kind of an infinite scroll world where, you know, nothing makes you take pause, these things that [...] disrupt these patterns that you're familiar with, [they] make you pause and [say], “What's going on?” (S. Smith, 2023, 10:53)

Both Guthrie and McFedries draw on visceral language to explain the defamiliarising effect of virtual influencers, “jolt[ing]” (Guthrie, 2020, p. 274) the audience from their scrolling stupor by “disrupt[ing]” (S. Smith, 2023, 11:02) the patterns of content they expect to see.

While these quotes refer to virtual influencers in general, I suggest the defamiliarising effect of virtual influencers is accentuated by staged liminality. When we recognise an actual person, place, or object in an image, our instinct is to use these referents to orient our “geometric perspective” (Goffman, 1976, p. 12) of the scene. However, upon doing so, we quickly become attuned to elements that are out of sync. The actual referents become visual benchmarks against which virtual influencers are assessed, potentially augmenting traces of virtuality in the characters’ appearance. Such an effect is referenced in an industry presentation by producer Joerg Zuber, who describes posing his virtual influencer Noonouri next to actual people to exaggerate her already “cartoonal” features (Hosea, 2012; see Chapter 6): the human model on one side “looks somehow true, natural, but on the other side doesn't, because the eyes are bigger, the face doesn't look like a real human, in a way” (Xsens Movella, 2021, 11:46). Even photorealistic characters, who usually strive to minimise or conceal visible traces of their virtuality, may incidentally reveal their digital composition via minor misalignments in the depth, perspective, lighting, or texture of computer-generated

elements, which are made visible through their proximity to actual referents.

Choices in the image's composition can further accentuate this contrast. For instance, in the image of Meta Kira and Ana Soulfull (see Figure 7.5), the pair wear nearly identical outfits, sitting with their heads slightly tilted and forearms outstretched. While the similarity in their styling and poses suggests their likeness, it also amplifies their differences: the viewer's attention is drawn to the exaggerated angle of Meta Kira's eyes, and the dewy glow of Soulfull's face that Meta Kira's skin lacks. Upon encountering staged liminality, we are encouraged to adopt what sociologists Christine Lavrence and Carolina Cambre (2020) call the "digital-forensic gaze", describing the "intensification of looking practices" (p. 2) to which images are subjected online. Lavrence and Cambre point to the ubiquity of beauty filters and photo-editing practices, which have "train[ed] the eye to look more critically at the images of the self and others, asking what has been or might potentially be 'fixed' or 'edited'", as reasons for this shift (p. 11). Staged liminality similarly invites us to "decipher the authenticity and artifice at play in the image" (Lavrence & Cambre, 2020, p. 2), but does so by defamiliarising our benchmarks for the virtual and the actual. In the case of selfies, for example, where there is often "an *a priori* assumption that filtering has been applied" (Lavrence & Cambre, 2020, p. 2, original emphasis), actual referents illuminate that virtual influencers exceed the degree of digital manipulation to which we have become accustomed. Albegova made this point in our interview, noting the arresting effect of the image when virtuality is unequally distributed. "Everyone is already used to Photoshop and, like, digital art," she explained, so when the character is photographed alone, "they think it's just a picture. But when [there's also] a real person, they start to think, 'What is this? What is happening?'"

With its defamiliarising effect, staged liminality revives visual interest in well-worn visual templates by inviting a more active mode of perception towards images that might otherwise go unnoticed. It subverts audience expectations, and calls upon the viewer as an active participant in deciphering and determining the boundary between virtuality and actuality (cf. Yoshida, 2004/2016). In a presentation at the 2021 Mocap Content Creators Conference, Joerg Zuber references this effect when describing how he poses his character Noonouri next to actual people to "grab the attention" (Xsens Movella, 2021, 12:00) of other social media users:

[When you] scroll through your feeds—like on Instagram, for example—you scroll, you scroll, and you see so many beautiful pictures, perfect grids, perfect tonalities and everything. And then you see, all of a sudden, [a] picture like this, where you see, like, wow... You would stop immediately. (Xsens Movella, 2021, 11:18)

Staged liminality can thus be understood as one way that virtual influencers achieve the “strong glance value” (Travers, as cited in Fang, 2020, para. 2) touted by industry stakeholders as one of their most valuable qualities. Although a glance is “a quick, fleeting, and indiscriminate type of seeing” (Zulli, 2018, p. 138), in the “attention economy” (Fairchild, 2007; Goldhaber, 1997) of social media, it carries significant weight. For influencers, whose value as commercial partners is often equated to the “number of glances they can offer to a particular company” (Zulli, 2018, p. 145), the ability to attract glances is “a necessary precursor to social and economic capital” (Zulli, 2018, p. 142). By foregrounding staged liminality, virtual influencers distinguish their content in the feeds of other social media users, inviting second, lingering glances that carry commercial value in social media’s attention economy (see Chapter 9).

7.3 Ontological Labour

In this final section, I return to analysing virtual influencer selfies, exploring what happens when we recognise them as sites of staged liminality that depict interactions between virtuality and actuality. I focus my discussion on the (im)mobility of the characters’ poses, the reactions of their actual interlocutors, and their handling of actual objects. I present these as examples of the *ontological labour* performed by virtual influencers. This term has elsewhere been used when describing sociologist Bruno Latour’s interventions in the sociology of scientific knowledge, which marked “a shift from the social determinants of scientific knowledge” (Seguin, 2000, p. 504) to the “ontological labour performed by science”, referring specifically to “the laboratory production of new nonhumans” (Seguin & Lord, 2023, p. 16). Based on the analysis that follows, I define ontological labour as the work of fostering an impression of agency, autonomy, and sentience for inanimate objects and nonhuman entities. Ontological labour encourages us to perceive virtual influencers as what sociologist of science and technology Sherry Turkle calls “relational artifacts”. Developed in relation to social robots (e.g. Turkle et al., 2006) and chatbots (e.g. Turkle, 2007), relational artefacts describe technologies that “present themselves as having ‘states of mind’” (Turkle et al., 2006, p. 348), and which “display behaviours that make people feel as though they are dealing with sentient creatures” (Turkle, 2007, p. 64). Turkle’s notion of relational artifacts is useful for highlighting how people ascribe qualities to technology exceeding what they in fact possess, “led by the human habit of making assumptions based on perceptions of behaviour” (Turkle, 2007, p. 64). In the case of virtual influencers, ontological labour encourages the perception that the characters transcend their capabilities as virtual puppets (see Chapter 4), and suggests their ability to interact with and affect the actual world.

7.3.1 Poses

Virtual influencers' poses can perform ontological labour by conveying a sense of movement, suggesting that the characters exist beyond the moment in which they are photographed. As “product[s] of kinetic bodily movement” (Frosh, 2015, p. 1623), selfies are exemplary sites for such poses. Frosh (2015) points out that:

taking selfies is not natural to the body: It is an acquired skill and requires practice, the attainment of limbic and manual dexterity [...] and the calibration of the body to technical affordances and desirable representational outcomes. (p. 1614)

A quintessential selfie pose features in an Instagram post by Singaporean virtual influencer Rae (see Figure 7.7). In the image, Rae sits with local artist, illustrator, and lifestyle influencer Tiffany Lovage (and her dog, Riot Rose) at an outdoor table at Kult Yard, a popular bar and music venue in Singapore. The image is a “selfie scene” (Ruchatz, 2018), showing Rae as she takes a selfie of the group. With her torso rotated towards Lovage, Rae holds an iPhone aloft in her left hand. Her fingers curl around the edges of the smartphone, with the exception of her index finger, which is fully extended, as though keeping the angled phone steady. Rae’s left eye is closed in a wink and her head is slightly tilted, purple hair dangling over her other shoulder. Both she and Lovage smile for the photo, gazing at the smartphone in anticipation. The scene foregrounds the “embodied constellation” (Frosh,

Figure 7.7: Singaporean virtual influencer Rae (right) poses for a selfie with local artist and illustrator Tiffany Lovage (left) and her dog, Riot Rose, at Kult Yard bar in Chinatown. Source: Instagram (RAE 蕊 [@here.is.rae], 2021), screengrab by author on 12 September 2023.

2015, p. 1612) of limbs, faces, and technology involved in selfie production, giving “aesthetic, visible form to that movement” (Frosh, 2015, p. 1623). Even Rae’s “three-quarter face” carries an implied sense of movement: somewhere between full-frontal and profile, “the partial averting of the face grants it the status of something in motion, a rudder steering a set of actions” (Coates, 2012, p. 33).

The example illustrates how virtual influencers can be posed to convey what film and visual culture scholar Marc Steinberg (2012) calls “dynamic immobility” (p. 6), a term he uses to describe how *anime*’s hand-drawn lines suggest movement for animated characters or objects even when they are depicted in static form. The importance of dynamically immobile poses for virtual influencers was raised in my interview with Yunna Albegova, creator of virtual influencer Meta Kira. When describing how she creates new images for Meta Kira, Albegova explained:

My idea for a photo is to be as realistic as possible. [...] When I’m scrolling Instagram, I always save good poses. But I’ve noticed that if you’re a human, your good poses are when you look like a doll; when you’re standing still; when you’re, like, posing [...] But for Kira, it’s [the] opposite. She has to be in a movement. She has to show the realness. Because if she stands like a model, she’s already a doll, so it’s too artificial.

Reading Albegova’s reflection alongside earlier photographic accounts accentuates how the poses of virtual influencers differ from those of their human counterparts. In 1983, American visual theorist Kaja Silverman wrote, “Once I feel myself observed by the lens, everything changes: I constitute myself in the process of ‘posing’, I instantaneously transform myself in advance into an image” (as cited in Warfield, 2016, p. 5). Likewise, in 1985, American postmodern art critic Craig Owens described the act of posing for a photograph as “‘freezing’, as if anticipating the still I am about to become, [and] mimicking its opacity, its still-ness” (as cited in Jerslev & Mortensen, 2016, p. 255). Unlike the “freezing” of human subjects anticipating or posing for a photograph to “show the realness” (in Albegova’s words), the poses of virtual influencers are often deliberately chosen to convey a sense of movement, transforming them into what Steinberg (2012) describes as “dynamically immobile character image[s]” (p. 6). For Steinberg, this “sense of dynamism” (p. 33) is what allows characters to “generate movement across media forms” (p. 6); for virtual influencers, it also performs ontological labour by suggesting the characters exist beyond the moment in which they are pictured. In Figure 7.7, Rae’s selfie-pose suggests the image is part of a longer sequence: the viewer is invited to imagine the moments after the photograph is captured, when Rae drops her arm and leans closer to Lovage to scroll through her camera roll, deliberating over which photograph to post online.

7.3.2 Reactions

The reactions of virtual influencers' companions also perform ontological labour by suggesting the character's ability to affect their surroundings, including the actual people that populate it. Marketing scholars Jenna Drenten and Gillian Brooks (2020) identify posing with actual people as one way that virtual influencers "get a halo effect of realness" (p. 3). A concept originating in social psychology, the "halo effect" was initially used to describe the ways that people make inferences about others based on preconceptions of certain traits or characteristics (see Nisbett & Wilson, 1977). The term has since been applied in marketing (e.g. Leuthesser et al., 1995) and influencer scholarship (see Abidin, 2016a; Abidin & Thompson, 2012) to explain the variety of mental and affective shortcuts that colour our responses to new information (see Chapter 9). When Drenten and Brooks suggest virtual influencers "gain a halo effect of realness" by posing with actual people (p. 3), they allude to the ontological legitimacy the actual interlocutor lends to our perception of the character. This "halo effect of realness" (Drenten & Brooks, 2020, p. 3) is heightened when the interlocutor is shown reacting to the character: when their arm wraps around the character's shoulders; when their look or expressions are directed towards the character; or when they angle a camera to also capture the character's face in a selfie (see Figure 7.8). In these instances, the "halo effect of realness" (Drenten & Brooks, 2020, p. 3) is activated because the interlocutor is imagining a fictional character that is not physically present, and conveying their faith in that character to the audience.

Appearing in an image with a virtual influencer requires what acting theorists call "scenic faith", a term attributed to renowned Russian theatre practitioner Konstantin Stanislavski (see Vakhtangov, 1971). In naturalistic theatre, scenic faith describes the necessity for actors to "believe in everything that is going on around him, and most of all in what he himself is doing", in order to convey the truth of the scene to the audience (Stanislavsky, 1926/2008, p. 260). The concept has been used to describe the imagination and conviction required of actors in film productions laden with VFX (visual effects; see Jacobs et al., 2017). Working with green screens and limited on-set stimuli, these actors must interact with environments and characters that are added in post-production. This acting approach parallels Lovage's role in Rae's post. In Figure 7.7, it is likely that Lovage is posing with a body-double standing for Rae; based on my observations, a composite model (a human body-double combined with a computer-generated face; see Chapter 6) seems to have been used for most of Rae's Instagram content. In other cases (such as Ana Soulful and Meta Kira's photo in Figure 7.5), the human companion must pose for the photograph alone, "leaving space", as Albegova put it in our interview, for the character to be digitally added in post-production (see section 7.1.1). In each case, scenic faith is required to imagine and

convincingly respond to a fictional character that is added only after the photograph has been taken (see Chapter 6).

To this end, while group selfies can be understood to have their own kind of halo effect, where social capital is extended from companions with higher social status (see section 7.1.2), for virtual influencers, this genre of image has an additional effect. When Lovage grins in Figure 7.7—her mouth open as though mid-sentence, or even mid-laugh—her joyous reaction adds legitimacy to Rae’s presence in the scene, and suggests Rae’s ability to affect the actual world.

7.3.3 Touch

Finally, ontological labour is performed when virtual influencers are shown touching actual objects, which suggests they are capable of physically interacting with the actual world. Most often, these actual objects are smartphones (see Figure 7.2 and Figure 7.7), or food and drink (see Figure 7.4), but virtual influencers are brought into contact with a wide range of objects. This is illustrated in a selfie of Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI with Grace Chow (周扬青), a prominent Chinese *wanghong* (网红, internet celebrity) and entrepreneur (see Figure 7.8). In the image, the pair smile softly at the camera, standing against a teal background and framed with green fronds. In this example, it appears that Chow is taking the selfie: her right arm extends out of the photo (Frosh, 2015). While Chow operates the camera, AYAYI stands behind her, her arms folded across her middle. AYAYI’s hand holds a silvery tube encased in a translucent shell, and a collection of flat pink packages fan out from the elbow of her oversized hoodie. AYAYI’s grip on these objects embeds her in the scene, not just as a composited, computer-generated image, but as an entity capable of interacting with her actual surroundings.

In this example, we also see how touch is used to ready virtual influencers for commercialisation (see Chapter 9). Just visible on one of the pink packages is a line of bold text reading “CODEMINT”, revealing that the items AYAYI holds belong to Chow’s personal cosmetics brand. The image can therefore be read not only as a group selfie, but also as a “merchandise selfie” (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9), with CODEMINT cosmetics subtly incorporated via “product placement” (Abidin, 2016a, p. 4). This highlights how touch can be used to legitimise virtual influencers as brand partners, especially when the objects they touch are made by actual brands. Aspiring human influencers will often create “fake sponsored content” without any communication or compensation from brands (Lorenz, 2018b, n.p.). For these individuals, creating unsolicited “merchandise selfies” (de Seta & Proksell, 2015, p. 9) is a way to accumulate a portfolio that attests to their ability to create

Figure 7.8: Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI (right) poses for a selfie with Grace Chow (left), a prominent Chinese *wanghong* with over 11 million followers on Weibo. Source: Weibo (AYAYI, 2021), screengrab by author on 4 August 2023.

sponsored content, and a potential path to eliciting paid opportunities with brands in future (Lorenz, 2018b). Selfies that show virtual influencers interacting with branded products likewise suggest the characters' potential for commercial partnerships, and their desirability as brand partners. As the commercial activities of virtual influencers are discussed at length in Chapter 9, I do not stress this point here, but it is useful to consider how the ontological labour of virtual influencers' interactions with actual objects are utilised with commercial intent.

Although I have argued that interacting with actual objects is a way of affirming that virtual influencers are capable of the commercial practices undertaken by human influencers, in Chapter 9, I highlight how touch is also used to convey the characters' immateriality. Specifically, I highlight how large commercial campaigns often depict virtual influencers as

unable to touch actual objects, either turning their flesh translucent upon contact, or by the energy of their skin causing objects to levitate just out of reach. While seemingly contradictory, we can understand the two approaches to touch as part of a linear progression: holding actual objects in day-to-day selfies helps to affirm the viability of virtual influencers as brand partners; once virtual influencers successfully secure commercial opportunities, they draw on a popular iconography to articulate their virtuality to a wider audience.

In the discussion of contemporary virtual beings in Chapter 3, I suggested conceptualising virtual influencers as “virtual puppets”, given their reliance on their producers for all facets of their social media presence. Looking more closely at the poses, reactions, and moments of touch foregrounded in virtual influencers’ selfies—and present throughout the characters’ social media feeds—reveals how the producers suggest the characters exceed this classification. Through their interactions with actual people, places, and objects, virtual influencers encourage the perception that they are capable of interacting with and affecting the actual world. By performing this ontological labour, they position themselves as “relational artifacts” (Turkle, 2007) who exist beyond the confines of a static image, and lead lives beyond the posts uploaded to their social media feeds. Later in the thesis, I return to examining how the overestimation of virtual influencers’ sentience and agency is utilised in their advertising campaigns (see Chapter 9), and minimises the behind-the-scenes labour required to create them (see Chapter 10).

7.4 Summary

In this chapter, I examined how virtual influencers emulate the visual templates favoured by human influencers, focusing on selfies. I argued that virtual influencers favour certain selfie subgenres not only for the social and cultural capital they offer, but also because they bring the characters into closer contact with actual people, places, and objects. I offered the term *staged liminality* to describe depictions of virtual influencers interacting with the actual world, a prominent feature in the characters’ social media feeds. I detailed how some producers see staged liminality as a way for virtual influencers to gain visibility in oversaturated social media environments, defamiliarising well-worn social media templates to prompt viewers to take a second glance.

Next, I highlighted the work done by staged liminality to suggest virtual influencers exist beyond the images in which they are featured. I used the term *ontological labour* to describe the work of suggesting inanimate objects are actually sentient beings. I considered three ways ontological labour is performed by virtual influencers’ selfies: in the potential for

movement invested in their bodily poses; in the faith conveyed by the reactions of their interlocutors; and in the characters' physical interactions with actual objects. Together, these three ways encourage the perception that virtual influencers can interact with and affect the actual world. In the next chapter, I analyse how virtual influencers are shaped by the actual world: its histories, customs, and cultures.

Framing Identity

8.1 Introduction

As I progressed in my fieldwork, the geography of virtual influencers became a point of increased salience. I observed that geographic markers were often displayed in characters' profiles on platforms like Instagram and TikTok, with text and flag emojis signalling national affiliations. Press headlines regularly celebrated the characters as a country's "first" virtual influencer, using their countries of origins as the key "hook" for press attention: an article in *Rolling Stone India* magazine bore the headline, "Rozy, Korea's First Virtual Influencer Isn't Human but Humane" (Dutta, 2022); Liam Nikuro was repeatedly hailed as Japan's "First Male Virtual Influencer" (e.g., 'Japan Gets Its First Male Virtual Influencer', 2019; Strusiewicz, 2019; Zaczekiewicz, 2019); Kyra was labelled "India's First Virtual Influencer" (Mathur, 2021); and Ailynn was titled the "First Made-in-Thailand Virtual Influencer" (Online Reporters, 2021). On professional social networking sites like LinkedIn, I saw producers adopting these same geographic epithets when identifying themselves as the characters' creators. It became increasingly apparent that public and professional perceptions and understandings of virtual influencers were framed by ideas of the national.

In this chapter, I explore how and why virtual influencers are attached to specific geographic contexts. Shifting from the layer of the *stage* analysed in Chapter 6, in this chapter, I focus on the *frame* of virtual influencers' posts, and the social media environments which mediate our encounters with them. I analyse how virtual influencers use different platform features or "affordances" (Bucher & Helmond, 2018) to add context, meaning, and nuance to the visual content they post, "enfram[ing]" (Spyer & Steedly, 2013) it with markers of cultural identity. Beginning with the geographical epithets which populate press and promotional rhetoric about virtual influencers, I analyse how social media affordances are used to emplace the characters in geographic contexts, and participate in cultural communities, traditions, and norms from the actual world.

8.1.1 Enframement

In this chapter, I analyse the layer of the *frame*, focusing on the (digital) contexts in which virtual influencers' social media content is encountered. To achieve this, I draw on the concept of "enframement", proposed by anthropologists Patricia Spyer and Mary Margaret Steedly (2013) to explore how images are presented and packaged to "travel" across cultural, social, and media contexts. Writing in a visual studies context, Spyer and Steedly

deploy enframement to describe the “various ways the image is foregrounded or separated from its general environmental surround in order to be apprehended *as an image*” (p. 19, original emphasis). Enframement prompts consideration of the borders that enclose and demarcate an image, as well as adjacent or surrounding information that influences our interpretation of the image. In film photography, examples of enframement include date stamps, wooden frames, and written placards; for digital images, enframement might take the form of a browser window, a widget, or a caption (Spyer & Steedly, 2013). The visual retains its communicative power, but enframement affects its interpretation, or the experience of its encounter.

In the context of social media, studying enframement requires attention to affordances, a term for the range of actions arising from the intersection of platform design and user interaction (Bucher & Helmond, 2018). As social media scholars Tama Leaver, Tim Highfield, and Crystal Abidin (2020) suggest in their analysis of Instagram, “the visual alone offers some – but not all – detail for interpreting meaning” on social media (p. 45). Instead, “surrounding contextual information, be it captions, hashtags, profile information, comments or other annotations” each play an important role in how the visual is understood (p. 44). I focus the analysis in this chapter on what social media scholars Taina Bucher and Anne Helmond (2018) describe as “low-level affordances” (p. 239): the “more concrete feature-oriented” features of social media platforms which are “typically located in the materiality of the medium, in specific features, buttons, screens and platforms” (pp. 239-240). Specifically, in section 8.2, I consider text-based affordances (focusing on captions), and in section 8.3, I look at tagging affordances (such as hashtags, audio tags, and geotags). By analysing the ways these low-level affordances enframe virtual influencers’ visual social media content, I identify two “high-level affordances”—that is, “dynamics and conditions enabled by technical devices, platforms, and media” (Bucher & Helmond, 2018, p. 239)—utilised by virtual influencers in the presentation of their content in online environments: firstly, *anchoring* how their content is interpreted, and secondly, *networking* their content with online communities and cultural practices.

Enframement has proven a useful analytic tool for researching content on visual social media platforms. In influencer research, media scholars Emma Baulch and Alila Pramiyanti (2018) use it in their study of *hijaber* influencers in Indonesia, showing how *hijabers* represent their own agency within “a broader social world [by] featuring performances of bodily and intellectual strength” (p. 4). Although these authors focus heavily on the visual composition of the *hijabers*’ Instagram posts (akin to the analysis of *staging* in Chapter 7), they also highlight how captions and hashtags position the images as articulations of

Muslimah (Muslim women) independence, empowerment, and community. These findings are echoed in a study of young women's Instagram use in post-Arab Spring Egypt and Tunisia, where captions and hashtags similarly accentuated "their choice to be distinctive and defiant" through visual self-representations (Bardhan, 2022, p. 689). As an analytic tool, enframement recognises the role and influence of the platforms involved in the presentation and circulation of visual content. In this chapter, I foreground enframement by exploring how virtual influencers use platform affordances to articulate cultural identities, and align themselves with cultural communities.

8.1.2 Cultural Commodification

This chapter builds on critical technology scholar Esperanza Miyake's (2022) suggestion that virtual influencers function as "cultural commodit[ies]" (p. 3). Miyake's analysis focuses on virtual influencer Imma, created by Aww, Inc. (née Modelling Café), a virtual influencer agency based in Tokyo. Miyake highlights that Aww carefully avoid calling Imma "Japanese", instead describing her as a "virtual girl from Tokyo" who is "interested in Japanese culture, film, and art" (p. 6). Even so, in English-language commentary about "her collaborations with well-known, international 'Western' corporations like Porsche and Calvin Klein" (p. 3), Imma is regularly described as a "*Japanese* virtual influencer" (emphasis added; e.g. Q. Wang, 2020a). This cultural epithet is problematised by Miyake, who asks, "How can a virtual influencer be Japanese?" (p. 2). Miyake further argues that Imma does not reflect what it is to live as a Japanese person, but instead represents non-native ideas about Japan, as evidenced by the "countless images [...] containing stereotypically Japanese locations and items (Japanese tea, shrines, local street food)" that populate Imma's social media profiles (p. 6). In fact, Imma's appearance was intentionally designed to tap into imaginaries of Japanese culture. In a press interview with *Bloomberg*, Yumi An Anzai (previously a director at Aww, and responsible for Imma's international activities) recounts, "When we created her look, we wanted to think like how overseas [people] think of Japan" (as cited in Ong, 2020, para. 13). Anzai's quote supports Miyake's (2022) argument that Imma is a product of "Japan's own self-commodification of Japanese virtuality aimed for global consumption" (p. 3).

Miyake's conceptualisation of virtual influencers as cultural commodities is central to this chapter, which interrogates how and why virtual influencers' producers ascribe cultural identities to non-human entities. Although the term "cultural identity" is critiqued by some scholars as a "floating signifier" (Dervin, 2012, p. 181), I use it to refer to a sense of self based on lived experiences, developed through social interactions, and strengthened through encounters with the unfamiliar (Iwabuchi, 2010; Y. Y. Kim, 2007). More specifically, I

understand cultural identities as a sense of group belonging predicated on shared values, beliefs, attitudes, and customs, which are always “multiple, intersecting, and simultaneously personal and social” (Y.-W. Chen & Lin, 2016, p. 2). While definitions of cultural identity sometimes overlap with national identity (see Anderson, 1983/2016), I adopt the former to recognise the heterogeneity of identity within national borders, especially along intersectional lines of ethnicity, religion, class, gender, and sexuality (Iwabuchi, 2010). For virtual influencers, the notion of cultural identity presents a compelling paradox: as fictional characters, virtual influencers are unable to experience or accumulate the social encounters, rituals, and knowledge that would give shape to a human influencer’s cultural identity. And yet, virtual influencers often accentuate a cultural identity, engaging with cultural customs, histories, and communities from the actual world.

Anime studies scholar Stevie Suan’s (2021b) theorisation of anime as performative offers a useful model for conceptualising the process by which virtual influencers establish their cultural identities. Acknowledging the instability of *anime* as a globalised media form, definitionally contested both within and beyond Japan, Suan draws on theories of performativity to conceptualise *anime* as “constituted by a series of repeated acts [...] citing conventionalized models in each iteration to sustain a recognizable identity as a category of media” (p. 74). Adapting this logic for this chapter usefully foregrounds virtual influencers’ repetitive, citational engagement with established cultural codes, norms, and practices “to sustain a recognizable”, in this case, cultural “identity” (p. 74). To account for the motivations behind such efforts, I draw on sociologist and media scholar Koichi Iwabuchi’s (2002) concept of “cultural odors”, and anthropologist of digital cultures Crystal Abidin’s notion of cultural “staining” (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 8), which each share an interest in the commodification of cultural identity.

In his influential book *Recentering Globalisation*, Iwabuchi (2002) studies the rise of Japan’s cultural power since the late 1980s, focusing on the “transnational” (pp. 16-17) flows of Japanese popular culture exports across East and Southeast Asia. Against the backdrop of globalisation, Iwabuchi argues, all cultural products have a “cultural imprint” or “cultural association with the country of [their] invention” (p. 27); acceptance of these cultural products in transnational markets relates to the “culture odor” that results from this association (p. 28). Cultural odours appear when the “cultural features of a country of origin and images or ideas of its national, in most case stereotyped, way of life are associated *positively* with a particular product in the consumption process” (p. 78, original emphasis). Subverting this idea, Iwabuchi suggests that the immense transnational popularity of Japanese cultural products like *anime*, *manga*, video games, toys, and technology can be

attributed to their *mukokuseki* (無国籍) or “culturally odorless” quality, in which the traces of their Japanese production are erased or diluted (p. 28). In a later article, Iwabuchi (2004) clarifies that “[c]onsumers and audiences of Japanese animations and games may be aware of the Japanese origin of these commodities, but they perceive little ‘Japanese bodily odour’” (p. 27). For Iwabuchi, it is precisely this lack of cultural odour that gives Japan’s cultural products transnational purchase, making it easier for them to travel across cultural contexts.

Media studies scholar Mehita Iqani (2019) observes a similar logic among influencers in South Africa, who have a tendency to “decontextualise” (Albers & James, 1988, p. 153) posts that promote luxury goods from recognisable landmarks and locations. By intentionally staging a background of placelessness and minimising the distinctiveness of their cultural identities, the South African influencers studied by Iqani seek to affirm their “equal footing” (Iqani, 2019, p. 241) in the global influencer ecology; in other words, these South African influencers used *mukokuseki* to appeal to luxury brands, proving themselves capable of emulating the same sleek commercial aesthetics as influencers in other parts of the world.

However, other scholars suggests that such odourlessness is an exception for individuals seeking online popularity. Building on Iwabuchi’s work (see Abidin & Brown, 2018), Abidin (2018a) emphasises the importance of cultural odours in the context of internet celebrity. She identifies overt cultural distinction, which she labels “exoticism” (p. 23), as one of the most valuable qualities in the online “attention economy” (Fairchild, 2007; Goldhaber, 1997). For Abidin (2018a), exoticism arises “whenever there is a gap in what is considered culturally normal or mainstream between the performer’s and the audience’s backgrounds and can occur within inter- and intracultural settings depending on the nuance of difference” (p. 23; see also J. Lee & Abidin, 2022). To benefit from “exotic” cultural associations, some influencers will purposefully “stain” themselves with a distinctive cultural identity (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 8). Abidin’s work underscores that in the visual social media context, cultural identity is subsumed by the logics of self-branding (see Chapter 4), becoming a way of making oneself distinctive, and accumulating visibility and attention.

The notion of distinction offers a compelling explanation for virtual influencers’ cultural identities. From 2018 to 2022, the number of virtual influencers multiplied. Annual reports published by social media measurement platform HypeAuditor expanded their sample from 30 virtual influencers in 2019 to 150 characters in 2022—a 400% increase over four years—reflecting the rising number of characters on Instagram, especially following the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic (Baklanov, 2019, 2022). My fieldwork, which looked beyond Instagram and popularity-based metrics (see Chapter 5), would suggest HypeAuditor’s numbers underrepresent the phenomenon’s true scope, involving many more virtual influencers than

included in their sample. The rapidly growing number of virtual influencers presented a new challenge, making it more difficult for the characters to attain distinction within an increasingly saturated niche. As the epithets in the opening of this chapter attest, when it was no longer enough to be distinguished as “virtual”, the characters were increasingly “stain[ed]” (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 8) with cultural identities.

For some virtual influencers, distinctive cultural identities were a way to appeal to local audiences. According to press interviews with her producers (e.g. Q. Wang, 2020b), Chinese virtual influencer Ling (翎) was created to reinvigorate young Chinese social media users’ interest in *guofeng* (国风), or “Chinese national style” (see Ng & Li, 2023). Communication scholars Lijun Luo and Wonkyung Kim (2024) suggest that Ling “holds a unique position among [virtual influencers because] she actively communicates her Chinese national identity and promotes traditional Chinese culture” (p. 326). Returning to Abidin’s (2018a) concept of “exoticism” (p. 23), although Ling shares the Chinese cultural background of her intended audience, it is her “traditional cultural traits” that drive her appeal among young Chinese social media users (Yuan, 2025, p. 324). On Weibo (微博), Ling poses in photos wearing traditional Chinese dress, such as *Hanfu* (汉服) and *Qipao* (旗袍); celebrates traditional Chinese holidays and festivals; and regularly posts about her love of Peking Opera, and her skill at Chinese calligraphy (L. Luo & Kim, 2024; Yuan, 2025). Communication scholar Jingyan Elaine Yuan (2025) connects the appeal of Ling’s identity to *guochao* (国潮), “a cultural sentiment trending in recent years among Chinese youth, whose renewed interest in traditional Chinese culture sparked strong demand for domestic products” (p. 324). For Ling, foregrounding Chinese heritage proved a successful strategy for attracting local audiences and brand partners: as of January 2022, Ling had accumulated almost 600,000 followers on Weibo, and a portfolio of partnerships with several major Chinese brands, including domestic haircare brand Centaine (see Zeng et al., 2023), and nationwide tea chain Nayuki (see Chapter 9).

Other virtual influencers have clearer aspirations for transnational success. For example, in an interview “with” the character published in *FEMALE* magazine, Singaporean virtual influencer Rae explains her five-year ambition to become “one of the top virtual influencers in the Asia-Pacific and work with global brands and partners for international campaigns” (as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 13). Echoing this sentiment, in an interview with *The Chosun Ilbo*, a daily South Korean newspaper, CEO of Sidus Studio X Baek Seung-yeop describes his hopes for virtual influencer Rozy: “I hope Rozy will succeed as a global virtual influencer,

*make a lot of money, and create a lot of jobs*⁵ (as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 12). Both quotes tie the desire for transnational popularity to the commercial opportunities this could unlock, affording chances to partner with “global brands” (Rae, as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 13), and in theory, “*make a lot of money*” (Baek, as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 12). When virtual influencers are taken out of their own geographic contexts, their cultural identities become advantageous, imbuing the products or services they promote with a recognisable—and desirable—“cultural odour” (Iwabuchi, 2002). This is illustrated by the use of Rozy as a cultural ambassador for the Korea Tourism Organisation on Weibo (see Figure 8.1), and in Imma’s partnership with ice-cream brand Magnum China (see Figure 8.2), where she was

Figure 8.1: Korean virtual influencer Rozy offers food-related Korea travel tips on the Korea Tourism Organisation’s official Weibo profile. Source: Weibo (韩国旅游发展局微博, 2021). Screenshot by author on 17 June 2025.

⁵ Italicised text machine-translated using Google Translate. Original text: “로지가 세계적인 버추얼 인플루언서로 성공해 돈도 많이 벌어들이고 일자리도 많이 만들어내길 바라기로 했다” (Baek, as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 12).

Figure 8.2: The cultural identity of Japanese virtual influencer is leveraged in her partnership with Magnum China, promoting two flavours associated with Japan. Top: Matcha flavour; source: PR Times Japan (株式会社 Aww, 2020), screengrab by author on 18 December 2023. Bottom: Cherry blossom flavour; source: Aww Tokyo (Aww Inc., 2021), screengrab by author on 11 June 2025.

enlisted to promote two limited-edition flavours with strong associations to Japan: *matcha* (抹茶, green tea powder), and cherry blossom (*sakura*, 桜). In both cases, the characters' recognisable cultural identities are used to augment the “cultural odors” (Iwabuchi, 2002) attached to the messages and products they promote, “carry[ing] aesthetic and exotic meaning” (Miyake, 2022, p. 8) intended to heighten the desirability of travelling to Korea and new flavours of ice-cream. Drawing on theories of cultural commodification, I argue that, like human influencers, virtual influencers utilise cultural identities as a self-branding strategy, a way of claiming distinction in an increasingly overpopulated niche. These cultural identities can be used both to engage the interest and attention of local audiences, while also augmenting their appeal for commercial opportunities in transnational contexts (see Chapter 9).

8.1.3 Shared Cultures

Although it is easy to presume that virtual influencers' cultural identities are shared with their producers, this is not always the case. Even if the characters and producers "live" in the same country, they do not necessarily share every facet of their identity, especially in regards to age, gender, and ethnicity. After all, as fictional characters, virtual influencers are products of their producers' creativity, not necessarily personal extensions or reflections. Assumptions of shared cultural identities are especially challenged when a character is managed by an agency (see Chapter 10), with a multi-person team contributing their skills and expertise to the character's production. A similar distribution of labour is observed by *anime* studies scholar Stevie Suan (2020). Although perceived as a uniquely Japanese cultural product, the different layers that comprise *anime*'s "multiplanar image" (LaMarre, 2009; see Chapter 6) are regularly produced by creative teams located in different countries. Suan explains:

one anime's animation-sequence may have been story-boarded in Japan, the background painted in Vietnam, key-animation done in South Korea and Japan, character in-betweens in China, then colored in the Philippines, and edited in Japan, merging the multiple locales of each part's production into the single images that make up the sequence. (p. 34)

Just as Suan highlights that the transnational distribution of *anime* labour complexifies reading *anime* purely as a reflection of Japan, we should be hesitant to equivocate the cultural identities of virtual influencers with those of their producers. This is not only because the individual identity of the creators is not always known (see Chapter 10), but also because the significant amount of labour and variety of skills involved in creating and managing a virtual influencer makes it increasingly unlikely that this relationship is one-to-one. For this chapter, I focus on how virtual influencers express cultural identities, and how their creators ascribe a cultural past and present to virtual bodies without lived or social experience. My interest is not in evaluating the accuracy of these representations, but on how social media affordances are utilised to "stain" virtual influencers with a particular cultural identity (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 8).

Deliberately "staining" oneself with a cultural identity for attention sits within an often-problematic history of cultural and racial identity in digital contexts. Writing of early online forums, digital media and cultural studies scholar Lisa Nakamura (2002) coined the term "cybertypes" to describe how racial identities are reduced to offensive stereotypes when performed online by individuals lacking embodied experience. Not long thereafter, global

studies scholar Theresa M. Senft (2008) offered the term “digital drag” to describe the act of “representing [oneself] in cyberspace as something other than their offline gender, sexuality, race, or ability” (p. 35). In the visual social media landscape, the highly fragmented “attention economy” (Fairchild, 2007; Goldhaber, 1997) has altered the conditions of expressing cultural identity. Given the limited length and depth of our encounters with online content, cultural identity must be visually distinctive, immediately recognisable, and easily interpreted, often increasing the reliance on stereotypes or “cybertypes” (Nakamura, 2002). Terms such as “blackfishing” (Jackson, 2017; see also Cherid, 2021; Stevens, 2021), “Asian fishing” (see Biggs, 2021; Harris, 2021), and “queerbaiting” (see J. Brennan, 2019; Mendez II, 2021) have emerged to describe the appropriation of Black American, (East) Asian, and queer cultures and aesthetics in the pursuit of cultural capital. In the era of visual social media, expressions of cultural identity are shaped by new economic incentives for online distinction, recognisability, and visibility. They are also shaped by the affordances of social media platforms, which encourage and constrain visual, textual, and networked articulations of identity (H. T. Dyer & Abidin, 2023; Stevens, 2021). In the sections that follow, I consider how text-based affordances such as captions are used to anchor virtual influencers’ visual social media content to cultural meaning; and how tag-based affordances such as hashtags, audio tags, and geotags embed virtual influencers in the online networks of established cultural communities.

8.2 Anchoring

In the highly visual landscape of social media, “[I]anguage, in the form of textual commentary, captions, or talk, frequently serves as an enframing device” (Spyer & Steedly, 2013, p. 19). Social media’s text-based affordances—including captions and graphic overlays such as stickers—add context that guides and enhances the viewer’s interpretation of visual content (Leaver et al., 2020). Spyer and Steedly (2013) conceptualise this guidance as an “anchoring” function, noting that a “textual explanation” is often necessary for an image “to function pictorially” (p. 20). This echoes literary theorist and semiotician Roland Barthes’ (1977/1982) notion of “anchorage”, which he uses to explain how captions help the viewer to “choose *the correct level of perception* [...] focus[ing] not simply [their] gaze but also [their] understanding” (p. 39, original emphasis). Below, I explore three ways virtual influencers use text captions to anchor their visual social media content to cultural knowledge, histories, and routines.

8.2.1 Partitioning

Firstly, virtual influencers draw upon linguistic resources like scripts, slang, and references to

make their posts legible to specific cultural audiences. This recalls the work of media linguist Jannis Androutsopoulos (2014), who argues that the “linguistic choices” made by multilingual social media users function either to “maximize” or “partition” their online audiences (p. 64). Maximising an audience involves styling content “in a way that makes it accessible to as many members of a user’s network as possible” (p. 66). Conversely, partitioning involves linguistic choices that make or leave the content inaccessible to some of its potential audience, often by limiting it “to those who are competent in the selected language(s)” (p. 67). For virtual influencers, partitioning is likewise enacted through linguistic choices that address certain audiences, often based on shared linguistic competency or cultural knowledge.

Producers will devise or adapt the languages used by their characters to reach specific audiences. For example, as Miyake (2022) observes, the captions on Imma’s Instagram posts are often written in both Japanese and English (p. 3; explored further below). However, surveying Imma’s cross-platform “digital estate” (Abidin, 2017a, p. 1) highlights her producers’ ambitions to reach an even larger transnational audience: Imma also has two Twitter accounts (one authored in Japanese, the other in English), as well as accounts on Chinese social media platforms Weibo, Xiaohongshu (小红书), and Douyin, where her content is exclusively authored in simplified Chinese. Both the platform selection and the linguistic diversity exercised across them clearly signals the intention of Imma’s producers to appeal to audiences geographically distant from Japan. Other virtual influencers I observed changed the language of their captions over time, suggesting new aspirations for the target audience of their content, or efforts to reflect the demographics of their existing followers. As one example, many of the early Instagram posts of Israeli virtual influencer Zoe Dvir have captions in Hebrew, which gradually transitioned to English as her account grew in popularity (Zoe Dvir [@zoedvir], n.d.). Such cases illustrate how partitioning is enacted by virtual influencers at the platform or account level, and how language belies the intended or imagined audience of their content.

Partitioning can also be used to address different audiences within individual posts. For example, an Instagram post by Imma about *Tsukimi* (月見), Japan’s annual moon-viewing ceremony, features a bilingual caption written in both English and Japanese (see Figure 8.3). Usually, this would suggest an intention to “maximize” (Androutsopoulos, 2014) the audience for the post. As Androutsopoulos (2014) explains, one “strategy for maximizing the audience is to replicate the propositional content [...] in more than one language [...] addressing as many segments of the networked audience in their ‘own’ language” as possible through the inclusion of “semantically equivalent clauses” (p. 67). However, closer

Figure 8.3: Virtual influencer Imma educates her English-speaking audience about the Japanese moon-viewing ceremony *Tsukimi*. Source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2021), screengrab by author on 13 November 2023.

inspection of Imma’s post caption reveals that the two clauses are not “semantically equivalent” (Androutsopoulos, 2014, p. 67): instead, they address non-native and native Japanese audiences in different ways. The opening English paragraph performs a role of cultural translation, explaining cultural nuance with which the audience is presumed to be unfamiliar. The caption contextualises the cultural significance of *Tsukimi* through references to other popular seasonal celebrations in Japan, such as “cherry blossom viewing” (*Hanami*, 花見), which may be more recognisable to non-native audiences, and details popular practices associated with *Tsukimi*, such as “look[ing] at the full moon 🌕 and eat[ing] moon shaped rice cakes” (imma [@imma.gram], 2021b, n.p.). The recurring use of the plural, first person pronoun “we” in this section (e.g. “In Japan we have holidays”) symbolically aligns Imma with the Japanese traditions and culture she explains (imma [@imma.gram], 2021b, n.p.). By contrast, the tone of the Japanese caption reads more like a diary entry, with a more personal and pensive tone:

今日はお月見っ 🌕 🌕 🌕 🌕
 日本には季節を感じる行事があって素敵だねっ
 ゆっくり時間の流れを感じるって大事。
 すべてに感謝〜

Today I watched the moon 🌕 🌕 🌕 🌕
It’s wonderful that Japan has events that allow
you to feel the seasons.
It’s important to feel the slow flow of time.
Thank you for everything~⁶

⁶ Italicised text machine translated with Google Translate.

In this (comparatively shorter) passage, Imma expresses her thanks for having a reason to pause and reflect on the changing of the seasons and the passage of time. The Japanese text omits any explanations of the cultural customs associated with *Tsukimi*, likely because the Japanese-speaking audience is expected to know them. Especially given social media platforms such as Instagram offer a native translation functionality, Imma’s bilingual captions are notable for intentionally crafting the information conveyed to her English- and Japanese-speaking audiences. In this example, multiple languages allow Imma to partition her address, simultaneously situating herself as a participant in the *Tsukimi* celebrations, while also translating the significance of these customs to a non-native audience.

A different partitioning effect can be seen in an Instagram post by Korean virtual influencer Sua, which addresses an audience that is expected to share her cultural background (see Figure 8.4). The image shows Sua in close-up, smiling at the camera from between several hanging decorations. A brief caption written in Hangul—“햅삐 메리 추석 🍂” (“*Happy Merry Chuseok* 🍂”⁷)—links the post to *Chuseok* (추석), South Korea’s annual autumn harvest celebration. However, for knowing audiences, this association is already established by the

Figure 8.4: Korean virtual influencer Sua holds two *songpyeon*, a ceremonial rice cake steamed in pine needles, typically made for Korea’s annual *Chuseok* festivities. Source: Instagram (나수아 SUA [@sua_to_z], 2021). Screenshot by author on 13 November 2023.

⁷ Italicised text machine translated with Google Translate.

cultural markers visible in the image: Sua holds up colourful rice cakes (송편, *songpyeon*) in each hand, and wears an ornamental headband (배씨댕기, *baesi daenggi*) associated with traditional *hanbok* (한복) dress, both commonly associated with *Chuseok* celebrations. Given the image contains several elements that communicate its cultural significance, Sua's caption does not add any new information; instead, it sends well-wishes to the same audience that is capable of interpreting the semiotic meaning in the image. Unlike Imma's *Tsukimi* post, the purpose of Sua's caption is not to translate Korean customs to an international audience, but instead to solely address a local audience, situating Sua as a fellow participant in the nationwide celebrations.

8.2.2 Orienting

Virtual influencers' captions can also perform an orienting function, highlighting what is relevant in an image and directing the viewer's gaze to where meaning is to be found. In his discussion of "anchorage", Barthes (1977/1982) proposes that captions assist with "identify[ing] purely and simply the elements of the scene and the scene itself [...] *direct*[ing] the reader through the signifieds of the image, causing him to avoid some and receive others" (pp. 39-40, original emphasis). Often, the captions posted by virtual influencers will direct the viewers' eye towards culturally significant elements in an image, accentuating their identity-making function.

For example, in Figure 8.5, Thai virtual influencer Katii stands outside an unnamed retail store. She leans casually against a concrete pillar decorated with faded, framed record covers, one hand in the pocket of her checkered dress. Written in Thai, the caption roughly translates to:

ถึงจะเกิดไม่ทัน แต่ก็รู้ว่าเพลงของ ไวพจน์
เพชรตะพิด เฮ้ย! ไวพจน์เพ็ดตะพิด เฮ้ย!
ไวพจน์ เพชรสุพรรณ
อมตะแค่ไหนจากร้านนี้ล่ะ

*Even though I wasn't born in time, I know that
song, "Waipót Pétdàpéut, hey!
Waipót Pétdàpát, hey! Waipót Pétsupán"
How immortal is this shop?*⁸

Echoing the discussion of partitioning (see section 8.2.1), Katii's caption contains several references legible to a Thai audience. It begins by referencing a longstanding meme among Thai internet users (e.g. โดนไลมาเล่นในนี้ [@donlaima], 2016) about mispronouncing the name of beloved Thai country singer Waiphot Phetsuphan (ไวพจน์ เพชรสุพรรณ). In 2018, the joke

⁸ Italicised text machine translated with Google Translate, with phonetic additions via Thai2English dictionary.

Figure 8.5: Thai virtual influencer Katii poses outside a record store in Bangkok, reminiscing about Thai music history. Source: Instagram (Katii [@katii.katie], 2022). Screenshot by author on 3 October 2023.

was adapted into a parody song (“ไผ่ตด เพชรตะพืด” or “*Waipót Pétápéut*”) for the Thai reality show *Cloning Singers* (เสียงซออรูบ; see Baichasong, 2018). Acknowledging that she was “born” after the song was released (her Instagram account launched in January 2022), Katii assures her followers that she is still familiar with the reference. The final sentence of the caption alludes to the reason for the reference, mentioning the immortality of “this” shop. With “this”, the viewer’s eye is directed to the concrete pillar Katii leans against, adorned with album covers of Thai folk musicians from the 1960s and 1970s. Although the location of the image is not mentioned in the caption, the distinctive cyan blue pillars assist in identifying it as Cathe Records (ห้างแผ่นเสียงคาเธ่ย์), a record store in Bangkok which opened in 1968 (บริษัทห้างแผ่นเสียงคาเธ่ย์ (1968) จำกัด, n.d.). In this case, the caption not only affirms Katii’s cultural competence, highlighting her knowledge of Thai popular culture, but it also orients the viewer’s gaze, directing attention to what is most important in the image. The viewer is encouraged to look beyond Katii’s direct stare, or the vibrant materials of her outfit, to the façade of the historic record store she stands before. By guiding the viewer to the image’s central locus of meaning, the caption helps to accentuate the post’s cultural significance, making Katii’s appreciation of Thai music history its primary message.

8.2.3 Elucidating

Captions can also be used to provide additional context or detail, altering how the image would otherwise be interpreted. Barthes (1977/1982) describes this as captions' "elucidating" effect, noting that "this elucidation is selective, [and is applied] only to certain of [the] signs" present in the image (p. 40). For virtual influencers, elucidation often adds cultural knowledge or significance.

An example can be seen in an Instagram post by Ghanaian virtual influencer Aba Wils (see Figure 8.6). In my interview with Aba Wils' creator, Reggie Goff, he described the inspiration for this post. Leaving his house one morning, he saw one of his neighbours doing laundry the "local way" outside. Goff explained that in his village:

On Saturdays, most of the ladies, they do the washing with their hands. I [thought], "Wow, this is so nice, I think I have an idea." [...] So I just went [over to her], and brought my tripod and camera.

Goff then approached his neighbour, and asked her permission to take a photo as she did her laundry. He then asked her to step out of the frame so he could take the photo again, leaving a blank space that Aba Wils could later fill (see Chapter 6). The resulting post shows Aba Wils sitting in a paved courtyard, bent over a bucket with soap suds covering her forearms (see Figure 8.6). Two other buckets sit nearby, with some crumpled clothing on the

Figure 8.6: Ghanaian virtual influencer Aba Wils posts about doing her laundry "the local way" on a Saturday morning. Source: Instagram (Aba Wils [@abawils], 2020), screengrab by author on 3 October 2023.

ground by her feet, and several rows of clean laundry hanging on a washing line behind her. The post caption characterises the visual depiction of Aba Wils doing laundry as part of a weekly routine, explaining, “My Saturday mornings are mostly for washing...” (Aba Wils [@abawils], 2020, n.p.). In this example, the caption elucidates the localised meaning of the image, even if it does not fully articulate the behind-the-scenes process that led Goff to create it. Audiences without this detailed context are still offered insight into why the post matters, characterising the scene as part of a regular domestic routine for this Ghanaian virtual influencer.

In this section, I presented examples of how text-based affordances like captions allow virtual influencers to “anchor” (Barthes, 1977/1982; Spyer & Steedly, 2013) their visual content, guiding how the visuals are interpreted by other social media users. Working in tandem with the visual, these textual anchors make the intended audience of the content legible, direct the audience’s gaze to what is most important, and offer explanations for why the visual is significant. As Barthes (1977/1982) wrote in relation to advertising images, text is used to “focus not simply [the audience’s] gaze but also [their] understanding” (p. 39). For virtual influencers, this anchoring function is often used to attach visual content to cultural knowledge, histories, and routines. Whether by using specific scripts, slang, or references to address users with shared or diverse cultural backgrounds; drawing attention to visual elements with cultural meaning; or offering additional context to explain the cultural significance of what is visually depicted, text-based affordances assist in “stain[ing]” (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 9) virtual influencers with cultural identities.

8.3 Networking

Virtual influencers also use social media’s tagging affordances, such as hashtags, audio tags, and geotags, to embed the characters’ posts within networked communities and practices. These affordances work differently to the text-based affordances aforementioned because tags are not only descriptive: they also play a “structural role” in the architecture of social media platforms, annotating visual content with information that makes it visible to other users and algorithms (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 74). Tags are “both organizational and social in nature” (Humphreys & Liao, 2011, p. 409). For instance, at a technical level, geotagging adds a label and geographic coordinates to “online materials and digital objects” (Humphreys & Liao, 2011, p. 409): when Japanese virtual influencer Liam Nikuro geotags his Instagram posts with “Tokyo, Japan”, and Thai virtual influencer Ai Ailynn geotags hers with “Bangkok Thailand”, they signal the location of the visual content, and connect their posts with all others tagged in the city. However, recalling the discussion in Chapter 7,

geotagging is also commonplace when virtual influencers visit popular or trendy places, such as cafes, restaurants, museums, and galleries. In such instances, geotags help to foreground the location of the image so the poster can benefit from the cultural capital associated with “being there” (Boy & Uitermark, 2017; Schwartz & Halegoua, 2015), thereby performing “both [an] organizational and social” function (Humphreys & Liao, 2011, p. 409). Another example can be seen in Figure 8.6, where Aba Wils uses the hashtags #GhanaGirl, #GhanaInfluencers, and #GhanaPhotography to categorise her post with relevant themes, and join local “hashtag communities” (Bruns & Burgess, 2015) related to gender identity, vocation, and interests (see also Bardhan, 2022).

Tagging’s dual function of organisation and sociality is captured in social media linguist Michelle Zappavigna’s (2015) term “social metadata” (p. 276). Whereas metadata is “information appended to some primary form of content to assist in retrieving and understanding that content when it is stored or published” (p. 276), often automatically, social metadata describes “the ‘user-generated’ tags that emerge over time within a community”, serving as “a form of descriptive annotation produced by users, rather than assigned by” platforms (p. 276). By using tagging affordances, virtual influencers thus enhance the dialogic nature of their posts, participating in ongoing social media conversations, and appearing in search results populated by content from actual social media users (Zappavigna, 2015). Tags enter virtual influencers into social media’s “networked publics” (boyd, 2010; Ito, 2008), joining the “imagined collectives” of social media users whose affiliations are forged or maintained using a range of networked practices (boyd, 2010, p. 39). Below, I explore three ways virtual influencers use tagging affordances to network their social media posts with markers of identity, local trends, and meaning.

8.3.1 Indexing

Tagging affordances are often used by virtual influencers to catalogue “the main subjects, ideas, events, locations or emotions” featured in their content (Highfield & Leaver, 2015, n.p.), making their posts searchable and retrievable. In information science, this process is known as “indexing”: allocating textual descriptions to (especially visual) objects to make their contents retrievable using computer systems (Shatford, 1986). The use of tags for indexing has been studied on photo-sharing sites like Flickr, and social media platforms like Twitter and Instagram (see Dorsch, 2018). In its most basic form, indexing comprises two primary approaches: “ofness” and “aboutness”, where ofness “refers to the elements that a picture consists of”, focusing on what can be seen, and aboutness describes “what is conveyed in a document, what it is about, what its content, subject or theme is”, often requiring more subjective input (Klenczon & Rygiel, 2014, p. 45). A third category,

“isness”, is sometimes included to identify “what the resource is”, such as its form or genre (Klenczon & and Rygiel, 2014, p. 46). Using tags, virtual influencers often index cultural signifiers within their content, making these legible to sorting algorithms and other users.

Two approaches to indexing can be seen in an Instagram post showing Aba Wils at the Kumasi Cultural Centre (see Figure 8.7). First, the post’s hashtags are used to describe the “ofness” of the image, identifying specific components of Aba Wils’ outfit (e.g. #Beads, #Kente, #KenteCloth, #FineKente). Wrapped around her body and over her shoulder, Aba Wils wears a bright yellow *kente* cloth—a style of hand-woven shawl originating in Southern Ghana, typically worn on special occasions (see Lartey & Asmah, 2016)—elaborately decorated with geometric designs. At the level of “aboutness”, hashtags recognise the cultural significance of the outfit (e.g. #TraditionalWear, #CultureFashion), with the hashtag #AkanCulture connecting the image of Aba Wils to the Akan people, the largest ethnic grouping in Ghana (Cox & Thompson, 2022). The hashtag #AkanCulture offers additional cultural context: *kente* were historically worn by Akan royalty, and the golden or yellow *kente* has particular associations with royalty, cultural richness, prosperity, and wealth (Asmah, 2009). The symbolic meaning of her outfit is referenced by hashtags like #Queen and #AfricanQueen, as well as by the hashtag #NanaHemaa, translating to “Queen Mother” in Akan (Banks, 2012). As the other posts included in this chapter highlight (see also Figure 8.6

Figure 8.7: Ghanaian virtual influencer Aba Wils wears an embroidered yellow *kente*, colourful beaded necklaces and a matching headdress, an outfit traditionally worn in Ghana in times of celebration. Source: Instagram (Aba Wils [@abawils], 2022), screengrab by author on 1 November 2023.

and Figure 8.9), Aba Wils often tags her posts with a long list of hashtags. In many cases, these hashtags serve not only to index the contents of the image for digital retrieval; they also categorise the image with labels imbued with cultural meaning, making their content visible to other social media users with shared linguistic and cultural backgrounds.

8.3.2 Participating

Tagging is also used by virtual influencers to signal their participation in localised social media practices. For example, a Weibo post by Chinese virtual influencer Vila shows her poses with an elaborate display for luxury cosmetics brand Lancôme (see Figure 8.8). With an arched gallery decorated in creams, pinks, and gold; flattering, high-key lighting; and an overflowing floral display of champagne-coloured roses, the display is highly “Instagrammable” (see H. Chang & Spierings, 2023). In the caption, Vila identifies the display as “兰蔻菁纯花颜悦坊” (“*Lancôme Jing Hua Yan Yue Fang*”), a pop-up marketing activation that toured shopping malls in several Chinese cities in late 2021 (see 巴适成都, 2021). Crucially, Vila’s caption concludes with #北京探店# (#*Beijing Tàndiàn*#), a hashtag with overtly local significance: *tàndiàn* (探店) is a Chinese online vernacular term that combines the characters 探 (*tàn*) “to explore” and 店 (*diàn*) “store” (Vica Li Chinese [@LearnChineseWithVica], 2021). In hashtag form, the term *tàndiàn* either denotes the

Figure 8.8: Chinese virtual influencer Vila posts about visiting a Lancôme marketing activation at Chaoyang Joy City at shopping mall in Beijing, using a local hashtag to recommend it to her followers. Source: Weibo (CallMeVila, 2022), screengrab by author on 8 August 2023.

experience of having been somewhere new and notable, or signals to others that a store, restaurant, or experience is worth visiting (Y. Li & Hayes, 2024; 杭州探店, 2023). Vila's use of the *#BeijingTàndiàn#* hashtag signals her participation in local social media practices. In this case, Vila utilises the vernacular meaning of the hashtag to enhance the post's commercial messaging, labelling the Lancôme activation for a local audience in search of social media-worthy adventures.

Virtual influencers also participate in localised social media "challenges", reproducing specific physical "templates" (Leaver et al., 2020) codified by other social media users, often attached to specific sounds or sound effects (Zulli & Zulli, 2022). Dance challenges, for example, are short sequences of choreography attached to specific musical sequences, filmed for, and circulated on social media. Dance challenges have grown in popularity since 2018 with the rise of apps, including Dubsmash, Music.ly, TikTok, and later, Instagram's Reels, facilitating short-form video production (Boffone, 2021), and making it easier for "users to repurpose existing audio in new videos" (Abidin & Kaye, 2021, p. 59). The use of audio is signalled by an audio tag displaying information about the name of the song or sound, and its original source or author (see Kaye et al., 2021). Like the other tagging affordances discussed in this section, clicking on the tag reveals a gallery of all other posts that have used it (Abidin & Kaye, 2021). By participating in a dance challenge, social media users enter into "imitation publics", whereby "digital connectivity is constituted through the shared ritual of content imitation and replication" (Zulli & Zulli, 2022, p. 1882).

For virtual influencers, participating in dance challenges involves additional production complexities, requiring advanced technical skill or expensive equipment (e.g. a motion capture suit, not to mention a physically coordinated body double) to accurately animate the model's movements to set choreography. Despite this complexity, over the course of my fieldwork, dance challenges became more commonplace among the virtual influencers I observed, many of whom were experimenting with the production of fully 3D models (see Chapter 6). Figure 8.9 shows Aba Wils participating in a dance challenge associated with "Kwaku The Traveller," a song by Ghanaian singer and rapper Black Sherif. Her participation is signalled both by an audio tag and the hashtag *#KwakuTheTravellerChallenge*. In the video, published on both Instagram and TikTok, Aba Wils struts purposefully towards the camera while singing along with the song, her arms gesturing to accentuate the lyrics while digital rain falls around her. In our interview, Goff offered insight into the inspiration for the video:

Figure 8.9: Aba Wils posts her tribute to Black Sherif's "Kwaku the Traveller" performance at the A3 Music Awards on Instagram Reels. Source: Instagram (Aba Wils [@abawils], 2022a), video screengrab by author on 3 October 2023.

There was this Kwaku The Traveler song, "Black Sherif". [...] It was a trending song in Ghana [...] What the singer did was [...] he was performing live on stage, and as soon as the song started, there was this—I don't know how they did it—there was this rain on stage. So everyone doing the [dance] challenge was, like, [using] either [actual] rain, or some water that's coming from [a hose above them]... (Laughs.) For Aba Wils, we decided to put her in the rain.

The performance to which Goff refers occurred at the 3 Music Awards 2022, an annual awards ceremony celebrating Ghanaian music (see TV3 Ghana, 2022). In the show's live broadcast, Black Sherif stands with a microphone on a small platform, several metres away from the musicians and choral group accompanying his act. As he reaches the song's first chorus, the stage lights flash, and a cascade of raindrops begins to fall only on Black Sherif, who continues to sing through the downpour. Browsing the #KwakuTheTravellerChallenge hashtag shows videos of other social media users lipsynching to the song, each showered with water upon reaching the song's chorus. Several behind-the-scenes videos (also tagged with the challenge hashtag) reveal how the effect was achieved, often with helpers standing

off-screen with bowls of water, colanders, and desk fans. As Goff explained in our interview, for Aba Wils, the use of digital rain required additional animation to make her hair and outfit appear wet. Through these efforts to digitally recreate the format of the challenge, Aba Wils enters into an “imitation public” (Zulli & Zulli, 2022) centred around a popular song by a local artist, and a popular culture moment with local impact.

8.3.3 Appropriating

Finally, we see virtual influencers appropriate the function of tagging affordances, untethering them from their formal or intended usage to more playfully frame their content with meaning. This aligns with what digital media scholars Kath Albury and Paul Byron (2016) call “off-label” use, where users engage with technologies “for purposes other than those ‘prescribed’ by the app’s developers” (p. 9). An example can be seen in an Instagram Reel posted by Brazilian-Korean virtual influencer Theo (see Figure 8.10), which uses a popular audio meme created by TikTok user @nopotatoess, wherein a wistful voiceover remarks, “My pronouns are ‘he’, but not ‘him’... ‘Cause I’ll never be him”. A play on the English-language practice of introducing preferred pronouns (for example, “My pronouns are he/him”), the audio was quickly taken up by other TikTok users to emphasise their inadequacy compared to another person: across different iterations of the meme, “him” was used to refer to figures from other internet memes, characters from pop culture, athletes, and celebrities. The comparison would often be accentuated by the poster dressing in a similar outfit, or performing a similar action, cutting dramatically to a clip of “him” as the voiceover laments, “Cause I’ll never be him”. In Theo’s Reel, a computerised voice provides the narration atop a video of Theo staring at the camera (see Figure 8.10), before cutting to a music video from Korean virtual idol Adam’s (see Chapter 2) second album, *Exodus*, released in 1999 (김인철, 1999). The colouring of their jumpers and similar hairstyles emphasises the likeness between the two, but, as Adam sings, the computerised voiceover concludes its lament: “Cause I’ll never be him”. In this example, the audio meme is used to playfully suggest Theo’s inadequacy in relation to a virtual idol that, as he jokes in the Reel’s caption, is old enough to be his father (Theo 테오 [@theo.rises], 2022).

Figure 8.10: Korean-Brazilian virtual influencer Theo uses a popular audio meme to emphasise his similarity and difference from Korean “cybersinger” Adam, accentuating the comparison with his appropriated use of the geotag. Source: Instagram (Theo 테오 [@theo.rises], 2022), video screengrab by author on 18 June 2022.

Theo’s appropriation of tagging affordances is seen in the Reel’s geotag. The geotag is not used to reference a place, but rather contains the phrase “Cybersinger”, a popular English-language descriptor for Korean virtual idols like Adam in the early 2000s (e.g. Kang, 2003). Clicking on the geotag reveals the “location” has been categorised as a “Music Production Studio”, but shows no geographic coordinates; instead, the geotag is an empty descriptor with a “playful and expressive”, not functional, purpose (Cramer et al., 2011, p. 62). This “off-label” (Albury & Byron, 2016, p. 9) use of the geotag feature has affinities to the tactical tagging practices observed among users of the microblogging platform Tumblr (Brett & Maslen, 2021). Although Tumblr tags have structural and functional uses (as discussed in section 8.3.1), they are often appropriated by users as sites for expressing intimate thoughts and confessions, with the shared understanding that these tags are “pseudo-private, and that they ought to treat them as such” (Brett & Maslen, 2021, p. 12). In Theo’s case, the geotag is divorced from its locative function, instead echoing the pop culture reference featured in the meme. By evoking the “cyber-” epithet popular in the late 1990s and early 21st century (Woolgar, 2002), the term “Cybersinger” instead suggests a temporal “location” for the post, connecting Theo to the much longer timeline of Korean virtual celebrity.

In section 8.3, I highlighted how virtual influencers use tagging affordances like geotags, hashtags, and audio tags to network their content with other social media posts. These affordances play a “structural role” in the organisation of visual social media platforms (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 74), and allow users to append their own “social metadata” (Zappavigna, 2015, p. 276) to their content, forging connections with other posts, practices, and social media users. As examples of enframement, virtual influencers use tagging affordances to categorise the contents of their posts; signal their participation in local social media practices; and convey meaning through creative appropriations of affordances for purposes other than their original design. Importantly, these practices make the characters’ cultural affiliations and practices visible not only to other social media users, but also to algorithms, who indiscriminately recognise these fictional characters as part of “networked publics” (boyd, 2010; Ito, 2008) organised around cultural markers.

8.4 Summary

In this chapter, I explored how virtual influencers—as fictional, non-human entities—are ascribed cultural identities. Specifically, I analysed how virtual influencers use platform affordances to “enframe” (Spyer & Steedly, 2013) their visual content with cultural meaning, thereby “stain[ing]” (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 8) themselves with recognisable cultural identities. Firstly, I analysed how text-based affordances like captions are used to “anchor” (Barthes, 1977/1982; Spyer & Steedly, 2013) visual content with context to guide its interpretation, demarcating audiences and making cultural significance salient. Secondly, I considered how tagging affordances like hashtags, geotags, and audio tags are used to network virtual influencers’ content within the “networked publics” (boyd, 2010; Ito, 2008) that are created through the use of hashtags (Bruns & Burgess, 2015) and participation in dance challenges and audio memes (Zulli & Zulli, 2022). Using these affordances aids in connecting virtual influencers to cultural communities, traditions, and practices from the actual world, accentuating the geographic markers that populate their biographies, press accounts, and promotional rhetoric. Given the strong visual focus of much scholarship on virtual influencers, this chapter offers new insights into how virtual influencers use platform affordances, and how these features influence our encounters with them.

Drawing on previous theorisations of cultural commodification (e.g. Abidin, 2018a; Iwabuchi, 2002), and supporting Miyake’s (2022) analysis of Japanese virtual influencer Imma, the key argument of this chapter is that virtual influencers use cultural identities as a means of self-branding amid a growing number of characters vying for attention, audiences, and brand partnerships. These cultural identities can be further commodified for commercial

opportunities, adding a recognisable and desirable “cultural odour” (Iwabuchi, 2002) to the products and messages they promote. Chapter 9 analyses another prominent theme in virtual influencers’ commercial activities, focusing on large, multi-channel marketing campaigns where these cultural identities are exchanged for recurring visual motifs that instead foreground ideas of the virtual.

Modelling Virtuality

9.1 Introduction

In the early-2020s, as the COVID-19 pandemic was upending daily life, forcing millions of people around the world to stay at home or shelter-in-place, virtual influencers were distinguished by their activity. Media outlets published numerous articles with headlines like “Virtual Influencers Make Real Money While Covid Locks Down Human Stars” (Ong, 2020), “The Lucrative Rise of the Virtual Influencer” (Yates, 2020), and “Virtual Influencers Kept Busy as Jobs Keep Coming In” (H.-S. Ahn & Lee, 2021), in each instance referencing a growing number of brands partnering with virtual influencers for commercial campaigns. Around the same time, UK-based e-commerce marketplace OnBuy (2020) published a blog post estimating the earnings of the most popular virtual influencers on Instagram: in the top spot was American virtual influencer Lil Miquela who, according to OnBuy’s estimates, could receive £6,550 (USD\$8,450) per sponsored Instagram post, earning an estimated £8,960,000 (USD\$11.5 million) per year. Though Miquela’s creators remained tight-lipped, offering no confirmation of the estimates, OnBuy’s figures were reproduced verbatim in the press (e.g. AFP News Agency, 2021; Chae, 2022; Ong, 2020; Teh, 2021), even prompting dedicated articles with headlines like “Sorry, Lil Miquela Could Make *How Much* This Year???” (Petrarca, 2020, original emphasis). Similar interest followed interviews with Baek Seung-yeop, the creator of Korean virtual influencer Rozy, who told various news outlets that Rozy had received partnership offers from over 100 brands (S. Kim, 2021); earned ₩1 billion (USD\$857,000) in her first year (H.-S. Ahn & Lee, 2021); and ₩2 billion (USD\$1.5 million) in profit the year following (Yeung & Bae, 2022). While press about the incomes of top-tier human influencers will often express “surprise at the fact that Influencers [sic] can command a sizable earning and that brands want to work with them” (Abidin, 2018a, p. 82), commentary on the earnings of virtual influencers ask how it is possible for influencers to earn income without a physical body. As one headline from the *Korea JoongAng Daily* newspaper put it, “You Don’t Even Have to Exist to Make Millions on Social Media” (E.-J. Park, 2021).

In this chapter, I examine the commercial application of virtual influencers. I focus on the layer of the *model*, analysing how the characters’ virtual bodies are used to promote actual brands and products. I start by recognising the various “templates” (Leaver et al., 2020) virtual influencers use to integrate sponsored messaging into their personal social media feeds, noting that many of these posts are visually identical to those of human influencers.

However, I highlight that the visual style of virtual influencers' commercial partnerships shifts when the campaigns are likely to encounter audiences unfamiliar with the characters. Such partnerships often feature what I describe as an *iconography of virtuality*—a collection of tropes, aesthetics, and visual effects that, through their recurring presence in popular culture, have come to signify virtuality—to quickly convey that the characters are more-than-human entities. I conclude by proposing that the benefit of accentuating the characters' virtuality is in activating what I call a *halo of innovation*, extending a sense of technological advancement to the brands and products they promote.

9.1.1 Modelling

I orient my analysis in this chapter around the *model*: the visual representation of the character. Two meanings of this term are especially useful for the analytic framework I adopt in this chapter. Firstly, in the animation industry, a “model” describes a computer-generated object created with 3D animation software (Vaughan, 2011, p. 2). As most virtual influencers are at least partly created with 3D imagery (see Chapter 6), focusing on the model draws our attention to virtual influencers as digitally created entities. Secondly, a “model” also refers to someone who “appear[s] in person, or in photographs, either in advertisements or to promote commercial transactions” (Wissinger, 2007, p. 251). As a profession, models “lend their image to sell products, incorporating their likeness into the image of the brand” (Wissinger, 2009, p. 274). This quality is shared by both human and virtual influencers, who are often called upon to “stimulate desire and motivate customers to purchase” by modelling commercial products and services on social media (Abidin & Thompson, 2012, p. 470). Scholarship on virtual influencers has thus far examined their commercial application in industries such as tourism (see Xie-Carson et al., 2023; Xie-Carson & Benckendorff, 2024), retail (see Brachtendorf, 2022; Z. Li, 2022), as well as automotive and hospitality (see Baumgarth et al., 2021). In this chapter, I look across industries to identify shared techniques and recurring motifs in advertising imagery featuring virtual influencers, drawing both on modelling's technical and vocational meanings to analyse the digital bodies of virtual influencers as sites of commodification.

9.1.2 Shoppable Lives

Like human influencers, virtual influencers often “promote brands or products with content of themselves engaged in everyday activities, like going to the gym or cooking” (Arriagada, 2021, p. 449), using their fictional lives as a backdrop for commodification (Guo, 2022). This illustrates what communication scholars Emily Hund and Lee McGuigan (2019) call the “shoppable life”, referring to “the idea that social media users perform and document aspirational lifestyles whose constituent elements can be bought instantly” (p. 20). For Hund

and McGuigan, the shoppable life is exemplified by beauty, fashion, and lifestyle influencers, whose social media content “cultivate[s] desire for an attractive life and its trappings, in a mediated environment that makes the wares and associated lifestyles seem immediately accessible” (p. 27). They situate the shoppable life within a cultural zeitgeist and social media ecosystem organised by “an aggressively expanding logic of *shoppability*” (p. 18, original emphasis), where it is both expected and increasingly possible that content will link directly to an opportunity to purchase. In a short period, social media’s logic of shoppability has evolved from third-party plug-ins—such as LikeToKnowIt, an affiliate marketing program which made it easier for influencers to “make their Instagram images shoppable with participating retail partners” (Hund, 2017, p. 3)—to a central component embedded in platform design, governance, and use (see Carah et al., 2023; Guo, 2022; Hund & McGuigan, 2019).

Within this context, virtual influencers often employ what has been described as a “shout-out” style of influencer promotion, utilising platform affordances like hashtags, captions, and tags to acknowledge the products and brands featured in their social media content (Leaver et al., 2020, pp. 118–119). They do not want for opportunities: like their human counterparts, virtual influencers’ social media feeds tend to depict what digital culture scholar Brooke Erin Duffy and Hund (2015) describe as “the glam life”, popularised by evidence of “global travel, invitations to exclusive events, and access to luxury goods and swag” (p. 6). Shout-outs direct additional attention to the myriad commodities that populate the characters’ glamorous lives, and “offer the possibility of redirecting traffic to the sponsors’ Instagram feeds” (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 119). Below, I identify three influencer “templates” (Leaver et al., 2020) commonly used by virtual influencers as opportunities for shout-outs: #OOTDs (#OutfitOfTheDay) posts, PR (public relations) unboxings, and event appearances. All three templates allow the producers of virtual influencers to integrate commercial messaging into the characters’ “lives”, and are well-suited for promotional efforts in which the virtual influencer’s followers are the target audience.

#OOTDs

Virtual influencers frequently upload #OOTD posts, modelling “highly fashionable apparel”, ranging from activewear and streetwear to luxury and couture fashion (Brachtendorf, 2022, p. 48). “OOTDs”, an acronym for “Outfit of the Day”, are “a genre of posts popular on social media in which users share photographs modelling the clothes they wear” (Abidin, 2016d, p. 92). On visual social media platforms like Instagram and Xiaohongshu (小红书), the phrase is often articulated in hashtag form—such as #OOTD, #OutfitOfTheDay or #今日穿搭(ootd)#,

translating to *#Today'sOutfit(OOTD)*⁹—networking it to posts from other social media users who also upload sartorial showcases (see Chapter 8). By accentuating how an individual has “ensembled an outfit from various apparel and accessories” (Abidin, 2016d, p. 92), *#OOTD* posts foreground the body as a site of commercial display and desire, further underscored by the details these posts often include about the brands and products featured. For example, in the *#OOTD* post shown in Figure 9.1, Chinese virtual influencer Reddi leans casually against a door, as though photographed just before leaving the house. The post caption lists the brands for different components of her outfit, including her sweater, jacket, pants, and handbag, translating her appearance into an amalgam of fashion labels.

It is often unclear what—if any—commercial arrangements incentivise virtual influencers’ shout-outs (Brachtendorf, 2022). Writing of human influencers, Hund and McGuigan (2019) point out that on social media, brand and product endorsements “may be motivated by

Figure 9.1: Chinese virtual influencer Reddi posts an *#OOTD*, using the post caption to list the brands of the items she wears. Source: Xiaohongshu (Reddi, 2021), screengrab by author on 22 June 2025.

⁹ Italicised text machine-translated by Google Translate.

genuine enthusiasm for a brand or product, promised or potential remuneration, or the perceived symbolic benefits of associating themselves with attractive companies” (p. 22). For example, in Figure 9.2, Thai virtual influencer Katii uses her caption and user tags to give “special thanks” to two brands featured in the image: Thai fashion brand Kloset and sneaker brand Camper. However, Katii’s “special thanks” dedication, a staple in many of this character’s Instagram posts, makes the commercial relationship ambiguous, suggesting gratitude towards the brands without acknowledging whether a transaction has occurred. As Brachtendorf (2022) highlights, even though

relationships between luxury fashion brands and virtual influencers are mutually beneficial as they create more visibility and traffic for each other [...] it often remains unclear whether there are financial agreements in place, as few posts are marked as sponsored. (p. 490)

It is likely that, in some cases, this ambiguity is precisely the effect the posts are intended to evoke, suggesting an everyday trendiness and sartorial elegance, and the saturation of the characters’ daily lives with desirable commodities and high-profile brands (Duffy & Hund, 2015).

Figure 9.2: Thai virtual influencer Katii uses tags to shout-out the brands of clothing and sneakers she wears. Source: Instagram (Katii [@katii.katie], 2022a), screengrab by author on 13 September 2024.

PR Unboxing

More clearly acknowledging a commercial relationship, virtual influencers also post about

receiving gifts from brands. It is now a commonplace public relations (PR) strategy for brands to send influencers new products, limited-edition items, and invitations to exclusive events (Leaver et al., 2020; Marchand et al., 2024). These gifts are typically sent “without any contractual obligations for the influencers to create content but in an effort to make the brand top of mind, signal appreciation, and build a basis for future cooperation” (Marchand et al., 2024, pp. 2341–2342). Being included on what is colloquially known as a brand’s “PR list”, and receiving these gifts, signals the influencer has reached a certain level of visibility and commercial desirability (Duffy & Hund, 2015; Marchand et al., 2024). As thanks, influencers will often post about the gifts on social media in the form of “PR unboxing” content, showcasing the product (usually surrounded by elaborate packaging), and publicly expressing their gratitude to draw their followers’ attention to the (usually tagged) brand (Duffy & Hund, 2015; R. Wood, 2021).

Despite their fictionality, virtual influencers also receive PR gifts and often post PR unboxing content on social media. During my fieldwork, this content would most frequently appear as ephemeral formats such as Instagram Stories, disappearing after 24-hours, unless saved as a “Highlight” on the character’s profile, enabling later access. Two examples of PR unboxing can be seen in Figure 9.3: Japanese virtual influencer Imma unboxes a limited-edition pair of Ray-Ban sunglasses, and Korean virtual influencer Rozy posts about a coffee capsule collection from Nespresso. Both examples assume the form of “implied selfies” (Zhao & Zappavigna, 2018, p. 1747), where the bodies of the virtual influencers are not featured; instead, the composition of the image suggests it has been taken “by” the character upon unwrapping the gift, with the camera’s gaze standing in for their perspective. Sometimes, as in the Ray-Ban sunglasses example, PR packages will be arranged to highlight hand-written notes, suggesting an even more personal connection between the brand and the character.

Importantly, the purpose of these PR unboxing posts is not to educate their followers about the products. They tend not to contain product detail – indeed, neither of the examples in Figure 9.3 name the products featured in the image, nor do they mention that these products are limited edition. In these cases, it tends to be the status and cultural capital (as discussed in Chapter 7) of being noticed by brands and receiving free products that incentivises such displays, with the (often temporary) exposure of the brand name offered in exchange (Duffy & Hund, 2015; Marchand et al., 2024).

Figure 9.3: Virtual influencers use Instagram Stories to document gifts received from brands: Japanese virtual influencer Imma expresses thanks for a limited-edition pair of Ray-Ban sunglasses (left; screengrab by author on 31 May 2022); and Korean virtual influencer Rozy thanks Nespresso for sending her a selection of limited-edition coffee capsules (right; screengrab by author on 15 January 2022).

Brand Events

Another opportunity often made available to influencers on brands' PR lists is invitations to exclusive events. Virtual influencers regularly take photos attending product launches and other branded events and activations. These events tend to be purposefully designed to encourage photo-taking and sharing on social media, replete with "Instagrammable" backdrops, like flower-walls and neon brand signs (C. Campbell et al., 2022). Figure 9.4 shows Weibo (微博) posts from two Chinese virtual influencers, Reddi and ALiCE, attending an event by fragrance brand VIKTOR & ROLF at a promotional pop-up in Hainan. Both characters post multiple images from the party, posing in front of the elaborate floral displays (themed to match the colour schemes of the brand's two flagship fragrances), standing next to comically oversized fragrance bottles, and holding regular-sized bottles of their preferred VIKTOR & ROLF scents.

Figure 9.4: Chinese virtual influencer Reddi poses holding a bottle of VIKTOR & ROLF's Spicebomb fragrance at a launch party for the VIKTOR & ROLF pop-up at Times DF x DFS Haikou Mission Hills Duty-Free City, a massive duty-free shopping complex in Hainan, China. Source: Weibo (IamReddi, 2022), screengrab by author 29 September 2024.

Chinese virtual influencer ALICE poses in front of a floral display and an oversized bottle of VIKTOR & ROLF's Flowerbomb perfume at the same launch party. Source: Weibo (虚拟人ALICE, 2022), screengrab by author on 23 September 2024.

The logistics of attending these events “as” a virtual influencer remain unclear. I have found evidence of characters’ producers attending events, and taking photos of themselves in Instagrammable spots, with their bodies later superimposed with the character’s face (see Chapter 6). In one of my producer interviews, Reyme Husaini described getting invited to attend a product launch event at Nasty Cookie, a gourmet cookie shop in Singapore, on behalf of his virtual influencer Elly. When he arrived, Husaini recalled: “Everyone was just, like, taking pictures. [...] They were doing the whole cookie-tasting [thing]. It was basically a PR event. So that was that. I just [went] there, had free food, and took some pictures with my friends.” Elly’s invitation was an opportunity for Husaini to attend and enjoy the event himself, participating as an influencer would, while taking photographs of the store for Elly’s Instagram post (ELLY [@ellychan.ai], 2021).

In other cases, it appears that a model is hired to attend the event as the character’s body double, with a professional photographer sometimes also enlisted to attend, taking photographs so the character can later be composited into the scene. In some cases, additional efforts are taken to convey a sense of liveness and “being-there” as the event is happening (Hammelburg, 2021), with the nominated attendee posting fragmented static or video updates using formats like Instagram Stories. Like the “PR unboxing” images previously discussed, these updates often take the form of “implied selfies” (Zhao & Zappavigna, 2018, p. 1747), surveying aspects of the event from the “character’s” point-of-view (see Figure 9.5). When compared with human influencers, the lack of faces in these

Figure 9.5: Thai virtual influencer Ai Ailynn posts Instagram stories at a pop-up event for luxury cosmetics brand Lancôme, photographing the various Instagrammable backgrounds and encouraging her followers to attend. Source: Instagram Stories (25 June 2022), screengrabs by author on 25 June 2022.

live updates is conspicuous (cf. Abidin, 2016a): given the additional time and attention required to superimpose the characters' digital faces onto their human doubles (see Chapter 6), polished posts showing the characters' faces "at" the event tend to appear several days later. In other cases (e.g. the event shown in Figure 9.5), the "live" updates are stored and shared after the fact, alongside the polished event photos. These polished photos (see Figure 9.4) tend to show the characters posing with displays, logos, and products, accentuating the posts' branded nature.

The three aforementioned commercial templates—#OOTDs, PR unboxing, and brand events—offer examples of how virtual influencers embody the concept of "shoppable lives" (Duffy & Hund, 2015), weaving commercial products and goods into the fictional moments and movements they document on social media. These formats are particularly effective for engaging the characters' existing audiences of social media followers, who have opted in to receiving updates of their latest posts. Like human influencers, the "luxurious commodity lifestyles" virtual influencers portray "invite [their] followers into a more sustained and intimate world of desire" populated by brands and products that can be easily browsed and purchased (Hund & McGuigan, 2019, p. 27). Except for the lack of face-focused selfies shared live from brand events, by and large, virtual influencers' use of these commercial templates replicates how they are used by human influencers, resulting in little aesthetic difference between the two.

However, I observed during my fieldwork that these were not the only commercial activities in which virtual influencers engaged. As the characters grew in popularity, they were increasingly recruited for marketing campaigns designed to travel beyond their own social media profiles, incorporating high-reach marketing channels like television commercials, online video, billboards and posters, in-store signage, and even custom product packaging. These campaigns were often national or transnational in scale, and usually publicised by the brand partners on company websites, social media profiles, and/or in press releases. In these instances, I observed a visual style distinct from the "glam life" (Duffy & Hund, 2015) portrayed in the aforementioned examples. Instead, these multi-channel marketing campaigns often foregrounded motifs from popular culture, drawing both from science fiction media and the visual language associated with technological bodies in advertising, to mark the characters as virtual entities.

9.2 Iconography of Virtuality

The specific visual lexicon used in these multi-channel marketing campaigns can be conceptualised as an *iconography of virtuality*: tropes, symbols, aesthetics, and effects that, through their prominent and/or recurring use in visual and popular culture, have become shorthand for the virtual. I employ the term “iconography” as it is commonly used in film scholarship—especially in discussions of genre—to reference recurring “visual conventions or icons, pictorial codes which [serve as] a graphic shorthand” and are immediately “understood by both [producer] and audience” (Sobchack, 1980, p. 65). For the virtual, this “graphic shorthand” (Sobchack, 1980, p. 65) chiefly reflects the colloquial usage of “virtual” as synonymous with “digital”, encompassing creations and experiences reliant upon digital technologies (K. M. Lee, 2004), such as virtual realities and virtual worlds (see Chapter 4). As the below examples attest, it may also hint at virtual’s other definitions, such as virtuality as potentiality (what becomes possible when we transcend the actual), and dimensionality (as a space of fiction and fantasy), though these are often tied to the term’s technological aspect.

The concept of an iconography of virtuality builds on marketing studies scholar Norah Campbell’s (2007) research into “how the discourses of science and technology – their narratives, metaphors and symbols – are used in advertisements” (p. 4), and on the analysis of American sociolinguist Fern L. Johnson (2007) of the “technological imprint on the discourse of advertising” (p. 154). Both scholars draw attention to the pervasiveness of technology-related imagery, metaphors, and terminology in marketing materials, noting how this visual language appears in advertisements for “both technology products and products that we do not think of as technology-based, such as hair care, snacks, and cigarettes” (Johnson, 2007, p. 154). Fitting within this tradition, virtual influencers likewise draw “from existing artifacts in art, literature, science and other cultural discourses”, especially science fiction media, “to establish meaning” for the brands and products they are enlisted to promote (N. Campbell et al., 2006, p. 345; see also Buchanan-Oliver et al., 2010). I suggest that this visual lexicon is used to quickly conjure ideas of virtuality, and in so doing, associations of technological innovation, novelty, and superiority (see section 9.4).

As a telling illustration, many of virtual influencers’ multi-channel marketing campaigns take place in settings reminiscent of iconic sci-fi films. This includes dark urban cityscapes illuminated with neon bars, familiar from cyberpunk films like *Blade Runner* (Scott, 1982; see Figure 9.6), as well as expansive voids of glowing grids representing virtual reality spaces in films, as in *Tron* (Lisberger, 1982) and its sequel *Tron: Legacy* (Kosinski, 2010; see Figure 9.7). Such examples immediately foreground “an aesthetic of digital artifice” (Matrix, 2006, p.

120) distinct from how virtuality is typically featured in the characters' social media feeds (see Figure 9.8). As discussed in Chapter 6, virtual influencers will often wear virtual fashion or appear in virtual environments, interacting with items, objects, and landscapes not found in the actual world. In such cases, the virtual additions tend to be creative and colourful, portraying fantastical experiences or encounters that relish in the wide-reaching potential of digital animation. By contrast, in virtual influencers' multi-channel marketing campaigns, virtuality is largely standardised, articulated using a visual iconography codified by several decades' worth of popular culture. These signifiers leave little doubt as to their intended meaning, immediately conjuring ideas of the virtual drawn from speculative technofutures.

Figure 9.6: Bars of red lights illuminate the dark cityscapes to promote Porsche's electric Taycan model. Left: Japanese virtual influencer Imma promotes the Taycan in Japan; source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2019b), screengrab by author on 6 October 2023. Right: Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI promotes the Taycan in China; source: Weibo (保时捷, 2021), screengrab by author 29 September 2024.

Stills of the dark, neon-lit city from *Blade Runner* (Scott, 1982).

Figure 9.7: Dark voids illuminated with tessellated grids and abstract polygons of light. Left: Chinese virtual influencer Liu Yexi promotes electric vehicle manufacturer XPENG; source: DAO Insights (Na, 2022), screengrab by author on 25 August 2024. Right: Chinese virtual influencer Ha Jiang promotes Elf Cosmetics; source: Weibo (哈酱99, 2022), screengrab by author on 23 September 2024.

Circuits, grids, and neon in the virtual reality spaces of *Tron: Legacy* (Kosinski, 2010; left), the sequel to *Tron* (Lisberger, 1982; right).

Figure 9.8: Examples of typical depictions of virtuality in virtual influencers' social media feeds. Left: Dubai-based influencer Meta Kira models a virtual dress; source: Instagram (MetaKira [@meta.kira], 2022c). Centre: Singaporean virtual influencer Rae eats breakfast with her virtual pet octopus, Tako; source: Instagram (RAE 蕊 [@here.is.rae], 2022). Right: Korean virtual influencer Rozy poses in a virtual world overflowing with pink and orange flowers; source: Instagram (Rozy [@rozy.gram], 2022). Screenshots by author on 23 September 2023.

The effectiveness of this iconography of virtuality can be understood in terms of the encoding and decoding model famously advanced by cultural theorist Stuart Hall (1980/2005). Hall challenges the idea that a “message” can ever be transferred directly from a “sender” to a “receiver” (p. 117). Instead, he proposes that meaning is always constructed through a series of signs—elsewhere described as a “social grammar of meaning” (Goldman, 1992, p. 2)—which are “encoded” by the sender (during production) and subsequently “decoded” by the receiver (during consumption; Hall, 1980/2005, p. 119). Critical advertising scholars have highlighted that advertisements are often designed to guide readers towards what Hall describes as the producer’s “preferred meaning” (p. 123). For example, writing of print advertisements, sociologist Erving Goffman (1976) remarks that “the picture itself is designed to tell its little story without much textual assistance” (p. 26), while fellow sociologist Robert Goldman (1992) suggests that advertisements “carry both a message and a set of instructions about how to make sense of it” (p. 124).

Given an iconography of virtuality exists independently from virtual influencers, it is highly effective at communicating meaning. This efficiency is particularly valuable given the variety of media channels and formats often involved in virtual influencers' multi-channel marketing campaigns. High-reach media formats such as television commercials, online video, digital billboards, and in-store displays compete for narrowing windows of audience attention and interest; according to recent studies of consumer behaviour, advertisers have mere seconds to make a brand or product distinctive, memorable, and desirable (Ritson, 2022). These

high-reach channels also deliberately broaden the audience of the campaign messaging well beyond the character's own social media followers. Unlike the brand "shout-outs" (Leaver et al., 2020, pp. 118–119) discussed in section 9.1.2, which targeted sponsored messaging towards the characters' existing followers, multi-channel marketing campaigns are likely to reach audiences unacquainted with the characters. As one example, in September 2020, just four months after her debut, Chinese virtual influencer Ling partnered with high-end tea chain Nayuki 奈雪的茶 (rebranded to Naixue 奈雪的茶 as of December 2022; see van Wyk,

Figure 9.9: Digital billboards featuring Chinese virtual influencer Ling appeared in subway stations in urban Chinese cities as part of her partnership with tea chain Nayuki. Source: Weibo (奈雪的茶, 2020), screengrabs by author on 15 September 2024.

2022). To promote the chain’s limited-edition “Supreme Pomegranate” tea flavour, Ling appeared on digital billboards in subway stations around Shanghai, Guangzhou, and Shenzhen, three of the most densely populated cities in China (奈雪的茶 (@奈雪的茶), 2020; see Figure 9.9). The billboards foreground an iconography of virtuality to quickly establish Ling’s virtuality for commuters unfamiliar with her backstory: Ling, wearing only white and silver, stands in a bright, featureless room, navigating a translucent—perhaps holographic—screen (see section 9.3.5). The room’s angled corners are accentuated by small glowing lines, similar to those used to represent faster-than-light travel in sci-fi series such as *Star Trek*. These iconographic elements are repeated in the animated designs used for Nayuki’s in-store paper bags and cup sleeves, which additionally depict Ling wearing a luminescent visor befitting a cyberpunk scene (see Figure 9.10). As these examples suggest, an iconography of virtuality is useful because it draws on a set of codes that are familiar and easily decoded, effectively communicating meaning even when audience attention is fleeting or fragmented, or the character is not widely known. The next section explores examples of an iconography of virtuality that pertain to the digital bodies of virtual influencers. I highlight that these tropes, symbols, aesthetics, and effects are especially valuable for marketing campaigns where the “preferred meaning” (Hall, 1980/2005, p. 123) for the brand or product relies upon the character being recognised as a virtual entity, a notion I return to in section 9.4.

Figure 9.10: Animated paper bag and cup sleeve featuring Chinese virtual influencer Ling wearing a VR visor available at tea chain Nayuki during the limited-edition Super Pomegranate promotion. Source: Sohu.com (东莞美食先锋队, 2020), screengrabs by author on 27 June 2025.

9.3 Digital Bodies

An iconography of virtuality is often used to draw attention to the immateriality and more-than-human capabilities of virtual influencers' digital bodies. In so doing, these iconographic displays extend media scholar Daniel Black's (2006) suggestion to view the bodies of virtual idols as "artefact[s] which [reflect] current conceptions of the body and their relationship to previous ones" (n.p.). Writing of Japan's virtual idols in the late 1990s and early 2000s (see Chapter 2), Black suggests that "[t]he virtual idol, a computer-generated media celebrity, is a figure representative of a cultural milieu in which arrangements of data seem interchangeable with physical materiality" (n.p.). Evoking science and technology scholar N. Katherine Hayles' (1999) definition of virtuality as "the cultural perception that material objects are interpenetrated by information patterns" (p. 69; discussed in Chapter 4), Black (2006) elaborates that "whereas, in the machine age, the body was imagined to be a machine, in the information age it is imagined to be information" (n.p.). A similar argument has been made of the representation of bodies in advertising, where "the body is not a neutral, natural, or objective entity but a central site of representation, heavily invested with multiple, shifting layers of cultural meaning" (Buchanan-Oliver et al., 2010, p. 636). Indeed, writing around the same time as Black, Campbell (2007) highlights the tendency for bodies in print and online advertisements to be "*informationalised*, or presented as data" (p. 9, original emphasis), a trope she attributes to the rise of imaging technologies that have "encourage[d] the viewer to adopt a new techno-logical [sic] perspective towards the body and its environment" (p. 13).

As of the mid-2020s, we not only see and understand ourselves as data, but also recognise that this data has value: as sociologist Deborah Lupton (2016) describes it, "detailed quantifiable data have become valorised above other forms of information about one's life, health and wellbeing" (p. 62). The use of smart and wearable technologies has become pervasive and unremarkable, facilitating self-tracking for everything from bodily rhythms and functions to "emotional states, sexual and social encounters, work productivity, physical activities and geo-location" (p. 62). The value of this data extends in both personal and commercial directions. On a personal level, self-tracking practices promise knowledge and empowerment, enabling us to understand and optimise daily life, as exemplified by the "quantified self" movement (see Lupton, 2016; Rettberg, 2014). However, data also has commercial value, accumulated *en mass* by technology corporations, who monitor, aggregate, and sell personal data elicited through everyday technology use and transactions as a central component of their business offerings (Lupton, 2016). The visual tropes discussed in this section draw attention to the more-than-human nature and capabilities of a

body that is digital, immaterial, and datafied. I highlight five examples: weightlessness (appearing to have no body mass); wired skin (flesh composed of or coursing with electricity); intangible touch (hindered efforts to make contact with actual objects); glitching (scrambled electronic signals or data arrangements); and augmented senses (the ability to perceive more than humans are capable).

9.3.1 Weightlessness

Virtual influencers are immediately marked as more-than-human when they are depicted floating, transcending laws of physics with seemingly weightless bodies. As sociologist Judy Wajcman (2004) writes, “[t]he urge to defy gravity has been a continuing impulse in our quest to transcend the natural world” (p. 1). When shown untethered from the Earth’s gravitational pull, virtual influencers are clearly signalled to be something other (or more) than human. This echoes animation and film studies scholar Aylish Wood’s (2015) observation that “[t]he possibilities of seeing [the] digital-ness in computer-generated imagery depends on the extent to which it sits outside of conventional behaviours associated with the laws of physical reality” (p. 10).

In Figure 9.11, this trope is leveraged by Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI to promote a new range of ALIENWARE laptops. Posed in a reclined sitting position, her arms and legs extended, AYAYI appears entirely composed, her lower body dripping with the molten chromatic material of her virtual dress. In this example, AYAYI’s weightless body visually

Figure 9.11: Official promotional image for Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI's ALIENWARE x14 laptop promotion. Source: SocialBeta (caya, 2022). Screenshot by author on 24 November 2023.

links her with what the campaign messaging describes as the “*ultra-light*”¹⁰ laptops floating around her, characterising AYAYI, too, as a piece of technology (天猫超级品牌日, 2022, n.p.). Visually reminiscent of the sprawling white simulation space known as “The Construct” in *The Matrix* (The Wachowskis, 1999), the featureless light grey backdrop draws additional attention to AYAYI’s technicity: digital environments are often “depicted as having no gravity” (A. Wood, 2015, p. 13), rendering bodies “boundaryless and floating” (Redmond, 2017, p. 80). Thus although the ALIENWARE brand has a history of using space-related imagery, the use of weightlessness in this example focuses on “*breaking the boundary between actuality and virtuality*”¹¹ (天猫超级品牌日, 2022, n.p.). AYAYI’s more-than-human-ness is made visible through her body’s exemption from physical laws, and instead, her alignment with the properties of virtual objects and environments. Her direct gaze towards the viewer can thus be read as an invitation (Kress & Van Leeuwen, 2021) to join her in fulfilling ALIENWARE’s brand’s slogan: to “defy boundaries”.

9.3.2 Wired Skin

Effects are often applied to virtual influencers’ skin, making their flesh appear to be coursing with electricity. Skin is often used to express more-than-human identities. Back in 2000, telecommunications provider Motorola requested that the digital body for their smart assistant Mya be made to look less like the human models on whom her design was originally based. It was Mya’s skin that was subsequently adjusted, configured to “shine and shimmer with a distinctly inhuman [...] luminescence” to more clearly mark her as more-than-human (Matrix, 2006, p. 111). For virtual influencers, wired skin often takes the form of a grid-like pattern, referencing the wireframes or mesh involved in creating digital models, and “the myriad polygons that make up CGI’s complex forms” (Cameron, 2021, p. 870; see Chapter 6). Even for those unfamiliar with the technical process of 3D modelling, films like *TRON* (Lisberger, 1982) and its sequel *TRON: Legacy* (Kosinski, 2010; see Figure 9.7) have solidified an iconographic association between the grid and digital environments. In Figure 9.12, AYAYI evokes this effect to promote global cosmetics brand MAKE UP FOR EVER’s HD Skin Foundation: a grid of white bars illuminates her right cheek, accentuated by a reflective shimmer highlighting her cheekbone. The grid encourages us to look beyond AYAYI’s photorealistic exterior to perceive her as a digital creation, adding new meaning to the foundation’s name, “HD Skin”. In an analysis of women’s magazines, Johnson (2007)

¹⁰ Italicised text machine-translated with Baidu Fanyi. Original text: “超轻” (天猫超级品牌日, 2022, n.p.).

¹¹ Italicised text machine-translated with Baidu Fanyi. Original text: “打破现实与虚拟界限” (天猫超级品牌日, 2022, n.p.).

notes the use of the phrase “HD” or “High Definition” in ads for cosmetics which promise clear and bright skin tone and texture, especially under the scrutiny of high-resolution photography. Here, the “wiring” of AYAYI’s skin encourages us to take the metaphor to its extreme, as a promise of foundation coverage that is literally “pixel perfect”.

Figure 9.12: Chinese virtual influencer AYAYI promotes the undetectable finish of a foundation by MAKE UP FOR EVER with a luminescent grid on her cheek (left). A bottle of foundation floats above AYAYI’s hand, enveloped by a white swirl with the same grid-like pattern (right). Source: Xiaohongshu (MAKE UP FOR EVER玫珂菲, 2022), screengrabs by author on 30 October 2023.

A variation of the luminous grid can be seen in Figure 9.13, where the wired skin effect is expressed as electric circuitry. The bottom still, taken from a television commercial for Watson’s X Soda, captures the moment Japanese virtual influencer Imma reaches for the can. When the two touch, the skin on Imma’s arm is illuminated by several interconnected lines, reminiscent of an electrical circuit. This effect is a nod to early virtual reality films like *The Lawnmower Man* (Leonard, 1992), which use circuitry to visually signal the characters’ transmutation into digital entities. In this example, it is upon touching the product that the virtuality of Imma’s skin is made visible: the glowing soda can “powers up” Imma’s flesh with a luminous circuit. Whereas the grid visible on AYAYI’s cheek reveals her to be a digital model, the pattern of circuitry that illuminates Imma’s arm points to the digitality of her body by portraying it as a conductor for the electrical charge of the objects around her.

Figure 9.13: Stills from Japanese virtual influencer Imma's television commercial for Watson's soda water in China: interacting with a translucent interface (top) and illuminating with circuitry upon touching the soda can (bottom). Source: YouTube (Aww, Virtual Human AI カンパニー, 2021) and PR Times (株式会社 Aww, 2021). Screenshots by author on 4 December 2023.

9.3.3 Intangible Touch

Attempts to touch actual objects are often used to accentuate virtual influencers' more-than-human-ness. For example, virtual influencers' limbs will sometimes disappear upon contact with an actual object. This trope of transparent touch is closely tied with wired skin but—like in Imma's Watson's X soda commercial (see Figure 9.13)—is prompted specifically by a moment of contact between the virtual influencer and the product they are promoting.

Whereas Imma's encounter with the product initiates a supercharged connection, in cases of transparent touch, the character's limb disappears on contact. The limb is often represented in outline or by a grid of light, so objects in the background become visible "through" where flesh should be. This offers an update to Campbell's (2010) analysis of how "technologized bodies" (n.p.) are represented in early 2000s advertising campaigns: Campbell observes that "a recurring convention in contemporary depictions of the skin of technologized bodies is its *translucency*" (n.p., original emphasis), listing several campaigns where "skin assumes a translucent ethereality" (n.p). However, unlike the examples cited by Campbell, where translucency revealed metallic "tendrils of activity pulsating beneath the surface" (n.p.), virtual influencers' transparent skin shows that, at most, their bodies are composed of grids of light, revealing the characters to be immaterial and incorporeal, and their bodies composed of digital data.

Touching physical objects is also complicated by levitation. Objects are often shown hovering above the virtual influencer's outstretched or open-palmed hand, an effect akin to two magnets repelled by their shared poles. For instance, in the second image from AYAYI's Make Up For Ever collaboration (see Figure 9.12), she reaches for a bottle of foundation which floats above her hand, and slightly out of reach. Tendrils of a fine white grid weave through AYAYI's outstretched fingers, as though reaching upwards towards the bottle, but are ultimately unable to bridge the distance between the two.

Both of these examples of intangible touch are particularly compelling because they subvert one of advertising's long-standing visual conventions: what Goffman (1976) calls "the feminine touch", wherein female models are often "pictured using their fingers and hands to trace the outlines of an object or to cradle it or to caress its surface" (p. 29). Goffman highlights that unlike a "utilitarian kind" of touch that "grasps, manipulates, or holds" (p. 29), the feminine touch is used to convey a product's desirability. In Chapter 7, I argued that selfies showing virtual influencers holding actual objects was an example of *ontological labour*, fostering an impression of agency and autonomy for the characters by encouraging the perception that they can interact with the world around them. A different effect is achieved in multi-channel marketing campaigns where intangible touch occurs. Here, the

characters accentuate their more-than-human identity through their inability to make contact with actual products, merging with or repelling them, often in ways that accentuate their shared technological composition.

9.3.4 Glitching

The digital composition of virtual influencers' bodies is also highlighted by the use of glitch effects. As screen studies scholar Sean Cubitt (2017) explains, glitching is a “visual and auditory [effect] of interruptions of electronic signals” (p. 299). In the context of digital screens, the glitch “appears as a pixelated stammer occupying part or all of the screen” (p. 299). When utilised by virtual influencers, glitching renders their body or movements momentarily pixelated and visually fragmented, with the scattered pixels reassembling into a recognisable body soon thereafter. Glitches are often used as transitions in short videos produced for virtual influencers' commercial partnerships, but their effect can also be more

Figure 9.14: The left hand of Japanese virtual influencer Imma glitches (left) and recovers (right) as she fastens the zipper on her windbreaker in a video announcing her collaboration with Tommy Jeans. Source: Instagram (Tommy Jeans [@tommyjeans], 2022), video screenshots by author on 3 December 2023.

localised. For example, Figure 9.14 shows a glitch effect across two stills from a video announcing a collaboration between Japanese virtual influencer Imma and American clothing brand Tommy Jeans. As Imma zips up her Tommy Jeans windbreaker, her left hand glitches, scattering in a series of small boxes. Both the movement of her arm and the glitch effect draw the viewer's eye in and upwards, bringing their gaze closer to the embroidered logo on her chest, and making the locus of branding more conspicuous (cf. Abidin, 2016a). Notably, in this example, the glitch effect only affects the body of the virtual influencer: the objects, buildings, and people around Imma retain their solidity, a contrast that draws additional attention to the character as ontologically unlike her surroundings.

9.3.5 Augmented Senses

Finally, virtual influencers are often portrayed with augmented senses, suggesting the capacity of their digital bodies to perceive and interact with a world in ways that exceed human abilities. Senses seemingly innate for virtual influencers are those humans would require technological assistance to attain. A popular example is augmented vision, such as that promised by wearable lenses like Google Glass (see Arthur, 2013) and Meta's Orion AR glasses (Meta, 2024), which overlay the world with dynamic and interactive digital displays. Virtual influencers are often shown encountering translucent digital interfaces, as shown in Figure 9.13 and Figure 9.15, reminiscent of those from the film *Minority Report* (Spielberg, 2002). Though these translucent interfaces are technically located outside of the virtual influencers' bodies, the characters' ability to perceive them without donning specialist hardware casts them as an expression of bodily capabilities. Campbell (2007) highlights the use of images generated by x-rays, "night vision, thermal vision and satellite imaging" (p. 11) in magazine advertisements to suggest that a deeper understanding of the world is only accessible using technology; technology enables us to move beyond "gazing on a deceptive 'surface' with human eyes, [to instead] penetrating its depths through a technological lens" (p. 11). Virtual influencers are often portrayed as innately capable of this technological insight. Indeed, it is both the characters' ability to perceive these translucent screens as well as their ability to interact with them—manipulating the information they display, much the like "gestural interfaces" associated with technologies like the Nintendo Wii (Guga, 2015a, p. 49)—that attests to their more-than-human capabilities.

Figure 9.15: Stills from Chinese virtual influencer Ling's collaboration with AVON skincare: Ling moves a floating proton ball to a translucent digital interface for scientific analysis. Source: Xiaohongshu (翎__LING, 2022), video screengrabs by author on 15 September 2024.

In these examples, both characters encounter translucent screens upon entering sleek, white-walled laboratories: Imma, in her commercial for Watson's X soda (see Figure 9.13), and Ling, in an online video promoting a face serum from global cosmetics brand AVON (see Figure 9.15). The "sterilised, bright environment of the laboratory" (N. Campbell et al., 2006, p. 349) is especially fitting for Ling's advertisement, given the longstanding efforts of the cosmetics industry to "suggest beauty is a scientific process which can be achieved only through assessments and treatments" (M. E. Adams, 2002, p. 282; see also N. Campbell, 2007). The characters are dressed almost identically, wearing high-neck white tops with matching chest cut-outs, a twist on the white lab coats typically associated with such settings. Both screens utilise what Campbell (2007) describes as the "[a]estheticization of [i]nformation" (p. 12), referring to the pervasive use of "[m]athematical and scientific symbology [in] popular culture as a visual device", wherein "their aesthetic shape and form is more important than their content" (pp. 12-13). In Figure 9.13 and Figure 9.15, progress bars, percentages, and even a rotating DNA strand are used as scientific signifiers, which "carry little value in terms of what they actually denote", and instead superficially represent "technical information [to give] the impression of high levels of specialisation and expertise" (p. 13).

In both ads, the translucent interfaces that the characters can see display information about the products' composition. In Imma's commercial for Watson's X soda, the screen has widgets showing the alcohol content of the soda to be 0.5%, along with zero sugar, fat, and calories. In Ling's video for AVON's ANEW facial serum, rotating diagrams of molecular structures appear on the interface after Ling guides a floating, glowing sphere towards it. On-screen captions identify the two diagrams as types of collagens, with counters ticking upwards to represent their percentage as the serum's active ingredients. The scientific insight afforded by these translucent screens recalls discourses around data's empowering qualities, connected to the popularity of technologies that promise users improved "self-awareness" and the ability to "optimize or improve their lives" through continual self-tracking (Lupton, 2016, p. 106). Here, the characters' more-than-human senses enable them to access the products' nutritional and scientific details, facilitating a more empowered mode of consumption. Imma's collaboration with Watson's extended this idea through the design of an augmented reality (AR) experience to accompany her television commercial, unlocked by scanning a QR code on a Watson's soda can featuring the character's face (see Figure 9.16). Completing the on-screen prompts allowed the customer to see an animated rendering of the soda's nutritional information circling their own can using their smartphone camera and screen. In this example, Imma's augmented vision was proffered to Watson's actual customers, offering them a first-hand experience of the data-driven insights unlocked

Figure 9.16: The face of Japanese virtual influencer Imma on a limited run of Watson's Soda X cans. On right, we see the QR code that can be scanned to unlock an AR experience themed after the commercial. Source: Facebook (imma [@imma.official], 2021), screengrabs by author on 16 October 2024.

Stills from the Watson's Soda X AR experience unlocked by scanning the can's QR code. First, a promotional image of Imma holding a Watson's can appears (left); the user is asked which flavour of soda they want to scan (centre-left); then, after allowing camera permissions, the user scans the can, and Imma appears, asking the user to slide the alcohol percentage bar (centre-right); once completed, Imma disappears (glitching away), and augmented text with key nutritional information appears around the can in the live camera feed (right). Source: YouTube (KIVISENSE, 2022), video screengrabs by author 20 September 2024.

by her more-than-human body.

This section identified five examples of an iconography of virtuality used in virtual influencers' multi-channel marketing campaigns to make their bodies recognisable as more-than-human. I highlighted how these tropes draw attention to the immateriality of virtual influencers' bodies and accentuate their datafied composition. I posit that this visual lexicon,

which draws from several decades of popular and visual culture, is especially useful when the success of the partnership relies on the characters being recognised as virtual entities, given the meaning this extends to the brands and products the characters endorse.

9.4 Halo of Innovation

When virtual influencers are made recognisable as virtual entities, they activate what I call a *halo of innovation* for the brands and products they promote. Aligned with Hall's (1980/2005) proposal that "[e]very visual sign in advertising connotes a quality, situation, value or inference, which is present as an implication or implied meaning" (p. 123), I argue that the characters' virtuality is used to connote innovation, imbuing the brand or product with ideas of technological originality, novelty, and superiority. The phrase "halo of innovation" intentionally evokes the concept of the "halo effect" (Nisbett & Wilson, 1977), briefly introduced in Chapter 7. In marketing and business studies, the "halo effect" has been used to explain how consumer attitudes towards new products are influenced by customers' previous brand experiences (e.g. Leuthesser et al., 1995). More recently, it has also been applied in influencer scholarship to describe how followers' affective intensity towards influencers attach to the products and brands they promote (Abidin, 2016a). The type of halo effect discussed in Chapter 7—called a "halo of realness" (Drenten & Brooks, 2020, p. 3)—involved symbolic meaning being extended by actual (human) companions to virtual influencers. Here, I argue that the halo is extended by the virtual influencers towards the brands and products they promote.

This process recalls what cultural anthropologist Grant McCracken (1989) theorised as "meaning transfer" (p. 313). Discussing the value of celebrity endorsers in advertising, McCracken defines meaning transfer as "an association [...] fashioned between the cultural meanings of the celebrity [...] and the endorsed product" (p. 313). A similar effect was noted by cultural studies scholar Judith Williamson in her book *Decoding Advertisements* (1978/2000). Writing about a print advertisement for Chanel No. 5 perfume starring French actress Catherine Deneuve, Williamson observes:

The ad is using another already existing mythological language or sign system, and appropriating a relationship that exists in our system between signifier (Catherine Deneuve) and signified (glamour, beauty) to speak of its product in terms of the same relationship; so that the perfume can be substituted for Catherine Deneuve's face and can also be made to signify glamour and beauty. (p. 25)

McCracken and Williamson both draw attention to the symbolic interaction between three

variables: a product/brand, a celebrity endorser, and the cultural associations attached to that celebrity. As illustrated in section 9.1.2, virtual influencers may likewise be selected to endorse a product or brand to imbue it with the personality or sense of style for which they are known. However, I argue that when the virtual-ness of a virtual influencer is brought to the fore, and made the character's most distinguishing attribute, it is the cultural associations of virtuality that are transferred to the products and brands they endorse.

I suggest that at the time this research was conducted, the "implication or implied meaning" (Hall, 1980/2005, p. 123) of virtuality was innovation. Although the term "innovation" is ubiquitous as a buzzword today (see Vinsel & Russell, 2020), in a historical review spanning more than seven centuries, sociologist Benoît Godin (2016) highlights that the positive connotations of the term "innovation" only began to outweigh its originally negative meaning as of the mid-twentieth century. After World War II, Godin writes, "international organizations and governments" began to "embrace innovation as a solution to economic problems and international competitiveness", and a tool for achieving "economic *growth*" and "industrial *leadership*" (p. 27, original emphasis). In contemporary use, innovation can be understood as

originality, in three senses. First, innovation is [an intentional] difference, departure [from an established order]. Second, innovation is creativity in the sense of *combination*. Innovation recombines ideas or things in a new way [...] Third, innovation refers to origin, namely being the *first* to originate (initiate) or use a new practice. (p. 29, original emphasis)

In advertising discourse, the term "innovation" is often used to refer to technological advancement. For example, Johnson (2007) highlights that the use of language "like 'new,' 'advanced,' 'innovative,' and 'breakthrough' [...] not only appropriates technology, but also explicitly uses it for seeking the consumer's interest in state of the art products" (p. 170). In the start-up culture of San Francisco's Silicon Valley (see Chapter 10), innovation is additionally imbued with ideas of disruption and profitability, reflected in the term's definition as "the *profitable* combination of new or existing knowledge, resources and/or technologies" (Vinsel & Russell, 2020, p. 10, emphasis added). I suggest that virtual influencers' halo of innovation draws from all of these definitions: variously imbuing the products and brands they promote with associations of originality, creativity, advancement, disruption, and superiority.

These associations with innovation are encouraged by virtual influencers' producers. For example, in an interview with South Korean newspaper *The Chosun Daily*, Baek Seung-

yeop, creator of Korean virtual influencer Rozy, suggests that partnering with “*virtual humans can give the [impression] of being ahead of the curve*”¹² (as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 10).

In other cases, innovation figures as a central theme for the promotional messaging surrounding the partnership. In a magazine interview “with” Singaporean virtual influencer Rae, the character suggests that luxury automotive brand Audi “recognised the natural synergy between my persona as a digital native, and how the Audi A3 integrates with our digital lives through connectivity and innovation” (as cited in Lean, 2022, para. 11). In another example, as part of a partnership with Penfolds wine, Rae explains in an Instagram post, “Innovation is in my DNA, and in @Penfolds” (RAE 蕊 [@here.is.rae], 2022b, para. 1).

Both examples accentuate a shared sense of innovation between Rae and the products she promotes, justifying her “fit” as an endorser. Curiously, this kind of rhetoric positioning may also activate a reverse halo effect. In such instances, the evident innovation of a particular product or brand may be extended towards the virtual influencer endorser, augmenting the audience’s perception of the character as technologically advanced, original, and superior.

Virtual influencers’ halo of innovation offers an explanation for why marketers view them as well-suited to promoting technology-related products, as well as “more innovative products [and] sectors such as beauty or luxury” (Allal-Chérif et al., 2024, p. 9). Indeed, marketing professionals describe partnering with virtual influencers as a way “to remain at the forefront of innovation” (Baudier et al., 2023, p. 5; see also Allal-Chérif et al., 2024). An article in *CNN Business* likewise suggests that partnering with virtual influencers is “a way for companies to show they’re creative and on the cutting edge of technology” (Yurieff, 2018, n.p.). Other marketers underscore associations with originality. In an interview with Hund (2023), a pseudonymous marketing manager “Beth” explains that partnering with American virtual influencer Lil Miquela “embodies this idea of thinking outside the box, doing things a little bit differently, which is what our brand is all about. [...] [W]e’re always pushing those boundaries of technology and digital” (as cited in Hund, 2023, p. 114). However, to unlock this halo of innovation, the virtual influencer must be recognised as a virtual entity: an iconography of virtuality is a popular method of ensuring this meaning is effectively conveyed.

¹² Italicised text machine translated with Google Translate. Original text: “가상 인간을 쓰면 앞서간다는 이미지를 줄 수 있어서 그런지 패션, 자동차, 친환경, 디지털 경영에 관심있는 기업 등에서 연락이 많이 옵니다” (Baek, as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 10).

9.5 Summary

In this chapter, I analysed how the digital bodies of virtual influencers are used as sites of commercial display and promotion. Although virtual influencers will often reproduce the commercial templates favoured by human influencers, including #OOTDs, PR unboxing, and brand event posts, a distinctive visual language is often evoked in large multi-channel marketing campaigns that are likely to reach audiences unfamiliar with the characters. I proposed the term *iconography of virtuality* to describe the amalgam of tropes, aesthetics, and effects from visual and popular culture that are used in these campaigns to immediately conjure ideas of virtuality. I outlined five examples used to mark virtual influencers' bodies as more-than-human: weightlessness, wired skin, intangible touch, glitching, and augmented senses. These examples each bring the characters' virtuality to the fore, enabling them to extend the associations of their virtuality to the brands and products they endorse, in a symbolic "meaning transfer" (McCracken, 1989, p. 313) I describe as a *halo of innovation*. Once activated, the halo of innovation encourages the perception of the brands and products promoted by virtual influencers as being on the forefront of technological experimentation. In Chapter 10, I look to those who directly profit from perceptions of virtual influencers as technologically advanced, original, and superior: the companies who specialise in creating and managing virtual influencers.

Industry Storytelling

10.1 Introduction

In the previous three chapters, I analysed the practices of virtual influencers, examining the different layers of their social media content. In this chapter, I reflect on the industry that emerged around these characters, and the efforts of its stakeholders to legitimate their work as valuable and profitable. Like other media and cultural industries, the virtual influencer industry comprises a variety of stakeholders financially invested in virtual influencers for “commercial purposes, meaning the distribution of goods or services in a marketplace for accumulation of profit” (Hilmes, 2008, p. 22). Producer estimates about the size of this industry vary, ranging from between ~~¥~~2.4 trillion (USD\$1.8 billion; Chae, 2022) and USD\$6 billion as of 2022 (Feiler, 2022). At the core of this industry are virtual influencer agencies: companies that specialise in the production and management of virtual influencers, and rely on virtual influencers as their primary source of income. These companies have grown in number since the late 2010s, particularly following the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in the early 2020s, when virtual influencers’ immaterial bodies were viewed as particularly advantageous (see Chapter 3). Virtual influencer agencies regularly interact and collaborate with advertising agencies, software developers, social media platforms, and investment firms, as discussed throughout this chapter.

In this chapter, I chart how the virtual influencer industry has evolved from one that deliberately obscures its own labour to one demanding recognition for its achievements. The chapter follows a loose chronology, tracing the expansion of the virtual influencer industry from 2016—the year in which the first virtual influencer agency, Brud, was formally established—to mid-2022, when my data collection concluded. I focus on three stories told by industry stakeholders (behind the curtain, change-seekers, and return to the human), highlighting patterns in how the producers of virtual influencers have sought to evidence the relevance and value not only of their characters, but of their own labour. I conclude the chapter by reflecting on the industry’s storytelling efforts during the cultural moment in which my data collection concluded: amid fervent hype over what was being hailed as the next generation of the web, the “metaverse”. Excitement about the metaverse emboldened the virtual influencer industry to loudly lay claim to their accomplishments, emphasising the specialist human labour involved behind-the-scenes. The recognition they sought was a clear precursor for their response to the mainstream debut of GenAI (generative artificial intelligence) tools, a trend which accelerated in the months directly following my fieldwork, as

discussed in this thesis' conclusion (see Chapter 11).

10.1.1 Virtual Influencer Agencies

Situated within the broader network of businesses comprising the virtual influencer industry (see Berryman et al., 2024), this chapter focuses on virtual influencer agencies: businesses that specialise in the production of virtual influencers, and have commercialised producing and/or managing virtual influencers as a product or service. Examples of virtual influencer agencies include Aww Inc. and 1sec Inc. (Tokyo), Ranmai Technology (燃麦科技, Shanghai), Next Generation Culture Media (次世文化传媒有限公司, Beijing), LOCUS-X (née Sidus Studio X, Seoul), and SIA (Bangkok). The term “virtual influencer agency”—featured in industry commentary (e.g. Baklanov, 2020; Sokolov, 2019), and sometimes adopted by the companies themselves (e.g. SIA Bangkok, which describes itself as ‘Thailand’s first virtual influencer agency’; see Mei, 2021)—is particularly useful for conceptualising the work of these businesses, given its allusion to the holistic management style popularised by East Asia’s idol agencies or *jimusho* (事務所). As discussed in Chapter 2, *jimusho* “create performers [...] from scratch and control every aspect of the performers’ public image and career” (Marx, 2012, p. 36). Likewise, virtual influencer agencies usually develop portfolios of one or more proprietary characters who they commit to managing as virtual influencers. Emulating talent management companies in other media industries, including idols (see Marx, 2012) as well as influencers (see Abidin, 2018a; X. Han, 2021), virtual influencer agencies oversee the career progression of their talent, brokering brand deals, managing public relations, facilitating community management, and closely monitoring social media performance. As communications scholar Jingyan Elaine Yuan (2025) highlights, virtual influencer production is “a niche in existing practices of the celebrity industry, rather than reinventing its production and dissemination structure” (p. 320).

Virtual influencer agencies tend to have small teams, ranging from 5 to 30 employees. They are organised for efficiency, usually comprised of employees with highly specialised technical and creative skills who contribute to different stages of character production or management (see Chapter 6). As the companies grow and mature, they may bring on a broader range of roles typical of traditional talent agencies, including “content marketers, data analysts, music managers [...] publicists, and more” (Drenten & Brooks, 2020, p. 2). Based on analysis of job vacancy postings, common roles at virtual influencer agencies include 3D and CG artists, animators, riggers, technical directors, and computer engineers; graphic designers and editors; directors, creators, producers, and project managers; stylists and 3D fashion designers; and social media managers and copywriters. Resumes and

professional portfolios of previous employees reveal that many virtual influencer agencies recruit freelance talent to complement the expertise of a core team for creative projects or commercial partnerships of greater scope and complexity.

To complement revenue generated through commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9), virtual influencer agencies productise their expertise in character design to create bespoke characters for other companies or brands. Costs for these characters range widely: as of 2019, a bespoke, fully 3D character reportedly cost around USD\$30,000 (Bernstein, 2019), whereas by 2022, it was reportedly “over RMB 3 million” (USD\$470,000) “without even calculating the time and human resources needed for production” (Dao Insights, 2022, para. 9). Along these same lines, virtual influencer agencies like Aww Inc. have successfully licensed proprietary animation technology to other aspiring agencies, including Ranmai Technology in China (Aww Inc., 2021b), and Sour Bangkok in Thailand (Aww Inc., 2021c), as well as making specialised production equipment available to hire, including 3D photography rigs and the use of virtual production studios (*Studio*, n.d.).

Despite the significant scholarly attention paid towards virtual influencers, little attention has so far been directed towards the industry that surrounds them. Research from marketing and business studies tends to examine the virtual influencer industry indirectly, offering perspectives from marketing and advertising professionals (e.g. Allal-Chérif et al., 2024; Baudier et al., 2023; Jauffret & Aubrun, 2022; Moustakas et al., 2020; Oliveira & Chimenti, 2021), but rarely individuals with first-hand experience working with virtual influencers. Only a handful of scholarly sources reference the companies that populate the virtual influencer industry (e.g. Baumgarth et al., 2021; Berryman et al., 2024; Parke, 2024), or include the voices of those who have personally contributed to or collaborated with it (e.g. Atherton, 2023; Guthrie, 2020; Hund, 2023; Yuan, 2025). These sit alongside a body of emergent critical analyses of the labour involved in creating virtual influencers (Hughes, 2023), including commentary on the human stand-ins and body doubles whose identities are effaced in post-production (e.g. Z. Li, 2023, 2024; Sobande, 2021b). This chapter intervenes in this knowledge gap, outlining the configuration of the virtual influencer industry, and mapping the promotional rhetoric its stakeholders have used over time to attract interest and investment in their characters, and recognition for their labour.

10.1.2 Start-Up Culture

Many virtual influencer agencies share the cultures, priorities, and funding models of technology startups. The label “startup” describes businesses that “are generally young, self-funded and/or reliant on venture capital, offering ‘disruptive’ products rather than existing

ones” (Davis, 2024, p. 2549). Originating in San Francisco’s Silicon Valley, startup culture has spread globally, with international startup hubs often adopting localised nicknames, including “Silicon Wadi” in Israel and “Silicon Cape” in South Africa (Davis, 2024; Marwick, 2018a). Innovation and entrepreneurship scholar Joseph C. Picken (2017) identifies four stages in the lifecycle of successful startups. This begins with an initial challenge to “define and validate the business concept”, which typically occurs within an “informal, loosely structured, and fluid” business setting (p. 588). The startup will then undergo a period of “transition”, where the founder must “complete the development of the offering, establish a solid foundation, and position the organization for rapid scaling” (p. 588). A period of rapid growth (known as “scaling”; see section 10.2) is the third phase, and it is here that “[c]onsistent profitability is required to provide a return for investors and fund the drive for market leadership” (p. 588). The final stage, and the driving ambition for the three earlier stages, is a “successful exit (by IPO [Initial Public Offering], private sale, merger, or acquisition)”, which is “usually required to harvest the value accumulated by the venture for the benefit of the entrepreneur and investors” (p. 588, original emphasis). At the time of my fieldwork, most of the virtual influencer agencies discussed in this chapter could be plotted against the first and second stages, working to formalise their business offerings and positioning, and preparing for imminent investment and growth.

Like startups, the virtual influencer industry “rel[ies] on venture capital as a major source of funds” (Yuan, 2025, p. 319). Virtual influencer agencies regularly publicise announcements of new investors and successful venture funding rounds, celebrating these milestones in social media posts and press releases. Several high-profile venture capital firms have invested in virtual influencer agencies, including global venture capital firm Sequoia Capital, who invested in Los Angeles-based virtual influencer agency Brud (see Shieber, 2018), as well as Shanghai-based technology start-up Xmov (魔法), co-creators of Chinese virtual influencer Ling (see Pandaily, 2022). Other virtual influencer agencies have received funding from technology conglomerates like Korea’s Naver (see Cha & Koo, 2021), corporate venture firms like Porsche Ventures (see Mayr-Uhlmann, 2022), and video game developers like China’s NetEase (see Jiangcheng, 2021).

The history of virtual influencer agencies, and its connections with startup culture, begins with Brud, creators of American virtual influencer Lil Miquela. Co-founded in 2016 by Trevor McFedries and Sara DeCou, early trade coverage positioned the company as a “Los Angeles-based startup” (e.g. Shieber, 2018). Interviews with McFedries point to how startup logics influenced Brud’s early internal approach. In a virtual fireside chat hosted by NYC Media Lab, Trevor McFedries credits his past employment at music streaming service

Spotify for teaching him about “modern software development” (NYC Media Lab, 2020, 4:54), and how “the lean start-up works” (NYC Media Lab, 2020, 4:53). McFedries’ mention of the “lean start-up” is significant, using vocabulary “pulled directly from Silicon Valley playbooks” (Davis, 2024, p. 2558): popularised by a book of the same name (Ries, 2011), the “lean start-up” describes a business methodology which “favors experimentation over elaborate planning, customer feedback over intuition, and iterative design over traditional ‘big design up front’ development” (Blank, 2013, n.p.). Instead of waiting until a product is perfected and fully-formed to release it to the public, prototypes are entered into the market as quickly as possible, using feedback from users and consumers to direct where and how the product is improved. In a lean startup, a product is incrementally and iteratively built, with each new update released (or “shipped”) to customers an opportunity for further feedback, refinement, and development. As McFedries describes on *DeFi Podcast*, the lean methodology was a stark change from his previous professional experience working at a record label:

I think my experience in music was, like, spend five years and \$5 million making a thing, and just push it off a cliff and hope people like it; versus software, making this product, shipping, and talking to customers, iterating into a thing people love. (Russo, 2020, 6:59)

Drawn from his experience at Spotify, the lean methodology shaped how McFedries approached designing and evolving Miquela, with audience responses used to inform decisions on the path her content would follow. In an interview with *a16z Podcast*, McFedries explains how the team at Brud adjusted Miquela’s narrative storyline based on audience feedback, recalling, “We had, like, data science teams every week bringing back what worked and what didn’t, building taxonomies of images and videos” (S. Smith, 2023, 16:11). In the same podcast, Brud’s former Chief Technical Officer Isaac Bratzel describes the “really quick feedback loop” (S. Smith, 2023, 16:49) facilitated by the social media platforms on which Lil Miquela was active, describing how:

when you're starting out, you have the ability to, like, do this quick thing and get that reaction immediately, and [then] steer that character and her narrative to the fans that are engaging [...] which then informs what you're going to do when you start to do more medium- and long-form stuff. (S. Smith, 2023, 16:53)

Brud’s approach was a success. Trade press reported the company reached a valuation of USD\$125 million in 2019 (Shieber, 2019) and USD\$144 million in 2021 (Blake, 2021), the same year it was acquired by Canadian startup DapperLabs for an undisclosed amount

(Matney, 2021). Brud's significant financial accomplishments and their pioneering storytelling approach set a benchmark and a template for many virtual influencer agencies that followed.

10.1.3 Storytelling

Production studies scholar John Caldwell (2006) remarks that media industries “invest tremendous resources in producing knowledge” about themselves (p. 110), manufacturing “over-arching metaphors, figurative paradigms, and master narratives that constantly frame and re-frame” the work they do (p. 116). Described by media studies scholar Nicholas Bestor (2016) as “promotional rhetoric” (p. 171), these stories are rarely objective or transparent, but instead form part of an effort to “sell” ideas of technologies, labour, and accomplishments to different audiences (see also O'Connor, 2004). I argue that this storytelling work is especially important for virtual influencer agencies given their affinities to tech startups. Research on nascent startups, which originates in sociology, organisation studies, and scholarship on cultural entrepreneurship, emphasises the role of storytelling for creating “accounts that explain, rationalize, and promote a new venture to reduce the uncertainty typically associated with entrepreneurship”, especially in lieu of “proven track records, obvious asset value, and [demonstrated] profitability” (Lounsbury & Glynn, 2001, p. 546). Conceptualised in sociology as a process of “legitimacy building” (see O'Connor, 2004), storytelling is one way that a startup can “insert itself into a social arena by conveying who the venture is[,] what it does”, and, importantly, why it is worthy of investor support (Gegenhuber & Naderer, 2019, p. 151). These stories are often modified “as circumstances change” (O'Connor, 2004, p. 106), evolving to re-engage and reassure key audiences of existing and potential investors over time (Lounsbury & Glynn, 2001).

Against this conceptual background, the storytelling efforts I analyse in this chapter offer insight into how virtual influencer agencies use stories to appeal to current and prospective investors (Burnett et al., 2009; Martens et al., 2007). Establishing “pragmatic legitimacy, meaning the security of confidence to win capital” is crucial for these companies to become financially viable (O'Connor, 2004, p. 121). Producing virtual influencers requires significant upfront investment, given the resource and technical skill necessary for creating an original character (see Chapter 6). According to Chen Yan, CEO of Beijing Next Generation Culture Media, the internal costs of creating a new virtual influencer can exceed one million RMB (USD\$155,000, as cited in Dao Insights, 2022, para. 8). Moreover, interviews with producers suggest anywhere between three, 12, or 18 months are required for ideation and production before the characters are ready to debut (e.g. Florian, 2021; pigabyte, 2021; 강경희, 2021). For most virtual influencer agencies, this is an unavoidable cost: proprietary characters are important for serving as “proof-of-concepts” for the company's technical capabilities (see

section 10.2). Virtual influencer agencies thus operate on a “high sunk” cost model similar to those adopted by film and animation studios, which likewise involve high initial investment to fuel new projects and productions (Lotz, 2019, p. 339). In lieu of cinema tickets or distribution arrangements, as in these other industries, virtual influencer agencies seek to recuperate these costs with investor funding.

In addition to character production, agencies must also plan to cover ongoing costs associated with content creation, which is necessary for building and maintaining the character’s social media following (Keegan, 2022). For example, in an interview with South Korean newspaper *The Chosun Daily*, Baek Seung-yeop, CEO of LOCUS-X, explains that his virtual influencer Rozy uploads one to two posts to Instagram each week, with each post taking around two days to produce (강경희, 2021). The costs of this ongoing social media activity accumulate quickly: *Business Insider Netherlands* reported that within the first six months, Rotterdam-based virtual influencer Esther Olofsson had absorbed an estimated €50,000 (USD\$55,000) worth of labour from the team at business-to-business (B2B) social media agency RAUWcc (Boerop, 2020). In another example, a profile on Brud’s co-founder Trevor McFedries on the blog of global venture capital firm Sequoia Capital describes the precariousness of the company’s future just a year after Lil Miquela’s debut:

McFedries was almost broke. He’d run through his savings while pitching his big idea to 60 investors who’d gone cold, and one who’d given him a few hundred thousand dollars, which was quickly disappearing into keeping his big idea alive. (Keeley, 2022, para. 1)

Suggesting an undercurrent of “individualized risk, rapid change, insecurity, and precariousness” in the virtual influencer industry (Davis, 2024, p. 2560), in an interview with local newspaper *Beijing News*, Chen claimed that “more than 90% of domestic virtual idol developers [in China] are struggling to profit” (as cited in Dao Insights, 2022, para. 8). While no sources were cited to support Chen’s claim, given the “high sunk” (Lotz, 2019, p. 339) cost model on which virtual influencer agencies tend to operate, it does seem reasonable that profitability would be a particular challenge. In this light, external investment and venture funding are central not only to the longevity and growth of virtual influencer agencies, but also to their immediate viability. As this chapter highlights, to appeal to investors, virtual influencer agencies have pursued several storytelling approaches, moving from efforts to deliberately obscure the extent and nature of human labour to showcasing the humans behind the characters as a core focus of their appeal.

10.2 Behind the Curtain

In its infancy, stories about the virtual influencer industry were often as tightly controlled as those of its characters. Early contributors to the virtual influencer industry tended to maintain an air of mystique, keeping their identities a secret (Oliveira & Chimenti, 2021; Robinson, 2020). This approach was pioneered by Brud who, for almost two years, operated in relative anonymity. In April 2016, Miquela began uploading a stream of photos, memes, and selfies to Instagram and Facebook, seemingly ignoring the hundreds of comments her posts soon attracted questioning her computer-generated appearance (S. Brennan, 2016). Bloggers, YouTube creators, and journalists from major press outlets—including *HuffPost* (Cherrington, 2016), *The Independent* (Oppenheim, 2016), and *Washington Post* (Dewey, 2016)—soon began to speculate about Miquela’s identity. In a rare media appearance on the *Influence* podcast, Miquela’s co-creator Sara DeCou laughs as she remembers the response to Miquela at the time: “What is this? How does it exist? Why does it exist? Is it real?” (Bradfield, 2020, 8:24). Although an email address appeared in Miquela’s early Instagram bio, requests for interviews were rarely answered (e.g. Oppenheim, 2016), and other times flatly declined (e.g. Dewey, 2016). Miquela’s first press “interview” was in *Vogue* magazine in August 2017, almost a year and a half after the creation of her Instagram account (E. Chang, 2017). Even then, details about her creators were omitted: the *Vogue* article describes Miquela as “a computer simulation of a person, designed for reasons that remain unclear, by people who would very seriously prefer to remain unknown” (E. Chang, 2017, n.p.). The story continued even as Miquela became a more active press commentator: six months later, when Miquela was interviewed by *The Business of Fashion* magazine, the article began by noting that Miquela “refuses to reveal who is actually behind her meticulously created, yet clearly artificial persona” (Morency, 2018, n.p.).

In the background, Brud was preparing to become a character in Miquela’s narrative, building out their own fictitious backstory as a “technology start-up specializing in artificial intelligence and robotics” (Sauers, 2019, n.p.). They obscured their identity as Miquela’s creators until the dramatic narrative reveal in April 2018: Miquela was actually a “robot”, “saved” by Brud from an evil (fictitious) corporation called Cain Intelligence (Petrarca, 2018a). Although the events were carefully orchestrated, Brud initially sought to minimise their role in the drama (Shieber, 2018). McFedries purportedly texted a reporter that the company suspected “some redditor [sic] idiots” were behind the hacking of Miquela’s Instagram account (as cited in Shieber, 2018, n.p.), a statement which the journalist coolly clarified “was a lie” (Shieber, 2018, n.p.). According to screenshots from the *Wayback Machine*, at the time of the hack, Brud’s website comprised just a red company logo and a

paragraph written in large serif font, describing the company as:

a group of Los Angeles based problem solvers specializing in robotics, artificial intelligence and their applications to media businesses. We've built a team of people interested in leveraging technology to better things as eloquently as possible. (Brud, 2018a, n.p.)

The timing of Brud's reveal was strategic. Just five days after Miquela's account was "hacked", technology news platform *TechCrunch* announced that Brud had received an estimated USD\$6 million in a recent funding round from "some of the biggest names in venture capital investment" (Shieber, 2018, n.p.). The sequence of events suggests an incompatibility between the theatrics of secrecy and the necessity of attribution for business growth: to receive financial support, and attract the interest of other potential investors, Brud was eventually forced make their identity widely known.

Brud's newfound prominence as Lil Miquela's creators did not translate to transparency. Press referenced unanswered interview requests (e.g. Hill, 2019), and denied opportunities to comment (e.g. Clein, 2019; Koh & Wells, 2018; Yurieff, 2018) as Brud continued to control what was known about the company's inner workings, sustaining what can be conceptualised as a "pnambic" narrative. An acronym originating in computer engineering, the adjective "pnambic" ("pay no attention to the man behind the curtain") describes "a process or function whose apparent operations are wholly or partially falsified," especially those which require human input to "simulate or replace" a computerised outcome (Klein, 1981, p. 112). The phrase is borrowed from the 1939 film *The Wizard of Oz* (Fleming, 1939), in which the eponymous Wizard maintains an illusion of power and grandeur using pyrotechnics, optical illusions, and a voice-changing microphone, operated from a small booth surrounded by green curtains. When his deception is discovered, revealing him to be an ordinary man without magical powers, the Wizard attempts to hide himself from view, crying, "Pay no attention to the man behind the curtain!" The term has since been applied to discussions of cinematic digital effects (e.g. North, 2014) to describe the audience's focus on visual spectacle, which elides scrutiny of the labour, technologies, and sometimes rudimentary mechanisms on which the on-screen illusions rely. Similar arguments have been made for technologies such as large language models or LLMs, wherein details about the technology's design and the human labour required behind-the-scenes are omitted to "hide the techniques of the illusion" about how it actually works (Nagy & Neff, 2024, p. 4946; see also Leaver & Srdarov, 2023). For Brud, maintaining a pnambic narrative was likely assisted by the elaborate public relations (PR) strategy and multiple firms enlisted to help tell Lil Miquela's story (Hsu, 2019; *Lil' Miquela*, n.d.).

Brud's pnambic narrative was also furthered by the company's repeated emphasis on robotics, which featured prominently both in Lil Miquela's fictional narrative, and in Brud's initial self-description as a company "specializing in robotics [and] artificial intelligence" (Brud, 2018a, n.p.). This obscured the nature of Brud's internal capabilities, misdirecting onlookers and commentators about the company's actual focus and business model. Only some reporters interrogated the company's claims: *Wall Street Journal* reported that "people familiar with the startup say it isn't primarily a technology company" (Koh & Wells, 2018, n.p.), while an editorial in *Cultured Magazine* highlighted that, after a review of the company's records, "Brud holds no patents in AI, robotics, or related fields" (Sauers, 2019, n.p.). Confusion was also stoked by how known employees represented themselves online: several Brud employees used "opaque" job titles on LinkedIn, with McFedries identified as Brud's "Head of Compassion" and DeCou as "Chief of Stuff" (Clein, 2019, n.p.). The secrecy extended even to the addresses used for Brud's business registration, which obscured actual glimpses of their workplace and workers from view. As reported by the *New York Times*, Brud's "California business registration lists an address in Silver Lake blocked by thick vegetation, but workers, who must sign nondisclosure agreements, said the company actually operates out of downtown Los Angeles" (Hsu, 2019, n.p.). The confusion surrounding the company's internal operations and capabilities was likely beneficial for Brud; given the significant funding invested into robotics and AI ventures during the 2010s (see Rowley, 2018; Su, 2019; Tabatabai, 2019), being viewed as associated with these emergent technologies may have augmented the company's appeal to potential investors.

As Brud's efforts illustrate, remaining behind-the-curtain gives the characters an opportunity to accumulate their own audiences, press interest, and brand opportunities, without visible interventions by their creators. The characters thus stand as prototypes both for their producers' technical capabilities, and as evidence of the potential value the characters are capable of accruing in future. In their research into how nascent startups demonstrate their potential value to investors, economists David B. Audretsch, Werner Bönnte, and Prashanth Mahagaonkar (2012) underscore the use of prototypes "to signal the actual *feasibility* of the proposed project", which may improve prospective investors' "assessment of the commercial potential of the new venture" (p. 1408, original emphasis). Aligned with this logic, the Sequoia Capital blog profile of McFedries describes how his ambition to "reinvent celebrity" was made tangible for a prospective investor by the "solid proof-of-concept" of Lil Miquela (Keeley, 2022, n.p.). The inclination to use characters as prototypes also appears to have shaped the launch approach of other virtual influencers, even several years after the reveal of Brud's identity. For instance, for the first three months after she debuted, Korean virtual influencer Rozy acknowledged neither her virtuality nor her producers. According to her

creator Baek Seung-yeop:

*When Rozy opened her Instagram account in August last year, she didn't even reveal that she was a [virtual influencer]. In just three months, she gained 13,000 followers [...] It wasn't until December 30th last year that she revealed that she is a [virtual influencer].*¹³ (as cited in 강경희, 2021, para. 6)

In an interview with *Kanto* magazine, a PR representative for LOCUS-X adds more context to the strategy for Rozy's Instagram debut, explaining, "We thought Rozy should be recognized as an influencer first, not as a digital model, and we are more than proud that Rozy met that goal" (Han, as cited in Austria, 2021, n.p.). As such testimonies highlight, remaining behind-the-curtain allows virtual influencer agencies to evidence the appeal of their characters for audiences and brands on their own merits, with the characters serving as in-market prototypes to "assure potential investors of the future value of their innovative nascent venture" (Audretsch et al., 2012, p. 1409).

However, without a sense of the individuals responsible for the character's production, or the nature of their work (see Chapter 6), virtual influencers obscure the significant time, resource, and labour involved in their production. Communications scholar Matt Stahl (2011) describes this dynamic as "virtual labor", referring to the "performative labor that *appears* to be performed by an individual, but which is actually the result of a division of labor incorporating creative and technical workers, intellectual property, and high-tech equipment" (p. 4, original emphasis). Focusing on "the power relations between creative performers and their cultural industry employers" (p. 4), Stahl elaborates that virtual labour is:

a dynamic *political* arrangement whereby the managerially driven concealment or displacement of creative and technical cultural workers [...] is correlated to the intensified alienation of those workers, the diminution of their power to claim credit, remuneration, proprietorship [or] autonomy. (p. 4, original emphasis)

The impact of this arrangement is minimised by the attention directed towards what Stahl refers to as "virtual laborers", or "the visible, audible, and nonagentic avatars of hidden ensembles of visual effects technology and divisions of cultural industry labor" (p. 18): in this

¹³ Italicised text machine-translated with Google Translate and Naver Papago, with minor amendments for clarity. Original text: "작년 8월 로지의 인스타그램 계정을 열 때 가상 인간이라는 사실도 밝히지 않았습니다. [...] 3개월 만에 팔로어가 1만3000명 됐습니다. 작년 12월 30일에야 가상 인간임을 공개했지요." (Baek, qtd. in 강경희, 2021, n.p.).

case, the virtual influencers themselves.

Upholding this dynamic of “virtual labor” (Stahl, 2011), and rendering the identities and contributions of the essential creative workers behind-the-scenes of virtual influencers invisible, encourages perceptions that the characters have more autonomy than they actually do, recalling the discussion of *ontological labour* in Chapter 7. In lieu of detailing the specialised, intensive process of content creation (see Chapter 6), the dynamics of virtual labour exacerbate perceptions of the characters’ technological advancement, which may appeal to prospective investors. In a blog post titled “Why I’d Invest in a Robot Teenager”, UK-based venture capitalist Clara Lindh Bergendorff (2019) describes a conversation with a fellow investor about how “many [venture capitalists] are allergic to content studios and hence startups pitch their [virtual influencers] as AI creations despite the manual process through which they currently come to life” (n.p.). She quotes a colleague, “Jared”, from New York City startup incubator Betaworks, who posits that:

the big opportunity comes when you get truly AI-generated characters. No company has this yet. But if you’re able to make a character from scratch without human input — that’s big dollars. (as cited in Bergendorff, 2019, para. 7)

These quotes allude to the concept of “scaling”, a specific stage in the startup lifecycle in which “the entrepreneur must add significant resources and leverage processes and partnerships [...] in order to achieve competitive scale and establish sustainable market leadership” (Picken, 2017, p. 588). As research on startups underscores, success is “predicated on the ability to scale and the potential for very high growth” (Marwick, 2018a, p. 315). Indeed, McFedries has described his ambitions for Miquela as part of an effort to create “scalable celebrity”, a term reflecting his interest in how public figures are “able to touch people all over the world and shape the way they behave” (S. Smith, 2023, 46:00). For McFedries, human celebrities offer a blueprint that technology can enhance; a scalable celebrity has the potential to “touch [the lives of] billions [of people] in parallel” (NYC Media Lab, 2020, 6:04). Talking to the *Masters of Scale* podcast, McFedries recounts the thinking that first inspired Miquela:

To me, it was like, man, I would love to find a way to take all of that appeal and all that charisma and all of that dynamism [of celebrity] and entangle that with [a] scalable backend, such that we could tell stories in real time to people in Guam, to people in the Philippines, to people in China, [to] people in Brazil, and do a lot of good really quickly. (Hoffman, 2020, 17:54)

However, at the time of Lil Miquela's debut, the technology did not match McFedries' ambitions to scale the characters' stories in "real time" (Hoffman, 2020, 18:04). In a different podcast interview, former Brud employee Bratzel remembered:

[In the e]arly days, we were really small, and it was crazy fun. We were trying to do things that were just, like, *way beyond* what the team of that size and experience level [...] should be trying to do. (S. Smith, 2023, 16:38)

Exemplifying the dynamics of virtual labour involved in maintaining a pnanbic narrative, McFedries' ambitions to deliver a "scalable celebrity" required a creative team tirelessly working behind-the-scenes to maintain the illusion that Lil Miquela could be anywhere and anything.

A similar story of technological advancement was used by Singaporean virtual influencer Rae, whose creative team remained behind-the-curtain for more than two years (Min, 2022). From Rae's first post in October 2020 until December 2022, her production was attributed to a pseudonymous entity known as "Team Rae" (e.g. Ewe, 2021; Ganesan & Wong, 2022); press releases concluded her biography with the disclaimer that "Rae's origins remain a mystery" (e.g. HereisRae.com, 2021, n.p.). This pnanbic narrative was explicitly used to characterise Rae as an example of AI. In an interview "with" *Female* magazine, Rae describes herself as "created by CGI (computer-generated imagery) technology and powered by AI (artificial intelligence)" (as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 3), later clarifying, "I'm powered by AI and deep learning technology (an AI function that imitates the workings of the human brain), which means I'm constantly evolving" (as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 9). For both Team Rae and Brud, downplaying the amount of labour involved in their characters' production (cf. Newlands, 2021) was utilised to encourage perceptions of the characters as advanced technological innovations. However, alongside efforts to accentuate her technological sophistication, Rae would also acknowledge that she was a product of a multi-person creative team. In the same *Female* interview in which she claims to be "powered by AI and deep learning technology", Rae also states, "I'm not a one-woman show. Unlike me, my team of real-world creators need to eat" (as cited in Chai, 2021, para. 11). It was only in December 2022 that the identity of Rae's creators were revealed to be CapitaLand, a large commercial developer in Singapore, along with their "innovation partners" at creative agency Dentsu Singapore, who eventually inherited the character's ownership rights (dentsu, 2022; Min, 2022). Rae's case belies a tension that would reappear for virtual influencer agencies seeking external investment: by accentuating the characters as artificially intelligent, there was no need to recognise or compensate the human-powered technological or creative innovations of her behind-the-scenes producers.

While Brud's behind-the-curtain approach was followed by some virtual influencer agencies, others laid louder claims to their characters. Aww Inc., a virtual influencer agency launched in 2019 under the banner of Tokyo-based 3D animation studio ModelingCafe, immediately identified themselves as the creators of virtual influencer Imma (Akiyoshi, 2020; CafeGroup Inc. [@CafeGroup.CG], 2018). 1sec Inc., launched in 2019 with the debut of fellow Japanese virtual influencer Liam Nikuro, likewise made their involvement known from the outset, with press releases describing them as "a venture company planning and developing virtual human[s]" (1sec Inc., 2019, n.p.). However, even after the names of their agencies were published, details of their operations were still obscured. As one industry commentator observed, "[c]ompanies that produce these characters rarely speak about the hows, the whats and the whys. We don't know what their strategies are, and little financial data is available to support the claims of their profitability" (Sokolov, 2019, n.p.). As interest in virtual influencers grew, press and trade articles continued to feature pseudonyms (e.g. Begum, 2020; M. Miller, 2019), requests for anonymity (e.g. Deighton, 2020), and allusions to non-disclosure agreements (NDAs) legally prohibiting discussions of insider knowledge (e.g. Bradfield, 2020; Hsu, 2019; Petrarca, 2018b). As another journalist wrote, "though it can be unclear *who* exactly" is behind virtual influencers, "you can be sure that *someone* is making money off of these 'people'" (Hill, 2019, n.p., original emphasis). Changing perceptions of the financial motivations for creating virtual influencers became a key focus, and motivated the industry's second story.

10.3 Change-Seekers

Once a company's identity was known, a new storytelling strategy was necessary. Select employees (usually the founders) of virtual influencer agencies began to appear as commentators in press and trade coverage (Z. Li, 2024; Yuan, 2025), using these opportunities to emphasise the capacity for virtual influencers to bring about positive social change. Indeed, as a telling example, at various times, the founders of both Brud and Aww Inc. have claimed their company mission is "to change the world for the better" (Clein, 2019, n.p.; Feiler, 2022, n.p.). This rhetoric aligns with the transformative logics often embraced by startups: as sociologist Jenny L. Davis (2024) explains, startups are rhetorically positioned as "disruptors' that (re)organize societies and usher in the future" (p. 2555), and often attribute the motivations for their work to the opportunity to achieve social good.

This has been a particularly prominent storytelling strategy for Brud, whose flagship character Lil Miquela has long been positioned as a "change-seeking robot". As strategic communications scholar Elena Block and PR practitioner Rob Lovegrove (2021) note, Lil

Miquela serves as “a communication platform that not only promotes brands and lifestyles, but that also raises money for charity organizations, marginalized communities, and civil rights causes” (p. 2), including Black Girls Code, Black Lives Matter, and the Los Angeles wildfire relief (D. Fowler, 2018; Newell-Hanson, 2017). In an industry presentation, Kara Weber, who became Brud’s CEO in 2020, describes Lil Miquela as “a social activist and a true change-seeker who’s using her large and growing platform to bring awareness and drive impact on behalf of marginalized communities and social justice” (Radicale Labs, 2020, 8:58). McFedries has elsewhere explained his intent to use Lil Miquela’s “platform to amplify voices that needed it” by “shar[ing] information about important subjects or themes, books that were important, and also handing it off to different creators and people that [...] had something to say” (Hoffman, 2020, 37:18). By September 2018, six months after their attachment to Miquela was publicised, Brud’s website was updated to redirect to a plain Google doc, describing the company as a “transmedia studio that creates digital character driven story worlds”, seeking to “create a more tolerant world by leveraging *cultural understanding* and *technology*” (Brud, 2018b, original emphasis).

Other virtual influencer agencies have likewise accentuated their desire to have a positive impact on society. Echoing a pattern in the human influencer industry, in which terms like “creator” are favoured over “influencer” (Bishop, 2021b; see Chapter 4), many virtual influencer agencies utilise these intentions to distance their characters from the commercial connotations of the term “influencer”. For instance, speaking to the *South China Morning Post*, Miyaji “Genie” Hirokuni, founder of virtual influencer agency 1sec Inc., explains that his virtual influencer Liam Nikuro was “not meant to be a typical influencer – he wasn’t created for marketing purposes, but as a fresh new voice to help combat cyberbullying in Japan” (Begum, 2020, para. 13). The sentiment is echoed by Brud’s Weber, who explains in an industry presentation that Brud does not “think of Miquela as an ‘influencer’; we really think of her as becoming an iconic voice of her generation” (Radicale Labs, 2020, 21:04). Such quotes reflect a prevailing view of “influencers” as “fundamentally commercialized, with any creativity and agency drained from their practice” (Bishop, 2021b, n.p.), despite the non-commercial messages these individuals are also skilled at communicating (Hutchinson, 2020). Likewise, when asked about future aspirations for Korean virtual influencer Rozy, Sidus Studio X director Kim Jin-soo explained, “*Rather than [only] commercial activities using Rozy, we plan to focus on activities that can exert a positive social influence, such as zero-waste campaigns or upcycling fashion that minimize waste emissions in daily life*”¹⁴ (as

¹⁴ Italicised text machine-translated with Google Translate and Naver Papago. Slight amendments for clarity.

cited in 황순민, 2021, para. 15). However, these ambitions do not preclude the characters from undertaking commercial activities: in the same week as Sidus Studio X's Kim described the company's ambitions to transcend Rozy's marketing utilities (see 황순민, 2021), he was also quoted in the *Korea JoongAng Daily* newspaper discussing the more than 100 partnership requests Rozy had received from brands, and her annual earnings of ₩1 billion (USD\$857,000; see Ahn & Lee, 2021). To reconcile this apparent contradiction, we can view this rhetorical focus on the social good the characters are capable of achieving as a reframing of their commercial activities as a necessary factor to deliver an improved social future.

A cynical interpretation of this emphasis on social good would be to view it as a public relations strategy, combatting a growing sense of public discomfort with the knowledge that companies have developed these characters for profit. By 2018, critical writing had appeared on the ethics of virtual influencers, focusing especially producers' ability to profit from the characters "fashionable" (Brachtendorf, 2022) identities without the need to compensate people who actually share these identities. These editorials carried headlines like "Exploring Mixed Race Identity in CGI Influencers" (S. Phillips, 2018), "Who Actually Benefits When Digital Queerness Gets Trendy?" (Holzer, 2019), and "This is Fucky: Simulated Influencers are Turning Identity into a Form of Currency" (Boshier, 2020). Journalist Emmeline Clein (2019) remains sceptical of Brud's company drive for social good, pointing out that this follows the script of Silicon Valley startups such as "Facebook [and] Twitter", allowing them "to claim they can make the world a better place and make untold sums at the same time" (n.p.). Along the same lines, fellow journalist Rosa Boshier (2020) describes virtual influencers as "moneymaking vessels that bend to the will of corporate interests in a world full of new-age cultural posturing" (n.p.). Against such critiques, the focus on social good offers a way of deflecting from the agencies' clear financial motives and activities.

10.4 Return to the Human

The third story told by the virtual influencer industry coincided with the beginning of this project in early 2021, and continued as a dominant narrative throughout my fieldwork over the first half of 2022. During data collection, I observed that stakeholders from the virtual

Original text: "로지를 활용한 상업적인 활동보다는 일상 속 쓰레기 배출을 최소화하는 제로 웨이스트 캠페인이나 업사이클링 패션 등 사회적으로 선한 영향력을 발휘할 수 있는 활동에 집중할 계획입니다" (Kim, qtd. in 황순민, 2021, n.p.).

influencer industry were more regularly accepting press and podcast interviews, and detailing their creative contributions and technical abilities across LinkedIn posts, company websites and online portfolios, and presentations at industry events. These various media formats were used to showcase the *mechanisms of virtuality* involved in creating virtual influencers, offering details about the technical processes, skills, and complexity required for the characters' back-end production and management. Examples of these mechanisms ranged from details about the specific software used or the amount of time required to create each post (see Chapter 6); to screenshots or screen recordings of works-in-progress or final renderings in digital animation software (see Figure 10.1); and the identities of the individuals involved behind-the-scenes, often including information about their professional credentials (e.g. Ogata, 2019). These efforts foregrounded the human creativity and talent behind virtual influencers, and reflected the industry's growing desire for recognition and compensation for the labour that had been obfuscated by their earlier mystique.

A useful point of comparison for these texts are the "making of" paratexts (Gray, 2010) released to promote (or packaged alongside the release of) Hollywood films, especially for films that utilise cutting-edge digital effects (VFX). In a reversal of the pambic narrative discussed earlier in this chapter, these promotional paratexts showcase the extensive behind-the-scenes labour, creativity, and artistry involved in bringing spectacular VFX to screen. As media studies scholar Jonathan Gray (2010) highlights, such paratexts can be used to "proffer 'proper interpretations,' [...] setting up pre-decodings [...] to subtly inflect the public understanding of" a media text, and also "assign *value* to a text, situating it as a product and/or as a work of art" (p. 81, original emphasis). It is common for these behind-the-scenes paratexts to feature time-lapses of the production process, or to overlay a single shot with layers representing the various steps involved in creating the final image (see Figure 10.1). Screen studies scholar Tanine Allison (2011) explains the contradictory logic of acquainting media audiences with the behind-the-scenes processes involved in creating on-screen effects, writing that:

unlike common wisdom that would tell a filmmaker to hide the production apparatus so as to avoid dispelling the fantasy of the image on screen [...] it is only by educating spectators about the production process that you can gain their willingness to believe in the image. (p. 336)

Figure 10.1: Mexico City-based advertising agency Freelander Studio post a stop-motion video showcasing the creative steps involved in creating a post for their virtual influencer, Maria. Source: Instagram (Freelander Studio [@freelanderstudio], 2022), video screengrabs by author on 19 July 2025.

While both Gray and Allison discuss how paratexts can affect the interpretations of general media audiences, their arguments also apply to the perspectives of potential investors. Specifically, by exposing the behind-the-scenes mechanisms involved in producing what is virtual about virtual influencers, virtual influencer producers educate potential investors about the value and extent of their artistic and creative talent that would be otherwise obscured as “virtual labor” (Stahl, 2011).

This shifted promotional approach occurred against the backdrop of the COVID-19 pandemic (see Chapter 3), a period marked by accelerated interest in the potential of the so-called “metaverse”. As Yuan (2025) describes, during the global lockdowns and stay-in-

place orders that marked the early COVID-19 pandemic, “people moved most of their economic and social activities to virtual spaces and spent significant time in immersive, social, digital worlds” (p. 319). The term “metaverse” was first coined in Neal Stephenson’s (1992) sci-fi novel *Snow Crash*, and gained momentum in 2020 as businesses scrambled to prepare for a possible future in which digital technologies would serve not only as tools but also the setting of day-to-day life. By 2021, the term was dominating industry discourse, as well as investor interest (Kunthara, 2021). Although the term was only loosely defined (Caminiti, 2022), it had become closely associated with technologies such as virtual worlds and virtual reality. In an evangelical op-ed for *Wired* magazine, David Baszucki (2021), CEO and founder of gaming platform Roblox, wrote: “The Metaverse is arguably as big a shift in online communication as the telephone or the internet. Within the next few decades its applications will exceed our wildest imaginations” (n.p.).

The industry buzz around the metaverse reached popular audiences in late 2021, when Mark Zuckerberg announced that his company, Facebook, would be rebranding to Meta. Hailing the metaverse as “the next frontier in connecting people” (Zuckerberg, 2021, n.p.), Zuckerberg shared the announcement at an industry event:

To reflect who we are and what we hope to build, I am proud to announce that starting today, our company is now Meta. Our mission remains the same — it’s still about bringing people together. [...] From now on, we’re going to be metaverse-first, not Facebook-first. (as cited in Matney & Hatmaker, 2021, para. 4)

In a founder’s letter published to the company’s blog, Zuckerberg (2021) explains the metaverse as “an embodied internet” where “you’ll be able to do almost anything you can imagine[, like] get[ting] together with friends and family, work, learn, play, shop, [and] create” (n.p.). This experience would unfold across multiple technologies, with metaverse inhabitants using “augmented reality glasses to stay present in the physical world, virtual reality to be fully immersed, and phones and computers to jump in from existing platforms” (n.p.). The company’s rebranding clearly signalled Zuckerberg’s conviction in the future of social networking being virtual, and his desire to position his company at the helm of its creation. This was a logical next step given the company’s established interest in virtual reality (VR) technology, tracing back to Zuckerberg’s acquisition of VR company Oculus in 2014 (Saker & Frith, 2022), and the launch of Reality Labs, “an internal [...] research and development division” dedicated to strengthening the company’s capabilities in VR, AR (augmented reality), and AI, in 2018 (Egliston & Carter, 2024, p. 4337).

Zuckerberg was far from alone in his desire to claim ownership of the metaverse. The

companies behind leading online games such as Roblox, Minecraft, and Fortnite, which had figured as key sites of experimentation during the pandemic for virtual experiences, were already considered prototypes of the kind of interconnected and interoperable online environments the metaverse could one day comprise. Alongside game developers, tech juggernauts like Apple, ByteDance, Microsoft, Tencent, and NetEase also publicised their interest in building the metaverse, with several making multi-billion-dollar acquisitions to further their competitive advantage (Kovach, 2022; Nan, 2022; Williams, 2021). In late 2021, a report from *Bloomberg* estimated that the potential revenue for the metaverse could reach USD\$800 billion by 2024 (Kanterman & Naidu, 2021).

The rise of the metaverse, envisioned as a virtual reality in which everyday internet users would experience all facets of daily life as digital avatars, presented a clear opportunity for virtual influencers, and seemed set to precipitate the industry's imminent growth. In an online interview, Becky Owens, then Meta's Head of Creator Innovation and Solutions, described virtual influencers as "a fast-rising phenomenon" which "as we head towards the metaverse [...] is only set to grow" (as cited in Travers, 2022, para. 7). Likewise, Nick Baklanov, analyst at social media measurement agency HypeAuditor, told press that, with their immaterial bodies and native affinity to digital environments, virtual influencers were "better suited to the role of the first inhabitants of the metaverse than anyone else" (as cited in AFP News Agency, 2021, para. 11). Many virtual influencers played into the hype, using "Metaverse" as the geotag for their posts (see Chapter 8), or branding themselves as "metaverse humans" (see Leesa-Nguansuk, 2021) or "meta-humans" ('China Launches First "Meta-Human" Virtual Influencer', 2021) to align their virtual identity with visions of the metaverse. It was thus at the same time as industry and investor interest was valorising the virtual that the character's producers shifted their storytelling approach, taking steps to make the human contributors and labour involved in creating virtual influencers increasingly visible.

I argue that this emphasis on the human labour behind virtual influencers was a strategic effort to validate and inflate the financial valuations of virtual influencer agencies by accentuating the specialist labour involved therein. Specifically, the producers of virtual influencers—many of whom had not received public recognition for their work—sought to affirm their credentials as prospective architects and contributors to the future metaverse. A clear example occurred between April and early August 2021, when the Brud Instagram account uploaded 18 posts with short video profiles introducing 19 of their company staff. In a knowing wink, the series claimed to "pull back the curtain on Brud" (e.g. Brud [@brud.fyi], 2021). While photos showing members of the Brud team had been published before (e.g. Brud [@brud.fyi], 2020)—dating back as far as the May 2018 version of the Brud website

(see Brud, 2018a)—those who appeared in them were rarely identified. A unique quality of this Instagram series was its emphasis on naming Brud’s employees, highlighting their roles, and giving those employees space to create content which not only showcased the type of work they did at Brud, but also to speak about what the company and its characters meant to them. These videos shared an emphasis on what anthropologist and media studies scholar Hirofumi Katsuno (2011) describes in his study of robot builders and watchers in Japan, as a sense of “recuperated humanity”, highlighting the ways in which working on (or as the Brud employees often put it, “with”) Miquela had allowed them to “reconnect [to] themselves and others, establish [...] intimate relations and reassert [...] their own humanity” (p. 108). A blog post “authored” by Miquela in mid-2021 mirrored Brud’s newfound shift to highlighting human talent, writing, “I am as much singular as I am the sum of all the talented creatives, technologists, writers, CG masterminds, and production wizards at Brud that help me tell my story” (Miquela, 2021, n.p.).

Once again, Brud’s storytelling efforts appear carefully orchestrated and strategically timed: the “pulling back the curtain” series concluded two months prior to the announcement of Brud’s successful acquisition by Dapper Labs (Matney, 2021). As they courted this buyer, and likely continued negotiations behind closed doors, Brud showcased the talent, specialties, and capabilities of their team in a dramatic reversal of their initial pnaibic strategy. By highlighting the human talent responsible for Miquela’s success, Brud accentuated the value of their internal capabilities, and reminded prospective investors, as Dentsu Singapore’s Chief Creative Officer Stan Lim put it in an interview with marketing blog *Campaign Brief Asia*, of the “real need for businesses and brands to remain human in a technology-driven world” (as cited in Shaw, 2022, para. 7).

10.5 Summary

In this chapter, I shifted focus from analysing the characters to charting the storytelling efforts of the businesses that produce them. I narrowed my view to discuss three key stories told by stakeholders from the virtual influencer industry to shape how the characters are perceived, especially by potential partners and investors. Although the virtual influencer industry originally committed to maintaining an air of mystique, obscuring traces of their own involvement and labour, and encouraging perceptions of the characters’ autonomy and advancement, these theatrics were always at odds with the need to claim credit for their characters to gain access to investor funding. Once their identities were known, industry stakeholders pivoted to accentuating virtual influencers’ capacity to deliver social good, downplaying their commercial goals in lieu of their characters’ support of social causes. As

broader tech and investment industries' interest turned to the metaverse, and the potential of VR technologies and virtual worlds to serve as the setting for everyday life, virtual influencers seemed well-positioned to capitalise on the accelerated investment into virtual experiences. At this juncture, the story changed once more, focusing on foregrounding the humans behind the virtual influencers, and showcasing *mechanisms of virtuality* that attested to the significant technical skill, creativity, and talent required to produce virtual influencers.

Together, this chapter presents an original account of the virtual influencer industry's "legitimacy building" efforts (O'Connor, 2004), not only mapping the increasing maturity of the industry, but also its participants' desire to be recognised and compensated for their creative labour. As I briefly discuss in the thesis' conclusion, the emphasis on the human essence of virtual influencers that arose in response to the metaverse hype foreshadowed the industry's response to the threat posed by GenAI tools like ChatGPT and Stable Diffusion in the months immediately following my data collection. These tools, which promised to generate outputs to text or image prompts practically instantaneously, added new urgency to the need to demonstrate the value of human creativity and insight behind virtual influencers.

Conclusion

11.1 Contributions

I began this project in February 2021, when only a handful of scholarly sources had referenced virtual influencers. Given the scarcity of research on the topic at the time, I designed this study around an intentionally broad research question, asking whether a meaningful difference exists between the practices of virtual influencers and the established practices of human influencers. I set out to examine how virtual influencers enacted this difference in their social media content, as well as how this difference was perceived and articulated by their producers and other industry stakeholders. To answer these questions, I conducted six months of data collection from January 2022 to early August 2022. Guided by digital ethnography (Markham, 2017, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012), I conducted non-participant observation of over 100 virtual influencers across 11 social media platforms; completed nine semi-structured online interviews with producers and industry stakeholders; and analysed a vast, multi-lingual corpus of documents relating to virtual influencers, including press articles, industry event and podcast recordings, and other promotional rhetoric produced by and about the emergent virtual influencer industry (see Chapter 5). My analysis was inductive and iterative, following the tenets of constructivist grounded theory (Charmaz, 2006), and paid particular attention to the visual (Highfield & Leaver, 2016), multimodal, and cross-platform (Pearce et al., 2020) nature of social media data.

In lieu of a substantive body of critical writing on virtual influencers when this project began, I referred to scholarship on human influencers to locate “sensitising concepts” to guide my analysis (Blumer, 1969, as cited in Charmaz, 2006, p. 16). Specifically, I analysed how virtual influencers engage with the visual templates (see Chapter 7), cultural identities (see Chapter 8), and commercial activities (see Chapter 9) codified by or associated with human influencers. A key finding was that literature on human influencers alone was not sufficient for analysing virtual influencers; a broader conceptual toolkit was necessary to make sense of the indicators and instances of virtuality that differentiate virtual influencers from their corporeal counterparts. Consequently, my analysis drew on a varied corpus of scholarship, spanning not only my home fields of media studies, film studies, social media studies, and celebrity studies, but also animation studies (see, especially, Chapter 6); art theory and performance studies (see Chapter 7); sociology and linguistics (see Chapter 8); and critical marketing and cultural studies (see Chapter 9). Chapter 10 took inspiration from sociology and production studies, mapping three stories told by the emergent virtual influencer industry

to appeal to current and prospective investors. In its final form, this thesis reflects a more ambitious project than I envisioned four years ago, presenting an ethnographically-grounded analysis of virtual influencers situated within a history of virtual celebrity, the cultures of visual social media platforms, and the influencer ecology writ large.

11.1.1 Aims & Objectives

The first aim of this project was to develop new theorisations to assist in explaining the role, function, and impact of virtual influencers within the broader influencer industry and visual social media landscape. To achieve this, I set out to map the scale, evolution, and practices of virtual influencers since 2018, when the term “virtual influencers” began appearing in popular discourse, to mid-2022, when my data collection concluded. As outlined in Chapter 5, I adopted digital ethnography (Markham, 2017, 2020; Postill & Pink, 2012) as my primary methodological approach to studying the characters, conducting six months of non-participant observation. To determine my field site, I “followed” the characters (cf. Postill, 2015), excavating their “multi-sited” (Marcus, 1995) and “networked” (Burrell, 2009) presence across 11 social media platforms, as well as dedicated messaging platforms, music streaming services, online marketplaces, video games, and virtual worlds. This cross-platform approach afforded insight into how the characters are made visible in algorithmically organised environments (see Chapter 7); use affordances to reach and address different audiences (see Chapter 8); and fulfil commercial partnerships (see Chapter 9).

I also set out to illuminate the behind-the-scenes mechanisms involved in the creation and management of virtual influencers, and the stakeholders involved in the emergent virtual influencer industry. Despite the many new businesses established to specialise in the characters’ production, and significant interest from venture capital in the industry’s expansion, this nascent industry has so far received little attention in scholarship. I thus set out to locate primary sources that could clarify the stakeholders, motivations, and configuration of this emergent industry. I contacted character accounts, producers, and key industry stakeholders with invitations to be interviewed for this project, and conducted nine semi-structured online interviews, totalling almost 700 minutes of recordings which I transcribed, coded, and analysed. I supplemented the rich insights from these producer interviews with additional analyses of 25 archived industry panels and presentations, and 33 podcast episodes featuring producers and industry stakeholders. Finally, I collected and analysed an array of other promotional rhetoric about the virtual influencer industry, including websites, blogs, social media posts, trade press, financial reports, and creative portfolios. I used these sources to detail the little-known technologies and processes involved in virtual influencers’ production (see Chapter 6), and to map the changing stories told by producers

to appeal to investors, which increasingly emphasised the specialised human labour, technologies, and time required to create virtual influencers (see Chapter 10).

The second aim of this research was to expand scholarly conversations around virtual influencers beyond the few examples and themes that dominated early English-language press and scholarship, offering a cross-cultural perspective of the phenomenon. Given the critiques of Anglocentricism often levied against the scholarly fields orienting this research—including media studies (see Thussu, 2009), internet studies (see Goggin & McLelland, 2009), celebrity studies (see Xu et al., 2021), as well as research on influencers and microcelebrity (see Mohamad, 2021)—I intentionally sought out case studies, pre-histories, scholarship, industry materials, and press from the Global South. In Chapter 5, I recounted the measures I took to locate virtual influencers from beyond the Global North. This included the use of cross-lingual hashtags, keywords, and local search engines, and the incorporation of "local apps" (Abidin et al., 2021) within my ethnographic field site, including Douyin (抖音), VK (short for *Vkontakte*, or “ВКонтакте”), Weibo (微博), and Xiaohongshu (小红书). Together, I accumulated a database of hundreds of virtual influencers varying in geographic distribution, popularity, and maturity. Most of the characters discussed in this thesis claim residence in East Asia (China, Japan, and Korea), Southeast Asia (Singapore and Thailand), Latin America (Brazil and Mexico), the Middle East (Israel and the United Arab Emirates), and Africa (Ghana and South Africa). By de-centering Western histories, case studies, platforms, and sources, this thesis paints a portrait of the virtual influencer phenomenon that better reflects its transnational distribution, accounting both for shared practices (e.g. Chapter 7) as well as local specificities (e.g. Chapter 8).

11.1.2 Key Findings

The opening chapters of this thesis introduced the reader to virtual influencers (see Chapter 1) and offered several origin stories for the phenomenon (see Chapter 2). It moved then to outlining the background (see Chapter 3), relevant literature (see Chapter 4), and methods and methodology (see Chapter 5) orienting this study. Chapters 6 to 10 were devoted to in-depth analysis of the findings of my ethnographic study.

Chapter 6 offered behind-the-scenes insight into the technologies, tools, and processes involved in creating and managing virtual influencers. I argued that this production pipeline is organised by a "digital first" design logic (Hutchinson, 2020), in which creative choices are shaped by a desire for social media visibility. Inspired by media and animation studies scholar Thomas LaMarre's (2009) concept of the "multiplanar image" (p. xxiii), I visualised the various steps of this pipeline according to three layers: the *model* (the visual

representation of the character), the *stage* (the environment in which the model is composited), and the *frame* (the social media platform to which the resulting content is published). In Chapters 7, 8, and 9, I demonstrated the utility of this schema as an analytic tool, organizing my discussion around each layer.

In Chapter 7, focusing on the *stage*, I explored how virtual influencers use selfies as sites for *staged liminality*: scenes where virtuality and actuality collide. I proposed that virtual influencers' interactions with actual places, people, and objects have an effect known in literary and film criticism as "defamiliarisation" (Spiegel, 2008), renewing interest in the unremarkable through the addition of something unfamiliar. I suggested this as an explanation for virtual influencers' ability to attract attention in the "attention economy" (Goldhaber, 1997) of visual social media, which is organised by a "logic of templatability" (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 214), and saturated by "formulaic, repeatable and simulatable aesthetics" (Leaver et al., 2020, p. 210). Finally, I argued that interactions with actuality present opportunities for what I call *ontological labour*, ascribing the characters a level of agency and sentience that they do not actually possess.

In Chapter 8, analysing the *frame*, I drew on theories of cultural commodification (Iwabuchi, 2002) to argue that virtual influencers are "stained" (Abidin & Brown, 2018, p. 9) with recognisable cultural identities that resonate with local audiences, and appeal to international audiences, brands, and investors. I explored how platform affordances are used to enframe (Spyer & Steedly, 2013) virtual influencers' visual content, anchoring it to cultural knowledge, histories, and routines, and networking it with markers of identity, local trends, and cultural meaning.

In Chapter 9, examining the *model*, I highlighted how virtual influencers deploy an *iconography of virtuality* drawn especially from science fiction film in their multi-channel marketing campaigns. Recurring visual tropes such as weightlessness, wired skin, intangible touch, glitching, and augmented senses are used to draw attention to the virtuality of virtual influencers' bodies, ensuring they are recognisably virtual even by audiences unfamiliar with the characters and their backstories. I argued that emphasising the characters' virtuality is central to the "meaning transfer" (McCracken, 1989) intended for their endorsements, activating what I call a *halo of innovation*, and extending associations of originality, creativity, advancement, disruption, and superiority to the brands and products they promote.

Finally, in Chapter 10, I considered the storytelling efforts of the virtual influencer industry. Examined within the context of startup culture, I analysed three stories used by producers to appeal to current and prospective investors. While the identities and labour of virtual

influencer producers were originally hidden behind the curtain, I noted their gradual efforts to make *mechanics of virtuality* increasingly visible, revealing the technical processes involved in their characters' creation, and drawing attention to the significant human input, oversight, and labour involved behind-the-scenes. I proposed that these stories reflect the industry's growing desire to be acknowledged and compensated for their labour, creativity, and skill, whether this be to gain opportunities to work on other virtual projects (e.g. the metaverse), to avoid erasure by emergent technologies that threaten to automate their work (see section 11.4), or to justify the financial investment necessary to make "virtual labour" (Stahl, 2011) sustainable.

Together, these chapters highlight that virtuality is both distinctive and generative: virtual objects and entities take on new significance and value once their virtuality is recognised. This value is heightened in the state of *ontological uncertainty* that characterises the contemporary social media landscape, where imperceptible processes and technologies of mediation complicate our ability to distinguish virtuality from actuality. Within this context, unabashed virtuality takes on a quality of exceptionalism. Take, for instance, the significant press attention dedicated to virtual influencers. What makes virtual influencers newsworthy is not the fact that they are any more (or even equally) "successful" than human influencers; indeed, there are numerous human influencers with more followers, and more lucrative brand partnerships. Instead, it is the characters' virtuality that renders their existence (see Chapter 7), social media debuts (see Chapter 8), and commercial activities (see Chapter 9) noteworthy. What this suggests is that when an object or entity is clearly identified as virtual, it becomes defined by (and celebrated for) being a virtual object. In a historical moment when actuality has become increasingly virtual, and virtuality has become increasingly actual (Miyake, 2022), objects that draw attention to their own virtuality are set apart, transcending critiques of being an ineffective or unconvincing emulation of the actual, precisely because they draw explicit attention to themselves as something else: *hyper-virtual*.

11.2 A Theory of Hyper-Virtuality

Grounded in the findings of this project, I propose a *theory of hyper-virtuality* to describe virtuality that embraces, promotes, and capitalises upon its own virtual-ness. Hyper-virtuality is distinct from virtuality which pretends to be, or wishes to be perceived as, actual; instead, it pursues distinction by drawing attention to the ways it is unlike the actual. Virtual influencers exemplify hyper-virtuality when their virtuality is made central to how audiences are encouraged to perceive them. As I will discuss, hyper-virtuality is often intentional, evoked so that virtual influencers benefit from the exceptionalism of the virtual. Hyper-

virtuality is useful because it allows us to transcend the definitional quandary of what is “real” and what is virtual. Instead, it focuses our attention on the ways that we come to know or recognise something as virtual; the production decisions and processes involved in creating virtual objects; and the effects and implications of (hyper-)virtuality’s encounters with the actual.

The term “hyper-virtuality” has appeared on rare occasion in previous scholarship, with several different applications. For example, “hypervirtuality” was used by sociologist Shanyang Zhao (2003) to describe forms of mediated co-presence in the early 2000s. Zhao differentiates between “hypervirtual copresence” and “hypervirtual telecopresence” (p. 449), depending on whether social interactions involve embodied or disembodied technologies. The term has also been applied in discussions of web design (e.g. Kalay & Marx, 2001) to describe a mode of design not tethered to natural law and order, as well as in urban design (e.g. Brusaporci et al., 2019) to describe the overlay of digital information on actual environments using technology like augmented reality. The closest affinity to the conceptualisation offered here is from a doctoral thesis by semiotician Kyle Davidson (2022), who evokes the concept of “hypervirtuality” in his discussion of the communicative practices and identity construction of two other examples of virtual beings, Vocaloids and vTubers (discussed in Chapters 2 and 3). However, Davidson’s use differs from my own insofar as he approaches “hypervirtuality” as the product of “virtual meaning from virtual symbols” (p. 21). By contrast, I conceptualise hyper-virtuality as virtuality which draws attention and derives value from its own virtual-ness.

My proposed definition of hyper-virtuality intersects with the conceptual terrain of several notable theorists. From the outset, the term “hyper-virtuality” invokes French philosopher Jean Baudrillard’s (1988/2001) concept of “hyperreality”, found in his critique of the postmodern condition. For Baudrillard, our increasing reliance on technology and forms of mediation have eroded the once clear border between fantasy and reality, precipitating a condition of hyperreality wherein the actual (or, in Baudrillard’s terms, “real”) has been replaced by simulations (or “simulacra”). Like others (e.g. Hayles, 1993), I do not share Baudrillard’s view that simulacra have become all-consuming, nor the postmodern pessimism for which his work has been critiqued (see A. King, 1998). Instead, my definition of hyper-virtuality relies upon a continued distinction between virtuality and actuality, even if what sociologist Christine Hine (2015) describes as our “embedded, embodied and everyday” experiences of technology render these concepts more a spectrum than a binary. Hyper-virtuality is not diminished by the blurriness between virtual and actual, but rather becomes important precisely because of the slippage between them; in this setting, hyper-

virtuality stands out for the unabashed and unambiguous attention it draws to itself.

11.2.1 Application

A theory of hyper-virtuality encourages us to think about how we come to know, recognise, and evaluate the virtual. This begins with production, and how technological and creative back-end processes manifest as indicators that alert us to an object or entity's virtuality. We may be shown something is virtual, be told something is virtual, or be shown how something is virtual. These indicators are not innate, nor ever-present; they can be deployed to different effect at different moments, and may even manifest differently in different cultural contexts. For example, the photorealistic virtual influencers popular in China (e.g. AYAYI or Ling) tend to minimise any visible traces of virtuality in the day-to-day content they upload to social media. However, when the characters appear in commercial campaigns, they overemphasise their virtuality using elaborate iconographic displays (see Chapter 9). In such cases, the exaggerated, iconographic virtuality of the characters initiates an aesthetic contrast with the photorealism of their appearance. This leads both to greater appreciation of the technical mastery of the character's animation, and mobilises the *halo of innovation* towards the products or brands they promote. While indicators can be strategically mobilised to make an object's virtuality more visible, as media reception theories have made clear (e.g. Hall, 1980/2005), there is no guarantee that the viewer will perceive or interpret them as producers intend.

Once an object is recognised as virtual, it becomes notable for being unlike the actual. A telling example is Korean virtual influencer Rozy's commercial partnership with local insurance provider ShinhanLife in July 2021. The partnership involved a long-form television commercial which depicted Rozy dancing in a variety of urban environments (신한라이프, 2021). Importantly, the campaign launch was relatively unexceptional until news of Rozy's virtuality spread among Korean netizens. On Twitter, a particularly prominent (now unavailable) tweet expressing shock at realising Rozy was a virtual influencer generated over six thousand retweets. On YouTube, the commercial accumulated more than ten million views as viewers returned to examine it for traces of virtuality missed on first viewing (Yoon, 2021). Citing a "positive reception from the public" (Shim, 2021, n.p.), Rozy's partnership with ShinhanLife was extended, and she appeared in a second television commercial for the company several months later (연합뉴스, 2022). In this instance, it was awareness of Rozy's virtuality that made the television commercial exceptional: once her performance was recognised and recast as that of a virtual influencer, the advertisement's value increased exponentially. It gained momentum in online discourse, raising the profile of Shinhan Life,

attracting thousands of new followers to Rozy’s Instagram profile, and hundreds of offers for future brand partnerships to her producers (H.-S. Ahn & Lee, 2021; 강경희, 2021). The case highlights that the exceptionalism of virtual objects or entities can be accessed only after they are recognised as virtual.

The theory of hyper-virtuality presents exciting opportunities for enriching scholarly discussions about virtual influencers, especially for popular concepts such as “authenticity”. Recent theoretical work—such as media production scholar Allan S. Taylor’s (2022) book *Authenticity as Performativity on Social Media*—argues that authenticity is performative, a contract initiated between an actor and an audience. From this perspective, authenticity is not an innate quality, and is instead bestowed by the judgement of a spectator. For virtual influencers, authenticity is often evoked in comparative analyses between virtual and human influencers (e.g. de Brito Silva et al., 2022; Jang et al., 2023). However, what these discussions tend to overlook is that such comparisons can only occur once we recognise a character as virtual, and therefore as distinct from the actual: hyper-virtuality precedes, and is a precondition, for evaluating virtual influencers’ authenticity. Likewise, we can only make judgements about how virtual influencers interact with the actual world (as in Chapter 7’s discussion of *ontological labour*) or commercial products (as in Chapter 9’s analysis of the *halo of innovation*) once we recognise the characters as virtual. Reflecting on the ways that virtuality is made known in particular circumstances, and to what effect, so that such judgements can be made presents a wide range of future possibilities.

11.2.2 Exceptions

The theory of hyper-virtuality resonates with the most popular, enduring, and commercially successful examples of virtual influencers discussed in this thesis. Using different indicators, these characters draw attention to their virtuality, and celebrate it as a point of differentiation and exceptionalism. They evoke hyper-virtuality to explore, experiment, and play with the slippage between virtuality and actuality. However, not all virtual influencers fit this model. Some characters do not embrace hyper-virtuality, and instead seek to obscure any indications of their virtuality. In such instances, it is the products of virtual production, rather than virtuality’s reflexive potential or promise, that figures as the main attraction. Digital tools are used to create what the producer’s fleshy body is not: a model whose appearance or aesthetic is perceived to resonate more with algorithms, audiences, and brands than their own (see Chapter 6). These models are not designed with the depth expected of fully-formed characters, but instead are valorised for being cheap, fast, and convenient. They might even form part of a get-rich-quick scheme. But these profiteering ambitions do not

tend to last long. The intensive and ongoing labour, resource, and skills required to create and manage a virtual influencer, as well as to accumulate the audiences that make them attractive to brands and investors, is at odds with the demotic promise of these tools. Indeed, the vast majority of virtual influencer accounts I encountered during my fieldwork were inactive (see also Baklanov, 2022; Y. Shin & Lee, 2023), leaving behind a graveyard of characters abandoned by their producers. Like any media object, motivations for the production of virtual influencers are varied and wide-ranging. The theory of hyper-virtuality works in cases where virtuality is viewed not only as an advantage, but as an opportunity for creative potential.

11.2.3 Implications

Although I ground my theory of hyper-virtuality in an analysis of virtual influencers, it is readily applied to other examples of virtual beings encountered online. Defining hyper-virtuality as virtuality that embraces and draws attention to its own virtual-ness, some future directions for exploring this theory include vTubers (virtual YouTubers), virtual idols, and generative AI artwork. For example, introduced in Chapter 3, vTubers typically appear as *anime*-esque characters, with stylised facial features and expressions choreographed using motion-capture and face-tracking technologies (H. Jiang et al., 2023; Suan, 2021a). Hyper-virtuality would be well-suited for analysing how vTubers embrace visible virtuality (see Gwillim-Thomas, 2023), for exploring how virtuality is imagined within the knowledge-sharing and technology development that characterises the vTuber community (H. Jiang et al., 2023), or moments of “virtual breaking” (M. Chen & Hu, 2025) which reveal the actual identity of the person behind the character. Another application could be for studying virtual idol groups like *æspa*, *PLAVE*, and *Eternity*, which are comprised of different combinations of human and virtual members. Hyper-virtuality could be used to analyse how the virtual members enact virtuality in “live” musical performances, whether as on-stage holograms, on-screen entities, or as figures only visible to viewers watching from home (see C.-Y. Kim & Han, 2020).

Finally, hyper-virtuality could also be useful for analysing the outputs of visual GenAI (generative artificial intelligence) tools such as DALL-E, Midjourney, and Stable Diffusion. For example, early images generated with these tools gained notoriety for the extra digits and distorted facial features of their human subjects (see Chayka, 2022; Dixit, 2023). These virtual traces necessitated an expanded repertoire for the “digital-forensic gaze” (Lavrence & Cambre, 2020) developed to detect traces of photo-manipulation and filtering in digital photography, becoming attuned to new visual clues that could help to identify AI-generated imagery. For some artists, these traces became inspiration; materials from which to create

new artwork commenting on the ethical quandaries of GenAI tools, or the limits of “artificial” creativity (see Sandry, 2022). These artworks, created by both human and machine, are in turn complicating the ability to distinguish between content created by humans and GenAI tools, exacerbating the current climate of ontological uncertainty, and suggesting that indicators of (hyper-)virtuality may need to assume an even more pronounced form in future.

11.3 Future Research

This project has sought to balance ethnographic insight into virtual influencers’ day-to-day social media presence with a broader view of the industry that surrounds them, their role in the visual social media landscape, and their continuation of a legacy of virtual celebrity spanning several decades, crossing industries, geographies, and temporalities. It is my hope that the depth and scope of these findings offer a productive foundation upon which future virtual influencer research may build. I briefly offer some recommendations for this research below.

An important direction for future scholarship is the labour of virtual influencers’ producers (Hughes, 2023), and the workplace conditions of the “proxy performers” who “stand in as if they are the virtual influencer to create its body and voice” (Z. Li, 2024, p. 79). Interviews with an ex-Brud employee suggest that producing a virtual influencer can have a significant mental toll: American playwright Max Wolf Friedlich worked at Brud for “about a year” (as cited in Nguyen, 2024, para. 16), writing Lil Miquela’s Instagram captions and responding to direct messages (Colyar, 2024). In interviews promoting his on-Broadway play *Job*, which tells the story of a mental breakdown of a content moderator working at a major social media platform, Friedlich describes the “incredibly adverse effect” running Lil Miquela’s account had “on [his] mental health” (as cited in D. King, 2024, paras 20–21). Further research into these effects is timely, given virtual influencers are increasingly being utilised as “virtual anchors” and livestream hosts, appearing in multi-hour video streams on platforms like Bilibili (哔哩哔哩) and e-commerce sites like Tmall (see Jarrett, 2023; Van Gastel, 2023). Although commentary is emerging on this topic (Cheon & Xu, 2024; Tobin & Zhou, 2022), research should more closely examine the experiences, perspectives, and safety of producers and proxy performers.

Virtual influencers’ representations of race, gender, disability, and sexuality is another wide-ranging focus for future research, building on critical studies already published in this area (e.g. Miyake, 2022; Neri, 2022). The importance of such research is underscored by the implication that, as discussed in Chapters 2 and 3, virtual influencers are commercially

desirable precisely because they lack the messiness, unpredictability, and fallibility of human influencers. This raises particular concerns when considering characters' alignment with identities and groups that are historically marginalised and undervalued in the creative industries. This includes virtual influencers that claim nonbinary or nonconforming gender identities, like Thailand's Bangkok Naughty Boo (see AFP News Agency, 2021), as well as the casting of virtual influencers in place of models of colour (see Z. Li, 2024; Neri, 2022; Sobande, 2021a, 2021b). Attention should also be paid to how virtual influencers represent disabilities, as in the case of Kami, the first virtual influencer with Down syndrome, created in 2022 in partnership with global advocacy organisation Down Syndrome International (Natividad, 2022). The characters' sexual identities offers another avenue for research, as are cases where virtual influencers have been ascribed human love interests, which especially in commercial contexts, have been critiqued as queerbaiting (see Holzer, 2019; Young, 2019).

Finally, recognising the linguistic limitations of this project, future scholarship would benefit from engaging with producers and industry stakeholders from predominantly non-English-speaking countries to understand the virtual influencers in the context of local markets, dynamics, and regulations. Communication scholar Jingyan Elaine Yuan's (2025) interviews with stakeholders in China's virtual idol industry, and information management scholar Oihab Allal-Chérif, business studies scholar Rosa Puertas, and applied statistician Patricia Carracedo's (2024) interviews with marketing professionals in Brazil are exciting examples of the insights such studies could unlock.

11.4 Looking Forward

In the months following the formal conclusion of my data collection in August 2022, the hype that had initially surrounded the metaverse faded (S. Rose, 2022). By late 2022, Meta—a company that had envisioned itself leading the creation of the metaverse, and so confident in this vision that the company's name was changed to reflect it—was reportedly losing more than USD\$1 billion per month on its metaverse division, Reality Labs (Partridge & Paul, 2022). Meta's proprietary virtual world app, *Horizon Worlds*, was attracting only 200,000 monthly users, less than half of its internal target (see Horwitz et al., 2022). In November 2022, amid a period of widespread redundancies in the tech industry, Meta laid off 11,000 employees—equating to 13% of the company's workforce—a decision outsiders attributed to Zuckerberg's struggle to convince investors of the metaverse's value, "while also grappling with a global economic slowdown and a decline in [revenue from] digital advertising" post-pandemic (Frenkel et al., 2022, n.p.).

In the metaverse's place, a new technology was gaining momentum: Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI). Beginning in January 2021, a range of AI image-generators were introduced to the market, facilitating the nearly instantaneous generation of images based on text prompts: OpenAI's DALL-E was released in January 2021 (OpenAI, 2021); Midjourney's beta opened in July 2022 (J. Rose, 2022); and Stability AI's open-source Stable Diffusion was released in August 2022 (Stability AI, 2022). Not long thereafter, in November 2022, OpenAI released their conversational text model ChatGPT (OpenAI, 2022), which used "sophisticated algorithms [that] are trained on vast datasets [...] to create novel outputs [for] prompts based on statistical likelihoods derived from training data" (Srdarov & Leaver, 2024, n.p.). Uptake of GenAI tools was swift: a report from McKinsey (2023) found that 79% of US-based respondents had exposure to GenAI tools, with 22% of those surveyed reporting regular use for work. Within the first half of 2023, the *New York Times* reported that investment into GenAI had soared to USD\$15.3 billion (Lohr, 2023), affirming descriptions of 2023 as "generative AI's breakout year" (McKinsey, 2023) and "the year of generative AI" (Thomson & Angus, 2023). As I put the final touches on this thesis in mid-2025, the fervour surrounding GenAI has settled to a familiar volume. It seems every website, platform, and computer program has incorporated new "AI" features (see Thomson & Angus, 2023), reflecting the *halo of innovation* (see Chapter 9) currently bestowed by artificial intelligence. Investments continue to pour into AI research and development: business and financial news outlet *Bloomberg* (2023) estimates that the global generative AI industry will reach a valuation of USD\$1.3 trillion by 2032.

The industry hype surrounding AI repopularised the term's presence in press coverage on virtual influencers (e.g. Criddle, 2023; Herrman, 2024). AI was credited for the voices of virtual influencers who launched musical careers (e.g. 이은주, 2022), and was used to describe the virtual influencers who debuted as "AI anchors", hosting multi-hour livestreams promoting commercial products for major sales events in China (e.g. Van Gastel, 2023). Some producers began to experiment with incorporating AI-generated content into their characters' feeds, creating AI-generated backgrounds (see Figure 11.1), or re-imagining their characters in different art styles (see Figure 11.2). However, the newfound ubiquity of these GenAI tools presented a challenge for the future of virtual influencers. GenAI tools appeared capable of composing an image to any specification, and accompanying captions on any topic, in any tone, in a matter of seconds. The ease with which new content could be

Figure 11.1: Chinese virtual Influencer AYAYI posts a tutorial instructing her followers on how to generate scenes using an AI image-generator app called Dream. Source: Weibo (AYAYI, 2022), screengrab by author on 13 August 2023.

generated directly challenged the utility of the virtual influencer agencies that had commercialised the characters' labour-intensive production and management. Enterprising individuals were quick to seize the opportunity. Start-ups were founded around platforms facilitating the creation of AI-generated influencers (Glambase, 2023), with others even promising to "pay users to create AI-driven influencers" at scale (Kautz, 2023, n.p.). Articles appeared revealing popular influencers to have been made with GenAI tools (e.g. L. Katz, 2023; Tangermann, 2023), and unsurprisingly, press soon began conflating virtual influencers made using the production pipeline outlined in Chapter 6 with these new AI-generated examples (e.g. Wengerodt, 2023).

Figure 11.2: The recognisable pink bob of Japanese virtual influencer Imma disappears in a carousel of AI-generated yearbook photos. Source: Instagram (imma [@imma.gram], 2023), screengrabs by author on 17 April 2024.

An AI-generated version of Singaporean virtual influencer Rae on a tropical island. Source: Instagram (RAE 蕊 [@here.is.rae], 2024), screengrab by author 17 April 2024.

Continuing the story introduced Chapter 10, in the face of the new availability of GenAI tools, virtual influencers' producers lay claim to their skills and contributions more loudly than before. In a remote presentation titled "The Future Realised by Virtual Humans" delivered at a MIT symposium on virtual humans, Sara Guisto (2022), a producer at Tokyo-based virtual influencer agency Aww Inc., explained:

[W]e think that [CGI and GenAI] technologies will be normalized in a few years, and we believe that everyone is going to be creating these realistic virtual humans. But [in this landscape, it is] these really precise production skills that we have [at Aww], and these branding skills [that] is what's really gonna set us apart from all [the] other, you know, available technology.

Similar ideas were expressed by Isaac Bratzel, previously Brud's Chief Technology Officer, in an interview with *a16z Podcast*:

I think one of the things we're going to run into a lot is this idea of like "Oh, anybody can do this now, with AI tools and everything else," and to me it feels a little bit like suggesting that because Ableton [Live, a digital music-making software] is, like, five dollars now, anybody can go be a superstar musician because they have this technology. And, like, technically speaking [versus] having the skill set to do it, it's not true—and then definitely, narrative and culturally, having the, like, ability to [...] connect with fans [...] it's definitely not true. (S. Smith, 2023, 23:00)

In a sentiment that echoed across Hollywood as the 2023 Writer's Guild of America strike likewise called for "regulations on the use of artificial intelligence in writing" (Porter, as cited in Leaver & Srdarov, 2023, para. 5), these producers underscored that while GenAI tools could facilitate the production of virtual influencers, it would only be with the skills, creativity, and input of their human creators that the characters would truly resonate.

The industry's call to recognise the human core behind virtual influencers is evocatively expressed in a three-minute short film starring Lil Miquela, created to promote a new electric vehicle from German automotive brand BMW in October 2023 (BMW, 2023). The film follows Lil Miquela on a road-trip through an ever-changing landscape. She drives through grassy hills, mist-covered highways, and along curved ocean-side cliffs. Along the way, Lil Miquela meets a curious dragonfly, almost kisses a stranger at a rave in an abandoned warehouse, and encounters a mysterious light beam in a metamorphosing desert. The film includes several examples of an *iconography of virtuality* (see Chapter 9): for example, when Miquela reaches to touch the hovering dragonfly, the tip of her finger becomes translucent, replaced

with iridescent sparkles that suggest she is more-than-human. The campaign's slogan—"Make it real"—manifests in Miquela's apparent transformation from a virtual being to human over the course of the film: she appears to feel an affective pull towards the dancing stranger at the rave, and experiences the feeling of rain for the first time, watching intently as the raindrops collect in her open palm. This narrative parallels the virtual influencer industry's call for brands and advertisers to *keep* it real, forgoing GenAI tools to instead prioritise the superiority of human creativity, connection, and input in the creation of virtual characters.

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Appendix A.

Participant Information Statement (PIS)

Analysing Virtual Influencers

Curtin University

HREC Project Number:	HRE2021-0773
Project Title:	Analysing Virtual Influencers: Celebrity, Authenticity and Identity on Social Media
Chief Investigator:	Professor Tama Leaver, Curtin University
Student researcher:	Rachel Berryman, Curtin University
Version Number:	1
Version Date:	28.04.22

Why is the research being conducted?

This research project examines the social media characters known as *virtual influencers* or *CGI influencers*. Although virtual influencers have evolved, multiplied and grown in popularity over the last half-decade, there is very little academic research about them, and not much is known about the people, software and businesses involved in their creation and management. To address this gap, this project will examine social media accounts of virtual influencers from around the world, exploring how they, and public responses to them, have changed over time. This analysis will be framed by the knowledge and perspectives about virtual influencers from those who have contributed to their growing popularity: the people behind the characters and the rapidly expanding virtual influencer industry.

The results of this three-year project will be submitted for consideration towards a PhD in Media, Creative Arts and Social Inquiry from Curtin University. The project is being led by PhD candidate Rachel Berryman under the supervision of Professor Tama Leaver and Associate Professor Crystal Abidin, and is funded by the Australian Government Research Training Program (RTP) scheme.

Why you have been selected to take part

You have been asked to take part in this research because of your experience and knowledge of creating and managing a virtual influencer. There will be no costs to you for taking part in this research, and you will not be paid for participating in this project.

Please note, you must be over 18 years old to participate in this research project.

What you will be asked to do

If you agree to take part in this research, you will be invited to attend an online interview with the student researcher, Rachel Berryman, via Microsoft Teams, at a mutually convenient time. We expect this conversation will take up to forty-five minutes, however we will block out an hour to allow ample time to troubleshoot any technical issues.

If you prefer, you may instead participate in this project via email. A list of questions will be sent to you, and you will be asked to provide your answers within two weeks. Based on the answers

you give, we may respond with a couple of follow-up questions for further information or clarification.

Microsoft Teams interviews (video and/or voice only) will be conducted in English, but email interviews will be available in English, Chinese (simplified or traditional), Japanese, Korean or Spanish. You can indicate the interview format and language you prefer on the Consent Form.

In the interview, we will ask you questions about the design, background and inspiration for your character/s, what your specific roles and responsibilities are, and about your contributions to their journey, growth and development.

Expected benefits of the research

There may be no direct benefit to you from participating in this research. However, we hope the results of this research will allow us to add new knowledge to the academic fields of celebrity studies, influencer studies and internet studies, as well as to help inform the future direction of the marketing industry more broadly.

Risks to you, discomforts and inconveniences

There are no perceivable risks or discomforts to you, should you decide to participate in this research. However, there may be a small inconvenience due to the time you will need to give up to participate in the interview.

In the course of the interview, you may feel that there are topics you are unable or uncomfortable discussing, and/or which you feel could lead to you experiencing harm in a professional or social context in future. You may refuse to answer or skip any question we ask, without explanation or penalty, and you will also have the ability to choose how you are identified throughout the interview. For example, you may choose to be identified by:

- Your legal name
- A different name of your choice
- A moniker/pseudonym (e.g. a username or screen name)
- A pseudonym that we assign (i.e. a name corresponding to your identified gender and/or ethnicity)
- Or as anonymous (e.g. Participant A from Company D)

Whatever your choice of identification, you will also have the ability to anonymise, pseudonymise or withdraw any part of the interview you choose. You may signal this at any time during the online interview, or by labelling the identity you would like to use in brackets if responding via email. Following the interview, we will send you a transcript to confirm you are happy with the record we have made of our conversation. This will be a chance for you to provide any further thoughts prompted by our discussion, to redact any comments, and/or to make any final adjustments to how you would like your answers to be identified. We will only proceed after you approve this transcript.

We will inform you in a timely manner if information becomes available that may affect your willingness to continue participating in this research.

Optional consent

If you choose to participate in a Microsoft Teams interview, provided you are happy for us to do so, we will make audio and video recordings of our conversation so that we can concentrate on what you have to say, and not distract ourselves with taking notes. After the interview, we will create a written record of our conversation. This written copy will be sent to you to confirm you are happy with it, and to confirm how you would like to be identified for each of your answers.

How will this information be stored, and who can access it?

The data collected for this project will be stored electronically on a password-protected computer and hard-drive, as well as under secure conditions at Curtin University. Aligning with

Curtin University's data policies, the information we collect will be kept for 7 years after the research is published, and then it will be destroyed.

The following people will have access to the information we collect in this research: the research team and, in the event of an audit or investigation, staff from the Curtin University Office of Research and Development.

How are we going to use your information?

The results of this research will be used to write a doctoral thesis, and may also be presented at academic conferences and published in professional journals, in book chapters and conference proceedings. How you are identified in this research will reflect how you have instructed us to identify you.

Your participation is voluntary

Taking part in a research project is voluntary. It is your choice to take part or not. You do not have to agree if you do not want to. If you decide to take part and then change your mind, that's okay, you can withdraw from the project. If you choose not to take part, or to start and then stop, there will be no comment or penalty, and this will not affect your relationship with the research team.

You can withdraw at any time

You are free to withdraw from the study any time prior to providing written approval for your interview transcript. You do not have to give us a reason: just tell us that you want to stop. If you choose to leave the study, we will use any information collected up until that point, unless you indicate you do not want us to in the Optional Consent section of your Consent Form.

Viewing the research

We will ask you for your preferred email address in the Consent Form so that we can send you the written record of our conversation for your approval. We will also use this email address to send you updates on outputs of the research, such as conference presentations, published papers and book chapters. We will also write to you with a link to the thesis (expected publication in 2024), which will include all of the information we have collected and reviewed as part of the research.

Questions and next steps

If you decide to take part in this research, we will ask you to sign the Consent Form. By signing it, you are telling us that you understand what you have read and what has been discussed. Signing the Consent Form indicates that you agree to be in the research project. You will be given a copy of this Information Statement and the Consent Form to keep. Please ask any questions you may have before you decide what to do.

If you have any questions, concerns or would like any further information about the project, please feel free to contact Professor Tama Leaver at t.leaver@curtin.edu.au.

Thank you very much for your time and consideration.

Kindest,

Rachel Berryman

PhD Candidate, Internet Studies, Curtin University

Website: rachelberryman.com

Email: r.berryman@postgrad.curtin.edu.au

Curtin University Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) has approved this study (HREC number HRE2021-0773). Should you wish to discuss the study with someone not directly involved, in particular, any matters concerning the conduct of the study or your rights as a participant, or you wish to make a confidential complaint, you may contact Curtin's Ethics Officer on +61 8 9266 9223, or the Manager, Research Integrity on +61 8 9266 7093 or email hrec@curtin.edu.au.

Appendix B. Participant Consent Form (PCF)

Analysing Virtual Influencers

Curtin University

HREC Project Number:	HRE2021-0773
Project Title:	Analysing Virtual Influencers: Celebrity, Authenticity and Identity on Social Media
Chief Investigator:	Professor Tama Leaver, Curtin University
Student researcher:	Rachel Berryman, Curtin University
Version Number:	1
Version Date:	28.04.22

By signing this form, I confirm that:

- I have read the Information Statement for this project and I understand its contents.
- I believe I understand the purpose, extent and possible risks of my involvement in this project.
- I voluntarily consent to take part in this research project.
- I confirm I am over 18 years old.
- I understand that I have control over how I am identified in this research, and that I can anonymise, pseudonymise or retract any of the answer I provide up to the point of approving my transcript.
- I understand that I may refuse to answer or withdraw from this project at any time, without explanation or penalty.
- I understand that this project has been approved by Curtin University Human Research Ethics Committee and will be carried out in-line with the National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007), updated in 2018.
- I understand I will receive a copy of this Information Statement and Consent Form.
- I have had an opportunity to ask questions and I am satisfied with the answers I have received.

INTERVIEW FORMAT

I would prefer to interview via	<input type="checkbox"/> Voice/Video Call (in English)	<input type="checkbox"/> Email
My preferred language is <i>(email interview only)</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> English <input type="checkbox"/> Chinese (Simplified) <input type="checkbox"/> Chinese (Traditional) <input type="checkbox"/> Japanese <input type="checkbox"/> Korean <input type="checkbox"/> Spanish	

Please provide your email address so that we can send you a Microsoft Teams invite and written record of our conversation (voice/video interview), or a list of questions and a written record of our conversation (email interview), as well as future updates about the publications and outputs from this project.

Appendix C.

Interview Protocol (Video Call)

PRE-RECORDING SEGMENT

- *Soft introduction and warm-up.*
- *Overview of project.*
- Do you have any questions before we start?

INTRODUCTORY SEGMENT

This segment will be the same for all participants.

Are you happy for me to start recording?

(Yes - select Record on Zoom, and show recording beginning on audio recorder to the camera.)

This is an interview between Rachel Berryman and _____ (nominated name, based on PCF), and today's date is _____.

To begin, thank you so much for taking the time to participate in this interview as part of my PhD research on virtual influencers. This call will take about forty-five minutes - I've got a list of questions prepared, but there may be extra talking points based on your answers that we'll end up discussing too.

We'll move through a few different topics, beginning with a few questions about you, your relationship with (character) and how they came to be; then about (character) themselves, their personality, design and their audience; then your hopes and aspirations for (character) moving forward, as well as your thoughts on the broader virtual influencer industry.

Only if pseudonymous/anonymous: Based on the name you included in your Consent Form, throughout this interview, I'll refer to you as _____ (nominated name, based on PCF).

If you'd like to answer a question anonymously, or use a pseudonym instead, you can mention that at any point. You also don't have to answer any questions that you're not comfortable answering, and you can stop participating at any time: you don't have to give a reason, you can just tell me that you want to move to the next question, or that you'd like to stop.

After we work through the questions, I'll stop the recordings and we'll have a quick debrief about our conversation. This will be another chance for you to let me know if there are any changes you'd like made to how you are identified for any of your answers. After the interview, I'll email you a written version of our talk for you to review and confirm that you're happy with it.

Are you ready to begin? Great!

OPENING SEGMENT

- i. What is your name?
- ii. Could you tell me a bit about the company you work for, and how you came to your current role?
- iii. Tell me about how you first discovered virtual influencers. What was your first impression of them?
 - *Prompts for whether/how this impression has changed since.*
- iv. I tend to use the term “virtual influencer”, but is there a different term that you prefer to use to describe this group of social media characters?
 - *Prompt for definition.*
 - *NB: The participant’s preferred term will be used throughout the interview, indicated by “ _____ (term for VI)”.*
- v. Are you comfortable sharing some demographic information about yourself?
 - What country are you currently based in, and what is your ethnicity?
 - What is your gender identity, and which pronouns do you use?
 - What age range do you fall into?
 - 18-29 | 30-39 | 40-49 | 50-59 | 60-69 | 70+

TOPIC ONE: CHARACTER AND/OR COMPANY

CHARACTER PROFILE

This segment will be used for Producers.

Now I'd like you to tell me about (name of character).

2. How would you describe _____ (name of character)?
 - *Prompts for backstory, ethnicity, location, personality, tone of voice, aesthetic or visual style – what makes them unique?*
3. What inspired _____ (name of character)'s creation, and their design?
 - *Prompts for process, research, software and tools.*

OR What inspired you to create (name of character)? How did you come up with their design? What sort of research did you do? What sort of things were you thinking about during this process? What tools did you use?

4. What platforms, websites or apps is _____ (name of character) on?
 - Could you tell me about how these were selected, and what each platform is used for? **OR** How these were selected, and what do you use each platform for?
 - Which is your favourite platform to use, and why?
5. Tell me about your role and responsibilities when it comes to _____ (name of character).
 - How much time in an average week do you spend working on _____ (name of character)?
 - Do you work with anyone else, and if so, what do they contribute?
 - *Prompts for story of how they came to work together, how they work together now.*

COMPANY PROFILE

This segment will be used for Industry Stakeholders.

6. Could you tell me a bit about _____ (name of company) is connected to _____ (term for VI)?
 - *Prompts for origins of this connection, explore how the company is positioned in relation to the wider social media, influencer and/or virtual being industries.*
7. Does your company work (directly or indirectly) with the producers of _____ (term for VI)?
 - *Prompts for how these relationships are formed, what they look like, and the benefits of these relationships for all parties.*

TOPIC TWO: CONTENT

CONTENT

This segment will be used for all Producers

For the next section, you might like to use your phone or computer to view one of _____ (name of character)'s profiles, and look through past content as you answer. If you're reminded of any particular stories or memories as you do so, feel free to mention them.

Now we're going to talk specifically about (name of character)'s content.

8. What inspires the content for _____ (name of character)? Is there a larger storyline or narrative you follow?
 - *If yes: prompts for inspiration, time period, planning process, fidelity, any experiences of going "off-script".*
9. Could you describe the process of creating a new post or Story, from start to finish, and when and how you contribute to this process?
 - How do you select your shoot locations? How do you photograph them?
 - Do you plan the visuals or the comments first? What do you think about when you're doing this?
 - What is your favourite piece of content you've ever been involved in creating, and why?
10. What skills are required to create or manage a virtual influencer?
 - When it comes to creating content, what sorts of things do you need to do or think about that human influencers don't?

This segment will be used for Industry Stakeholders.

11. Have you been personally involved with any projects involving _____ (term for VI)?
 - *If yes: prompts for objectives, outcomes, challenges and learnings.*

AUDIENCE

This segment will only be used for Producers.

13. How would you describe _____ (name of character)'s audience?
 - *Prompts for alignment with expectations, differences across platforms, dynamic between character and their audience – how, and how often, do they interact?*
14. What have you done to grow _____ (name of character)'s audience?
 - *Prompts for efficient, inefficient strategies, unexpected success or exposure.*

TOPIC THREE: COMMERCIALS

PARTNERSHIPS

This segment will be used for Producers.

15. Does _____ (character name) have any commercial engagements at the moment?
 - If yes: *Prompts for first partnership, most memorable partnership, their average fees, product types and genres, project deliverables, future plans working with brands, any other objectives.*
 - If no: *Prompts for future plans working with brands, factors that might influence decisions to partner.*
 - If none: What is your intention or motivation for creating _____ (character name)?

MARKET VALUE

This segment will be used for Industry Stakeholders.

16. What do you see as the benefits, challenges and risks of brands working with _____ (term for VI)?
 - *Prompts for specific examples of campaigns or partnerships that have used virtual influencers well, or poorly.*
17. What do you think the _____ (term for VI) industry will look like in 5 years' time?
18. What challenges do you see facing the _____ (term for VI) industry, now and in future?

CONCLUDING SEGMENT

This segment will be used for Producers.

19. Looking back on your journey with _____ (name of character), are there any particular moments, events or memories that stand out in your mind?
 - What are you proudest of?
 - *Prompts for fan/audience interactions, connections, projects, achievements, awards or accolades, etc.*
20. What are your hopes or aspirations for _____ (name of character) in future?
 - *Prompts for ties to personal/professional aspirations, how long they expect to be involved with the character, what they want to do afterwards.*

This segment will be the same for all participants.

21. What advice would you give someone who wants to create their own _____ (term for VI)?
 - How about to someone/a company who would like to engage or partner with virtual influencers?
22. In your opinion, what is the biggest misconception that people have about _____ (term for VI)?
23. Which [other] _____ (term for VI) do you think are paving the way, and why?
24. Is there anyone else that you'd recommend I get in touch with to participate in this research?
25. Is there anything else you'd like to talk about, or anything that I've missed?

Well, that brings us to the end of my list of questions! Thank you so much again for chatting

with me today, and for sharing so much about your expertise and experience.

It's important to remember that what we write is for print, which may not be so easily deleted or erased in future, so you should feel comfortable with how you choose to be identified for each of the answers you've given today. Your choices will inform how we represent your words and perspective in our writing.

Were there any moments from our chat that you feel could be potentially sensitive that you would like to retract, or change how you are identified for? Were there any answers that you feel may cause harm to yourself or others, that you would like to remove from the record?

- *Student researcher's suggestions, if necessary.*

Are you happy for me to stop the recording?

(Yes – stop Recording on Zoom, show pausing recorder to the camera.)

DEBRIEF

Appendix D. Interview Protocol (Email)

Dear [nominated name, per PCF],

Thank you very much again for taking the time to participate in this interview for my PhD research on virtual influencers at Curtin University. Below, you will find 10 questions about your experience and knowledge of virtual influencers, as well as the industry surrounding them. There are no right or wrong answers to these questions - I'm interested in hearing your own thoughts and opinions.

Based on the name you included in your Consent Form, by default, your answers will be attributed to _____ (nominated name, per PCF). However, if you'd like to answer a question anonymously, or use a pseudonym instead, please indicate that by using brackets (e.g., (anonymous), (use pseudonym here) or a (*name*) of your choice at the beginning of the sentence or section). After the interview, I'll send you a copy of your answers for you to confirm that you are happy with how you are identified throughout.

Remember, you can skip any question that you are not comfortable answering, and you can stop participating in this project at any time. You don't have to give a reason for withdrawing, you can simply reply to this email saying that you no longer want to be involved.

If you are happy to go ahead, we would appreciate if you could please return your answers within two weeks. Please don't hesitate to reply to this email with any questions or queries prior to this date.

Demographic Information

- i. What is your age range?
- ii. What country are you currently based in, and what is your ethnicity?
- iii. What is your gender identity, and which pronouns do you use?
- iv. Could you tell me a bit about your primary occupation, the company you currently work for, and how you came to this role?
- v. In the questions below, I use the term "virtual influencers". Is there is a term you prefer to describe this group of social media characters? If so, please include it, as well as a definition of what it means to you, below.

Preferred term:

Definition:

Interview Questions

The below question will be used for all participants.

1. How did you first discover virtual influencers? What was your first impression of them, and how, if at all, has your view changed since?

The below questions will only be used for Producers.

2. How would you describe _____ (name of character)? Please provide as much detail as possible about their background, personality, aesthetic and personal style, and what makes them unique.

3. What inspired the creation of _____ (name of character)? What did the process of creating them look like, and what sorts of software, tools and research did this involve?
4. What platforms (e.g. websites, social media platforms, apps, video games, etc.) is _____ (name of character) on? How were these selected? What is each platform used for? Which is your favourite platform to use, and why?

5a. In as much detail as possible, tell me about your role and responsibilities when it comes to _____ (name of character). How much time in an average week do you spend on these tasks? Do you work with anyone else, and if so, what do they do?

5b. Please describe the process of creating a new post or Story, from start to finish. When and how do you contribute to this process? What is your favourite piece of content you've ever been involved in creating, and why?

6a. What is the intention or motivation behind _____ (name of character)?

- 6b.** Does _____ (character name) have any commercial engagements at the moment?
- If so, please describe these partnerships in as much detail as possible. What was their first partnership, and the most memorable? What is the average fee, what types of products have been promoted, what kind of deliverables did the partnerships involve? Do you have any upcoming plans for commercial partnerships?
 - If not, what plans, if any, do you have to work with brands in future?

7a. Looking back at on your journey with _____ (name of character), are there any particular moments, events or memories that stand out in your mind? (This might be an interaction with a fan, a connection you made, or a project you worked on, or something else you're proud of!)

7b. What are your hopes or aspirations for _____ (name of character) in future?

The below questions will only be used for Industry Stakeholders.

2. Please describe your company's relationship to virtual influencers, and as much as you know about the origins of this connection.
3. Does your company work (directly or indirectly) with the producers of virtual influencers? If so, how are these relationships formed, what do they look like, and what are the benefits for those involved?
4. Have you been personally involved with any projects involving virtual influencers? If so, please describe these projects in as much detail as possible. What were the objectives, outcomes, challenges and learnings from these projects?
5. What do you see as the benefits, challenges and risks of brands working with virtual influencers?
 - Benefits:*
 - Challenges:*
 - Risks:*
6. What do you think the virtual influencer industry will look like in 5 years' time? Related to this, what challenges do you see facing the virtual influencer industry, now and in future?

7. Which virtual influencers do you think are paving the way, and why? (Please provide links to profiles where relevant.)

The below questions will be used for all participants.

8. In your opinion, what is the biggest misconception that people have about virtual influencers?
9. What advice would you give someone interested in creating their own virtual influencer, or to someone/a company who would like to engage or partner with virtual influencers?
10. Is there anything else you'd like to mention, or anything that you think that I've missed in the questions above?

Again, thank you very much for your time and participation! Please do not hesitate to get in touch if you have any questions or queries about any of the questions above.